

THE DEVELOPMENT OF PHYSICAL
PERFORMANCE IN ADOLESCENT YOUTH
SOCCER PLAYERS: THE IMPACT OF
MATURATION AND TRAINING

CILLIAN MCGOLDRICK

Thesis submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements
of the University of the West of Scotland
for the award of Doctor of Philosophy

Collaborating establishments: Celtic Football Club

February 2024

Acknowledgements

Firstly, I would like to gratefully thank Prof. Vish Unnithan for all his support, both from a personal and professional standpoint, you have been unbelievably supportive throughout this process, thank you. Secondly to Dr Antonio Dello Iacono. Your expertise and continued support in developing and assisting with our research projects has been monumental in my personal and academic development. I am truly grateful to have had the supervisory team I had during my studies, the rapport we developed is testament to your personality and commitment over the last three and a half years.

In addition, the support I received from individuals in the Sport Science department at Celtic Football Club will always be something I remember fondly. Specifically, Oliver Morgan, Mark Maxwell, Janice Buchanan and Neil Addington were always on hand to provide support. Each of you granted me invaluable professional advice in your own unique way whilst maintaining a pragmatic outlook on the importance of life outside the club. I am extremely grateful for all your help the past few years.

In addition, the thesis would not have been completed in its current form without the help from Dr Hannah Lithgow. I thoroughly enjoyed working with and getting to know you from a personal standpoint, I wish you every success in your future.

Lastly, thank you to my family and close friends, in particular my brother Ruaidhrí. You have all been fantastically supportive, empathetic, and helped steer my focus through difficult times, I will never forget your unwavering friendship.

Statement from the author

The current thesis presents research conducted over a period of three and a half years between February 2020 and August 2023. The research was conducted with the University of the West of Scotland and in partnership with Celtic Football Club. This was an incredibly worthwhile experience for my personal, and practical and academic development. I believe the experience and knowledge I gained as an applied practitioner was greater than had I undertaken the applied role and PhD separately or in succession.

While all PhD's, and more so applied PhD's, require the candidate to continually problem solve throughout the process, this was certainly the case of the current PhD from the get-go. The global COVID-19 pandemic resulted in an added layer of complexity to the research process. Creating and conducting research projects in accordance with the requirements and scheduling with a professional sporting organisation presents numerous challenges, however with the addition of guidelines to reduce the spread of COVID-19 this became impossible for the first 14 months of the research presented in the current thesis. After the government-imposed lockdowns, while possible to collect data, it was a difficult process due to the need to follow guidelines related to sanitising of surfaces, physical distancing, the use of face masks and protocols of isolation in the event of symptoms. Nonetheless, the originally proposed research projects agreed upon by both the aforementioned organisations remained consistent until completion, with the results of which are presented here. However, in order to carry out the projects, certain aspects of the projects needed to be merged together so to increase efficiency of data collection.

Although the more intensive data collection process which was carried out was shorter in duration than originally proposed, this also meant that any issues or mistakes with data or data collection procedures could not be corrected by re-collection the data. In essence, any unusable data was discarded and was not possible to rectify through retesting. Although this occurred in a small number of cases, and the broad aims of the thesis remained unchanged, it speaks to the larger difficulty experienced throughout this process.

Specifically, due to the delay in conducting research alongside other constraints in being able to reconduct the isometric squat testing, it was not possible to align the physical performance testing with the ultrasound measurements (Figure 3.1), thereby resulting in a purely descriptive study (Chapter 7). This was also the case of the results presented in Chapter 5, as the time

constraints imposed meant it was not possible to conduct a longitudinal analysis of the data to determine the change in relationships of performance tests over time. In addition, due to time constraints of working in an applied environment, it was not always possible to conduct the physical fitness testing within the same day. This often meant tests of different physical qualities were carried out in different training weeks so as to both ensure players conducted the tests in similar physical condition (i.e., with regards to fatigue), and, to not detract from the players' time on the pitch. However, while the reduced time made some elements of the research not possible, the use of players across multiple studies (Figure 3.1) likely adds to the stability of the data, and the reduction in familiarisation effect.

The aim of the current statement was to provide you, the reader, of a sense of context around the current research, and a small insight into me as both a researcher and applied practitioner.

Cillian McGoldrick (author)

Abstract

Physical performance in soccer is dependent upon a multitude of fitness components for successful performance. Specifically, strength, speed, and power performance has been linked to game defining moments, and can aid youth players in transitioning through an academy structure. Despite the importance of the development of these qualities, little research has quantified the development of strength, speed, and power capabilities using reliable performance tests over durations similar to standard soccer season lengths. Research such as this could assist the applied practitioner in developing programming aimed at enhancing these qualities, and/or, provide normative data from which to use to compare individual/team magnitude of changes.

The first study included in this thesis (Chapter 4) aimed to validate a strength test for use with youth soccer players. Specifically, we evaluated the reliability of two different isometric squat test (ISqT) protocols and compared the outputs and levels of reliability between the two, specifically in youth soccer players. A more time-efficient protocol was developed where participants self-selected their body position for use during the assessment as opposed to utilising a set knee joint angle. In addition, the minimum number of familiarisations required for data to stabilise was also evaluated for both protocols. The results of this study demonstrate that the isometric squat test is reliable for use in youth soccer populations. In addition, this study demonstrates that the self-determined protocol resulted in larger peak force values with data also stabilising at a faster rate.

Subsequently, the following study aimed to determine the relationships between ISqT metrics which displayed acceptable reliability, and common global measures of speed and power. In addition, this study aimed to examine how change in ISqT performance metrics relates to changes in that of speed and jump performance. It was demonstrated that peak and relative peak force displayed the strongest relationships (44.1–53.8%) with different measures of speed and jump performance. Therefore, the results of Chapters 4 and 5 demonstrate the ISqT metrics which are both reliable and display statistically significant relationships with, and explain large proportions of the variability of measures of physical performance related to youth soccer.

Chapter 6 then sought to utilise these metrics to longitudinally evaluate change to strength, speed, and power characteristics over a 7–8-month period. In addition, this study aimed to determine the change in physical performance of youth soccer players associated with a top

tier soccer academy compared to that of an amateur soccer academy as an indication of the efficacy of the strength and conditioning specific training programme. Lastly, the influence of growth and maturation on these measures was also evaluated. The results of Chapter 6 show that measures of strength and jump performance improved in youth soccer players from the professional academy compared to the amateur academy over the study duration when proxy measures of maturation were controlled for. In addition, strength and 10m sprint performance was greater for the professional academy players compared to that of the amateur academy players. Lastly, maturation (percentage of estimated adult height) was shown to have demonstrated an effect on all measures of physical performance. It could be suggested from the results of this study that a primary reason for the difference in change between academy players was the inclusion of a strength and power specific programme.

The final study of this thesis then aimed to determine the underpinning physiological adaptations which contribute to strength, speed, and power performance. Therefore, changes to vastus lateralis muscle architecture were examined following an 8-month period. We show that muscle thickness, pennation angle, fascicle length, and relative muscle thickness displayed no changes over the study duration. Furthermore, there was no observed interaction with measures of maturation. However, relative fascicle length was shown as statistically significantly longer post-intervention compared to pre-, but did not display any interaction with maturation, and was therefore likely related to the training programme undertaken.

In conclusion, this thesis provides novel research in the areas of applied performance monitoring and development in youth soccer. Specifically, a novel testing methodology has been demonstrated to be reliable and capable of being utilised in the longitudinal monitoring of youth soccer players. Indeed, the self-determined isometric squat test protocol is likely more time efficient, autonomy supportive, and subjectively comfortable for the participant when compare to traditional testing methods. Changes to strength, speed, and power performance over a duration akin to that of a standard season length has demonstrated larger accelerative running, strength, and jump improvements for youth soccer players participating in structured and targeted strength and power training compared to amateur controls participating in pitch-only training. Nonetheless, it was also show here that maturation exerts the largest effect on all measures of strength, speed, and power performance. There is evidence of muscle morphological adaptations that may contribute to enhanced strength, speed, and power performance in elite youth soccer players likely a result of specific strength and power training.

Abbreviations

%EAH	Percentage of estimated adult height
1RM	1 repetition maximum
ACSA	Anatomical cross-sectional area
ASA	Amateur soccer academy players
aPF	Allometrically scaled peak force
AvgF	Average force
AvgIMP	Average impulse
avgPF	Average peak force
BB	Biceps brachii
CG	Control group
CI	Confidence intervals
CMJ	Counter- movement jump
CSA	Cross sectional area
CT	Computerised tomography
CV	Coefficient of variation
ES	Effect size
F30ms	Force at 30 milliseconds
FL	Fascicle length
FPA	Fibre pennation angle
G1	Group 1

GM	Gastrocnemius medialis
GRF	Ground reaction forces
ICC	Intraclass correlation coefficient
IMP	Impulse
IMTP	Isometric mid- thigh pull
IST	Isometric squat test
MRI	Magnetic resonance imaging
MT	Muscle thickness
mVOL	Muscle volume
n	n number
N	Newtons
N/kg	Newtons per kilogram
$N/kg^{0.67}$	Newtons per kilogram scaled allometrically
N/s	Newtons per second
N.s	Newton-seconds
NetF	Net force
OPTIMAL	Optimising performance through intrinsic motivation for learning theory
p	p value
PCSA	Physiological cross-sectional area
PDet	Pre-determined
PF	Peak force

PRFD	Peak rate of force development
PHV	Peak height velocity
PSA	Professional soccer academy players
PWV	Peak weight velocity
QF	Quadriceps femoris
<i>r</i>	Correlation coefficient
RAE	Relative age effect
RF	Rectus femoris
RFD	Rate of force development
rFL	Relative fascicle length
rMT	Relative muscle thickness
rPF	Relative peak force
rTEM	Relative TEM
SD	Standard deviation
SDet	Self-determined
SEM	Standard error of the mean
SJ	Squat jump
TB	Triceps brachii
TEM	Technical error of measurement
TG	Training group
TTPF	Time to peak force

TW	Tanner-Whitehouse stage
U9	Under 9
US	Ultrasound
VI	Vastus intermedius
Vilat	Lateral vastus intermedius
Vlant	Anterior vastus intermedius
VL	Vastus lateralis
VM	Vastus medialis

Table of contents

Acknowledgements	2
Statement from the author	3
Abstract.....	5
Abbreviations	7
Table of contents	11
Chapter 1.0	15
Introduction.....	15
1.1 Thesis background, aims and rationale	17
1.2 Aims and objectives of the thesis.....	21
1.2.1 Broad aim of the thesis	21
1.2.2 Specific aims of the thesis	22
Chapter 2.0	25
Literature review	25
2.1 Literature review background, aims and rationale.....	25
2.3 Methods.....	28
2.2 Match demands in elite youth soccer in relation to muscular force production capabilities.....	30
2.4 The effect of maturation on muscular force and power in youth soccer athletes	33
2.5 The physiological determinants of muscular force production capabilities and power	38
2.5.1 Muscle size changes as a result of training.....	40
2.5.2 Muscle architecture.....	60
2.5.2.1 Muscle fibre pennation angle.....	60
2.5.2.2 Muscle fascicle length	73
2.6.0 The assessment of maximal muscular force and power production capabilities	74
2.6.1 The isometric squat test	76
2.6.1.1 Validity and reliability of the isometric squat	77
2.6.1.2 Methodological considerations for isometric squat testing	108
2.7.1 Isometric squat associations with dynamic performance	112

2.7.0	Assessment of proxy measures of soccer performance	114
2.7.2	Muscular power assessments	114
2.7.3	Speed assessments	116
2.8.0	Autonomy	117
Chapter 3.0	122
General Methodology	122
3.1	Participant information	122
3.2	Anthropometric measurements and adult height estimation.....	122
3.3	Physical performance testing	124
3.3.1	Counter-movement jump	124
3.3.2	Isometric squat test	125
3.3.3	Isometric squat force-time data assessment.....	128
3.3.4	Sprint assessment.....	128
Chapter 4.0	129
Reliability, Familiarisation Effect, and Comparisons Between a Predetermined and a Self-Determined Isometric-Squat Testing Protocol.....	129
4.1	Abstract	129
4.2	Introduction.....	129
4.3	Methodology	130
4.3.1	Experimental approach to the problem.....	130
4.3.2	Participants	131
4.4	Procedures.....	131
4.4.1	Isometric squat test	131
4.4.1.1	Pre-determined isometric squat procedures.....	131
4.4.1.2	Self-determined isometric squat procedures.....	132
4.4.2	Self-report measures	132
4.4.3	Statistical analysis.....	133
4.5	Results.....	134
4.5.1	Protocol comparisons	134
4.5.2	Reliability	135
4.6	Discussion	140
4.7	Practical implications.....	143
4.8	Thesis implications	143

Chapter 5.0 144

Relationship between isometric squat test performance and measures of physical performance in youth soccer 144

5.1	Abstract.....	144
5.2	Introduction.....	144
5.3	Methods.....	145
5.3.1	Experimental approach to the problem.....	145
5.3.2	Participants	145
5.4	Procedures.....	146
5.4.1	Isometric squat test	146
5.4.2	Counter-movement jump	146
5.4.3	Sprint assessment.....	146
5.4.4	Statistical analysis.....	146
5.5	Results.....	147
5.6	Discussion	147
5.7	Practical implications.....	150
5.8	Thesis implications	150

Chapter 6.0 152

A longitudinal analysis of strength and power performance between elite and amateur youth soccer players..... 152

6.1	Abstract	152
6.2	Introduction.....	152
6.3	Methods.....	154
6.3.1	Experimental approach to the problem.....	154
6.3.2	Participants	154
6.4	Procedures.....	156
6.4.1	Isometric squat test	156
6.4.2	Counter-movement jump	156
6.4.3	Sprint assessment.....	156
6.4.4	Monitoring of external load during pitch-based training sessions	156
6.4.5	Statistical analysis.....	157
6.5	Results.....	157
6.6	Discussion	159
6.7	Practical implications.....	162
6.8	Thesis implications	163

Chapter 7.0	164
Morphological changes in the Vastus Lateralis of highly-trained youth soccer players: a longitudinal evaluation	164
7.1 Abstract	164
7.2 Introduction.....	164
7.3 Methods.....	166
7.3.1 Experimental approach to the problem.....	166
7.3.2 Participants	167
7.4 Procedures.....	167
7.4.1 Vastus lateralis muscle imaging.....	167
7.4.2 Monitoring of external load during pitch-based training sessions	169
7.4.3 Statistical analysis.....	169
7.5 Results.....	169
7.6 Discussion	172
7.7 Practical implications.....	175
Chapter 8.0	176
Findings, implications, limitations and identified areas for future research	176
8.1 Thesis findings	177
8.2 Practical implications.....	181
8.3 Reflections: research, and applied practice.....	186
8.4 Limitations and areas for future research.....	189
Chapter 9.0	191
References	191
Appendices	218
Publication from the current thesis.....	218
Appendix 1: Isometric testing protocol participant reference sheet.....	219
Appendix 2: Participant perception of autonomy questionnaire	221
Appendix 3: Ethical approval.....	224
Appendix 4: Organisational approval.....	226
Appendix 5: Informed consent	227
Appendix 6: PAR-Q training questionnaire	232

Chapter 1.0

Introduction

A deliberate multi-disciplinary approach was taken to refine the current research. Specifically, during initial stages of the PhD, numerous conversations took place with not only the PhD's Director of Studies and Supervisor, but also the Head of Academy Sport Science, lead Academy Sport Scientists, and Psychologist at Celtic Football Club. This was to ensure that the resulting research was not only methodologically sound, but was also implementable and meaningful from an applied standpoint. Ensuring the research presented here had utility and was practically useful in an applied environment was paramount. Research in the area of Sport Science should aim to assist practitioners in operating within, and/or impacting the applied field in a meaningful way. From this standpoint, it is logical that applied problems which had not been answered sufficiently formed the basis of the research questions presented here, therefore the research in the current thesis aimed to address these problems with methodologically sound procedures to ensure confidence in findings. The research presented in this thesis as a result broadly attempted to provide information which could assist with specific problems encountered by applied professionals, and are likely encountered by others.

Given the current thesis is broadly centred around the research presented in Chapter 6, it may be of use to detail why this study arose as one of importance to the applied practitioner. Strength and conditioning specific training has become commonplace in many youth development programmes for reasons such as injury prevention and performance enhancement. However, due to a multitude of reasons, substantial within- and between-individual variability may occur in the performance change in response to training. Specifically, growth and maturation processes have been suggested as a significant contributor to these variances due to the physiological changes which occur as a result of an individual progressing towards a more mature state. This formed the basis of a research question this thesis attempted to answer. Given normal growth and maturation interact with training stimuli to enhance athletic performance, the research presented here aimed to quantify this change. This was decided to assist with evaluating the efficacy of training programmes, with the 'noise' attributable to changes in maturity status problematic to accurate evaluation. For example, this data aims to assist the applied practitioner in determining if the change observed in physical performance testing is

above that which could be expected due to a combination of maturation processes and training exposure. For this reason, the addition of the control group was necessary to obtain an estimate of this change over the study duration. In addition, given adolescents within their highest rate of growth display the greatest variability to programming, it would appear obvious the change during this stage of maturation to be important to elucidate. Indeed, during conversation in the past, technical coaches have joked that strength and power development “happened anyway”, and was therefore a process of maturity status change and not necessarily a result of strength and conditioning specific training; and so, the research presented here set about to determine the extent this assumption could be proved or disproved.

While this then led to the formation of the main aim of the current thesis, the other studies naturally took shape thereafter. For example, determining global strength characteristics longitudinally was included in the aims of Chapter 6, therefore, establishing the reliability, and validity of a specific performance test was required. The isometric squat test was the preferred strength test in the data collection environment, a performance assessment which can be relatively time-consuming to conduct. Therefore, a novel time-efficient protocol was evaluated for use with large groups of athletes.

Determining the change in proxies of physical performance is a primary challenge for strength and conditioning coaches. However, understanding the underpinning mechanistic basis for performance change can similarly assist coaches in the prescription of programmes which aim to enhance adaptation, and not simply replicate sporting movements under different loaded conditions. Therefore, in an attempt to partly explain any changes observed in Chapter 6, ultrasound measurements were utilised in Chapter 7.

The research to be conducted here therefore seemed to fit with the general attempt to provide worthwhile solutions to applied problems. For example, the isometric squat test could be implemented in an applied setting as a test and/or readiness monitor, and the data from the latter chapters could inform the extent a strength and power-based programme has efficacy, and provide information on the physiological changes which contribute to physical performance change. The applied practitioner could then utilise this information so to design more specific programmes targeted at enhancing specific qualities.

1.1 Thesis background, aims and rationale

Despite the primary contribution of energy sources from aerobic metabolism for soccer performance (Stølen *et al.*, 2005a), anaerobic metabolism predominantly fuels the powerful actions such as sprinting, jumping, and changing direction (Aslan *et al.*, 2012) which typically precede games defining moments (e.g., goal opportunities) (Faude, Koch and Meyer, 2012). As a specific reference to youth soccer, the number of these actions increases in older age groups (Al Haddad *et al.*, 2015; Bellistri *et al.*, 2017; Goto, Morris and Nevill, 2015b; Vigh-Larsen, Dalgas and Andersen, 2018a), and they have also been suggested to discriminate between playing standards, with higher playing standards displaying greater numbers of the aforementioned neuromuscular actions (Sherwood *et al.*, 2020).

Development of neuromuscular capabilities, particularly of the lower limbs, is therefore of utmost importance given the contribution of these characteristics to ‘physical’ proxies of performance, such as sprint and change of direction ability (Thomas *et al.*, 2015). Indeed, youth soccer players have previously been observed to sprint an average of ~100 m during match play (Hunter *et al.*, 2015), therefore, the ability to produce and tolerate large ground reaction forces (GRF) is particularly important for soccer performance. Given stronger athletes are typically capable to produce greater GRFs (Comfort *et al.*, 2014), it is unsurprising that muscle force and power characteristics are key components of modern youth athletic development frameworks (Lloyd *et al.*, 2015; Ryan *et al.*, 2018).

Youth soccer players are required to carry out changes in momentum during match play approximately ~120 times (Pettersen and Brenn, 2019). Producing large GRFs in short timeframes is an important ability, given actions involved in changing momentum, such as accelerations and decelerations, occur as a result of changing GRF expression over time. Similarly, change of direction movements consist of a deceleration phase, a change of direction phase (during which the lower limbs act quasi-isometrically during foot plant in order to reposition the body), and a reacceleration phase (Dempsey *et al.*, 2007). Therefore, it is unsurprising acceleration has been shown as an important ability across positions (Pettersen and Brenn, 2019) and competitive standards (Delaney *et al.*, 2018). Furthermore, improvements in change of direction speed have also been demonstrated as a result of resistance training in youth (Chaabene *et al.*, 2020). Strength and power development should therefore be of paramount importance for practitioners working with youth soccer athletes, as relationships exist between muscular power and force capacities and both acceleration (Chelly

et al., 2010) and deceleration performance (Spiteri, Hart and Nimphius, 2014). The ability of the lower limbs to produce and tolerate large GRFs could therefore contribute to global physical performance.

The importance of muscular strength and power to sporting performance has led to the implementation of different performance tests with the aim to evaluate these characteristics isoinertially (Peña-González *et al.*, 2019), isokinetically (Bogdanis and Kalapotharakos, 2016), or isometrically (Dos'Santos *et al.*, 2018; Morris *et al.*, 2018b; Thomas *et al.*, 2015). Isoinertial strength tests (e.g., 1-, 3-, 5-repetition maximum tests) are typically time-consuming and greatly impacted by training experience (Weakley *et al.*, 2017). Despite the need for expensive equipment, isometric tests are not affected by these issues and are typically more reliable than isoinertial tests, require less technical skill for execution and, therefore, are safer for use (Brady, Harrison and Comyns, 2020). Commonly, the isometric squat test (ISqT) (Marshall *et al.*, 2019) and the isometric mid-thigh pull test (IMTP) (Dos'Santos *et al.*, 2018) are used within the literature, with the ISqT found to produce larger peak force values (Brady *et al.*, 2018; Brady *et al.*, 2019; Nuzzo *et al.*, 2008). Therefore, it appears that isometric tests are suitable for use in applied environments where access to this equipment is possible. Due to the reduced impact of familiarity and training experience on the execution of these tests, isometric tests are a time efficient testing alternative when compared to isoinertial or isokinetic tests. Therefore, in time restricted environments or when working with large groups of athletes, isometric tests may be preferred by practitioners.

To select the most appropriate test for use in the applied environment, the validity, reliability, and methodological procedures should be carefully considered. Measurement error directly impacts the performance measure's reliability, as it may inflate the difference between the measured value, and the true value of the performance test. This would thereby lead to within-individual variance, and as a result, poorer reliability measures. This may also result in a lack of sensitivity of the ISqT, as changes in performance may be masked by the measurement error of the test. Indeed, consistent and validated methodological procedures may help reduce this error, therefore procedures which assist the collection of stable data are important for applied practitioners.

Following the confirmation of a test's reliability, comparing the total error of specific protocols of the same test may further indicate the most appropriate method for performance assessment. Total error is composed of random error and systematic bias with random error the degree to

which differences in test values differ due to biological variation or mechanical variation. Systematic bias means a performance test contains a consistent measurement error across trials as a result of changes in measurement protocol or the technical bias of the measurement tool (Atkinson and Nevill, 1998). Reliability as a result refers to the reproducibility of the ISqT, where reproducibility in turn is the extent a test provides similar values between two testing points within close proximity.

Learning effects may occur when conducting performance testing, thus resulting in improved performance even in the absence of any true physiological or neurological adaptations (Maffiuletti *et al.*, 2016) increasing within-individual measurement variance (Drake, Kennedy and Wallace, 2018). Regarding the ISqT, the familiarisation effects on performance have been observed to fade following three familiarisation sessions, each consisting of three maximum 5-second efforts (Drake, Kennedy and Wallace, 2018). However, no research has yet evaluated the familiarisation effects on ISqT performance among youth athletes (Drake, Kennedy and Wallace, 2017). This is an important consideration for practitioners, as motor learning and control differences between youth and adults would likely result in data stabilising at different rates.

Although including reliable and validated performance tests is of paramount importance to Strength and Conditioning professionals, so too should be promoting optimum engagement in the athletes they work with. Indeed, the inclusion of autonomy-supportive practices has numerous performance-focused (Halperin *et al.*, 2018) benefits. For example, the ability to exert influence over one's own environment results in enhanced feelings of psychological contentment (Deci and Ryan, 2000) due to neuroscientific gratification (Leotti and Delgado, 2011). Maximal force and power related outputs may also stabilise at the same rate when performing isometric performance tests utilising an autonomous self-determined (SDet) body position compared to a pre-determined (PDet) body position (Comfort *et al.*, 2015). Additionally, a simple provision of choice may improve training adherence (Silva *et al.*, 2011), motor learning and performance (Wulf and Lewthwaite, 2016), accuracy (Post *et al.*, 2014) and balance (Chiviacowsky *et al.*, 2012). Therefore, there may also be a psychological benefit to the addition of choice provision during an ISqT. Practitioners may opt to utilise autonomous testing protocols due to a reduced assessment time resulting from not needing to standardise body positions alongside a need for less equipment such as goniometers.

In addition to maximal isometric tests of strength and power, dynamic actions which represent different aspects of the stretch shortening cycle should also be assessed within an athlete testing battery. The counter-movement jump (CMJ) is frequently used for this reason (Dobbs *et al.*, 2020; Kennedy and Drake, 2021). Indeed, Meylan *et al.* (2012) investigated GRF variables among youth and reported jump tests as reliable performance assessments irrespective of age or maturity status. In addition, jump ability may discriminate between playing standard in youth soccer, with players of a higher standard typically achieving greater jump performances (Dugdale *et al.*, 2019).

Sprint tests over distances ranging from 5 m to 40 m (Rumpf *et al.*, 2011) are consistently used to determine the speed capabilities of soccer players. Distances below 20 m are typically chosen to describe the acceleration ability of an athlete, with longer distances used to illustrate the maximum speed capability of the athlete (Mendez-Villanueva *et al.*, 2011a; Paul and Nassis, 2015). The importance of speed and acceleration capacities are unequivocal, with demonstrated differences observed between playing standards, age group, maturity status groups, and experience levels in youth soccer (Dugdale *et al.*, 2019). In addition, the reliability of sprint assessments has shown reliability on multiple occasions (Dugdale *et al.*, 2019; Paul and Nassis, 2015; Rumpf *et al.*, 2011), highlighting the useability of these tests in applied settings.

Youth athletes typically compete within age groups according to their chronological age (Cobley *et al.*, 2009), which has previously been suggested to favour chronologically older individuals born earlier in the selection year (Dugdale, McRobert and Unnithan, 2021; Helsen, van Winckel and Williams, 2005; Vaeyens, Philippaerts and Malina, 2005). This is termed as the relative age effect (RAE), and it has been observed to occur across a variety of competitive standards as a result of the perception that chronologically older players possess a more progressed maturity status (Kelly *et al.*, 2020). The RAE has been proposed to occur within youth sport corroborated by the extensive literature reporting that individuals born earlier in the selection year possess superior somatic growth such as increased height and mass (Cobley *et al.*, 2009).

The selection of individuals based on these physical attributes has previously been thought to occur due to individuals possessing a more advanced biological status and, in turn, possessing greater physical and functional performance characteristics (Cobley *et al.*, 2009; Doncaster, Iga and Unnithan, 2018). Indeed, maturation stage is suggested to be strongly related to the

ability to gain improvements in muscular strength and power throughout adolescence (Morris *et al.*, 2018b). Hormonal changes (Murray and Clayton, 2013) occur as an individual, males in particular, transition towards a more mature state. This transition from pre-peak height velocity (PHV) to circa-PHV and finally post-PHV, can result in varying abilities to express maximum force between these phases (Morris *et al.*, 2018b). In addition, less mature individuals typically develop muscular strength and power following training interventions at a slower rate compared to their more mature counterparts (Dobbs *et al.*, 2020). In addition, compared to that of less mature, more mature individuals have been observed to have greater muscle thicknesses, an important contributor to force production (Narici *et al.*, 1996; Radnor *et al.*, 2020). This maturation-related difference may therefore demonstrate why the selection of individuals after these ages tends to favour the more physically mature (Malina *et al.*, 2007).

The reduced potential for muscular strength and power adaptations among immature individuals have been suggested to stem from the delayed skeletal muscle mass changes (Ozmun, Mikesky and Surburg, 1994). It appears while immature (Ozmun, Mikesky and Surburg, 1994) or untrained (Dons *et al.*, 1979) individuals attain strength and power improvements due to neurological adaptations, further gains are likely heavily reliant upon physiological adaptations (i.e., muscle size; O'Brien *et al.*, 2010b). When aiming to increase muscle size characteristics, programme duration is an important consideration. Indeed, equivocal results of training interventions' efficacy on improving muscle morphological characteristics have been demonstrated in the literature. These differences may be due to the contrasting durations employed in each individual study (McKinlay *et al.*, 2018; Secomb *et al.*, 2015a; Secomb *et al.*, 2017). Given the differences in results from interventions ~8 weeks in duration, it can be assumed interventions may need to be longer to attain improvements in muscle morphological characteristics. In agreement, research shows much more consistent results in youth individuals when intervention periods have been longer in duration than this 8-week duration (Gavanda *et al.*, 2019; Kanehisa *et al.*, 2006; Mersmann *et al.*, 2017).

1.2 Aims and objectives of the thesis

1.2.1 Broad aim of the thesis

The aforementioned considerations present in applied settings and the existent literature surrounding the strength and power development of youth soccer players results in the need for

further research in this area. Broadly, this thesis will aim to investigate the extent adolescent youth soccer players develop global strength, speed and power performance longitudinally. The authors specifically aimed to provide an objective quantification of the performance improvements attributable to the impact of growth and maturation and specific training.

Specifically, the reliability of an autonomy supportive self-determined ISqT protocol for use with youth athletes will be determined. The next broad aim is to determine the ability of the ISqT as a surrogate of physical performance measures of youth soccer players. The following aim is to evaluate the influence of gym and pitch-based training on changes in ISqT, CMJ and sprint performance. The final study aims to evaluate the effect of training adaptations on changes in muscle ultrastructure.

1.2.2 Specific aims of the thesis

Aim 1: To determine the reliability of two isometric squat protocols in youth soccer players.

Objective 1: To determine the inter-day reliability of a pre-determined ISqT protocol and a self-determined protocol.

Objective 2: Investigate the effects of familiarisation on force-time outputs of the ISqT.

Objective 3: To compare ISqT outputs obtained via a traditional PDet and a SDet protocol.

Aim 2: To explore the relationships between reliable ISqT metrics determined in study and dynamic proxies of performance.

Objective 1: Determine the relationship between different ISqT metric and dynamic measures of speed and power capabilities.

Objective 2: Calculate how changes in ISqT performance relate to changes in dynamic performance measures.

Aim 3: Examine the impact of a structured, targeted strength and conditioning programme on the development of strength, speed, and power adaptations in adolescent youth soccer players over an 8–9-month period.

Objective 1: Determine the extent of change in strength, speed, and power-based performance measures over a 12-month period in elite youth soccer players.

Objective 2: Compare changes in strength, speed, and power-based performance between professional and recreational youth soccer players.

Objective 3: Examine the influence of maturation and its interaction with training standards on the development of strength, speed, and power capabilities in well-trained and recreational youth soccer players.

Aim 4: Establish the Musculo-skeletal morphological adaptations in elite youth soccer players over a full competitive season.

Objective 1: Determine the changes in vastus lateralis muscle morphology over a 9-month period in elite adolescent soccer players.

Figure 1.1 outlines the organisation of the thesis chapters.

Figure 1.1: Organisation of thesis chapters.

Chapter 2.0

Literature review

2.1 Literature review background, aims and rationale

Alongside the development of technical, tactical, and psychological skills and abilities, physical and athletic development are fundamental aspects of youth soccer development programmes. Soccer is an intermittent sport with reliance on the contribution of both aerobic and anaerobic metabolisms to total energy requirements (Stølen *et al.*, 2005b). Evaluation of youth soccer match metabolic demands illustrates a high anaerobic energy contribution (Aslan *et al.*, 2012) due to a large reliance on high intensity efforts such as sprinting, acceleration, deceleration, changes of direction, and jumping activities (Bangsbo, Mohr and Krstrup, 2006). Lower limb neuromuscular and force capability development is of utmost importance for youth soccer development programmes given their strong association with sprint speed (Comfort *et al.*, 2014; Thomas *et al.*, 2015; Wisloff *et al.*, 2004), change of direction performance (Appleby, Cormack and Newton, 2020; Thomas *et al.*, 2015), and jumping ability (Comfort *et al.*, 2014; Cormie, McGuigan and Newton, 2010; Wisloff *et al.*, 2004). Additionally, force and power production capabilities have been shown to discriminate between different playing standards (Barker *et al.*, 1993; Wisloff, Helgerud and Hoff, 1998).

As youth soccer athletes develop and progress towards a more mature state, the changes observed due to natural development have large implications for practitioners working with youth populations (Philippaerts *et al.*, 2006). The maturation related developmental changes therefore have been suggested as a large reason why the selection of individuals for participation in team sports tends to favour the more physically mature (Malina *et al.*, 2007). Changes in stature observed during maturation in males are accompanied by changes in an individual's amount of skeletal muscle mass (McCarthy *et al.*, 2014). Evaluation within youth soccer shows that these changes observed as a result of maturation translate into improvements in speed, force, and power capabilities (Malina *et al.*, 2004; Morris *et al.*, 2018; Murtagh *et al.*, 2018a).

The capability of force production is defined as the ability to accelerate or decelerate mass:

$$Force = mass \times acceleration$$

Where the force produced by a body is determined by both its mass and its acceleration, the acceleration of a body in any given direction is proportional to the force applied and its direction. In addition, inertia is the ability of a body to change its velocity, a stationary body's inertia is therefore defined solely by its mass. However, the ability of a body to overcome inertia can be defined by momentum, which is equal to the body's impulse:

$$\Delta Force \times \Delta Time = mass \times \Delta Velocity$$

Therefore, an individual's ability to carry out intensive dynamic actions such as those mentioned above, can be measured while the body is stationary via the left side of the formula above. Similarly, the elements which determine muscular power can be illustrated through the following:

$$Power = \frac{Work\ done}{\Delta Time}$$

In addition, given the formula for work done is:

$$Force \times Displacement$$

the formula for power can be rewritten as:

$$Power = Force \times \frac{Displacement}{\Delta Time}$$

and finally:

$$Power = Force \times Velocity$$

Therefore, the development, and accurate quantification of these elements, in particular maximum force and the rate of force production capabilities, should be of importance to practitioners aiming to improve these qualities (e.g., power). Indeed, force testing outputs have previously shown to discriminate between individuals based on their running speed (Tillin, Pain and Folland, 2013), although, they may require the use of expensive equipment (Hori *et al.*, 2009). Isometric testing has many benefits as mentioned previously (see Chapter 1), such

as the reduced time needed to carry out the testing. However, there is currently a sparsity of research evaluating the reliability of these types of tests in youth populations. This would be of great benefit to practitioners working within a youth sporting environment, as ensuring a performance test is reliable will grant accurate and unbiased within- and between-athlete comparisons of physical measurements. It is also of relevance to the applied practitioner to help delineate the influence of growth and maturation related variations in performance from the biological and technical error of a test among youth cohorts.

Despite isometric testing being commonly carried out utilising specific body configurations to ensure stability of measures (Brady, Harrison and Comyns, 2020), recent data suggest an autonomous body configuration during isometric testing to yield similarly reliability values when compared to predetermined 'controlled' lower body joint angles (Comfort *et al.*, 2015; Thomas *et al.*, 2017). Athletes' motivation is largely impacted by their perceived control over the current task and/or the surrounding environment (Eitam, Kennedy and Tory, 2013). This construct represents the underpinning conceptual rationale of well renowned theories such as the self-determination theory (Deci and Ryan, 2000) and the optimising performance through intrinsic motivation and attention for learning theory (OPTIMAL) (Wulf and Lewthwaite, 2016). Autonomy supportive conditions during exercise, tasks, or movements have been shown as an effective catalyst for improving motor learning and performance (Wulf and Lewthwaite, 2016). Positive effects of choice provision have been observed on movement velocity and force output (Halperin *et al.*, 2017), grip strength (Iwatsuki *et al.*, 2017), lower limb leg press strength (McNamara and Stearne, 2010), and volume of work undertaken via resistance training (Wulf, Freitas and Tandy, 2014; Rauch *et al.*, 2020). However, there is a current lack of research examining the effects of self-determination on the reliability of assessment measures, particularly among youth cohorts. Additionally, the use of a previously validated questionnaire for the evaluation of players' perceptions of autonomy within a youth soccer setting could help explain the variance to programming often displayed by groups of athletes. Indeed, autonomy supportive conditions have previously been shown to produce contrasting results following specific training interventions when compared to that of pre-determined and controlled conditions (Halperin *et al.*, 2016; Halperin *et al.*, 2017; Halperin *et al.*, 2018; McNamara and Stearne, 2010). For example, when evaluating the efficacy of different potentiation protocols on jumping performance, Dello Iacono, Beato and Halperin (2020) compared self-selecting the potentiation volume of exercise, with a pre-determined volume of exercise, and an imposed volume consisting of the same volume as the self-selected condition but imposed by the

researcher. It was found that the self-selected condition lead to enhanced jumping performance and mechanical efficiency when compared to both contrasting conditions (Dello Iacono, Beato and Halperin, 2020). Questionnaires may therefore help elucidate the efficacy of strategies aimed at improving perceptions of autonomy within an elite sporting environment for the purposes of learning, development, and engagement (Eitam, Kennedy and Tory, 2013).

The current review firstly aims to discuss the demands of youth soccer performance in relation to muscular strength and power. The physiological adaptations that underpin muscular force production capabilities and power will also be reviewed with a specific focus on youth populations and with respect to maturity. This review also aims to discuss muscular strength and power assessment, and specifically summarise the available literature on the use of the isometric squat, its validity constructs, reliability, and methodological considerations for an effective implementation. Finally, the available research which details the positive mediating effects of choice provision upon performance-related tasks will also be discussed.

2.3 Methods

A search was undertaken of databases PubMed, SPORTdiscus and Web of Science from inception until the 19th of October 2023 inclusive. The search details are shown in Figure 2.1. The following syntax was initially utilised within each database and applied to the title, abstract and keyword search fields to search for isometric squat related literature: (“isometric*”) AND (“squat*” OR “strength”). A secondary search strategy was then applied to further select articles from the initial pool. The inclusion criteria were: full-text available and published in English; participants that were athletes or recreationally trained individuals; healthy participants without any musculoskeletal disorders or general clinical health disorders; maximal isometric contractions of at least 3 seconds; measurement of kinetic data using a force plate (James *et al.*, 2017) with a sampling frequency ≥ 500 Hz for time dependant variables (McMaster *et al.*, 2014), ≥ 25 Hz for peak force measurements (Hori *et al.*, 2009); articles reporting reliability data (e.g., coefficient of variation, intraclass correlation coefficient, typical error of measurement, standard error of measurement); articles reporting normative data or descriptive data from which normative scores could be calculated. Lastly, the reference lists of selected articles were scanned manually to obtain articles not identified electronically through the online search.

Figure 2.1: Flow chart of search strategy and criteria.

A second search was then utilised to attain literature which related to physiological adaptation resulting from force production and power training in youth populations: (“youth” OR “adolescent” OR “young people” OR “teen” OR “children” OR “kids”) AND (“ultrasound” OR “sonography” OR “sonogram” OR “ultrasonography” OR “muscle size” OR “muscle volume” OR “muscle architecture” OR “muscle thickness” OR “cross-sectional area” OR “pennation angle” OR “fascicle length”). Secondly, filtering of the article selection criteria was undertaken. The criteria included: full-text available and published in English; participants that were either athletes or recreationally trained individuals 18 years old or younger (e.g., average age of 18.0 years or less); healthy participants without any musculoskeletal disorders or general clinical health disorders; muscle tissue measurements carried out using magnetic resonance imaging, computerised tomography, ultrasonography or dual energy x-ray absorptiometry; articles reporting normative data or descriptive data of muscles of the lower limbs; articles reporting changes in lean tissue following specific training. Finally, following the search strategies outlined above, the reference lists of selected articles were scanned to obtain articles not previously identified.

2.2 Match demands in elite youth soccer in relation to muscular force production capabilities

The importance of high-intensity intermittent actions in youth soccer is particularly evident through analysis of match locomotive demands. Depending on the age group, soccer players may be required to cover distances of from 4366 ± 478 m at under 9 (U9) (Goto, Morris and Nevill, 2015a), to 10296 ± 683 m at under 18 (U18) (Hunter *et al.*, 2015). Similar to total distance covered, when utilising fixed speed thresholds, peak match running velocities, high intensity running, and high intensity activities have been observed to increase with progressing age within youth soccer (Al Haddad *et al.*, 2015; Bellistri *et al.*, 2017; Goto, Morris and Nevill, 2015b; Vigh-Larsen, Dalgas and Andersen, 2018a). However, this discrepancy may be due to concurrent increments in competitive fixture durations with increasing age group (Goto, Morris and Nevill, 2015b; Goto, Morris and Nevill, 2015a).

Nevertheless, it is evident that the ability to repeatedly produce high intensity movements is a requirement of all age groups within youth soccer, with this demand generally increasing in absolute terms as players increase in age (Al Haddad *et al.*, 2015; Bellistri *et al.*, 2017; Goto, Morris and Nevill, 2015b; Vigh-Larsen, Dalgas and Andersen, 2018a). Furthermore, peak and

high-intensity (> 19 km/h) match running performance have been reported as higher in more mature compared to less mature individuals (Buchheit and Mendez-Villanueva, 2014), indicating that performance capabilities are also related to biological age. The aerobic system is as a result fundamentally key in order to repeatedly produce high intensity anaerobic movement demands; indeed, a high anaerobic energy contribution to youth soccer match metabolic demands has previously been observed irrespective of playing position (Aslan *et al.*, 2012). Similarly, neuromuscular capabilities are an important quality with soccer match play, with these movement demands including the ability to accelerate, decelerate, and jump (Bangsbo, Mohr and Krstrup, 2006). Such movements have previously been observed to constitute the most frequent actions performed prior to goal situations (Faude, Koch and Meyer, 2012) and so are believed to be key to match success (Deprez *et al.*, 2013).

The positive mediating effects of force production capabilities on sprint performance is of particular importance to the applied practitioner as youth soccer players cover on average 1% of the total distance covered (10296 ± 683 m) during soccer match play (Hunter *et al.*, 2015). Moreover, a consistent trend is commonly observed in youth soccer, as younger age groups generally display greater amounts of repeated sprint sequences during match play (Buchheit *et al.*, 2010b); potentially as a result of lower tactical game understanding and reduced technical proficiency (Al Haddad *et al.*, 2015; Mendez-Villanueva *et al.*, 2013). However, as previously mentioned, absolute sprint distance during match play tends to increase with age (Buchheit *et al.*, 2010a), with older players displaying greater acceleration abilities and maximum running speeds, therefore reaching higher velocities and sooner when compared to their younger counterparts (Vigh-Larsen, Dalgas and Andersen, 2018a). Investigations into the physical contributors of sprinting demonstrate that peak ground reaction forces are strong determinants of sprint performance (Wisloff *et al.*, 2004); suggesting that stronger individuals who are better able to express large amounts of force typically perform better during sprint performances (Comfort *et al.*, 2014; Cormie, McGuigan and Newton, 2010; Wisloff *et al.*, 2004). Maximal force capabilities are therefore of utmost importance in youth soccer players as to efficiently exploit the kinetic determinants of high-speed running.

Similarly, as total sprint durations during youth soccer are typically less than 3 seconds (Buchheit *et al.*, 2010b), the ability to rapidly generate momentum and accelerate during match play is paramount to reach peak running velocities as quickly as possible. Due to differences in tactical roles between positions, research illustrates contrasting evidence on the number of

accelerations carried out within each playing position (Bloomfield, Polman and O'Donoghue, 2007; Ingebrigtsen *et al.*, 2015). Nevertheless, observational analyses investigating the time-motion characteristics of youth match play indicate players perform accelerative type movements ($\geq 2 \text{ m/s}^2$) on average 119.0 ± 17.8 to 185.2 ± 30.1 times within match play, depending on playing position (Pettersen and Brenn, 2019). The ability to rapidly accelerate is undoubtedly important for soccer match play not just for each playing position (Pettersen and Brenn, 2019), but also at all competitive levels (Delaney *et al.*, 2018). Indeed, previous research has shown similar total number of accelerations in youth players as in senior soccer players (Vigh-Larsen, Dalgas and Andersen, 2018b), highlighting its developmental importance early on in youth programmes aimed at improving physical competencies. Additionally, research conducted within youth soccer players has displayed strong relationships between acceleration and lower body force production and power capabilities while utilising dynamic multi-joint measures of force and power production (Chelly *et al.*, 2010; Comfort *et al.*, 2014). This indicates the value of enhancing lower body muscular force production and power within soccer development programmes for the development of acceleration.

Agility movements during match play are comprised of a deceleration phase, a change of direction phase (during which the lower limbs act isometrically during foot plant in order to reposition the body), and a reacceleration phase (Dempsey *et al.*, 2007), in response to a stimulus. Due to the multi-directional nature of soccer, youth players are required to perform ~ 300 changes of direction per game (Morgan *et al.*, 2022). This requires the need for players to develop sufficient force and power capabilities of the lower limbs in order to tolerate the substantial braking ground reaction forces (GRF) required during deceleration actions (Spiteri, Hart and Nimphius, 2014). This is potentially why improvements in lower body force and power capabilities have been shown to occur alongside improvements in change of direction performance (Appleby, Cormack and Newton, 2020). This is important not only for change of direction performance but also for mitigating injury risk associated with these movements given the higher physiological cost associated with accelerations (Osgnach *et al.*, 2010) and multiple changes of direction (Tang *et al.*, 2018).

Scientific evidence suggests that muscular force and power attributes directly transfer to proxies of soccer performance such as sprint, acceleration, and deceleration abilities. Therefore, it would seem good practice for long term athletic development programmes to enhance force and power capabilities to support a player's effective progressive transition from

one age group to the next. This recommendation relies on research indicating older age groups to possess greater physical attributes related to force and power characteristics compared to younger age groups (Mendez-Villanueva *et al.*, 2011a; Spiteri, Hart and Nimphius, 2014). Indeed, it has been suggested that if physical characteristics are a discriminant quality of elite players compared to players of a lesser playing standard, it is indicative of a physical determinant necessary for this standard of performance (Reilly *et al.*, 2000). Recent research evaluating the relationship between these components of fitness and different proxies of performance confirm this claim (Comfort *et al.*, 2014; Thomas *et al.*, 2015). Future research should evaluate the changes in force and power characteristics within youth soccer players because of specific training, and assess how these changes transfer to different measures of physical performance.

2.4 The effect of maturation on muscular force and power in youth soccer athletes

As youth soccer athletes develop and progress towards a more mature state due to the vast changes in an individual's hormonal milieu (Murray and Clayton, 2013), such changes have large implications for practitioners working with youth populations (Philippaerts *et al.*, 2006). The beginning of adolescence is identified by the onset of puberty; as activation of the hypothalamo-pituitary-gonadal axis greatly elevates circulating levels of hormones including growth hormone, insulin-like growth factor 1 and sex hormones, predominantly testosterone in boys and oestrogen in girls (Malina, Bouchard and Bar-Or, 2004; Murray and Clayton, 2013). This in turn stimulates the development of somatic and sexual maturity (Murray and Clayton, 2013) leading to a rapid increase in body stature, which is followed by increases in body mass around 6 months later (Malina, Bouchard and Bar-Or, 2004). These periods are commonly referred to as PHV and peak weight velocity (PWV), respectively. The onset of puberty commonly starts between the ages of 11–12 years old in boys, and 10–11 years old in girls, with PHV typically commencing in males around 14 years old and around 12 years old in females (Malina, Bouchard and Bar-Or, 2004; Malina *et al.*, 2004) and lasting on average until 6 months–1 year post-PHV (Malina and Bouchard, 2004; Philippaerts *et al.*, 2006).

Alongside dramatic changes in body height observed as a result of PHV, PWV is accompanied by changes in an individual's overall amount of skeletal muscle mass, especially in males (McCarthy *et al.*, 2014). This increase in skeletal muscle mass occurs to a greater extent in

males as opposed to females, mostly due to the larger amounts of the circulating hormone testosterone (McCarthy *et al.*, 2014); as testosterone has been found to directly stimulate muscle protein synthesis (Griggs *et al.*, 1989; Mauras *et al.*, 1998), and inhibit muscle protein breakdown (Demling and Orgill, 2000; Zhao *et al.*, 2008) as a result of its active uptake by intracellular androgen receptors. This is of particular importance to the developing athlete, as the effects of increased circulating testosterone may result in improved force and power capabilities (Malina *et al.*, 2004).

Cross-sectional studies within youth soccer indicates that these somatic and skeletal muscle-related changes that are observed because of maturation have also been seen to translate into performance related improvements in speed, force, and power capabilities (Malina *et al.*, 2004; Morris *et al.*, 2018b; Murtagh *et al.*, 2018a). Similarly, it has been shown that the development of these qualities differs depending on maturity status, with pre-PHV cohorts typically displaying smaller increments in absolute force production capabilities post intervention compared with circa- or post-PHV individuals (Dobbs *et al.*, 2020; Lloyd *et al.*, 2016; Meylan *et al.*, 2014; Moran *et al.*, 2018). A meta-analysis including interventions of 4–16 weeks duration confirmed such assumptions, with circa- and post-PHV cohorts displaying greater increases in force production capabilities following resistance training when compared to pre-PHV cohorts (Moran *et al.*, 2017a). However, from the results of Moran *et al.* (2017a) it is unclear whether the observed differences were a direct effect of the training plan, or simply occurring due to the inherent maturity-related changes in physical capacities.

This data may be obtained either from observational research conducted specifically on youth cohorts throughout adolescence, through the evaluation of control group related changes in performance tests within intervention studies, or through evaluation of baseline values between maturity status groups. To this end, the previously mentioned meta-analysis by Moran *et al.* (2017a) did include a brief analysis of the changes in muscular force generating outputs observed in control groups of the included intervention studies, and found moderate (effect size [ES] = 0.7) increases in force capabilities within control groups. However, the results of this sub-analysis are to be interpreted with caution as the meta-analysis only included studies of 4–16 week durations (Moran *et al.*, 2017a). Although sufficient to provide preliminary clues for the interaction between training and maturation, within this timeframe, maturation related changes in performance are unlikely to have exerted a significant influence in the absence of additional specific training (Dobbs *et al.*, 2020); a longer duration for evaluation is required to

evaluate this research question. This has been shown in previous studies of similar (4–16 weeks) durations which report no significant change in performance measures over time in the absence of specific training (Dobbs *et al.*, 2020; Moran *et al.*, 2018; Peña-González *et al.*, 2019). For example, Dobbs *et al.* (2020) observed no statistically significant changes in any force production or power related performance measures within either the pre- or post-PHV (maturity offset: -2.28 ± 0.67 and 1.20 ± 0.48 , respectively) control group athletes from a sporting academy following a 12-week period.

Results from a longer duration study by Sander *et al.* (2013) may better allude to the maturation related changes in performance measures. In a 2-year investigation, Sander *et al.* (2013) investigated the influence of training on muscular strength in elite youth soccer players of the under-13 (U13), 15 (U15) and 17 (U17) age groups (at the beginning of the intervention) additional to their routine soccer training, and compared the performance test results to a control group only participating in soccer training. U13, U15 and U17 participants only undertaking regular soccer training showed $29.2 \pm 22.7\%$, $67.0 \pm 51.4\%$ and $59.7 \pm 43.4\%$ improvements in 1 repetition maximum (1RM) back squat ability, respectively. Considering the changes in force performance were found significant only for the U15 group, it can be assumed that individuals who are presumably circa-PHV may be more prone to increases in force production capabilities than post-PHV cohorts, and this may occur as a result of maturation alone. However, maturation status was not directly measured in the study by Sander *et al.* (2013) so the results being theorised as due to discrepancies in maturation status between the three groups is based solely off average growth and maturation trends previously observed in European boys (Malina and Bouchard, 2004). Therefore, the need for well-designed longitudinal studies that quantify the maturational change over time are required to elucidate the answers to this question.

The lack of significance observed within the U17 control group in the aforementioned study by Sander *et al.* (2013) may be due to the large variance observed in this group; this is possibly due to a variance in maturity status as less players would be statistically likely to be circa-PHV (Malina and Bouchard, 2004) and therefore less likely to gain improvement in force production capabilities naturally. A similar trend was observed in a study by Vantinen *et al.* (2011) who noted significant increases in absolute isometric leg press force output within youth soccer players from 12 to 17 years old with peak increases being observed from 14 to 15 years old, which coincided with relative growth rates which also peaked at 14 years old. In this study

spanning 2 years, the performance changes of a youth soccer cohort aged 11–17 years were assessed, with comparisons to chronological age-matched recreational controls also made. It was found that although the youth soccer players displayed greater values in the U17 age group when compared to controls, presumably due to their athletic status, training years, and sport-specific background, the ability of all other age groups to produce force isometrically was non significantly different compared to controls (Vänttinen *et al.*, 2011).

Similar findings were also observed in an earlier study conducted over a 2-year period which aimed to compare the development of force production ability between elite and non-elite youth soccer players (Hansen *et al.*, 1999). Hansen *et al.* (1999) reported while higher levels of knee extension force production capacities were observed among elite youth male soccer players, the increase in force production capabilities over time was similar compared to the non-elite cohort. Similar to the aforementioned study by Sander *et al.* (2013), maturity status was not measured in either of the previously cited studies (Hansen *et al.*, 1999; Vänttinen *et al.*, 2011). However, both studies measured serum testosterone concentrations and reported similar findings. For example, Vänttinen *et al.* (2011) found a progressive relative increase in testosterone from 11–17 years old, with changes between 12–13 and 14–15 years old reaching statistical significance. Additionally, Hansen *et al.* (1999) also reported a progressive increase in absolute serum testosterone concentrations from ~12 years old to ~14 years old. As mentioned previously, growth is stimulated approximately 6 months to 1 year following this endocrinological change. It can therefore be theorised that the players in these studies experienced their PHV at a similar time to the reported average for European males (e.g., 14 years old in boys) (Malina, Bouchard and Bar-Or, 2004). Taken together, the results of these studies suggest that soccer training alone does not induce significant improvements in force production capabilities throughout adolescence, and natural changes in maturity status may account for a larger proportion of the change observed in youth soccer players' force production capabilities. However, controlling for longitudinal changes in maturity status limits our understanding of the efficacy of training compared to growth on changes in force production capabilities. More research is therefore needed in this area to fully explain this indeed.

In a previous study 5 years in duration, participants were grouped according to their maturity timing, as to assess maturation related change on knee extension force production capabilities in youth male soccer players (Duarte *et al.*, 2018). Duarte *et al.* (2018) observed greater increments in lower limb force production ability for youths who's maturity status was more

advanced (e.g., early maturing individuals) when compared their lesser biologically mature counterparts (e.g., on time and late maturing). This was observed across all age groups from under-11 (U11) to U15 but not the U16 age group, demonstrating an effect of biological maturity on lower limb force production ability. This also indicates, that although skeletal maturity may determine the extent of which individuals differ physically throughout adolescence, this variation largely disappears towards the end of adolescence (i.e., up to 1-year post-PHV).

The reduced level of force production related adaptations observed within biologically immature cohorts has previously been suggested to be due to an inability to attain significant increases in muscle mass of the trained limbs. This has previously been shown to occur in studies that have found nonsignificant changes in skeletal muscle mass as a result of training in pre-PHV cohorts despite improvements in muscle activation (Ozmun, Mikesky and Surburg, 1994); leading to the understanding that adaptations of the neurological system are predominantly responsible for changes in force production capability within this group (Ramsay *et al.*, 1990).

A major limitation of previous research investigating the effect of maturity status on the development of physical force and power characteristics (Dobbs *et al.*, 2020; Lloyd *et al.*, 2016; Meylan *et al.*, 2014; Peña-González *et al.*, 2019; Radnor, Lloyd and Oliver, 2017; Radnor *et al.*, 2020) is the use of the predicted age at PHV using the maturity offset equation (Mirwald *et al.*, 2002). This is a non-invasive anthropometric based method which calculates maturity offset, an estimate of time to PHV. While this method is time- and cost-effective as well as non-invasive, it has been previously questioned due to a major limitation. In fact, it likely overestimates the maturity status of early maturers and underestimates the maturity status of late maturers (Kozieł and Malina, 2018; Malina and Kozieł, 2014a; Malina and Kozieł, 2014b). Although the direct assessment of skeletal age or current hormone levels is expensive and invasive, practitioners may instead consider to alternatively estimate maturity status based on individual current height expressed as a percentage of estimated adult height (%EAH) (Khamis and Roche, 1994). The %EAH method is a non-invasive, cost-effective, and only requires the record of a few easily accessible information such as chronological age, standing stature, body mass, and biological mid-parent height (Khamis and Roche, 1994). This method has recently proven as superior at predicting elite youth soccer players' age at PHV using a window of 85–96 %EAH when compared to an age window based on maturity offset (Parr *et al.*, 2020).

Available research shows that the pubertal period of development which contains PHV brings about substantial changes which may improve performance related measures (Malina *et al.*, 2004; Morris *et al.*, 2018; Murtagh *et al.*, 2018). This may confound the results of intervention and observational studies if maturation status is not accurately measured or adequately controlled for. Future research evaluating the effect of interventions on youth populations should include an age- and maturity-matched control group to attempt to delineate the changes observed because of programming, and those observed as a result of changes in maturation status. Researchers should also carefully consider the method of maturity status prediction, and be aware of the potential validity and reliability issues which accompany their chosen method.

2.5 The physiological determinants of muscular force production capabilities and power

Skeletal muscle adapts neurologically and morphologically to training via exposure to mechanical load, neural activation, changes in endocrinological levels, and metabolite accumulation (Flück and Hoppeler, 2003; Folland and Williams, 2007; Kraemer and Ratamess, 2005). It has previously been shown that neural adaptations typically precede morphological changes to skeletal muscle (Behringer *et al.*, 2011; Ozmun, Mikesky and Surburg, 1994), and are essentially learning related changes in coordination which potentiate activation and recruitment of targeted muscles (Folland and Williams, 2007). Evidence reports meaningful changes in force capabilities unaccompanied by changes in muscle size in children (Ozmun, Mikesky and Surburg, 1994; Mota, Stock and Thompson, 2017), and disproportionately greater gains in dynamic compared to isometric force production capabilities (Dons *et al.*, 1979). This may indirectly allude to the important role neurological adaptations play in adaptation to resistance and power training. However, neurological adaptations are typically less pronounced in trained compared to untrained individuals following a training intervention, potentially indicating individuals reach transitory ceiling effects relatively soon following the initial adaptation phase (Baratta *et al.*, 1988; Mitchell *et al.*, 2011). Therefore, it appears that force production related adaptations are initially induced primarily through neural adaptations, and that further improvements are likely attributed to a combination of neural and morphological adaptations (Moritani and deVries, 1979; Seynnes, de Boer and Narici, 2007).

The morphological characteristics that determine force production of skeletal muscle tissue are likely related to changes in muscle size (Narici *et al.*, 1996), architecture (Kawakami *et al.*,

1995), and composition (Dons *et al.*, 1979). Determining the changes in these components as a result of training allows practitioners to design more in depth, effective, and functionally specific training interventions in order to enhance performance (Cormie, McGuigan and Newton, 2010). Although determining changes in fibre type may provide useful information regarding the composition changes observed as a result of training, measurement of these changes require muscle biopsies which pose serious ethical issues when considering its use within youth populations. Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), computerised tomography (CT), and ultrasonography (US) are typically utilised to evaluate the underpinning morphological changes in skeletal muscle that drive force production and power adaptations (Folland and Williams, 2007). MRI and US do not subject the participants to ionizing radiation and therefore may be ethically better suited for use within paediatric populations when compared to the significant levels observed with CT (Ngan *et al.*, 2003). MRI is currently considered the gold standard measurement method due to its higher resolution (Lieber and Ward, 2011), however, is expensive, time consuming, and difficult to administer given the complexity of its equipment (Narici, 1999). US on the other hand is more time and cost efficient, is easier to administer (Narici, 1999), and has shown to be a reliable measure of muscle characteristics within youth populations (Legerlotz, Smith and Hing, 2010).

Changes in muscle size and architecture are typically associated with strength and conditioning specific activities. However, activities performed during technical/tactical pitch based sessions may also contribute to changes in muscle morphological characteristics (Vanrenterghem *et al.*, 2017). Indeed, regardless of the source of mechanical stress, both structural and functional adaptations occur directly as a result of the subsequent skeletal muscle tissue damage and repair (Wang *et al.*, 2013). Soccer players are consistently subject to mechanical stresses via a range of locomotive demands such as accelerations, decelerations, jumping, and running activities. The primary biomechanical adaptations to the muscular system associated with these types of activities are changes to fascicle length, pennation angle, and muscle size (Wisdom, Delp and Kuhl, 2015), and may differ in nature and response rate to typical physiological adaptations (Vanrenterghem *et al.*, 2017). In addition, whether the adaptative response to conditioning, or technical drills are primarily physiological or biomechanical in nature is in turn dependent upon the characteristics of the drill, such as running intensity (Buchheit and Laursen, 2013) or relative area size (Gaudino, Alberti and Iaia, 2014; Hill-Haas *et al.*, 2011; Köklü *et al.*, 2011). As a result, training drills (or days) may elicit higher biomechanical loads depending on the technical focus, with smaller relative spaces typically eliciting a higher biomechanical load

(Hill-Haas *et al.*, 2011; Gaudino, Alberti and Iaia, 2014) which may lead to greater biomechanical adaptations (Bujalance-Moreno, Latorre-Román and García-Pinillos, 2019), potentially due to a higher number of accelerations and decelerations (Hodgson, Akenhead and Thomas, 2014).

It therefore seems necessary to elucidate the physiological adaptations within youth populations, given the potential use of non-invasive and safe equipment (Legerlotz, Smith and Hing, 2010) and the practical relevance these insights would have for the applied practitioner (Cormie, McGuigan and Newton, 2010). Despite this, there is currently a sparsity of available literature specifically examining the underpinning changes to the muscular system (e.g., muscle thickness, architecture) as a result of training interventions in youth populations (Legerlotz *et al.*, 2016). To provide information on the available literature, normative data, inconsistencies and relevant gaps, a systematic review was carried out. Figure 2.1 details the search strategy and criteria, with available evidence synthesised and presented within the following sections.

2.5.1 Muscle size changes as a result of training

Muscle fibres are exposed to increased mechanical loads during strength training which leads to structural adaptations related to an increased number of sarcomeres being generated, and ultimately an increased muscle size (Johnson and Klueber, 1991). The maximal amount of force a muscle can exploit is dependent upon the number of sarcomeres arranged in parallel (Goldspink, 1985), and so a strong association exists between muscle size and muscular force output (Narici *et al.*, 1996).

While force production increments pre-PHV may be limited primarily to neural influences (Ozmun, Mikesky and Surburg, 1994), large amounts of testosterone during adolescence mediate the development of muscle volume increases throughout PWV (McCarthy *et al.*, 2014). As such, morphology of individual muscle groups displays increases in muscle volume, muscle length, and anatomical cross-sectional area (ACSA) (O'Brien *et al.*, 2010a; Radnor *et al.*, 2020; Radnor *et al.*, 2022), leading to an increase in total muscle mass (particularly in males) as a result of maturation (McCarthy *et al.*, 2014).

In a recent study, Radnor *et al.* (2020) evaluated the differences of muscle morphology characteristics between pre-, circa-, and post-PHV school children (Table 2.1). Muscle

thickness (MT) values of the vastus lateralis (VL) and gastrocnemius medialis showed a strong relationship with biological age, with individuals of a more biologically advanced status displaying greater values compared to their less mature counterparts (e.g., post-PHV > circa-PHV > pre-PHV) (Radnor *et al.*, 2020). However, this study employed a cross-sectional study design to infer a longitudinal interaction between maturation and morphological changes in the screened musculature.

To this end, research (Radnor *et al.*, 2022; Sekine, Hoshikawa and Hirose, 2019) has examined the development of skeletal musculature in groups of varying maturity status (pre-, circa-, and post-PHV) and timing (early-, mid-, or late-maturing) over 12- to 18-month periods. It was displayed in the study by Radnor *et al.* (2022) that individuals who were post-PHV at both the start and retest time points, which were 18 months apart, displayed greater increases in gastrocnemius medialis and VL muscle thickness. In agreement, Sekine, Hoshikawa and Hirose (2019) display higher rates of growth for some (rectus femoris [RF] and biceps brachii) of the muscle groups at baseline (Table 2.2) for early-maturing (chronological age > 6 months after predicted age at PHV) individuals compared to mid- (chronological age within 6 months of predicted age at PHV) and late-maturing (chronological age > 6 months before predicted age at PHV) adolescent (12–14 years old at baseline) male team sport athletes. The athletes participated in a strength and conditioning programme and were assessed for skeletal muscle morphological characteristics on two occasions with an interval of 1 year. However, despite these differences at baseline, when remeasured after 1 year, there were no significant differences between groups for any of the measured musculature, apart from the triceps brachii muscle group (Table 2.1) (Sekine, Hoshikawa and Hirose, 2019). The results of both these studies suggests that maturation status (e.g., pre-, circa-, post-PHV) likely impacts the rate of skeletal muscle growth when combined with regular structured training. Indeed, it could be theorised that the muscle sizes of the mid- and late-maturing participants may develop and ‘catch up’ to comparable sizes of early maturers’ towards the end of PHV and during PWV (Malina, Bouchard and Bar-Or, 2004).

However, Radnor *et al.* (2022) measured participants’ maturity status using the previously mentioned maturity offset method which has been observed to be of limited reliability with both early- and late-maturing individuals (Mirwald *et al.*, 2002). Sekine, Hoshikawa and Hirose

Table 2.1: Research reporting changes in muscle size following training interventions or comparison between groups within youth populations.

Study	Participant information (age)	Sex	Biological age/ Maturation status	Study details	Results
Daly <i>et al.</i> (2004)	Competitive tennis players (8–17 years)	Female	Tanner stages: pre-, mid-, and post- pubertal	Playing arm vs nonplaying arm CSA comparison	Total arm muscle CSA: Pre-pubertal: + 6.7 ± 1.0% * Mid-pubertal: + 7.8 ± 1.4% * Post-pubertal: + 7.8 ± 1.0% *
Eliakim <i>et al.</i> (2001)	Untrained (9.1 ± 0.1 years)	Female	Tanner stages: pre- and early- pubertal	Endurance- type exercise (running, jumping, dance): 5 days/week, 5 weeks	Total thigh mVOL: TG: + 4.3% * CG: + 0.5% Sig. higher mVOL/CSA compared to adolescents observed by Eliakim <i>et al.</i> (1996)
Eliakim <i>et al.</i> (1996)	Untrained (15–17 years)	Female	Not assessed	Endurance- type exercise (running, jumping, dance): 5 days/week, 5- weeks	Total thigh mVOL: TG: + 4.3% *
Fukunaga <i>et al.</i> (1992)	Prepubescent school children (6.9–11.2 years)	Male & female	TW2 (skeletal age): Males: TG1: 6.9 ± 0.3 CG1: 7.0 ± 0.3 TG2: 9.0 ± 0.3 CG2: 9.0 ± 0.2 TG3: 11.0 ± 0.3 CG3: 11.1 ± 0.2 Females: TG1: 7.0 ± 0.3 CG1: 7.0 ± 0.3	Maximum isometric contractions 3/week for 12- weeks	Upper arm musculature CSA Males: TG1: + 5.6% CG1: + 9.7% TG2: + 7.8% * CG2: + 3.2% TG3: + 9.9% * CG3: + 6.5% * Females: TG1: + 13.1% CG1: + 10.6%

			TG2: 9.0 ± 0.4 CG2: 9.0 ± 0.3		TG2: + 9% * CG2: + 5.1%
			TG3: 10.9 ± 0.3 CG3: 11.2 ± 0.2		TG3: + 7.9% CG3: + 9.6% *
Gavanda <i>et al.</i> (2019)	Adolescent American Football players ($17 \pm$ 0.76 years)	Male	Not assessed	12-week block vs undulating periodisation of 3 sessions/week	MT at 60% femur length: Block: RF: + 4.2% * VL: + 7.8% * TB: + 11.6% * Undulating: RF: + 8.3% * VL: + 6.0% * TB: + 8.2% *
Kanehisa <i>et al.</i> (2003)	Junior Olympic weightlifters ($16.4 \pm$ 0.6 years at baseline, 3.4 ± 0.6 years strength training experience)	Male	TW2: Skeletal age at 18- month follow up: 1 participant: adult The remaining 6 participants: 17 years	18-month follow up study	30% femur length: Total CSA: + 30.7% * RF ACSA: + 600% VL ACSA: + 60.0% * VM ACSA: + 11.2% * VI ACSA: + 55.7% * No change in CSA at 50% or 70% femur length
Kanehisa <i>et al.</i> (2006)	Tennis players (10.7–13.2 years)	Male & female	All participants: TW2 skeletal age at baseline: Male: 12.7 years Female: 13.0 years At 2-years: Male: 14.5 years Female: 14.4 years	2-year follow up study	Quadriceps total muscle CSA: 30% femur length: Male: 23.9% * Female: 20.6% * 50% femur length: Male: 26.5% *# Female: 10.1% *# 70% femur length:

						Male: 26.9% *# Female: 9.7% #
McKinlay <i>et al.</i> (2018)	Youth soccer players (11–13 years)	Male	Maturity offset: pre-PHV	8 weeks of resistance or plyometric training		VL MT: Resistance training: + 6.5% * Plyometric training: + 7.5% *
Mersmann <i>et al.</i> (2017)	Late adolescent volleyball athletes (16 ± 1 years at baseline)	Male & female	Not assessed	2-year follow up study		CG: + 0.4% VL: Muscle volume: + 5.4% * ACSA: + 4.1% * Muscle length: + 1.3% VI: Muscle volume: + 8.1% * ACSA: + 4.9% * Muscle length: + 1.7% VM: Muscle volume: + 6.6% * ACSA: + 9.0% * Muscle length: - 1.6%
Metaxes <i>et al.</i> (2014)	Youth soccer players (G1: 11.2 ± 0.4 years; G2: 13.1 ± 0.5 years; G3: 15.2 ± 0.6 years)	Male	Tanner stages: G1: stage 2 G2: stage 3 G3: stage 4	Between age group evaluation		VL fibre type CSA: G3 and G2 had sig. higher fibre CSA's compared to G1 in all fibre types & had more muscle fibres G2 (21.3% *) and G3 less type I fibres compared to G1 G2 more type IIA muscle fibres compared to G1 (18.1% *)
Mota <i>et al.</i> (2017)	School children (12 ± 1 years)	Male	Not assessed	16-week strength and conditioning programme of 2 days/week		Thigh lean mass: TG: + 9.1% CG: + 6.1%

Panidi <i>et al.</i> (2021)	Adolescent (13.5 ± 1.4) volleyball players	Female	Maturity offset (-0.8 ± 0.9)	12 weeks of high-volume static stretching	GM ACSA: + 1.2%
Radnor <i>et al.</i> (2020)	Active pre- (12.5 ± 0.5 years) mid- (14.1 ± 0.7 years) and post- (15.8 ± 1 years) PHV school children	Male	Maturity offset	Cross-sectional analysis	Post- (d = 1.19) and mid- (d = 0.57): sig. larger GM MT (at 30%) than pre-PHV. VL (at 50%) MT: sig. larger for post-compared to mid- (d = 0.72) and pre-(d = 1.39). Mid- sig. larger than pre-PHV (d = 1.06).
Ramsay <i>et al.</i> (1990)	Prepubertal children (9–11 years)	Male	Not assessed	20-week RT 3 times/week	Lean arm CSA: + 2.6% * Elbow flexor CSA: + 7.7% * Leg CSA: + 5.3% * Thigh extensor CSA: + 8.1% *
Ritsche <i>et al.</i> (2021)	Youth soccer players (U13: 12.5 ± 0.1 years; U14: 13.5 ± 0.3 years; U15: 14.4 ± 0.3 years)	Not reported	Not assessed	Cross-sectional analysis	BFlh ACSA: U14 vs U13: + 12.4% U15 vs U14: + 19.8% U15 vs U13: + 36.8%
Secomb <i>et al.</i> (2015)	Competitive surfers (15.1 ± 1.4 years)	Not reported	Not assessed	Strength training 2 sessions/week for 7 weeks	VL (at 50% femur length) MT: + 4.9% * GL MT: - 2.1%
Secomb <i>et al.</i> (2017)	Competitive surfers (14 ± 1.8 years)	Not reported	Not assessed	Cross-over study design: strength training or gymnastics and plyometric 2 sessions/week for 7 weeks VL measured at 50% femur length	RT: VL MT: + 1.9% GL MT: + 2.8% Gymnastics and plyometrics: VL MT: + 3.0% GL MT: + 7.9% *

Sekine <i>et al.</i> (2019)	At baseline: Early (13.3 ± 0.6 years), mid (12.8 ± 0.4 years) or late (13.1 ± 0.5 years) maturing adolescent basketball players	Male	Triphasic generalized logistic model (BTT model) to determine age at PHV: Early: 11.9 years Mid: 12.7 years Late: 14.2 years	1-year follow up study RF, VI & VL measured at 50% femur length	<p>Early: VL MT: + 2.7% * RF MT: + 2.4% VI MT: + 2.0% VM MT: + 5.6% * BB MT: + 7.8% *</p> <p>TB MT: + 8.2% # sig. larger than mid & late</p> <p>Mid VL MT: + 12.3% * RF MT: + 10% * VI MT: + 14.7% * VM MT: + 13.5% * BB MT: + 14.9% *</p> <p>Late: VL MT: + 12.3% * RF MT: + 10% * VI MT: + 8.3% * VM MT: + 13.2% * BB MT: + 23.9% *</p>
Siddle <i>et al.</i> (2022)	Youth soccer players (16.7 ± 0.6 years)	Male	Not assessed	8-week Nordic hamstring curl training	<p>No sig. effect of time for TB for any group</p> <p>BFlh MT: - 2.2% Semimembranosus MT: + 4.5% Semitendinosus MT: + 4.0%</p>
Takai <i>et al.</i> (2013)	Untrained adolescents (13.7 ± 0.6 years)	Male	Self-assessed Tanner stages: Stage 3–4 (12.5–15 years)	8-week bodyweight squat training of 45 sessions	<p>Anterior thigh MT: + 3.2% * Relative anterior thigh MT: + 2.3% *</p>

Key: TG: training group; CG: control group; RT: resistance training; CSA: cross-sectional area; mVol: muscle volume; MT: muscle thickness; TB: triceps brachii; BB: biceps brachii; RF: rectus femoris; VL: vastus lateralis; VM: vastus medialis; VI: vastus intermedius; QF: quadriceps femoris; GM: gastrocnemius medialis; GL: gastrocnemius lateralis; PHV: peak height velocity; ACSA: anatomical cross-sectional area; TW: Tanner-Whitehouse stage. *: indicates significant within group change/ effect ($p \leq 0.05$). #: indicates significant between groups change/ effect ($p \leq 0.05$).

Table 2.2: Research reporting normative data concerning musculature of the lower limbs within youth populations.

Study	Participant information (age)	Sex	Maturation status	Baseline values
Eliakim <i>et al.</i> (2001)	Untrained (9.1 ± 0.1 years)	Female	Tanner stages: pre-and early-pubertal	Total thigh mVOL (cm ³): 935 ± 43
Eliakim <i>et al.</i> (1996)	Untrained (15–17 years)	Female	Not assessed	Total thigh mVOL (cm ³): 986 ± 30
Fitze <i>et al.</i> (2022)	Competitive youth skiers (male: 14.9 ± 0.7 years; female: 14.7 ± 0.6 years)	Male & female	Maturity offset: U15: 14.4 ± 0.3 U16: 15.4 0.2	BFlh: MT (cm): U15: 18.0 ± 3.0 U16: 19.0 ± 3.0 ACSA (cm ²): U15: 7.9 ± 1.6 U16: 8.5 ± 1.4 RF MT (mm): 25.0 VL MT (mm) 17.0
Gavanda <i>et al.</i> (2019)	Adolescent American Football players (17 ± 0.76 years)	Male	Not assessed	RF MT (mm): 25.0 VL MT (mm) 17.0
Herda <i>et al.</i> (2018)	Prepubescent children (8.7 ± 0.6 years)	Male & female	Not assessed	VL ACSA (cm ³): 9.8 ± 0.9
Kanehisa <i>et al.</i> (1994)	Prepubescent children (7.8 ± 0.2 years)	Male & female	Not assessed	Thigh ACSA (cm ²): Boys: 33.0 # (sig. smaller than men and women) Girls: 30.8 # (sig. smaller than men and women)

Kanehisa <i>et al.</i> (2003)	Junior Olympic weightlifters (15.5–17.1 years)	Male	TW2: Skeletal age at 18-month follow up: 1 participant: adult The remaining 6 participants: 17 years	At 30% femur length: Quadriceps total muscle CSA (cm ²): 56.1 RF ACSA (cm ²): 0.1 VL ACSA (cm ²): 10.5 VM ACSA (cm ²): 34.0 VI ACSA (cm ²): 11.5
Kanehisa <i>et al.</i> (2006)	Teenage tennis players (10.7–13.2 years)	Male & female	TW2: Skeletal age: Males: TG: 12.7 ± 2.1 years Females: TG1: 13.0 ± 1.1 years	Quadriceps total muscle CSA (cm ²): 30% femur length: Male: 27.3 Female: 32.1 50% femur length: Male: 42.0 Female: 45.6 70% femur length: Male: 40.6 Female: 41.3
Kearns <i>et al.</i> (2001)	Youth soccer players (16.5 ± 0.5 years)	Male	Not assessed	GM MT (at 30% lower limb length; mm): 21.5 ± 2.6
McKinlay <i>et al.</i> (2018)	Youth soccer players (11–13 years)	Male	Maturity offset: pre-PHV	VL MT (mm): 20.0 ± 2.0
Mersmann <i>et al.</i> (2014)	Adolescent volleyball athletes (15.9 ± 0.6 years)	Male & female	Not assessed	Male: VL mVOL (cm ³): 862 ± 129 # VL PCSA (cm ²): 53.4 ± 13.1 # Female: VL mVOL (cm ³): 620 ± 155 VL PCSA (cm ²): 45.5 ± 8.0
Mersmann <i>et al.</i> (2017)	Late adolescent volleyball athletes (18 ± 1 years)	Male & female	Not assessed	VL: mVOL (cm ³): 742 ± 181 ACSA (cm ²): 29.6 ± 6.5

				Muscle length (cm): 38.7 ± 2.5
				VI:
				mVOL (cm ³): 680 ± 160
				ACSA (cm ²): 28.3 ± 5.8
				Muscle length (cm): 40.9 ± 1.5
				VM:
				mVOL (cm ³): 505 ± 107
				ACSA (cm ²): 25.7 ± 5.2
				Muscle length (cm): 37.1 ± 2.3
Morse <i>et al.</i> (2008)	Prepubescent boys (10.9 ± 0.3 years) compared to men	Male	Not assessed	GL ACSA (cm ²): 5.6 ± 1.6 # GL mVOL (cm ³): 64.5 ± 18.9 # GL PCSA (cm ²): 15.5 ± 3.2 #
Mota <i>et al.</i> (2017)	School children (12 ± 1 years)	Male	Not assessed	Thigh lean mass (kg): TG: 3.61 ± 1.06 CG: 3.27 ± 1.00
Murtagh <i>et al.</i> (2018)	Elite (18.1 ± 1.0 years) and non-elite (22.3 ± 1.7 years) soccer players	Male	Not assessed	Elite: Quadriceps femoris mVOL (cm ³): 2853 ± 508 # Quadriceps femoris PCSA (cm ²): 227.2 ± 42.3 # Quadriceps femoris ACSA (cm ²): 80.9 ± 15.8 # VL MT (40% femur length; mm): 26.4 ± 2.9 Non-elite Quadriceps femoris mVOL (cm ³): 2429 ± 232 Quadriceps femoris PCSA (cm ²): 192.6 ± 25.4 Quadriceps femoris ACSA (cm ²): 69.8 ± 6.2 VL MT (40% femur length; mm): 26.1 ± 3.3
Nasirzade <i>et al.</i> (2014)	Young swimmers (13.9 ± 0.9 years) Faster (G1) or a slower (G2) group	Male	Not assessed	G1: VL (50% femur length) MT (mm): 22.5 ± 1.2 # GL (30% lower limb length) MT (mm): 17.0 ± 2.1 # TB MT (mm): 22.4 ± 1.5 # G2:

				VL MT (mm): 21.4 ± 1.1 GL MT (mm): 15.1 ± 2.0 TB MT (mm): 21.0 ± 1.3
Panidi <i>et al.</i> (2020)	Rhythmic gymnasts and volleyball players (8–10 years)	Female	Maturity offset: Rhythmic gymnasts: -5.5 ± 0.2 Volleyball players: $-5.0 \pm 0.3\#$	GM MT (mm): Mid-belly: Rhythmic gymnasts: 15.3 ± 1.2 Volleyball players: 15.3 ± 2.4 Distal: Rhythmic gymnasts: 7.4 ± 2.2 Volleyball players: 6.4 ± 2.5
Panidi <i>et al.</i> (2021)	Adolescent (13.5 ± 1.4 years) volleyball players	Female	Maturity offset (-0.8 ± 0.9)	GM ACSA (cm ²): 16.3 ± 3.4
Radnor <i>et al.</i> (2022)	Secondary school children (12.4 ± 0.2 years)	Male	Maturity offset (-1.7 ± 0.3)	GM MT (mm): Pre-PHV: 14.7 ± 1.7 Circa PHV: $17.0 \pm 2.4 \#$ (sig. larger than pre-PHV) Post-PHV: $19.2 \pm 3.0 \#$ (sig. larger than pre- and circa-PHV) GM Physiological MT (cm; Blazeovich <i>et al.</i> , 2003): Pre-PHV: 16.7 ± 2.6 Circa PHV: $10.5 \pm 4.4 \#$ (sig. larger than pre-PHV) Post-PHV: 25.6 ± 7.4 (sig. larger than pre- and circa-PHV) VL MT (mm): Pre-PHV: 18.3 ± 2.3 Circa PHV: $21.3 \pm 2.8 \#$ (sig. larger than pre-PHV) Post-PHV: $24.1 \pm 4.3 \#$ (sig. larger than pre- and circa-PHV) VL Physiological MT (cm; Blazeovich <i>et al.</i> , 2003): Pre-PHV: 21.1 ± 3.9 Circa PHV: $26.3 \pm 5.9 \#$ (sig. larger than pre-PHV) Post-PHV: 31.7 ± 9.5 (sig. larger than pre- and circa-PHV)

Ritsche <i>et al.</i> (2021)	Youth soccer players (U13: 12.5 ± 0.1 years; U14: 13.5 ± 0.3 years; U15: 14.4 ± 0.3 years)	Not reported	Not assessed	BFlh ACSA (cm ²): U13: 7.78 ± 2.02 U14: 8.88 ± 1.56 U15: 10.64 ± 2.21
Rock <i>et al.</i> (2021)	Younger (7.2 ± 1.2), and older (10.2 ± 0.7) children, and adolescents (14.7 ± 2.0)	Male & female	Not assessed	RF MT (mm): Younger children: 15.4 ± 2.1 Older children: 19.0 ± 2.8 Adolescents: 21.0 ± 3.9 VL MT (mm): Younger children: 13.9 ± 1.9 Older children: 18.1 ± 3.6 Adolescents: 19.2 ± 3.3
Secomb <i>et al.</i> (2015)	Adolescent surfing athletes (14.8 ± 1.7 years)	Male & female	Not assessed	VL (50% femur length) MT (mm): 20.8 ± 3.7 GL (30% lower limb length) MT (mm): 13.8 ± 2.0
Secomb <i>et al.</i> (2015)	Competitive surfers (15.1 ± 1.4 years)	Not reported	Not assessed	VL (50% femur length) MT (mm): 20.6 ± 4.2 GL MT (mm): 14.4 ± 2.0
Secomb <i>et al.</i> (2017)	Competitive surfers (14 ± 1.8 years)	Not reported	Not assessed	VL (50% femur length) MT (mm): 20.7 ± 2.2 GL (30% lower limb length) MT (mm): 14.2 ± 17.0
Sekine <i>et al.</i> (2019)	Early (13.3 ± 0.6 years), mid (12.8 ± 0.4 years) or late (13.1 ± 0.5 years) maturing adolescent basketball players	Male	Triphasic generalized logistic model (BTT model) to determine age at PHV: Early: 11.9 years Mid: 12.7 years Late: 14.2 years	Early: VL MT (50% femur length; mm): 26.0 ± 4.0 RF MT (50% femur length; mm): 25.0 ± 3.0 # sig. larger than mid and late VI MT (50% femur length; mm): 20.0 ± 3.0 VM MT (20% femur length; mm): 36.0 ± 5.0 BB MT (mm): 30.0 ± 2.0 # sig. larger than mid and late TB MT (mm): 28.0 ± 5.0 # sig. larger than late

				<p>Mid</p> <p>VL MT (mm): 23.0 ± 3.0</p> <p>RF MT (mm): 22.0 ± 3.0</p> <p>VI MT (mm): 18.0 ± 3.0</p> <p>VM MT (mm): 33.0 ± 5.0</p> <p>BB MT (mm): 25.0 ± 3.0</p> <p>TB MT (mm): 25.0 ± 3.0 # sig. larger than late</p> <p>Late:</p> <p>VL MT (mm): 23.0 ± 4.0</p> <p>RF MT (mm): 21.0 ± 3.0</p> <p>VI MT (mm): 18.0 ± 4.0</p> <p>VM MT (mm): 33.0 ± 4.0</p> <p>BB MT (mm): 23.0 ± 3.0</p> <p>TB MT (mm): 23.0 ± 3.0</p>
Siddle <i>et al.</i> (2022)	Youth soccer players (16.7 ± 0.6 years)	Male	Not assessed	<p>Biceps femoris long head MT (cm): 22.3 ± 2.6</p> <p>Semimembranosus MT (cm): 30.2 ± 4.2</p> <p>Semitendinosus MT (cm): 28.4 ± 3.8</p>
Stock <i>et al.</i> (2017)	School children (12 ± 1 years)	Male	Not assessed	<p>VL MT (50% femur length; mm): 15.8 ± 3.4</p> <p>RF MT (50% femur length; mm): 19.2 ± 3.5</p> <p>Anterior thigh MT (mm): 45.2 ± 6.0</p> <p>Relative anterior thigh MT (mm): 13.2 ± 1.3</p>
Takai <i>et al.</i> (2013)	Untrained adolescents (13.7 ± 0.6 years)	Male	Self-assessed Tanner stages: Stage 3–4 (middle adolescence: 12.5– 15 years)	
Tottori <i>et al.</i> (2018)	Sprint trained adolescent boys (11.6 ± 0.4 years)	Male	Not assessed	<p>QF CSA (cm²): 40.7 ± 2.8</p> <p>QF relative CSA (cm²/kg²): 4.04 ± 0.44</p> <p>Hamstring CSA (cm): 21.2 ± 3.7</p> <p>Hamstring relative CSA (cm²/kg²): 2.13 ± 0.27</p>

Key: TG: training group; CSA: cross-sectional area; mVol: muscle volume; MT: muscle thickness; TB: triceps brachii; BB: biceps brachii; RF: rectus femoris; VL: vastus lateralis; VM: vastus medialis; VI: vastus intermedius; QF: quadriceps femoris; GM: gastrocnemius medialis; GL: gastrocnemius lateralis; PHV: peak height velocity; ACSA: anatomical cross-sectional area; PCSA: physiological cross-sectional area; TW: Tanner-Whitehouse; *: indicates significant within group change/effect ($p \leq 0.05$). #: indicates significant between groups change/effect ($p \leq 0.05$).

(2019) utilised a previously reported growth model (Ali *et al.*, 2007) for this population in order to predict the age PHV occurs through the use of serial stature records, and therefore did not use the criterion reference standard of skeletal age (Tanner *et al.*, 2001). Nonetheless, the increased energetic demands associated with maturation and growth processes coupled with the increased energy expenditure resulting from additional strength training may preclude an adequate muscular growth (Hannon *et al.*, 2020). This highlights the need to monitor maturity timing and status within youth sport, to ensure the prescription of individually specific and biologically appropriate programming (Duarte *et al.*, 2018; Sekine, Hoshikawa and Hirose, 2019).

In a study evaluating male youth athletes (skeletal age of 12.7 years at baseline) involved in regular sport training but not participating in resistance training aimed to improve muscular force production capabilities, Kanehisa *et al.* (2006) found significant increases in quadriceps total cross-sectional area (CSA) at a 2-year follow up. However, the results from the former (Kanehisa *et al.*, 2006) displays greater variability of the outcome estimate than the observed average increases in muscle CSA (at 30% femur length; $+ 23.9 \pm 24.7 \text{ cm}^3$) suggesting considerable inter-individual variability in the adaptative response. Similarly, in the study by Kanehisa *et al.* (2003), as measured using the gold-standard carpal radiographs, the skeletal age of 6 of the 7 participants were classified as 17.0 years at baseline, compared to “Adult” for the same number of participants at the 18-month measurement. The results displayed by Kanehisa *et al.* (2003) show an increased level of adaptation (30.7% vs 23.9% increase in total CSA) for post-PHV individuals also continually participating in intensive resistance training when compared to the participants partaking in sport only observed by Kanehisa *et al.* (2006). These results suggest that the changes in muscle CSA circa-PHV are largely varied between individuals participating in sport only (Kanehisa *et al.*, 2006). Therefore, depending on maturation alone or coupled with sport involvement may not result in consistent significant increases in muscle size throughout adolescence within groups of youth athletes; to continually obtain improvements in muscle size it appears necessary to utilise resistance training throughout adolescence and into early adulthood. However, the participants studied in the aforementioned research (Kanehisa *et al.*, 2003; Kanehisa *et al.*, 2006; Sekine, Hoshikawa and Hirose, 2019) were Japanese adolescents, who were observed to attain their PHV earlier (Table 2.2) than European counterparts (Malina, Bouchard and Bar-Or, 2004), and also would appear to attain increases in muscle growth before they reach PHV (Table 2.1). Indeed, it may not be prudent to generalise the results of this study to other populations.

Throughout adolescence, as mentioned previously, males will display increases in muscle thickness values as a result of maturation (Radnor *et al.*, 2020) which may be partly due to potential changes in muscle fibre type (Metaxas *et al.*, 2014). The large variance in responses observed within circa-PHV adolescent males (Kanehisa *et al.*, 2006) may therefore be partly explained by the changes to the musculature system that occur as a result of advancements in maturity status, specifically increments in individual muscle fibre CSA (Metaxas *et al.*, 2014); as individuals towards the end of their PHV would display marked differences than those towards the start of their PHV, but would however, be categorised as being the same maturity status. During maturation, youth males may display a shift in muscle fibre composition from predominantly type I to type II fibres, with adolescent soccer players displaying a higher percentage of type IIA muscle fibres when compared to pubertal and young groups of players (Metaxas *et al.*, 2014). Given the greater potential for muscular hypertrophy of these type II muscle fibres compared to type I (Fry *et al.*, 2014), it could therefore be assumed that the greater muscle sizes within during- and post-PHV individuals (Radnor *et al.*, 2020) could be partly due to difference in muscle fibre compositions (Metaxas *et al.*, 2014). The greater CSA of type II muscle fibres allows for greater force production, and so these fast twitch fibres are more responsive to resistance training (Verdijk *et al.*, 2014). Maturation status may therefore partly explain the contrasting results seen within the literature for changes in MT within circa-PHV (Table 2.1; Table 2.2) cohorts as a result of growth rate variability seen during this stage of development (Malina, Bouchard and Bar-Or, 2004).

Another possible explanation for the inconsistencies observed within the literature is the variance in measurement sites used between studies, as different sites along the muscle's length would yield different values due to the nonuniform morphological proportion of skeletal muscle. In a study by Kanehisa *et al.* (2003) measurements of the ACSA were taken in adolescent (16.4 ± 0.6 years at baseline) male Olympic weightlifters at 30%, 50%, and 70% of the femur length for all four quadriceps femoris heads at the start and end of an 18-month period (Table 2.1). Significant increases were found for all muscles apart from the RF, and total CSA only at 30% femur length, which could be due to the participants' potential exposure to intensive resistance training over the course of the 18-month period (Kanehisa *et al.*, 2003). However, the sample size ($n = 7$) in the study by Kanehisa *et al.* (2003) was small, limiting the transference of results to other populations. Also, the results indicated a nonuniform increase in muscle CSA, with significant increments only being observed for the measurement site most proximal to the knee joint (30% femur length). This is in contrast to Kanehisa *et al.* (2006) who

found increases in quadriceps femoris CSA following a 2-year follow up; however, the latter study utilised untrained participants with smaller quadricep CSA's at baseline also only participating in tennis practice (Table 2.2). It could therefore be theorised that the results observed related to segment specific preferential hypertrophy are due to training status; and therefore, the proximal region of the quadriceps may continually develop to a greater extent when compared to mid or distal regions in well trained athletes. Indeed, Mogi and Wakahara (2022) display uniform changes to the rectus femoris and vastus intermedius musculature with changes in maturity offset. However further research which utilises measurement techniques, such as ultrasonography, in order to measure specific portions along a muscle's length is needed to clarify whether this is indeed the case or whether programming factors such as exercise type, frequency, volume, or intensity may have contributed to such an outcome.

In order to accurately evaluate the underpinning morphological changes in skeletal muscle inducted by strength related adaptations, MRI, CT, and US are frequently reported in the literature (Folland and Williams, 2007). In contrast to MRI and US, CT relies on the use of ionizing radiation and therefore may be ethically less suited for use within youth populations or when conducting multiple assessments within brief increments (Ngan *et al.*, 2003). US is time and cost efficient, and easy to administer when compared to the expensive, time consuming and difficult administration associated with MRI use (Narici, 1999). US imaging techniques rely on the use of echo pulses emitted from a transducer, whereby sound waves pass through the body and reflect off different structures. The degree of reflection (echogenicity) is dependent upon the acoustic impedance (Chan and Abbas, 2008), which is in turn determined by the composition of the structure or tissue (Ihnatsenka and Boezaart, 2010). Tissues with high water content, such as muscle fibres, tend to have lower echogenicity compared to those with high collagen content, such as tendonous connective tissue (e.g., fascia, aponeurosis, perimysium) (Chan and Abbas, 2008; Ihnatsenka and Boezaart, 2010). Therefore, different tissues can be distinguished as different colours and tones ranging from white to black when imaging whole structures using US for tissues with higher, and lower echogenicity respectively. Echogenicity is also dependent on the frequency of sound wave emission from the transducer, with the ability of the US wave to pass through the body directly proportional to its wavelength. Specifically, skeletal muscle evaluation is commonly evaluated at frequencies of 5–10 MHz, with the optimal range for superficial structures between 10–12 MHz, and deeper structures between 6–8 Hz (Lichtwark, 2018). In addition, the reflection coefficient is determined by not only the US wavelength and the ratio of the echogenicity at the interface of two different

tissues, but also the angle the US wave makes contact with the surface of interest (Lichtwark, 2018). Enhanced images are typically observed with transducers positioned perpendicular to the structure of interest while taking the pennation angle of the muscle fibres into account. When these methodological issues have been addressed, acceptable reliability has been observed for the quantification of MT (English, Fisher and Thoirs, 2012; Franchi *et al.*, 2018; Noorkoiv, Nosaka and Blazevich, 2010) and muscle architecture (e.g., pennation angle, fascicle length) related measurements (Kwah *et al.*, 2013), within youth populations (Legerlotz, Smith and Hing, 2010) and even during movement of the interested musculature (Van Hooren, Teratsias and Hodson-Tole, 2020). US can therefore be utilised as an acceptable measurement method when aiming to determine the muscular adaptations associated with strength training (Timmins *et al.*, 2016).

Although the ACSA has previously been shown to be a strong determinant of muscular force production capabilities in parallel fibred muscles, accurate assessment requires multiple images and imaging techniques that are time consuming and difficult to perform. As an alternative the use of single images may be more time efficient using US. Therefore, the use of US to obtain MT values in order to calculate muscle volume, or in order to collect numerous ACSA's may be a more appropriate assessment method when working with groups of athletes in an applied setting. It has also been suggested that in pennate muscles, physiological cross-sectional area (PCSA) theoretically may provide a better estimate of the muscles' force-generating capacity, as this method provides a better estimation of the number of sarcomeres in parallel compared to the ACSA. Given that the overall force production of a muscle is determined by the number of sarcomeres in parallel, it is understandable why the force-generating potential is dependent on its PCSA; as the PCSA representing the total cross-sectional area of all the constituting muscle fibres of a muscle perpendicular to their long axis (Close, 1972; Lieber and Fridén, 2000). Indeed, Murtagh *et al.* (2018a) found the PCSA and muscle volume to be significantly correlated with countermovement jump performance in both elite and non-elite youth soccer players. However, given none of the studies included in this review longitudinally evaluated PCSA changes, future studies should longitudinally investigate changes in the PCSA because of training.

Similar to the intensity of training, the total duration of an intervention is an important consideration while evaluating previous literature. Following a 7-week intervention period, significant increases in VL MT (+ 4.9%; Table 2.1) were reported by Secomb *et al.* (2015b)

who utilised a block periodised resistance training programme for twice a week throughout the intervention period. This is in contrast to the results of Secomb *et al.* (2017) who observed significant changes in the gastrocnemius lateralis muscle only after 7 weeks of plyometric and gymnastics training but not resistance training by comparison in a cross-over design intervention study. However, the participants in the aforementioned research were on average 14.0 years old (Secomb *et al.*, 2017) and 15.1 years old (Secomb *et al.*, 2015b) respectively, therefore the differences in training response may have been as a result of the interaction between maturation status and training stimulus.

As an alternative, it could also be assumed that 8 weeks of resistance training in untrained adolescents is insufficient in duration to obtain the necessary prerequisite neural gains in agonist motor unit recruitment before further gains in muscle morphology can be gained (Behm *et al.*, 2017; Behringer *et al.*, 2011; Ozmun, Mikesky and Surburg, 1994). However, in a study evaluating youth soccer players with no previous experience in strength training, McKinlay *et al.* (2018) found increases in VL MT following 8 weeks of both resistance training and plyometric training once per week (+ 6.5 and 7.5% respectively; Table 2.1). Although the participants had no previous training experience specific to enhancing force production capacities, the participants investigated by McKinlay *et al.* (2018) were pre-PHV, yet still obtained significant improvements in VL MT (Table 2.1), hinting that an individual may not necessarily require circulating androgens to provoke increases in MT and that programme efficacy may be a more potent indicator of changes to the muscular system. In addition, although the training intervention period in the study by McKinlay *et al.* (2018) was 8 weeks in duration, prior to the intervention all participants underwent a 2-week familiarisation period to ensure proper training technique. Therefore, it can be assumed that longer intervention durations may be required when aiming to invoke improvements in MT, as evidenced by the lack of agreement between studies and the aforementioned time commitment needed to ensure adaptations in neural activation (Behm *et al.*, 2017).

In line with this assumption, Gavanda *et al.* (2019) evaluated the effect of block vs undulating periodisation over 12 weeks on changes in VL, RF and triceps brachii MT values. The participants in this study were late adolescents (17 ± 0.76 years) engaged in strength training for just under 1 year, and displayed significant improvements in MT values for each muscle group observed (+ 4–11% in MT values; Table 2.1). It appears that the participants in this study used higher, and therefore more appropriate and practically relevant training intensities for

more advanced maturity status groups to attain greater increments of muscle mass, as mentioned previously. In addition, an intervention duration of 10–12 weeks seemingly provides more consistent improvements in MT values as evidenced by the research presented previously (Gavanda *et al.*, 2019; McKinlay *et al.*, 2018). However, despite percentage changes in muscle size being comparable between the aforementioned studies utilising participants of different biological and chronological ages (Table 2.1) (Gavanda *et al.*, 2019; McKinlay *et al.*, 2018), absolute MT values have naturally been shown to increase with advancing maturity status as evidenced with the differences in baseline values from (Radnor *et al.*, 2020; Sekine, Hoshikawa and Hirose, 2019) (Table 2.2). Future research should therefore utilise longer duration study lengths in order to evaluate programme related changes of the underpinning physiological adaptations over prolonged periods more specific to youth sport season lengths.

The aforementioned results (Gavanda *et al.*, 2019) are also in agreement with that of Mersmann *et al.* (2017) who evaluated the changes in VL, VI and vastus medialis at the start and end of a 2-year period. Participants in this study were trained volleyball adolescent athletes (18 ± 1 years) and participated in resistance training (~3 hours per week) over the course of the period (Mersmann *et al.*, 2017). Significant increases were observed for muscle volume and ACSA at the end of the 2-year period for all muscle groups studied, with responses varying (+ 4.1–9% in ACSA values) depending on the muscle head measured (Table 2.1) (Mersmann *et al.*, 2017). However, a limitation of this study was that the participants were both male and female with results from both sexes combined into the analysis, which may have underestimated the results of the males, and overestimated that of the females.

In support of this assumption, Kanehisa *et al.* (2006) observed significant different changes in quadriceps total muscle volume between males and female teenage tennis players at the start and end of a period 2 years in duration (Table 2.1) (Kanehisa *et al.*, 2006). This discrepancy was also observed in a study by Mersmann *et al.* (2014) who found significantly larger muscle volume and PCSA values for adolescent males compared to both adolescent and adult females due to a lack of circulating androgens in females (Table 2.2). Therefore, future research should avoid combining male and female results in order to provide a more accurate representation of training induced changes to the musculature system. In addition, the similarity of results between studies by Eliakim *et al.* (1996) and Eliakim *et al.* (2001) suggests a reduced adaptative potential as a result of maturity status in females compared to that of males (Table 2.1; Table 2.2). Similarly, Daly *et al.* (2004) evaluated the interaction of training and maturation

on morphological changes of the musculature in the upper limbs of female tennis players and found statistically significant differences between playing and non-playing arms without significant differences between maturity status groups (Table 2.1). Therefore, given the similarly low level of circulating androgens in females compared to pre-PHV males, it can be assumed from the evidence that immature youth male athletes can still attain increments in muscle CSA (Table 2.2).

In summary, although muscle size is a key determinant of muscular force output (Lieber and Fridén, 2000; Narici *et al.*, 1996), there is currently a sparsity of research evaluating its changes due to strength and power training over prolonged periods of time within youth populations (Table 2.1), and trained adolescents and youth soccer players in particular. Similarly, given the variance in adaptations displayed here with study durations of 8 weeks or less; as a minimum, research should ensure that the study duration is appropriate (e.g., 10–12 weeks) in order to attain the neurological adaptations necessary prior to significant morphological adaptations can be attained.

Conversely, research could aim to evaluate adaptations in already trained populations, to better evaluate the morphological adaptive potential of the muscular system in adolescent populations. Collectively the results of the presented studies highlight changes in muscle size are best determined by programme design and not necessarily always maturation status, future research should consider this to design appropriate training interventions. Maturation status should, however, be considered when recruiting participants for intervention studies, as varied results have been displayed here which correspond to periods of development within which adolescents experience varied growth patterns. Maturation status should therefore be determined in studies evaluating the effects of training interventions on the physiological adaptations to strength training in youth to appropriately prescribe training programmes provided a prior necessary familiarisation period has been conducted. Given post-PHV groups within this review have typically displayed larger absolute values of muscle size-related measurements (e.g., MT) and would therefore display larger absolute changes due to programming. However, from the available literature presented in this review, it can be inferred that for training periods of 7–12 weeks, increments in MT values of the musculature of the lower limbs could range from 4–8% depending on the muscle observed (Table 2.1); provided the training intervention is of sufficient intensity relative to the participants maturation status.

2.5.2 Muscle architecture

The importance of understanding the underpinning mechanisms by which youth athletes develop maximal force producing capabilities is clearly important given the large expression of muscular forces during common match play locomotive demands (Wisloff *et al.*, 2004). Moreover, as match demands require soccer players to rapidly accelerate, decelerate, change direction, and jump maximally (Bangsbo, Mohr and Krstrup, 2006), it is vital to exploit the underpinning forces in timeframes as short as possible, given the time-dependency of these movements. The architecture of a muscle, specifically muscle fibre pennation angle (FPA) and length (FL), are associated with the muscles ability to contract both forcefully and rapidly. It is therefore important to elucidate how to optimally facilitate these adaptations in order to inform practice within applied environments.

2.5.2.1 Muscle fibre pennation angle

The muscle FPA of a muscle tissue is the angle at which the muscle fibre inserts into the aponeurosis, and despite the aforementioned increments in both total muscle mass and cross-sectional area of individual muscles as a result of maturation (McCarthy *et al.*, 2014; O'Brien *et al.*, 2010a; Radnor *et al.*, 2020) FPA is seemingly a characteristic independent of age or maturation status (O'Brien *et al.*, 2010b; Radnor *et al.*, 2020). FPA may also be measurement site specific depending on the muscle head examined, with youth individuals previously displaying significantly different FPA values for the vastus medialis and anterior VI depending on the measurement site (Table 2.3) (O'Brien *et al.*, 2010b). Larger pennation angles are as a result typically associated with a greater potential of force production due to a concurrently increasing muscle fibre CSA (Aagaard *et al.*, 2001). As muscle FPA increases, an increase in PCSA occurs, with force production output capabilities linked to a greater amount of muscle fibres able to produce work (Aagaard *et al.*, 2001). However, assuming other (e.g., MT, fascicle length) variables of muscle size and architecture remain the same, as FPA increases a theoretical mechanical disadvantage may occur as the absolute amount of force muscle fibres can transmit to the tendon has been suggested to decrease at larger angles (Alexander and Vernon, 1975).

Nevertheless, a muscle FPA $\geq 40^\circ$ has been suggested as the threshold at which this biomechanical disadvantage occurs, an angle most pennate muscles are unlikely to achieve

Table 2.3: Research detailing differences in muscle architecture variables including youth populations.

Study	Study design	Participant information (age)	Sex	Maturation status	Study details	Results
Lacome <i>et al.</i> (2020)	LS	Elite youth soccer players (17.3 ± 0.7 years)	Male	Not assessed	12 weeks eccentric hamstring strength training	BF FL: + 5.2% SM FL: + 6.8%
Mersmann <i>et al.</i> (2014)	CS	Adolescent volleyball athletes (15.9 ± 0.6 years)	Male & female	Not assessed	Male and female elite volleyball athletes RFL compared	RFL: Male + 23.7% compared to female
O'Brien <i>et al.</i> (2010)	CS	Prepubescent untrained children (9.1 ± 0.7 years)	Male & female	Not assessed	Adults muscle architectures were compared to that of children at different patella- iliac distances: Proximal regions: VM: 5% VL: 22% RF: 39% VIlat: 22% VIant: 39% Central regions: VM: 22% VL: 39% RF: 56% VIlat: 39% VIant: 56% Distal regions: VM: 39% VL: 56% RF: 73% VIlat: 56% VIant: 73%	VL: Boys and girls sig. shorter FL than men & women at all measurement sites; apart from proximal measurement of FL between girls and women. No sig. between site differences for FL No sig. differences observed for FPA VM: Boys and girls sig. smaller FL than men across all sites Women sig. larger FL than boys for central and proximal sites; and girls for proximal site Distal measurement site displayed sig. larger FPA than proximal and central for boys. Distal and central measurement sites sig. larger than proximal for girls VIlat: Boys had sig. larger FL measured proximally compared to distally No other sig. differences observed between groups or measurement sites for FL or FPA VIant: Boys sig. smaller FL measured distally compared to all

other groups. FL measured proximally sig. smaller for boys and girls compared to men & women; and measured centrally sig. smaller for girls compared to women. FPA measured distally sig. smaller when compared to proximally for boys, and sig. smaller when compared to centrally for girls

RF:

Sig. larger FL for men compared to all other groups at distal and central sites

No other sig. differences observed

Panidi <i>et al.</i> (2021)	LS	Adolescent (13.5 ± 1.4 years) volleyball players	Female	Maturity offset (-0.8 ± 0.9 years to PHV)	12 weeks of high-volume static stretching of one limb (STR) on GM architecture at different distances between the popliteal crease and the centre of the medial malleolus. Architecture was compared between time points and between limbs (STR vs CON)	GM FL: 50% STR: + 6.3%* 30% STR: + 8.9% GL FL: 50% STR: + 10.4% 30% STR: + 28.3%
-----------------------------	----	--	--------	---	---	---

Radnor <i>et al.</i> (2020)	CS	Active pre- (12.5 ± 0.5 years), circa- (14.1 ± 0.7 years) and post- (15.8 ± 1 years) PHV school children	Male	Maturity offset	Comparing maturity status' muscle architecture differences VL images taken at 50% femur length; GL images were taken at 30% of the distance from the popliteal crease to the centre of the lateral malleolus.	<p>Post- (d = 1.19) and circa- (d = 0.57) PHV group had sig. larger GM muscle thickness than pre-PHV</p> <p>GM pennation angle was sig. larger in post- compared to pre- (d = 0.94) and circa- (d = 0.59) PHV</p> <p>GM fascicle length and RFL not different between groups</p> <p>VL muscle thickness sig. larger for post- compared to circa- (d = 0.72) and pre-(d = 1.39) PHV groups. Circa- sig. larger than pre-PHV (d = 1.06)</p> <p>Pennation angle was sig. larger in post-PHV compared to pre- (d = 0.59) in the VL</p> <p>Fascicle length in the VL was sig. larger for post-PHV compared to pre- (d = 0.66)</p>
Radnor <i>et al.</i> (2022)	CS	Secondary school children (12.4 ± 0.2 years)	Male	Maturity offset	Cross-sectional comparison between different maturity status groups	<p>GM PA: Pre-PHV: 19.3 ± 3.1 Circa PHV: 20.7 ± 3.7 # (sig. larger than pre-PHV) Post-PHV: 23.4 ± 3.8 # (sig. larger than pre- and circa-PHV)</p> <p>GM Physiological FL (cm; Blazevich <i>et al.</i>, 2003): Pre-PHV: 4.6 ± 8.1 Circa PHV: 4.9 ± 0.9 Post-PHV: 4.9 ± 0.9 (sig. larger than pre- and circa-PHV)</p> <p>VL PA: Pre-PHV: 16.6 ± 3.2 Circa PHV: 17.5 ± 4.1 Post-PHV: 18.2 ± 3.7</p> <p>VL Physiological FL (cm): Pre-PHV: 16.6 ± 3.2</p>

Circa PHV: 17.54 ± 4.1
 Post-PHV: 18.2 ± 3.7 (sig. larger than pre-PHV)

Ritsche <i>et al.</i> (2021)	CS	Youth soccer players (U13: 12.5 ± 0.1 years; U14: 13.5 ± 0.3 years; U15: 14.4 ± 0.3 years)	Not reported	Not assessed	Compared BFlh morphology between U13, U14 and U15 age groups.	BFlh FL: U14 vs U13: + 2.9% U15 vs U14: + 6.6% U15 vs U13: + 9.2% BFlh FPA: U14 vs U13: + 7.3% U15 vs U14: + 1.0% U15 vs U13: + 7.7%
Secomb <i>et al.</i> (2015b)	LS	Competitive surfers (15.1 ± 1.4 years)	Not reported	Not assessed	Strength training 2 sessions/week for 7 weeks VL measurements: 50% femur length	VL: FPA: + 3.5% FL: - 4.6% GL: FPA: + 1% FL: - 1%
Secomb <i>et al.</i> (2017)	LS	Competitive surfers (14.8 ± 1.8 years)	Not reported	Not assessed	Strength training or gymnastics and plyometric 2 sessions/week for 7 weeks VL measurements: 50% femur length	RT: VL: FPA: - 6.2% FL: + 8.5% * GL: FPA: - 2.6% FL: + 4.5% Gymnastics and plyometrics: VL: FPA: - 11.6% * FL: + 15.4% * GL: FPA: + 2.8% FL: + 5.4%

Siddle <i>et al.</i> (2022)	LS	Youth soccer players (16.7 ± 0.6 years)	Male	Not assessed	8-week Nordic hamstring curl training	BF1h: FL: + 2.8% FPA: - 3.4%
-----------------------------	----	--	------	-----------------	--	------------------------------------

Key: LS: longitudinal study; CS: cross-sectional study; RT: resistance training; BF: biceps femoris; SM: semimembranosus; GM: gastrocnemius medialis; GL: gastrocnemius lateralis; VL: vastus lateralis; VM: vastus medialis; VIlat: lateral vastus intermedius; VIant: anterior vastus intermedius; RF: rectus femoris; TB: triceps brachii; FPA fibre pennation angle; FL: fascicle length; RFL: relative fascicle length; *: indicates significant within group change/ effect ($p \leq 0.05$). #: indicates significant between groups change/ effect ($p \leq 0.05$).

Table 2.4: Research detailing normative values in knee extensor muscle architecture variables measured within youth populations

Study	Participant information (age)	Sex	Maturation status	Baseline values
Fitze <i>et al.</i> (2022)	Competitive youth skiers (male: 14.9 ± 0.7 years; female: 14.7 ± 0.6 years)	Male & female	Maturity offset: U15: 14.4 ± 0.3 years U16: 15.4 ± 0.2 years	BFlh: FL (cm): U15: 8.9 ± 1.3 U16: 9.5 ± 1.3 FPA (°): U15: 10.9 ± 2.3 U16: 11.2 ± 2.5
Mersmann <i>et al.</i> (2014)	Adolescent volleyball athletes (15.9 ± 0.6)	Male & female	Not assessed	Male: rFL (cm): 0.36 ± 0.09 # Female: rFL(cm): 0.29 ± 0.05 #
Morse <i>et al.</i> (2008)	Early pubescent boys (10.9 ± 0.3 years)	Male	Tanner stage 2	GL FPA (°): 10.8 ± 2.5
Nasirzade <i>et al.</i> (2014)	Young swimmers (13.9 ± 0.9 years)	Male	Not assessed	G1: VL: FPA (°): 16.0 ± 2.6 FL (cm): 8.3 ± 1.1 # rFL(cm): 0.21 ± 0.03 # GL: FPA (°): 16.1 ± 1.6 FL (cm): 6.13 ± 0.7 # rFL(cm): 0.15 ± 0.02 TB: FPA (°): 16.9 ± 2.3 # FL (cm): 7.9 ± 1.4 # rFL (cm): 0.21 ± 0.03 #

G2:
 VL:
 FPA (°): 18.0 ± 3.7
 FL (cm): 7.04 ± 1.2 #
 rFL (cm): 0.18 ± 0.03 #
 GL:
 FPA (°): 17.2 ± 2.1
 FL (cm): 5.23 ± 1.1 #
 rFL (cm): 0.13 ± 0.03
 TB:
 FPA (°): 19.1 ± 2.8 #
 FL (cm): 6.55 ± 1.1 #
 rFL (cm): 0.18 ± 0.04 #

O'Brien (2010)

Prepubescent untrained children (9.1 ± 0.7)

Male & female

Not assessed

Proximal:
 Male:
 VL:
 FL (cm): 63.2 ± 2.9
 FPA (°): 16.2 ± 1.0
 VM:
 FL (cm): 53.6 ± 1.6
 FPA (°): 20.6 ± 1.1 #d
 Vlat:
 FL (cm): 60.1 ± 3.76 #d
 FPA (°): 15.4 ± 1.0
 Vlant:
 FL (cm): 57.2 ± 2.9
 FPA (°): 16.7 ± 1.42 #d
 RF:
 FL (cm): 50.3 ± 3.0
 FPA (°): 22.3 ± 1.5
 Female:
 VL:
 FL (cm): 69.4 ± 2.6
 FPA (°): 15.2 ± 0.8
 VM:
 FL (cm): 53.9 ± 7.0
 FPA (°): 16.3 ± 2.3 #d,c

Vilat:
FL (cm): 61.4 ± 1.2
FPA ($^{\circ}$): 14.8 ± 1.2
VIant:
FL (cm): 61.1 ± 2.1
FPA ($^{\circ}$): 12.3 ± 0.6
RF:
FL (cm): 52.5 ± 2.2
FPA ($^{\circ}$): 19.7 ± 1.1

Central:
Male:
VL:
FL (cm): 64.4 ± 3.7
FPA ($^{\circ}$): 15.8 ± 0.6
VM:
FL (cm): 60.4 ± 2.0
FPA ($^{\circ}$): 24.7 ± 3.5 #d
Vilat:
FL (cm): 50.8 ± 4.8
FPA ($^{\circ}$): 14.9 ± 1.3
VIant:
FL (cm): 53.3 ± 2.1
FPA ($^{\circ}$): 12.5 ± 0.4
RF:
FL (cm): 52.4 ± 2.9
FPA ($^{\circ}$): 24.0 ± 1.2

Female:
VL:
FL (cm): 68.3 ± 2.3
FPA ($^{\circ}$): 17.0 ± 1.3
VM:
FL (cm): 68.0 ± 2.0
FPA ($^{\circ}$): 24.4 ± 3.5 #p
Vilat:
FL (cm): 59.5 ± 2.2
FPA ($^{\circ}$): 14.9 ± 1.7
VIant:

FL (cm): 60.2 ± 3.6
FPA (°): 14.1 ± 1.2 #d
RF:
FL (cm): 55.6 ± 1.6
FPA (°): 21.6 ± 1.4

Distal:
Male:
VL:
FL (cm): 60.3 ± 1.9
FPA (°): 16.0 ± 2.1
VM:
FL(cm): 61 ± 2.2
FPA (°): 33.0 ± 1.6 #c,p
VIlat:
FL (cm): 48.2 ± 4.5 #p
FPA (°): 11.8 ± 1.1
VIant:
FL (cm): 50.9 ± 2.3 *
FPA (°): 11.1 ± 0.9 #p
RF:
FL (cm): 57.3 ± 5.4
FPA (°): 21.1 ± 2.4

Female:
VL:
FL (cm): 61.0 ± 3.1
FPA (°): 18.2 ± 1.4
VM:
FL (cm): 66.2 ± 2.1
FPA (°): 31.2 ± 1.8 #p
VIlat:
FL (cm): 55.6 ± 2.7
FPA (°): 11.4 ± 1.4
VIant:
FL (cm): 61.1 ± 2.1 *
FPA (°): 12.3 ± 0.6 #c
RF:

Panidi <i>et al.</i> (2020)	Rhythmic gymnasts and volleyball players (8–10 years)	Female	<p>Maturity offset: Rhythmic gymnasts: -5.5 ± 0.2 Volleyball players: $-5.0 \pm 0.3\#$</p>	<p>FL (cm): 58.9 ± 3.9 FPA (°): 20.7 ± 2.4</p> <p>GM FL (cm): Mid-belly: Rhythmic gymnasts: 4.2 ± 0.4 Volleyball players: $4.2 \pm 0.5\#$</p> <p>Distal: Rhythmic gymnasts: 4.3 ± 0.4 Volleyball players: 4.2 ± 0.7</p> <p>GM FPA (°): Mid-belly: Rhythmic gymnasts: 21.8 ± 1.8 Volleyball players: $21.2 \pm 1.4\#$</p> <p>Distal: Rhythmic gymnasts: 18.0 ± 2.0 Volleyball players: 19.5 ± 2.5</p>
Panidi <i>et al.</i> (2021)	Adolescent (13.5 ± 1.4) volleyball players	Female	Maturity offset (-0.8 ± 0.9)	<p>GM FL (cm): 50% STR: 5.1 ± 0.7 50% CON: 4.8 ± 0.6 30% STR: 4.9 ± 0.7 30% CON: 4.6 ± 0.7</p> <p>GL FL (cm): 50% STR: 5.3 ± 0.7 50% CON: 4.9 ± 0.6 30% STR: 4.9 ± 0.7 30% CON: 4.6 ± 0.7</p>
Ritsche <i>et al.</i> (2021)	Youth soccer players (U13: 12.5 ± 0.1 ; U14: 13.5 ± 0.3 ; U15: 14.4 ± 0.3)	Not reported	Not assessed	<p>BFlh: FL (cm): U13: 6.9 ± 0.8 U14: 7.1 ± 0.8 U15: 7.6 ± 0.8</p>

				FPA (°): U13: 17.9 ± 2.2 U14: 19.2 ± 2.0 U15: 19.4 ± 1.4
Secomb <i>et al.</i> (2015)	Competitive surfers (15.1 ± 1.4)	Not reported	Not assessed	VL: FPA: 17.1 ± 2.1 FL: 7.11 ± 1.34 GL: FPA: 14.2 ± 2.8 FL: 6.08 ± 1.16
Secomb <i>et al.</i> (2015a)	Adolescent surfing athletes (14.8 ± 1.7)	Male & female	Not assessed	VL: FPA: 17.27 ± 2.62 FL: 7.14 ± 1.23 GL: FPA: 14.67 ± 2.76 FL: 5.65 ± 1.12
Secomb <i>et al.</i> (2017)	Competitive surfers (14 ± 1.8 years)	Not reported	Not assessed	VL: FPA: 17.95 ± 1.85 FL: 6.78 ± 0.57 GL: FPA: 14.7 ± 2.3 FL: 5.74 ± 0.86
Siddle <i>et al.</i> (2022)	Youth soccer players (16.7 ± 0.6 years)	Male	Not assessed	BFlh: FL (cm): 7.82 ± 1.06 FPA: 17.33 ± 3.12

Key: LS: longitudinal study; CS: cross-sectional study; RT: resistance training; BF: biceps femoris; BFlh: Biceps femoris long head; SM: semimembranosus; GM: gastrocnemius medialis; GL: gastrocnemius lateralis; VL: vastus lateralis; VM: vastus medialis; Vlat: lateral vastus intermedius; VIant: anterior vastus intermedius; RF: rectus femoris; TB: triceps brachii; FPA fibre pennation angle; FL: fascicle length; rFL: relative fascicle length; STR: stretching intervention; *: indicates significant within group change/effect ($p \leq 0.05$). #: indicates significant between groups change/effect ($p \leq 0.05$); p: sig. different to the proximal site; c: sig. different to the central site; d: sig. different from the distal site.

(Table 2.4). This indicates any increase in FPA will likely lead to an increase in maximal force production capabilities due to the concomitant increments in muscle fibre CSA and PCSA (Alexander and Vernon, 1975). On the other hand, a larger FPA has been proposed to be at the expense of contraction velocity, with more acute pennation angles being associated with greater contraction speeds (Abe, Kumagai and Brechue, 2000). Indeed, Secomb *et al.* (2017) found significant decrements (-11.6%; $p < 0.05$) in FPA following gymnastics and plyometric training, but not resistance training (Table 2.3), suggesting muscle architectural remodelling in response to exercise involving high velocity movements. Despite this, as muscular power output is determined by both contraction force and velocity (see section 2.1.0), the positive effect an increased FPA may exert upon contraction force (associated with increased muscle CSA) may counter-balance the resulting negative effects this remodelling exerts upon contraction speed. This may be partly the reason for the lack of significant change seen with either group examined by Secomb *et al.* (2017) in countermovement jump (CMJ) performance, as VL MT values (see section 2.5.1) were non-significantly different post-intervention for either of the intervention groups. This finding was observed despite the aforementioned FPA remodelling having occurred in the gymnastics and plyometric group, but not the resistance training group (Table 2.3); yet the resistance training group displayed increments in maximal force production capabilities (see section 2.5.2). Therefore, it could be assumed that the resistance training group obtained changes associated with greater force production capabilities, and the gymnastics and plyometric group with greater contraction velocities of the VL. This either/or response by both groups seems to have resulted in an unchanged CMJ performance (Secomb *et al.*, 2017). It is also likely that the intervention duration was of insufficient length to exert a positive influence upon CMJ height. In agreement with this notion, a meta-analysis by Moran *et al.* (2017b) concluded that longer (> 15 sessions) plyometric interventions may be more effective in improving CMJ height.

Similarly, Secomb *et al.* (2015b) displayed non-significantly larger muscle FPA values following resistance training without any observed increments in lower body isometric force production capabilities or CMJ performance (Table 2.3). However, Murtagh *et al.* (2018) found in their study on elite youth soccer players (average age: 18.1 years) that unilateral vertical and medial CMJ height to be significantly correlated ($r = 0.48$ and 0.41 respectively) with VL pennation angle. In addition, the authors also noted horizontal-forward CMJ power to be negatively correlated ($r = -0.41$, $p = 0.04$) with VL FPA, indicating the effects of FPA on powerful actions to be direction specific (Murtagh *et al.*, 2018b). Collectively, the results of

these studies indicate that resistance training should be performed concurrently with plyometric-type activities that utilise fast SSC actions within youth development programmes to holistically attain desirable physiological adaptations. Despite this, research evaluating the effect of FPA on force production of power output in youth populations requires further evaluation before any clear conclusions can be drawn.

2.5.2.2 Muscle fascicle length

FL can be assessed reliably (English, Fisher and Thoirs, 2012; Kwah *et al.*, 2013) among youth cohorts (Legerlotz, Smith and Hing, 2010), particularly when the muscle of interest is in an unactive state (Kwah *et al.*, 2013). A muscle's contraction velocity is dependent upon the number of sarcomeres arranged in series which is, in turn, related to the length of the muscle's fascicles (Goldspink, 1985). Therefore, it is likely that for greater contraction speeds, assuming other aspects of the musculature remain equal, increases in FL is of important consideration when designing programmes aimed at developing components which are influenced positively by speed or power, such as acceleration, maximal sprint speed, deceleration, or jump height.

Despite absolute FL increases with age and maturation (O'Brien *et al.*, 2010b), when expressed relative to limb length (e.g., femur length) or muscle length (e.g., VL length), differences are not observed between children and adults (Mersmann *et al.*, 2014; O'Brien *et al.*, 2010b). In addition, it has been shown that these differences in FL vary depending on the examined muscle and site of observation (O'Brien *et al.*, 2010b; O'Brien *et al.*, 2010a). Similarly, this change is relatively smaller compared to changes to the muscle CSA, suggesting maturation alone tends to remodel musculature in favour of force production compared to maximum shortening velocity (O'Brien *et al.*, 2010b). Therefore, in order for adolescent athletes to obtain increases in FL, additional specific training is likely required as opposed to relying on natural increases due to a change in maturity status.

In line with this assumption, previous research has reported increments in FL of trained musculature following specific resistance training interventions (Lacome *et al.*, 2019; Secomb *et al.*, 2017) (Table 2.3). Indeed, Lacome *et al.* (2019) demonstrated possibly-to-likely changes in biceps femoris long head (+5.2%) and semimembranosus (+6.8%) FL in elite youth soccer players following 12 weeks of eccentric hamstring exercise training and Secomb *et al.* (2017) observed significant changes in VL (+15.4%) FL following 7 weeks of gymnastics and

plyometric training absent of any change to muscle size related measures (see Table 2.1), which seemingly did not contribute to improved CMJ performance (jump height or force output) in adolescent athletes. Similarly, the comparative resistance training group in this study obtained changes in VL (+8.5%) FL, but did not display any differences in CMJ performance (Secomb *et al.*, 2017). However, improvements in squat jump peak velocity were observed alongside improvements in maximal isometric strength in the resistance training group (Secomb *et al.*, 2017). In addition, the gymnastics and plyometric training group displayed significant improvements in eccentric leg stiffness (Secomb *et al.*, 2017). This is in agreement with Lacombe *et al.* (2019) who observed improvements in eccentric hamstring strength following their 12-week intervention. Therefore, it is likely that improvements in FL of associated musculature to performance tasks may result in improvement of those tasks provided adequate training durations above the thresholds displayed here have been permitted (Moran *et al.*, 2017b), particularly when concurrent improvements in muscle size have been obtained. It has also been demonstrated that adolescent athletes are capable of obtaining increases in FL following specific training programmes.

2.6.0 The assessment of maximal muscular force and power production capabilities

The relevance of high-intensity neuromuscular actions has led to the wide-spread implementation of performance tests aimed at evaluating muscular force and power characteristics in youth soccer athletes either via isoinertial (Chelly *et al.*, 2010; Comfort *et al.*, 2014; Kobal *et al.*, 2017; Peña-González *et al.*, 2019), isokinetic or hand-held dynamometry (Bogdanis and Kalapotharakos, 2016), or isometric testing procedures (Dos'Santos *et al.*, 2018; Morris *et al.*, 2018b; Thomas *et al.*, 2015).

Isoinertial field-based strength assessments in youth soccer typically involve repetition maximum (e.g. 1-, 3-, 5-repetition maximum) (Chelly *et al.*, 2010), or predicted repetition maximum tests, which use regression equations based on either velocity measurements (e.g. barbell velocity) collected during the assessed movement (Peña-González *et al.*, 2019), or repetitions to failure protocols using submaximal loads (Comfort *et al.*, 2014). However, these isoinertial tests can be influenced by resistance training experience in youth populations, making between-group comparisons problematic (Weakley *et al.*, 2017). Similarly, repetition maximum tests can be difficult to administer due to their associated difficulties in selecting a

suitable number of attempts, large within-subject variation of 1RM values, and issues surrounding participant fatigue when performing multiple attempts which are likely to be to the detriment of subsequent performance (Seo *et al.*, 2012).

However, these methodological issues seem to not affect multiple-joint isometric strength tests (Bazyler, Beckham and Sato, 2015). Moreover, excellent reliability (Brady, Harrison and Comyns, 2020) for isometric tests have been observed among well trained (Nimphius *et al.*, 2019) athletes and recreationally active (Markovic *et al.*, 2007) populations. Isometric tests may therefore be preferred by practitioners for use with youth populations due to their reduced required technical skill, reduced injury risk, and greater reliability when compared to isoinertial tests of strength (Brady, Harrison and Comyns, 2020; Drake, Kennedy and Wallace, 2017). Moreover, multiple-joint isometric tests are widely utilised due to the greater level of transference and specificity of results to powerful actions such as accelerating and jumping when compared to isometric single-joint tests (Drake, Kennedy and Wallace, 2017; Wilhelm *et al.*, 2013). Additionally, when utilising appropriately sensitive equipment, isometric testing allows the reliable characterisation of specific force-time components which may provide a more in-depth understanding of training adaptation (Brady, Harrison and Comyns, 2020; Drake, Kennedy and Wallace, 2017).

Two common assessment procedures used to measure multiple-joint lower body isometric strength in youth populations are the ISqT (Marshall *et al.*, 2019) and the IMTP (Dos'Santos *et al.*, 2018). Research evaluating both tests found the ISqT to outperform the IMTP due to the ability to detect larger peak force production values (Brady *et al.*, 2018; Brady *et al.*, 2019; Nuzzo *et al.*, 2008), thus indicating the ISqT as a superior proxy tool for measuring lower-body absolute force production. This may be due to the use of the upper-body during the IMTP, as confirmed by associations with tasks heavily involving the upper-body musculature (Stone *et al.*, 2003; Stone, Sands and Stone, 2007; Wells *et al.*, 2018). This suggests that deficits in upper-body strength would likely lead to decrements in IMTP performance when compared to ISqT performance, with consequent biased accurate evaluations. Indeed, reduced upper body force production capabilities may have contributed to the reduced performance of the IMTP compared to the ISqT for female athletes, but not for their male counterparts (Brady *et al.*, 2018), as adult male soccer players have been shown to outperform adult female soccer players in upper-body strength and power related tasks (Ramírez-Campillo *et al.*, 2016). This alludes to the possible contribution of upper body force production capabilities to IMTP performance.

Therefore, the use of the IMTP may not best evaluate lower body absolute maximal force production capabilities in youth male athletes, as upper-body strength levels may have not developed yet to the same level of adult males (Catley and Tomkinson, 2013; Falk *et al.*, 2009).

As a result, youth soccer players may not have sufficient upper body strength capabilities in order to appropriately engage with the barbell. Consequently, they may be unable to produce large enough GRF's during an IMTP to accurately represent lower-limb maximum force producing capabilities. Therefore, this cohort may not be best able to perform the IMTP effectively, with programming related changes in upper body strength potentially contributing to performance scores. As a result, the use of the upper limbs may disguise an effective evaluation of the lower limbs given individuals with greater upper limb strength would have out perform their peers. Moreover, in a recent review evidence for higher reliability and responsiveness (i.e., ability to detect change over time) was reported for the ISqT compared the IMTP test (Drake, Kennedy and Wallace, 2017). In summary, the use of isometric multiple-joint strength tests are safe for use within youth populations, with the ISqT indicated as an appropriate test to isolate lower-body force production qualities.

2.6.1 The isometric squat test

To understand the usefulness of the ISqT, validity, reliability, and methodological factors should be carefully considered. Construct validity is the extent a performance test measures what it proposes, therefore establishing the ISqT is a valid performance test of muscular strength and power is important for the applied practitioner to evaluate programming aimed at improving these components. Similarly, by ensuring a performance test is reliable it will allow for accurate and unbiased within- and between-athlete comparisons of physical performance measurements, and therefore confirm the consistency of the performance assessments. By ensuring that the methodological elements of the ISqT are made consistent will lead to a reduction in between-trial variability due to possible methodological flaws. The measurement error of the ISqT is the difference between the true value of the test and measured value, it is important to understand this difference and whether its magnitude is acceptable in practice (Hopkins, 2000). This error will directly impact the reliability of the ISqT, as any changes in performance values between two testing points smaller than that of the measurement error cannot be certainly assumed to reflect improvements in performance. It is important to understand the sources of measurement error of a performance test in order to make decisions

regarding its implementation. Therefore, the validity and reliability of performance tests are closely linked, as poor reliability will result in difficulties in interpreting the validity of a performance testing method. The following sections will expand on these elements specific to the ISqT.

2.6.1.1 *Validity and reliability of the isometric squat*

Although a broad definition of validity has previously been provided, many different types of validity exist, with numerous methods for providing evidence of each validity type available. The validity of force outputs collected during the ISqT have been investigated in detail (Drake, Kennedy and Wallace, 2017). Criterion validity of the ISqT is typically assessed against a 1RM back squat test, the widely accepted gold standard assessment of isoinertial strength. Strong, significant relationships ($r^2 = 0.61$; $r = 0.77$) have previously been observed between the average maximal force produced during two trials of the ISqT performed at a knee angle of 90° and the load lifted during a 1RM back squat performed to the same knee angle in recreationally trained adult males (Blazevich, Gill and Newton, 2002). This suggests isometric strength may partly predict dynamic strength test performance. Similarly, absolute peak force (PF) values for adult male populations obtained during the ISqT at knee angles of both 90° and 140° have been previously observed to hold a strong association with 1RM back squat performance ($r = 0.69$, and 0.62 respectively) (Drake, Kennedy and Wallace, 2018; Nuzzo *et al.*, 2008). In addition, Drake *et al.* (2018) found significant relationships between the load lifted during a 1RM back squat test and net force produced during an ISqT (Table 2.5 summarises the mechanical variables that can be collected during the ISqT and the methodological steps for their calculation). A significant relationship was also found between relative PF (rPF) produced during an ISqT (Table 2.5) and the relative load lifted during a back squat 1RM (relative 1RM load = 1RM load/ bodyweight). This is in contrast to Nuzzo *et al.* (2008) who found no significant relationship between rPF obtained during the ISqT and relative back squat 1RM performance.

Although in both the aforementioned studies participants were resistance trained males, the knee joint angle at which the ISqT was performed differed between the two studies (90° vs 140°; Drake, Kennedy and Wallace, 2018; Nuzzo *et al.*, 2008; respectively). This presumably had a direct effect on the divergent force output between these two studies, as the ISqT PF values observed by Nuzzo *et al.* (2008) is noticeably larger than that observed by Drake *et al.* (2018) (ISqT PF: 3522 ± 635 N vs 2510 ± 582 N respectively). This would, in-turn, confound the rPF values given the body mass of the participants were relatively similar between these two studies (90.1 ± 1.4 kg vs 93.5 ± 12.4 kg). Indeed, PF during the concentric phase of a squat has previously been reported to occur during knee flexion angles of 130° to 170° (Cormie, McCaulley and McBride, 2007) with peak isometric torque of the knee extensors previously been observed to be produced at a 120° knee joint angle (Bazyler, Beckham and Sato, 2015; Blazeovich, Gill and Newton, 2002; Smidt, 1973). Additionally, Bayzler and colleagues (2015) demonstrated that the PF values obtained from the ISqT performed at knee joint flexion angles of 90° and 120° among recreationally trained adult males were significantly correlated to 1RM performance in the back squat ($r = 0.86$ and 0.60 respectively). The ISqT performed at a knee joint angle of 120° may be of practical relevance when assessing lower-body peak multiple-joint force output, as peak outputs in the ISqT have been observed to be produced at this knee joint angle (Bazyler, Beckham and Sato, 2015; Blazeovich, Gill and Newton, 2002; Smidt, 1973).

Table 2.5: Definition of metrics that can be measured through examination of an isometric squat test.

Metric (unit)	Abbreviation	Definition
Absolute peak force (N)	PF	Highest instantaneous absolute force recorded
Average peak force (N)	avgPF	PF divided by time of contraction/epoch
Net force (N)	NetF	PF minus the participants body weight
Relative peak force (N/kg)	rPF	PF divided by the participants body weight
Allometrically scaled peak force (N/kg ^{0.67})	aPF	PF ÷ (participants body weight x 0.67)
Time to peak force (s)	TTPF	Time to achieve PF value during the contraction
Average force (N)	AvgF	Average force achieved during the contraction
Impulse (N.s)	IMP	Change in force x change in time
Average impulse (N.s)	AvgIMP	The average impulse over a given contraction/epoch
Rate of force development (N/s)	RFD	Change in force ÷ change in time
Peak rate of force development (N/s)	PRFD	Highest instantaneous rate of force development during a given contraction/epoch

Key: N: newtons; N/kg: newtons per kilogram; s: seconds; N.s: newton seconds; N/s: newtons per second.

Practitioners can therefore assume from the research presented here that the ISqT holds acceptable criterion validity when assessed against the gold standard 1RM back squat assessment, particularly at knee joint angles at or above 120°. However, further research is warranted, particularly in well-trained, youth and female populations (Brady, Harrison and Comyns, 2020; Drake, Kennedy and Wallace, 2017).

The ISqT has been shown to discriminate between playing position in elite male field-based team sport athletes based on their physical attributes (Comfort *et al.*, 2011). In addition, Bazylar *et al.* (2014a) found significantly different 1RM back squat performances between individuals which were grouped according to an allometric scaling based on the ISqT performance at 120° of knee flexion, thereby confirming the ISqT had successfully polarised the group based on the performance of the criterion 1RM assessment. Similarly, in trained males, the ISqT has been shown to discriminate between individuals with different 1RM strength levels when the athletes were grouped according to either their absolute PF, or, net force, or relative force production outputs during the ISqT (Drake, Kennedy and Wallace, 2018). Therefore, there is sufficient evidence to support that the ISqT holds acceptable levels of discriminant validity and the ability to differentiate between contrasting groups, strength levels, or force production capabilities.

The correct interpretation of performance test results requires practitioners to determine to what extent which the test can detect true changes in performance over time, and as such the efficacy of training interventions or recovery from injury accurately (Hopkins, Hawley and Burke, 1999; Norman, Wyrwich and Patrick, 2007). This is termed sensitivity, and is directly impacted by the measurement error the performance test contains, as assessment methods containing large measurement errors are less likely to accurately describe changes in performance (Hopkins, 2000). Small measurement errors have also been previously suggested to be of importance in order for performance assessments to also detect subtle changes in performance, which may contribute to meaningful changes in the overall performance of the athlete (Atkinson and Nevill, 1998). A higher level of sensitivity has been suggested as one of the advantages of isometric strength tests as compared to traditional 1RM strength tests, as indicated in research which demonstrated significant improvements in the ISqT but not in 1RM performance following strength training interventions (Bazylar *et al.*, 2014b). Indeed, recent research has directly evaluated the sensitivity of the ISqT and found acceptable smallest-detectable difference values (270.33–273.35 N), absolute error (CV = 3.88–6.11%) and relative

reliability (ICC = 0.56–0.89) for the ISqT (Drake, Kennedy and Wallace, 2018). These findings are in agreement with the results of a recent review, in which the authors collected more research outputs of higher methodological quality as available to infer that the ISqT holds better sensitivity compared to the IMTP test (Drake, Kennedy and Wallace, 2017).

The usefulness of a performance test is highly dependent upon the measurement error it contains. Reliability can be considered as the reproducibility of assessment variables administered on more than one occasion typically over short periods of time the assessed variable would not be expected to change throughout (Atkinson and Nevill, 1998). Reliability of a performance test is typically measured using the intraclass correlation coefficient (ICC) which provides information pertaining to the correlation between two datasets. Indeed, numerous studies have utilised the ICC when evaluating the reliability of the ISqT (Brady, Harrison and Comyns, 2020). An ICC less than 0.5, between 0.5 and 0.75, between 0.75 and 0.9, and greater than 0.90 were indicative of poor, moderate, good, and excellent agreements, respectively (Koo and Li, 2016; Portney and Watkins, 2000).

However, since it is entirely possible to obtain scores which are correlated but not repeatable, the ICC does not provide an indication of the systematic bias of a performance test. As a result, research evaluating the reliability of a performance test should include the coefficient of variation (CV) that allows the estimation of the measurement error of a performance test from repeated measurements (Hopkins, 2000). This has been observed as an important addition to the statistical analysis when evaluating the ISqT, as numerous reliability studies have reported acceptable ICC values, but also high levels of measurement variability as determined by the CV (Bazyler *et al.*, 2014b; Hart *et al.*, 2012b; Marshall *et al.*, 2019). Therefore, results from ISqT reliability studies which report the ICCs but not CV in this review are to be interpreted with caution (Bartolomei *et al.*, 2017; Marián *et al.*, 2016; Marshall *et al.*, 2012; Tsoukos *et al.*, 2016) as the ICC, a representation of relative reliability, is greatly strengthened with an additional measure of absolute reliability (i.e., the CV). Thus, reporting both reliability statistics results in a greater level of evidence. Through measuring the degree to which an individual measurement maintains its position within the group dataset, these measurements are affected by group homogeneity. Contrary to this, absolute reliability does not depend on group homogeneity as these measures display the variation for individuals over numerous trials. Therefore, an ICC equal or greater than 0.8 or a CV equal or lower than 10% have been

previously suggested as reference cut-off thresholds to infer good reliability and low measurement variability (Hopkins, 2000).

Despite the appropriateness of these measures, the absolute amount of measurement error should be appropriate for the chosen test despite whether or not the level of variance is within the acceptable limits. For example, in a given case, a 10% variance of a 2500N force output for an ISqT, a likely estimate for youth soccer players (Table 2.6) (Brady *et al.*, 2019; Marshall *et al.*, 2019; Young, McLean and Ardagna, 1995), would equate to 250N of force. Despite this being theoretically within the acceptable range of variability (i.e. $\leq 10\%$; Hopkins, 2000), this absolute score has been previously proven to be unacceptable for within-individual between-trial comparisons (Kraska *et al.*, 2009). To account for the level of uncertainty a reliability measure holds, thus allowing for more accurate comparisons between studies and accurate interpretation of results, the confidence intervals (CI) should also be reported (Atkinson and Nevill, 1998; Hopkins, 2000).

For example, although an average CV of 9.9% and 8.1% for impulse at 200 ms and impulse at 250 ms was reported by Brady *et al.* (2018), CI ranged from acceptable to unacceptable for both these metrics (7.9–14.3% and 6.3–11.4% respectively). Therefore, reporting the CI will better reflect the error across the sample of participants studied, whereas variation between testing trials conducted within the same day, and therefore can be mitigated when the assessment procedures are conducted by the same researcher using the same equipment (Hopkins, 2000). Therefore, the ISqT should be performed by the same researcher utilising the same force-plate technology between different trials where possible. Conversely, where not possible, inter-tester reliability should be evaluated to ensure consistent performance observations.

To date, numerous studies have reported intra-day relative reliability data for the ISqT conducted through the use of ICCs (Table 2.7) (Bazyler, Beckham and Sato, 2015; Brady *et al.*, 2018; Brady *et al.*, 2019; Davies *et al.*, 2018; Gannon, Stokes and Trewartha, 2016; Hart *et al.*, 2012a; Marián *et al.*, 2016; Markovic *et al.*, 2007; Marshall *et al.*, 2012; Marshall *et al.*, 2019; Wilson *et al.*, 1995), with the majority of those studies ($n = 9$) reporting excellent

Table 2.6: Research reporting normative data for the isometric squat test.

Study	Participant information (age)	Sex	Knee joint angle	Instruction	Force-time metric(s) measured (unit)	Normative baseline values \pm SD
Bartolomei <i>et al.</i> (2017)	Resistance trained (24.5 \pm 4.2 years)	Male	90°		PF (N)	2744 \pm 410
					PRFD20ms (N/s)	5100 \pm 1379
Bartolomei <i>et al.</i> (2021)	Resistance trained (24.1 \pm 4.4)	Male	90°		PF (N)	2153
Bartolomei <i>et al.</i> (2022)	Resistance trained (25.3 \pm 6.1 years)	Male	Not reported		PF (N)	2242 \pm 387
Blagrove <i>et al.</i> (2021)	Youth distance runners (17.5 \pm 0.4 years)	Male & female	140°		aPF (N/kg ^{-0.61})	168
Brady <i>et al.</i> (2017)	Athletes from multiple sports (male: 23.0 \pm 4.8 years; female: 24.5 \pm 3.1 years)	Male & female	136 \pm 3°	Push as hard and as fast as you can, push the ground away, drive your feet into the ground and the bar from the floor	Male: PF (N)	2466 \pm 761
					rPF (N/kg)	33.30 \pm 7.00
					aPF (N/kg)	137.66 \pm 33.00
					RFD200ms (N/s)	6044 \pm 2090
					RFD250ms (N/s)	5297 \pm 1701

IMP300ms (N.s)	407 ± 142
Female:	
PF (N)	2090 ± 578
rPF (N/kg)	33.40 ± 8.70
aPF (N/kg)	130.60 ± 34.60
RFD200ms (N/s)	5614 ± 1589
RFD250ms (N/s)	4741 ± 1335
IMP300ms (N.s)	333 ± 75
Male & female:	
PF (N)	2322 ± 709
rPF (N/kg)	33.30 ± 7.50
aPF (N/kg)	134.90 ± 33.10
RFD200ms (N/s)	5879 ± 1891
RFD250ms (N/s)	5083 ± 1566
IMP200ms (N.s)	212 ± 74
IMP250ms (N.s)	294 ± 99
IMP300ms (N.s)	379 ± 124

Brady <i>et al.</i> (2019)	Sprint athletes (male: 21.7 ± 3.6 years; female: 23.9 ± 2.3 years)	Male & female	141 ± 4°	Push as hard and as fast as you can	Male:	
					PF (N)	2314 ± 646
					rPF (N/kg)	30.6 ± 8.6
					PF100ms (N)	1193 ± 446
					PF150ms (N)	1395 ± 2386
					PF200ms (N)	1660 ± 437
					RFD150ms (N/s)	7395 ± 2386
					RFD200ms (N/s)	6351 ± 1725
					IMP200ms (N.s)	225 ± 70
					Female:	
					PF (N)	1884 ± 521
					rPF (N/kg)	29.2 ± 7.4
					PF100ms (N)	897 ± 339
					PF150ms (N)	1179 ± 412
					PF200ms (N)	1380 ± 442
					RFD150ms (N/s)	5805 ± 1869
					RFD200ms (N/s)	5360 ± 1544
					IMP200ms (N.s)	173 ± 63

Comfort <i>et al.</i> (2011)	Professional rugby league players (21.7 ± 4.1 years)	Male	135°		Forwards: PF (N)	3122 ± 611
					rPF (N/kg)	30.7 ± 7.9
					Backs: PF (N)	2927 ± 607
					rPF (N/kg)	34.3 ± 5.3
Cormie <i>et al.</i> (2006)	Recreationally trained (19– 23 years)	Male	100°		PF (N)	1816 ± 416
Cormie <i>et al.</i> (2007)	Recreationally trained (21.1 ± 2.5 years)	Male	100°		PF (N)	2230 ± 446
Davies <i>et al.</i> (2018)	Resistance trained (23 ± 3 years)	Male	110°	Push into the barbell as fast and as forcefully as possible	PF (N)	701 ± 177
					RFD150ms (N/s)	2472 ± 1325
Davies <i>et al.</i> (2020)	Recreationally trained (23.5 years)	Male	110°	Push into the barbell as fast and as forcefully as possible	PF over 1s	776 ± 205
Drake <i>et al.</i> (2018)	Strength trained (21.4 ± 4.5 years)	Male	90°	Push against the ground as hard and as fast as possible	PF (N)	5005 ± 582
					NetF (N)	3169 ± 514
					rPF (N/kg)	54 ± 6.9

Drake <i>et al.</i> (2019b)	Resistance trained (26.8 ± 4.5 years)	Male and female	100° & 125°	Push against the bar as hard and as fast as possible	100°: PF (N)	2013 ± 252
					TTPF (s)	1.78 ± 0.43
					RFD30ms (N/s)	1261 ± 529
					RFD50ms (N/s)	1950 ± 937.6
					RFD90ms (N/s)	3122 ± 1652
					RFD100ms (N/s)	3315 ± 1711
					RFD150ms (N/s)	3890 ± 1709
					RFD200ms (N/s)	3982 ± 1506
					RFD250ms (N/s)	3828 ± 1237
					AvgRFD (N/s)	1034 ± 337.8
					PRFD1ms (N/s)	7068 ± 1819
					PRFD2ms (N/s)	6875 ± 1808
					PRFD5ms (N/s)	6664 ± 1784
					PRFD10ms (N/s)	6580 ± 1774
					PRFD20ms (N/s)	6479 ± 1748
					PRFD30ms (N/s)	6377 ± 1713
					PRFD50ms (N/s)	6171 ± 1630
					125°: PF (N)	2904 ± 409

					TTPF (s)	2.03 ± 0.30
					RFD30ms (N/s)	1787 ± 1015
					RFD50ms (N/s)	2829 ± 1781
					RFD90ms (N/s)	4343 ± 2279
					RFD100ms (N/s)	4581 ± 2229
					RFD150ms (N/s)	5548 ± 2165
					RFD200ms (N/s)	5833 ± 1980
					RFD250ms (N/s)	5577 ± 1662
					AvgRFD (N/s)	1302 ± 221.3
					PRFD1ms (N/s)	9422 ± 3190
					PRFD2ms (N/s)	9244 ± 3223
					PRFD5ms (N/s)	9008 ± 3228
					PRFD10ms (N/s)	8934 ± 3223
					PRFD20ms (N/s)	8815 ± 3169
					PRFD30ms (N/s)	8667 ± 3068
					PRFD50ms (N/s)	8316 ± 2826
Ishida <i>et al.</i> (2023a)	Resistance trained men (27.8 ± 3.9 years)	Male	120°	Push as fast and hard as possible	PF (N)	3672 ± 635
					rPF (N/kg)	42.0 ± 5.1
					RFD250 (N/s)	4837 ± 1068
					IMP250 (N.s)	528 ± 110

Kadlec <i>et al.</i> (2021)	Australian footballers (22.6 ± 4.5 years)	Female	140°		PF (N)	2127 ± 393
Kennedy <i>et al.</i> (2018)	Elite rugby union players (age = 19.5 ± 2.3 years)	Male	90°	Push as hard and as fast as possible	rPF (N/kg)	17.0 ± 3.0
Lum <i>et al.</i> (2021)	Kayak athletes (21 ± 4 years)	Male & female	90° & 120°		90°: PF (N)	1837
					RFD90 (N/s)	2880
					120°: PF (N)	2615
					RFD90 (N/s)	4005
Lynch <i>et al.</i> (2021)	Recreationally active (23.5 ± 4.1 years)	Male	65°, 90°, & 120°		PF (N): 65°	820 ± 205
					90°	919 ± 287
					120°	1259 ± 525

Nimphius <i>et al.</i> (2019)	Resistance trained (21.4 ± 1.8 years)	Male & female	100°	Push as hard as possible through the ground	Male:	
					PF (N)	2660 ± 618
					rPF (N/kg)	3.39 ± 0.68
					Female:	
PF (N)	2219 ± 533					
					rPF (N/kg)	3.38 ± 0.8
Nuzzo <i>et al.</i> (2008)	Athletes from multiple sports (19.8 ± 1.4 years)	Male	140°	Push with maximal effort as quickly as possible	PF (N)	3522 ± 635
					rPF (N/kg)	39.6 ± 4.6
					PRFD (N/s)	6102 ± 1579
Tillin <i>et al.</i> (2013)	Rugby union players (20 ± 1 years)	Male	118 ± 5°	Push against the bar as hard as possible	PF (N)	2934 ± 339
					aPF (N/kg)	149 ± 19
Travis <i>et al.</i> (2021)	Athletes (23.8 ± 4.1 years)	Male & female	90°		aPF (N/kg)	125.6 ± 14.4
Travis <i>et al.</i> (2022)	Athletes (23.8 ± 4.1 years)	Male & female	90°		PF (N)	2272 ± 40.5
					aPF (N/kg)	113.6 ± 16.5
Tsoukos <i>et al.</i> (2016)	National level jumpers and decathletes (27.1 ± 7 years)	Male	90° & 140°		90°:	
					PF (N)	2138 ± 340
					IMP (N.s)	17848 ± 2836

					AvgF (N)	1811 ± 277
					140°: PF (N)	3831 ± 584
					IMP (N.s)	30252 ± 6974
					AvgF (N)	2917 ± 419
Wagner <i>et al.</i> (2022)	Youth soccer players (18.4 ± 1.5 years)	Male	120°		PF (N)	3071 ± 647 (95%CI: 2754–3388)
					rPF (N/kg)	40.3 ± 7.9 (95%CI: 36.4–44.2)
Wilson <i>et al.</i> (1995)	Athletes from multiple sports (22.6 ± 4.5 years)	Male	110° & 150°	Perform contraction as rapidly and forcefully as possible	110°: PF (N)	1855 ± 361
					PRFD (N/s)	14059 ± 7876
					f30ms (N)	88.5 ± 48.1
					IMP100ms (N.s)	23810 ± 1180
					150°: PF (N)	1989 ± 361
					PRFD (N/s)	11662 ± 7036
					f30ms (N)	106 ± 70
					IMP100ms (N.s)	23386 ± 13999

Wilson <i>et al.</i>	Recreationally trained (26 ± 6 years)	Male	90°		PF (N)	1741
					RFD50–100	4932
					RFD100–200	5009
Young <i>et al.</i> (1995)	Athletes from multiple sports (16–18 years)	Male & female	120°	Progressively build up force	PF (N)	2.603 ± 575
					rPF (N/kg)	3.70 ± 0.85

Key: SD: standard deviation; PF: peak force; N: newtons; PRFD: peak rate of force development; ms: milliseconds; N/s: newton seconds; rPF relative peak force; N/kg: newtons per kilogram; aPF: allometrically scaled PF; RFD: rate of force development; IMP: impulse; TTPF: time to peak force; s: seconds; AvgRFD: average RFD; aRFD: allometrically scaled RFD; AvgF: average force; f: force (at time epoch).

Table 2.7: Research reporting reliability data for the isometric squat test.

Study	Participant information (age)	Knee joint angle	Number of familiarisations	Force-time metric(s) measured (unit)	ICC (CI)	CV (CI)	TEM	SEM (CI)
Ansdell <i>et al.</i> (2020)	Recreationally active (25 ± 5 years)	90°	1	PF		14.5%		
Bartolomei <i>et al.</i> (2017)	Resistance trained (24.5 ± 4.2 years)	90°		PF	0.73			
				PRFD20ms	0.51			
Bartolomei <i>et al.</i> (2021)	Resistance trained (24.1 ± 4.4 years)	90°		PF	0.83			219.6
Bartolomei <i>et al.</i> (2022)	Resistance trained (25.3 ± 6.1 years)	Not assessed		PF	0.85			822.5
Bazyler <i>et al.</i> (2014b)	Recreationally trained (20.8 ± 2 years)	90° & 120°	6	90°: aPF	0.97			
				RFD200ms			≥ 19.6%	
				IMP50ms	≥ 0.92			
				IMP90ms	≥ 0.92			
				IMP200ms	≥ 0.92			

				120°: aPF	0.98	
				RFD200ms		≥ 19.6%
				IMP50ms	≥ 0.92	
				IMP90ms	≥ 0.92	
				IMP200ms	≥ 0.92	
Bazyler <i>et al.</i> (2015)	Recreationally trained (20.8 ± 1.9 years)	90° & 120°	6	90°: PF	0.97	rTEM: 2.3%
				IMP250ms	0.95	4.3%
				RFD250ms	0.90	8.1%
				120°: PF	0.99	2.8%
				IMP250ms	0.97	4.3%
Blagrove <i>et al.</i> (2021)	Youth distance runners (17.5 ± 0.4 years)	140°	1	RFD250ms aPF	0.90 0.86 (95% CI: 0.61– 0.96)	9.4%
Blazevich <i>et al.</i> (2002)	Recreationally trained (19–26 years)	90°		PF	0.97 (95% CI: 0.91– 0.99)	

Brady <i>et al.</i> (2018)	Athletes from multiple sports (male: 23.0 ± 4.8 years; female: 24.5 ± 3.1 years)	136 ± 3°	1	PF	0.97 (95%CI: 0.94–0.99)	4.6% (95%CI: 3.6–6.4)
				rPF	0.95 (95%CI: 0.88–0.98)	4.6% (95%CI: 3.6–6.4)
				aPF	0.96 (95%CI: 0.90–0.98)	4.6% (95%CI: 3.6–6.4)
				RFD30ms	Unreliable (ICC < 0.8/CV > 10%)	Unreliable (ICC < 0.8/CV > 10%)
				RFD50ms	Unreliable (ICC < 0.8/CV > 10%)	Unreliable (ICC < 0.8/CV > 10%)
				RFD90ms	Unreliable (ICC < 0.8/CV > 10%)	Unreliable (ICC < 0.8/CV > 10%)
				RFD100ms	Unreliable (ICC < 0.8/CV > 10%)	Unreliable (ICC < 0.8/CV > 10%)
				RFD150ms	Unreliable (ICC < 0.8/CV > 10%)	Unreliable (ICC < 0.8/CV > 10%)
				RFD200ms	0.91 (95%CI: 0.80–0.96)	9.9% (95%CI: 7.7–14)
				RFD250ms	0.91 (95%CI: 0.91–0.80)	9.8% (95%CI: 7.5–15.4)
				PRFD2ms	Unreliable (ICC < 0.8/CV > 10%)	Unreliable (ICC < 0.8/CV > 10%)
				PRFD5ms	Unreliable (ICC < 0.8/CV > 10%)	Unreliable (ICC < 0.8/CV > 10%)
				PRFD10ms	Unreliable (ICC < 0.8/CV > 10%)	Unreliable (ICC < 0.8/CV > 10%)

				PRFD20ms	Unreliable (ICC < 0.8/CV > 10%)	Unreliable (ICC < 0.8/CV > 10%)
				PRFD30ms	Unreliable (ICC < 0.8/CV > 10%)	Unreliable (ICC < 0.8/CV > 10%)
				PRFD50ms	Unreliable (ICC < 0.8/CV > 10%)	Unreliable (ICC < 0.8/CV > 10%)
				AvgRFD	Unreliable (ICC < 0.8/CV > 10%)	Unreliable (ICC < 0.8/CV > 10%)
				IMP100ms	Unreliable (ICC < 0.8/CV > 10%)	Unreliable (ICC < 0.8/CV > 10%)
				IMP200ms	0.92 (95%CI: 0.84–0.97)	9.9% (95%CI: 7.9–14.3)
				IMP250ms	0.95 (95%CI: 0.88–0.98)	8.1% (95%CI: 6.3–11.4)
				IMP300ms	0.96 (95%CI: 0.91–0.98)	6.7% (95%CI: 5.2–9.4)
Brady <i>et al.</i> (2019)	Sprint athletes (male: 21.7 ± 3.6 years;	141 ± 4°	1	PF	0.99 (95%CI: 0.97–0.99)	4% (95%CI: 3.1–5.7)
				rPF	0.98 (95%CI: 0.97–0.99)	4% (95%CI: 3.1–5.7)

	female: 23.9 ± 2.3 years)				0.97–0.99)	
				PF100ms	0.97 (95%CI: 0.93–0.99)	9.6% (95%CI: 7.4–13.7)
				PF150ms	0.97 (95%CI: 0.93–0.99)	6.8% (95%CI: 5.3–9.6)
				PF200ms	0.96 (95%CI: 0.92–0.98)	6.5% (95%CI: 5.0–9.1)
				RFD100ms	Unreliable (ICC < 0.8/CV > 10%)	Unreliable (ICC < 0.8/CV > 10%)
				RFD150ms	0.94 (95%CI: 0.87–0.97)	9.3% (95%CI: 7.2–15.2)
				RFD200ms	0.94 (95%CI: 0.87–0.97)	8.3% (95%CI: 6.4–11.8)
				IMP100ms	Unreliable (ICC < 0.8/CV > 10%)	Unreliable (ICC < 0.8/CV > 10%)
				IMP200ms	0.97 (95%CI: 0.92–0.98)	7.8% (95%CI: 6.1–11.0)
Davies <i>et al.</i> (2018)	Resistance trained (23 ± 3 years)	110°	1	PF		4.4%
				RFD150ms		16.2%
Davies <i>et al.</i> (2020)	Recreationally trained (23.5 years)	110°		PF over 1s		7.6%
		90°	3			

Drake <i>et al.</i> (2018)	Strength trained (21.4 ± 4.5 years)			PF	0.89 (95%CI: 0.79–0.94)	3.9%	98.6 (95%CI: 71.1– 126.1)
				NetF	0.86 (95%CI: 0.74–0.92)	6.1%	97.5 (95%CI: 70.2– 124.9)
				rPF	0.91 (95%CI: 0.83–0.95)	3.8%	1.0 (95%CI: -1.8–3.9)
Drake <i>et al.</i> (2019b)	Resistance trained (26.8 ± 4.5 years)	100° & 125°	2	100°: PF	0.96 (90%CI: 0.89–0.99)	2.79% (90%CI: 2.0–4.6)	48.2 (90%CI: 28.9–67.4)
				TTPF	0.44 (90%CI: - 0.1–0.78)	22.2% (90%CI: 15.8–39.2)	0.32 (90%CI: - 1.25–1.89)
				RFD30ms	0.52 (90%CI: 0.00–0.82)	43.7% (90%CI: 30.2–81.6)	366.9 (90%CI: 313.8–420.0)
				RFD50ms	0.38 (90%CI: - 0.18–0.75)	67.34% (90%CI: 45.6–133.3)	739.7 (90%CI: 664.3–815.1)
				RFD90ms	0.20 (90%CI: - 0.36–0.65)	89.1% (90%CI: 59.18–185.3)	1479 (90%CI: 1372–1586)
				RFD100ms	0.18 (90%CI: - 0.37–0.64)	86.5% (90%CI: 57.6–178.8)	1545 (90%CI: 1436–1654)
				RFD150ms	0.25 (90%CI: - 0.31–0.68)	63.1% (90%CI: 42.9–123.6)	1482 (90%CI: 1375–1588)
				RFD200ms	0.39 (90%CI: - 0.16–0.76)	41.1% (90%CI: 28.6–76.2)	1174 (90%CI: 1079–1269)
				RFD250ms	0.63 (90%CI: 0.17–0.87)	25.2% (90%CI: 17.8–44.8)	747.4 (90%CI: 671.6–823.2)
				AvgRFD			

PRFD1ms	0.62 (90%CI: 0.15–0.86)	23.8% (90%CI: 16.9–42.1)	208.3 (90%CI: 168.3–248.4)
PRFD2ms	0.69 (90%CI: 0.26–0.89)	16.6% (90%CI: 11.8–28.7)	1019 (90%CI: 930.8–1108)
PRFD5ms	0.68 (90%CI: 0.24–0.89)	17.3% (90%CI: 12.34–30.0)	1025 (90%CI: 936.5–1114)
PRFD10ms	0.69 (90%CI: 0.26–0.89)	17.1% (90%CI: 12.3–29.8)	998.4 (90%CI: 910.8–1086)
PRFD20ms	0.68 (90%CI: 0.24–0.89)	17.6% (90%CI: 12.6–30.6)	1009 (90%CI: 921.0–1097)
PRFD30ms	0.68 (90%CI: 0.24–0.89)	17.8% (90%CI: 12.7–31.0)	994.0 (90%CI: 906.6–1081)
PRFD50ms	0.67 (90%CI: 0.24–0.88)	17.97 % (90%CI: 12.8–31.3)	978.3 (90%CI: 891.6–1065)
125°: PF	0.65 (90%CI: 0.20–0.88)	18.5% (90%CI: 13.1–32.1)	959.3 (90%CI: 873.4–1045)
TTPF	0.92 (90%CI: 0.78–0.98)	4.98% (90%CI: 3.6–8.3)	113.1 (90%CI: 83.6–142.6)
RFD30ms	0.07 (90%CI: - 0.47–0.57)	15.4% (90%CI: 11.0–26.6)	0.29 (90%CI: -1.2–1.8)
RFD50ms	0.22 (90%CI: - 0.34–0.66)	64.3% (90%CI: 43.6–126.3)	899.0 (90%CI: 815.9–982.1)
	0.34 (90%CI: -	58.4% (90%CI:	1451 (90%CI:

	0.22–0.73)	39.9–113.1)	1346–1557)
RFD90ms	0.55 (90%CI: 0.05–0.83)	38.5% (90%CI: 26.8–70.8)	1521 (90%CI: 1413–1630)
RFD100ms	0.58 (90%CI: 0.09–0.85)	35.4% (90%CI: 24.8–64.7)	1439 (90%CI: 1334–1544)
RFD150ms	0.61 (90%CI: 0.13–0.86)	29.7% (90%CI: 20.9–53.4)	1351 (90%CI: 1249–1453)
RFD200ms	0.68 (90%CI: 0.25–0.89)	25.0% (90%CI: 17.7–44.4)	1114 (90%CI: 1022–1207)
RFD250ms	0.77 (90%CI: 0.41–0.92)	19.9% (90%CI: 14.2–34.8)	805 (90%CI: 726–883)
AvgRFD	0.31 (90%CI: - 0.25–0.72)	16.3% (90%CI: 11.7–28.2)	184 (90%CI: 146–221)
PRFD1ms	0.62 (90%CI: 0.15–0.86)	23.3% (90%CI: 16.5–41.2)	1955 (90%CI: 1832–2077)
PRFD2ms	0.63 (90%CI: 0.16–0.87)	24.4% (90%CI: 17.3–43.2)	1961 (90%CI: 1838–2083)
PRFD5ms	0.64 (90%CI: 0.17–0.87)	24.7% (90%CI: 17.4–43.7)	1947 (90%CI: 1824–2069)
PRFD10ms	0.63 (90%CI: 0.16–0.87)	25.2% (90%CI: 17.8–44.8)	1969 (90%CI: 1846–2092)
PRFD20ms	0.63 (90%CI: 0.17–0.87)	25.0% (90%CI: 17.7–44.3)	1916 (90%CI: 1794–2037)
PRFD30ms	0.64 (90%CI:	24.5% (90%CI:	1837 (90%CI:

					0.18–0.87)	17.4–43.5)	1719–1956)
				PRFD50ms	0.65 (90%CI: 0.20–0.88)	23.6% (90%CI: 16.7–41.7)	1661 (90%CI: 1548–1774)
Gannon <i>et al.</i> (2016)	Professional rugby union players (21 ± 2.7 years)	137.6 ± 3.7°		aPF	0.95		2.40%
Hart <i>et al.</i> (2012)	Recreationally trained (24.2 ± 2.2 years)	140°	1	PF	0.97	3.6%	
				AvgF	0.91	8.4%	
				RFD	0.94	15.2%	
Ishida <i>et al.</i> (2023b)	Moderately resistance trained men (27.8 ± 3.9 years)	120°	1	PF	0.97 (95%CI: 0.92–0.99)	3.3% (95%CI: 2.3–4.4)	
				rPF	0.89 (95%CI: 0.75–0.95)	3.6% (95%CI: 2.5–4.8)	
				RFD90	0.81 (95%CI: 0.60–0.92)	23.8% (95%CI: 16.3–31.2)	
				RFD200	0.91 (95%CI: 0.80–0.96)	9.4% (95%CI: 6.4–12.3)	
				RFD250	0.96 (95%CI: 0.91–0.98)	5.0% (95%CI: 3.4–6.6)	
				IMP90	0.93 (95%CI: 0.83–0.97)	7.6% (95%CI: 5.2–10.0)	
				IMP200	0.93 (95%CI: 0.84–0.97)	6.9% (95%CI: 4.8–9.1)	

				IMP250	0.94 (95%CI: 0.86–0.97)	6.2% (95%CI: 4.3–8.2)
Kadlec <i>et al.</i> (2021)	Australian footballers (22.6 ± 4.5 years)	140°		PF	0.95 (95%CI: 0.88–0.98)	4.1% (95%CI: 3.2–4.8)
Lum <i>et al.</i> (2021)	Kayak athletes (21 ± 4 years)	90° & 120°	1	90°: PF	0.93 (95%CI: 0.88–0.95)	
				RFD90	0.84 (95%CI: 0.73–0.88)	
				120°: PF	0.95 (95%CI: 0.90–0.97)	
				RFD	0.87 (95%CI: 0.72–0.88)	
Lynch <i>et al.</i> (2021)	Recreationally active (23.5 ± 4.1 years)	65°, 90°, & 120°	1	PF: 65°	0.92 (95%CI: 0.77–0.97)	9.6 ± 9.3%
				90°	0.89 (95%CI: 0.70–0.96)	8.9 ± 6.7%
				120°	0.97 (95%CI: 0.91–0.99)	7.3 ± 4.3%

Marian <i>et al.</i> (2016)	Moderately trained athletes (21.9 ± 2.5 years)	~90°	1	rPF RFD100ms	0.94 0.90	
Markovic <i>et al.</i> (2007a)	Recreationally active, resistance trained (20.1 ± 1.1 years)	120°		PF	≥ 0.91	≤ 4.1%
Marshall <i>et al.</i> (2012)	Resistance trained (25.0 ± 1.7 years)	90°	1	PF RFD	0.87 0.80	
Marshall <i>et al.</i> (2019)	Elite academy rugby players (16 ± 0.4 years)	140°		PF aRFD300ms	0.88 (90% CI: 0.95–0.75) 0.81 (90% CI: 0.92–0.62)	7% 13%
Tillin <i>et al.</i> (2013)	Rugby union players (20 ± 1 years)	118 ± 5°		PF	0.96	4.0%
Tsoukos <i>et al.</i> (2016)	National level jumpers and decathletes (27.1 ± 7 years)	90° & 140°	2	90°: PF 140°: PF	0.97 0.93	
Wagner <i>et al.</i> (2022)	Youth soccer players (18.4 ± 1.5 years)	120°	1	PF (N)	0.97 (95%CI: 0.90–0.99)	

Wilson <i>et al.</i> (1995)	Athletes from multiple sports (22.6 ± 4.5years)	110° & 150°		110°:	
				PF	19.5%
				PRFD	56.0%
				f30ms	54.4%
				IMP100ms	5.0
				150°:	
				PF	18.2%
				PRFD	60.3%
Wilson <i>et al.</i>	Recreationally trained (26 ± 6 years)	90°	1	PF (N)	0.98
				RFD50–100	0.74
				RFD100–200	0.74

Key: ICC: intraclass correlation coefficient; CI: confidence interval; CV: coefficient of variation; TEM: technical error of measurement; SEM: standard error of the mean; SD: standard deviation; PF: peak force; PRFD: peak rate of force development; aPF: allometrically scaled PF; RFD: rate of force development; IMP: impulse; AvgRFD: average RFD; NetF: net force; rPF relative peak force; TTPF: time to peak force; aRFD: allometrically scaled RFD; AvgF: average force; f: force (at time epoch).

reliability (ICC > 0.9) for PF metrics (resulting in 9 instances of high reliability: Bazyler, Beckham and Sato, 2015; Brady *et al.*, 2018; Brady *et al.*, 2019; Gannon, Stokes and Trewartha, 2016; Hart *et al.*, 2012b; Marián *et al.*, 2016; Markovic *et al.*, 2007). Good reliability (ICC = 0.8–0.9) was reported in two studies (Marshall *et al.*, 2012; Marshall *et al.*, 2019); and moderate reliability (ICC = 0.73) only in one study (Bartolomei *et al.*, 2017) (Table 2.7). Acceptable CV values have been found for PF metrics on seven occasions for differing knee joint angles in six of the included studies, indicating good absolute reliability and low between trial variance of results (Brady *et al.*, 2018; Brady *et al.*, 2019; Davies *et al.*, 2018; Hart *et al.*, 2012b; Markovic *et al.*, 2007; Marshall *et al.*, 2019). One early study by Wilson *et al.* (1995) reported unacceptable CV's for two different knee joint angles (110° and 150°; Table 2.7). However, an internal focus strategy was adopted during the test execution which has previously been shown as unfavourable for maximal physical performance testing procedures, especially decreasing PF outputs during isometric testing when compared to external attentional focus cues (Halperin *et al.*, 2016). Nevertheless, the current literature collectively indicates high intra-day reliability for PF related values across a range of knee joint angles.

Researcher reliability (e.g., intra-rater reliability or inter-rater reliability), measurement tool reliability, intra-day, and inter-day reliability are other important measures of reliability to consider when determining the appropriateness of a performance test. Intra- and inter-rater reliability explains the variation observed in repeated trials measured by the same tester or between testers, respectively. The intra-day reliability of time-dependent variables such as rate of force development (RFD) and impulse (IMP) in current research is equivocal. RFD is calculated from the slope of the force time curve (dividing the change in force of the chosen time period by the duration of the time period, usually measured in milliseconds), whereas IMP is determined from the force-time curve as an integral of the force output over a specific time period (i.e., sum of the force applied in a given time period, usually in milliseconds) (Brady, Harrison and Comyns, 2020). While RFD and IMP results are widely reported as reliable for time epochs greater than 200 ms in the literature, reliability is affected for time epochs smaller than this. Recently, Brady *et al.* (2018) have demonstrated unreliable (ICC < 0.7, and/or CV > 10.0%) reliability for RFD and IMP for time epochs up to and including 150 ms, but not 200 ms, 250ms or 300 ms (Table 2.7). This is partially in agreement with the results displayed by Brady *et al.* (2019), apart from the RFD in 0–150 ms timeframe which was also deemed to be reliable (ICC = 0.94, CV = 9.3%). These discrepancies across the reliability of RFD metrics are likely due to the high CV associated with these metrics as shown in Table 2.7 (Bazyler *et*

al., 2014b; Davies *et al.*, 2018; Drake, Kennedy and Wallace, 2019b; Hart *et al.*, 2012b). Therefore, it may be that the reliability of time-dependent metrics such as IMP and RFD improves as the time frame these metrics are calculated from increases (Brady *et al.*, 2018; Brady *et al.*, 2019).

Previously published research suggests intervals greater than one day between assessments to be of improved benefit in order to more accurately determine the inter-day variability in measurements (Atkinson and Nevill, 1998). On the contrary, inter-day reliability studies reported both random error and systematic bias summing up to the total absolute error, demonstrated across a more practically appropriate time period to sport testing periods (e.g., ~40 weeks) (Hopkins, 2000; Taylor *et al.*, 2010). In the current review, only five of the included studies have assessed the inter-day reliability of the ISqT, with two evaluating the inter-day reliability of two different knee joint angles (Blazevich, Gill and Newton, 2002; Drake, Kennedy and Wallace, 2018; Drake, Kennedy and Wallace, 2019b; Tsoukos *et al.*, 2016; Tillin, Pain and Folland, 2013).

Force production expressed as PF, net PF, or rPF have consistently displayed good-to-high inter-day reliability statistics (ICC = 0.86–0.97; CV = 2.8–6.1%) irrespective of the knee joint angle (90°–140°) when examined among recreationally trained and athletic populations, with no clear difference between these groups (Table 2.7) (Blazevich, Gill and Newton, 2002; Drake, Kennedy and Wallace, 2018; Drake, Kennedy and Wallace, 2019b; Tsoukos *et al.*, 2016; Tillin, Pain and Folland, 2013). However, the inter-day reliability of time-dependent measures, such as RFD, has only been assessed in one of the included studies within this review. In this study, Drake, Kennedy and Wallace (2019b) reported unreliable statistics (ICC < 0.7 and/or CV > 10%) for time to peak force, average RFD, RFD, and peak RFD (PRFD) at all sampling windows examined in trained adults (Table 2.7). This lack of consistency may have been due to how the onset of contraction was determined. In order to eliminate the potential for inaccurate determination of contraction onset influenced by measurement noise, recent research advocates the use of a threshold of the pre-contraction at a value exceeding 5 standard deviations of the mean GRF measured in the starting position (Dos'Santos *et al.*, 2017; West *et al.*, 2011). Alternatively, and perhaps more appropriate for the applied practitioner working with large groups of athletes, previous research has determined the onset of contraction by examining the force-time trace of each individual trial and determining the contraction onset as the first instantaneous point where the RFD crosses zero following the weighing period

(Drake, Kennedy and Wallace, 2019a; Drake, Kennedy and Wallace, 2019b; Tillin, Pain and Folland, 2013). This is of particular importance for the calculation of time-dependent methods, as an inaccurate contraction onset value would confound the calculation of these metrics leaving results unreliable, and interpretation difficult for the practitioner. Similarly, it is necessary to ensure a stable baseline force trace is achieved prior to the commencement of contraction in order to attain more reliable subsequent force measurements, as a more stable baseline results in an improved ability to identify contraction onset (Brady, Harrison and Comyns, 2020). Therefore, future research should address this potential reliability issue with time-dependent metrics further, particularly within youth cohorts. However, previous research evaluating the CMJ has indicated reliability not to be affected by confounding factors specific to youth populations such as maturation status (Meylan *et al.*, 2012), therefore it is unlikely this would exert a negative influence upon performance of the ISqT.

While the reliability of PF values obtained during the ISqT has been discussed within the current section, only a small number of studies have reported reliability statistics of different knee joint angles of the ISqT on resulting force-time metrics (Bazyler *et al.*, 2014b; Bazyler, Beckham and Sato, 2015; Drake, Kennedy and Wallace, 2019b; Tsoukos *et al.*, 2016; Wilson *et al.*, 1995). Within the current review, reliability statistics (ICC and/or CV/technical error of measurement) have been reported for knee joint angles from 90° to 150° (Table 2.7). Reliability data for maximum output related metrics, such as PF, net PF, or rPF has mostly been reported for knee joint angles of 90°, 120°, or 140°, with eight studies concerning a 90° knee joint angle (Bartolomei *et al.*, 2017; Bazyler *et al.*, 2014b; Bazyler, Beckham and Sato, 2015; Blazevich, Gill and Newton, 2002; Drake, Kennedy and Wallace, 2018; Marián *et al.*, 2016; Marshall *et al.*, 2012; Tsoukos *et al.*, 2016); four studies a ~120° knee angle (Bazyler *et al.*, 2014b; Bazyler, Beckham and Sato, 2015; Markovic *et al.*, 2007; Tillin, Pain and Folland, 2013); and four studies a knee angle of ~140° (Brady *et al.*, 2019; Hart *et al.*, 2012b; Marshall *et al.*, 2019; Tsoukos *et al.*, 2016). Reliability data for a 90° knee angle was found to display high reliability in five studies, good reliability in two studies, and questionable reliability within one study. Reliability for a 140° knee joint angle displays similar data, with three studies observing high reliability and one displaying good reliability. However, maximum force output-related reliability for the ISqT performed at a 120° knee angle has shown high reliability across all studies included within the current review (Table 2.7).

While previous research alludes to a more reliable RFD or IMP measure with increased time epochs, only a small number of studies have directly compared the reliability of these with varying knee joint angles (Bazyler *et al.*, 2014b; Bazyler, Beckham and Sato, 2015; Drake, Kennedy and Wallace, 2019b; Wilson *et al.*, 1995). While the majority of research evaluating time-dependent measures has used early-stage force development epochs of up to 300 ms, this can generally be further divided into 0–100 ms, 0–200 ms and 0–300 ms groupings (Table 2.7), given the relative large differences in values observed at each epoch (Table 2.6) (Drake, Kennedy and Wallace, 2019b). Research conducted evaluating RFD and IMP has been conducted on knee joint angles from 90°–150°, with the majority of studies utilising a 90° (Bazyler *et al.*, 2014b; Bazyler, Beckham and Sato, 2015; Marián *et al.*, 2016; Marshall *et al.*, 2012), 120° (Bazyler *et al.*, 2014b; Bazyler, Beckham and Sato, 2015), or a 135–140° (Brady *et al.*, 2018; 2019; Hart *et al.*, 2012b; Marshall *et al.*, 2019) knee angle. Of the limited research to date, the available literature consistently demonstrates unreliable statistics for knee angles of 100°, 110°, and 125° on RFD and IMP metrics (Davies *et al.*, 2018; Drake, Kennedy and Wallace, 2019b). However, within research utilising a knee angle of 90° or 120°, RFD and IMP has consistently shown acceptable reliability in the majority of the included studies, particularly for IMP which has displayed reliable statistics in all included studies (Table 2.7). For research conducted at the larger knee angles of 135°–140°, reliability statistics are more varied (Table 2.7). RFD and IMP from 0–100ms typically displays unacceptable reliability, whereas longer duration timeframes have shown to be more reliable (Brady *et al.*, 2018; 2019).

In summary, it has been shown that the ISqT holds reasonable levels of measurement sensitivity, discriminant validity, and criterion validity particularly at knee joint angles at or above 120°. In addition, it appears an ISqT protocol can vary broadly, and this may have a further impact on the reliability of the performance test. The ISqT performed at a knee joint angle of 120° has been shown to be reliable for the measurement of both PF and time-sensitive metrics (e.g., RFD and IMP; Table 2.7) (Brady, Harrison and Comyns, 2020). In future research, reliability should be evaluated using both the ICC and CV with CI reported for each reliability measure. Similarly, future research should address reliability issues with time-dependent metrics further, particularly among youth cohorts by implementing best cueing and instructional strategies aiming at optimising testing and procedural outputs. It is also noteworthy that no research included in this review has assessed the inter-day reliability of IMP for the ISqT, a metric that was found to have acceptable intra-day reliability in previous investigations (Brady *et al.*, 2018; Brady *et al.*, 2019). Therefore, future research should

attempt to address this, given the ability of this metric to explain an individual's ability to change momentum and therefore quantify underpinning accelerative ability. Inter-day reliability studies in youth cohorts are also non-existent within the current review, given the relative safety of isometric testing, future research should aim to address this in order to determine whether the quantification of the training related changes attained due to programming across different testing periods are reliable.

2.6.1.2 Methodological considerations for isometric squat testing

Multi-joint tests of force production capabilities possess greater transference to high-intensity dynamic movements when compared to single-joint tests (Drake, Kennedy and Wallace, 2017; Wilhelm *et al.*, 2013). Given the usefulness of a performance test is determined by its reliability, research has aimed to determine the most reliable configuration of the ISqT by varying the knee joint angle adopted during the examination (Table 2.7) (Bazyler *et al.*, 2014b; Bazyler, Beckham and Sato, 2015; Drake, Kennedy and Wallace, 2019b; Wilson *et al.*, 1995). Knee extensor peak isometric force output is produced at or above a knee joint angle of 120° (Table 2.6) (Bazyler, Beckham and Sato, 2015; Blazevich, Gill and Newton, 2002; Smidt, 1973) with PF values obtained during the ISqT being shown to increase as knee joint angle increases (150° vs 120° vs 90°) (Palmer, Pineda and Durham, 2018). Indeed, a recent review found increased isometric force output during the ISqT with knee angles above 110° (McMaster *et al.*, 2014). Of additional practical relevance, greater knee angles (i.e. > 120°) induce performance variations during maximal isometric fatigue tests to a lesser extent compared to a 90° knee joint angle (Tsoukos *et al.*, 2016) likely due to lower perceived pain and discomfort being found to occur at smaller knee joint angles (Marcora and Miller, 2000). These perceptual responses would confound the ability of an individual to develop force maximally (Wilson and Murphy, 1996), thus potentially explaining in part the inconsistencies within the research surrounding the reliability of RFD and IMP metrics of the ISqT (Bazyler *et al.*, 2014b; Brady *et al.*, 2018; Drake, Kennedy and Wallace, 2019b).

While the ISqT is becoming more utilised in applied settings, methodological considerations may hinder its usefulness within a team sport setting. Despite the reliability of the ISqT (Brady, Harrison and Comyns, 2020), ensuring subjects perform the ISqT at the selected knee angle can be time consuming, therefore alternative methods have been devised within previous research. Tillin, Pain and Folland (2013) evaluated the ISqT performed by adult male team

sport athletes at 75% of the participants stature, equating to a $118 \pm 5^\circ$ knee angle. However, although this may be more time efficient when compared to procedures based on precise knee angle configurations, it would be inappropriate to assume that this methodology ensures similar and consistent knee joint angles across youth athletes due to the non-linear growth of the lower limbs relative to the upper body throughout maturation (Mirwald *et al.*, 2002). Conversely, previous research across academy team sport athletes investigating multi-joint isometric performance tests have utilised a knee angle range (e.g. 120° – 130°), as opposed to a singular joint configuration, thereby slightly reducing the time needed to setup the performance test (Darrall-Jones, Jones and Till, 2015). Alternatively, a potential option for the applied practitioner is to allow the participant to self-select the body configuration during the ISqT. Such an approach was firstly utilised by Comfort *et al.* (2015) with participants performing an IMTP with self-selected ankle, knee, and hip angles at a mid-thigh bar height. PF, maximum RFD, and IMP at multiple timeframes were not different compared to a protocol performed at controlled knee (120° , 130° , 140° , or 150°) and hip (125° or 145°) angles (Comfort *et al.*, 2015). Despite the applied implications of this method, this has yet to be evaluated for the ISqT within athletic populations. Future research should aim to determine if a self-determined body position during the ISqT yields similar reliability and normative data to that of controlled body configurations at pre-determined knee joint angles.

Sampling frequency (McGinnis, 2013) may have a direct effect on the reliability of the collected data (Hori *et al.*, 2009; McMaster *et al.*, 2014; Street *et al.*, 2001). It is thought that higher sampling frequencies ($> 500\text{Hz}$) produce more reliable measurement outputs, particularly for time-dependent metrics such as RFD or IMP (McMaster *et al.*, 2014; Street *et al.*, 2001), given the lower CV these metric types display compared to lower sampling frequency procedures (Hori *et al.*, 2009). This is due to the assumption that the change between two consecutive GRF data points over time occurs in a linear fashion, resulting in missed changes in GRF between these consecutive points increasing as the sample frequency decreases (Street *et al.*, 2001).

The Nyquist sampling theorem dictates the required sampling frequency to be at least twice the highest frequency of the measured signal to confidently collect data reflecting the original signal (Robertson *et al.*, 2013). However, as velocity of movement increases, the required sampling frequency does so as well, resulting in the recommended sampling frequency to be 5–10 times the signal of interest for non-time-dependent metrics (Hori *et al.*, 2009; Robertson

et al., 2013). Concerning time dependent metrics, such as RFD and IMP, it is recommended the sampling frequency be significantly larger than previously stated (McMaster *et al.*, 2014). Therefore, in order to accurately evaluate both peak and time-dependent variables of interest, it is recommended a force plate sampling at 500 Hz for static performance tests such as the ISqT to mitigate the measurement error as much as possible, and as such so to allow for repeatable measurements (McMaster *et al.*, 2014).

The typical duration of the ISqT within the literature ranges from 3–5 seconds (Table 2.6; 2.7) (Brady, Harrison and Comyns, 2020; Drake, Kennedy and Wallace, 2017; McMaster *et al.*, 2014), although there are inconsistencies within the literature with regards to the ideal contraction duration yielding reliable time-dependent metrics. Some recent research advocates the use of 1 second duration protocols to assess RFD more accurately, due to the increased reliability observed with these protocols when compared to longer ‘PF protocols’ similar to those mentioned previously (Drake, Kennedy and Wallace, 2019b; Tillin, Pain and Folland, 2013). However, this research is only very recent and requires further examination. Conversely, to measure PF outputs during ISqT, evidence suggests the use of contraction durations greater than 2 second (McMaster *et al.*, 2014) while utilising external cues of attention (Halperin *et al.*, 2016), as PF values consistently display high intra- and inter-day reliability in these conditions (Table 2.7 summarises reliability data for contractions of 3 seconds or more) (Brady *et al.*, 2018; Drake, Kennedy and Wallace, 2019a).

The applied practitioner should also be aware of the learning effects of a performance test and the effect of familiarisation on physical outputs prior to its implementation (Dos’Santos *et al.*, 2018; Drake, Kennedy and Wallace, 2018). The learning effect refers to the improvement in performance of a test due to factors outside of true changes in strength which are primarily neural in nature, such as increases in motor unit recruitment and discharge rate (Maffiuletti *et al.*, 2016), improvements in movement skill and proficiency (Amarante do Nascimento *et al.*, 2013; Maffiuletti *et al.*, 2016), improved ability of both intra- and inter-muscular coordination, and decreased agonist-antagonist co-contraction (Calder and Gabriel, 2007). Therefore, controlling for learning effects will allow the practitioner to make confident decisions regarding whether the results of a test are due to improvements in physical capabilities, or due to the learning effect.

Limited research exists evaluating the effect of familiarisation on physical outputs obtained during the ISqT. In a recent investigation, Drake and colleagues (2018) reported stable effects

following three familiarisation sessions consisting of three trials among strength trained males (age: 21.4 ± 4.5 years; 4.1 years resistance training experience). In this study, the third familiarisation session displayed significantly larger average values when compared to both the first and second familiarisation sessions. However, in a study conducted in male youth soccer players (age: 16.7 ± 0.5 years; 6–12 months resistance training experience) there was no significant between-session variability in PF measured isometrically (Dos'Santos *et al.*, 2018). However, in this latter study (Dos'Santos *et al.*, 2018), PF was measured using the IMTP and there were only two sessions evaluated as opposed to three in the formerly mentioned research (Drake, Kennedy and Wallace, 2018). Therefore, although familiarisation session number may be exercise specific, it is likely that a minimum of three trials is needed to stabilise learning effects. Despite this, in the current review, eleven studies provided information regarding the familiarisations conducted by the participants (Table 2.7), with the majority of these indicating only one familiarisation session was conducted for a maximum of three trials each (Brady *et al.*, 2018; 2019; Davies *et al.*, 2018; Hart *et al.*, 2012b; Marián *et al.*, 2016; Marshall *et al.*, 2012; Tsoukos *et al.*, 2016). This methodology is in contrast to the results of both the aforementioned studies (Dos'Santos *et al.*, 2018; Drake, Kennedy and Wallace, 2018) and also that of Pekünlü and Özsü (2014), who evaluated the influence of systematic error on intra-day ISqT measurements. Indeed, it was shown here a minimum of 7–8 trials to be necessary in order to eliminate the influence of the learning effect within resistance trained males (age: 22.6 ± 3.0 years; 5.5 resistance training experience) (Pekünlü and Ozsu, 2014).

Therefore, future research should further evaluate the effect of the number of familiarisations on ISqT outputs among different populations than reported above, such as female or youth athletes. Indeed, there is a need to specifically research the optimisation of familiarisations in youth populations due to observed differences in motor control and learning with this group compared to adult athletes. Research should also aim to provide better recommendations regarding the familiarisations procedures adopted (e.g., number of familiarisation sessions, and trials per session) to allow for better interpretation of results. Regarding the effect of familiarisation on ISqT outputs, research evidence recommends the use of three familiarisation sessions consisting of a minimum of three trials as sufficient to reduce bias due to learning effects. In summary, a potential limitation of conducting isometric testing is the time constraints associated with the test setup, therefore future research should aim to validate more time-efficient methods for performing the ISqT. Lastly, data collection during the ISqT should be obtained through the use of a force plate sampling at a frequency of 500 Hz for 3–5 seconds in

order to accurately quantify both maximal force related and time-dependent metrics (McMaster *et al.*, 2014).

2.7.1 Isometric squat associations with dynamic performance

Whilst establishing the criterion validity of a performance test compared to the gold standard assessment is important to determine the tests' ability to measure a specific construct, it is also important for the applied practitioner to establish relationships between measurement tests and measures of performance. Previous investigations examining the relationship between performance of the ISqT and sprint performance often display equivocal findings (Brady *et al.*, 2019; Marián *et al.*, 2016; Tillin, Pain and Folland, 2013; Wilson *et al.*, 1995; Young, McLean and Ardagna, 1995). Typically, studies display significant relationships between ISqT PF outputs and sprint times over shorter (e.g., 0–20 meters) distances, when expressed absolutely and relative to body mass (Brady *et al.*, 2019; Tillin, Pain and Folland, 2013; Young, McLean and Ardagna, 1995). Recently, Brady *et al.* (2019) reported significant relationships between ISqT variables such as measures of PF (e.g., PF, rPF), RFD and IMP and 0–5 meter sprint times ($r = -0.52$ to -0.71) in trained male athletes. This is partially in agreement with the results of Tillin, Pain and Folland (2013) who found significant relationships between force produced at 100 ms during the ISqT and 0–5 m sprint times (absolute force $r = -0.5$; force relative to body mass $r = -0.62$). In addition, it was found that when the male athletes were stratified into fast and slow groups based on their 0–5 m sprint times, the faster group achieved greater force outputs in the first 50 ms, 100 ms and 150 ms when normalised to bodyweight, and also greater absolute force at 50 ms and 100 ms (Tillin, Pain and Folland, 2013). In addition, significant relationships were observed between force produced at 100 ms and 0–20 m sprint times (absolute $r = -0.5$; relative to bodyweight $r = -0.54$) (Tillin, Pain and Folland, 2013).

Similarly, significant associations have been observed between metrics produced during the ISqT and sprint times, such as 0–10 m and ISqT PF (Young, McLean and Ardagna, 1995), 0–30 m and ISqT force at 30 ms (Wilson *et al.*, 1995), and 0–50m and ISqT PF (Marián *et al.*, 2016) in male athletes. It is likely that measures obtained during certain timeframes during the ISqT are more specific to sprint distances which elicit similar ground contact times. Despite ground contact times during the acceleration phase (~300 ms) of sprinting typically lasting longer than those observed during the maximal speed phase (~100 ms), individuals could apply ground reaction forces of over 2.5 times their body mass during maximal speed running

(Weyand *et al.*, 2000). Given the direction of force is predominantly vertical during maximal speed running, this may explain the aforementioned relationships between ISqT PF and sprint times over longer acceleration distances (e.g., > 20 m) (Marián *et al.*, 2016). In addition, the GRF's during sprint running are also substantial despite the fast GCT's (Brady *et al.*, 2019), therefore time dependent variables may better relate to sprint times, particularly over 20 m (Kawamori, Nosaka and Newton, 2013; Weyand *et al.*, 2000), however this has not been examined extensively within the literature. To this end, Brady *et al.* (2019) found no relationship between ISqT IMP (from 0–200 ms), or RFD (from 0–150 ms or 0–200 ms) and sprint times for distances of 10–30 m. However, the participants within this study were adult male sprint athletes, which limits the transference of results to other populations such as youth or female.

Similarly, given the knee joint angles observed within the aforementioned research have tended to be 120° or greater (see section 2.6.1.2) (Brady *et al.*, 2019; Tillin, Pain and Folland, 2013; Wilson *et al.*, 1995; Young, McLean and Ardagna, 1995), specific reasons for the conflicting results are unclear at the current time. Future research should aim to provide information clarifying the associations between sprint times over distances greater than 5 m and ISqT performance. In particular, given the underpinning mechanisms that determine ISqT performance are similar to those that underpin sprint performance, the association between sprint times and time-dependent measures should be assessed, especially in youth athletes.

When the performance of the ISqT has been related to the performance of powerful lower body movements predominantly vertical in nature such as jumps height and underpinning outputs (e.g., flight time, eccentric impulse etc.), research has shown clear associations (Kennedy and Drake, 2018; Marián *et al.*, 2016; Nuzzo *et al.*, 2008; Tillin, Pain and Folland, 2013; Young, McLean and Ardagna, 1995). In a recent study, Kennedy and Drake (2018) found significant positive correlations ($p < 0.05$; $r = 0.53$ – 0.71) between ISqT rPF, and jump peak and average concentric power, peak and average concentric force, peak velocity, and jump height in elite male team sport athletes. This is in contrast to the results reported by Nuzzo *et al.* (2008), who found no significant associations between ISqT rPF and measures obtained during a CMJ. The discrepancies between these studies may be due to the differences in knee joint angle examined (90° vs 140° in Kennedy and Drake, 2018; & Nuzzo *et al.*, 2008, respectively), or due to the methodological differences of reporting rPF between these two studies. In the study of Kennedy and Drake (2018) net PF scaled relative to body mass was used, whereas Nuzzo *et al.* (2008)

utilised absolute PF measurements which would confound the comparison as rPF values were noticeably dissimilar between the two studies (17.0 N/kg vs 39.6 N/kg respectively).

In the study of Nuzzo *et al.* (2008) the same significant associations found between ISqT PF and the CMJ were also evident between the back squat 1RM and the CMJ. Nuzzo *et al.* (2008) also found significant associations between RFD and the same absolute CMJ variables (PF, peak power). This trend of results displayed by Nuzzo *et al.* (2008) is in agreement with previous research evaluating the agreement between metrics obtained during the ISqT and the CMJ (Tillin, Pain and Folland, 2013). Indeed, Tillin, Pain and Folland (2013) showed significant correlations between CMJ height and ISqT absolute PF, and absolute PF at 100 ms, 150 ms, 200 ms and 250 ms. However, no research included in the current review has evaluated the association of vertical jumping ability and ISqT performance among youth populations. This information would have important practical implications in the evaluation of the appropriateness of the ISqT as a tool for monitoring the efficacy of youth athletic development programmes. Similarly, no additional evidence evaluating the relationship of RFD or IMP metrics between the ISqT and vertical jumps apart from that reported above is available.

2.7.0 Assessment of proxy measures of soccer performance

2.7.2 Muscular power assessments

Despite the reliability and usefulness of isometric assessments (Brady, Harrison and Comyns, 2020; Drake, Kennedy and Wallace, 2017), a more accurate assessment of overall athletic performance should include power production assessments through powerful dynamic actions including the stretch shortening cycle as well (Dobbs *et al.*, 2020). To this end, the CMJ is commonly utilised to assess stretch shortening cycle function (Kennedy and Drake, 2021; McMahon *et al.*, 2018; Meylan *et al.*, 2012).

In addition, when assessing ballistic dynamic movements research advocates the use of measuring systems with 1000–2500Hz sampling frequencies in order to accurately evaluate the resulting time-dependent force-time metrics (McMaster *et al.*, 2014). However, CMJ assessments are typically carried out using jump mat technology (Kobal *et al.*, 2017; Comfort *et al.*, 2014). Therefore, contrary to research in youth populations which have utilised jump mats (Dobbs *et al.*, 2020; Dugdale *et al.*, 2019; Lloyd *et al.*, 2009), it appears that measurement via force plate would be necessary in order to attain a high level of accuracy.

The direct measurement and assessment of jump kinetics is therefore important to attain actual values of power output, however the reliability of these kinetics within youth athletes has not been studied in great detail. Generally, research has found the reliability of vertical jumps such as the CMJ to improve with age and increasing maturity (Gerodimos *et al.*, 2008). However, reliable jump testing measurements has been observed also in pre-PHV cohorts consistently involved in organised sports training (Meylan *et al.*, 2012). In their study, Meylan *et al.* (2012) showed jump protocols can be reliably used as a performance assessment irrespective of age or maturity status.

Evaluations of vertical jump testing within youth populations display numerous significant associations justifying its inclusion within youth testing batteries (Dugdale *et al.*, 2019; Gillen *et al.*, 2018). Indeed, recent research has displayed the ability of vertical jump testing in discriminating between youth soccer players who are signed to a professional academy, and those who compete at the amateur level (Dugdale *et al.*, 2019). Similarly, Dugdale *et al.* (2019) found significantly higher CMJ values in youth soccer players competing within higher ranked academies compared to lower ranked academies, and significantly higher CMJ heights for individuals competing within lower ranked academies compared to recreational individuals. In addition, vertical jumps have been shown to be significantly associated with horizontal jumps ($r = 0.66-0.89$), change of direction performance ($r = -0.61--0.81$), and sprint ($r = -0.39--0.94$) performance (Gillen *et al.*, 2018).

While vertical jumps typically display strongest associations with jumps of a horizontal nature due to the similarities in mechanical components between these tests (Gillen *et al.*, 2018; Robbins, 2012), the correlations with sprint times illustrate a less consistent pattern. While significant associations have been displayed in youth cohorts between sprint times over shorter distances and vertical jumps, the magnitude of relationships are typically stronger when vertical jumps are compared to sprint distances over longer distances (Gillen *et al.*, 2018; Robbins, 2012). Despite this, similar independent relationships have been observed between vertical jumps and horizontal jumps and 20-yard sprint, 40-yard sprint and agility performance (Gillen *et al.*, 2018). Therefore, it has been shown here that vertical jump testing holds high levels of construct and discriminant validity and appears to be related to various actions typically performed during youth soccer match play such as horizontally propulsive, sprint, and change of direction actions.

In summary, the CMJ is a reliable performance test to assess stretch shortening cycle function in youth cohorts. Furthermore, previous research displays strong relationships between vertical jumps and powerful actions typically performed during soccer match play.

2.7.3 Speed assessments

Velocity capabilities of youth athletes are typically assessed via sprint tests over distances ranging from 5–40 m, and measured through the use of timing gates for reliable measures (Rumpf *et al.*, 2011). Longer sprint distances performances, typically those above 20 m, are elected as an indication of an individual's maximum sprint speed, and offer marginally higher levels of reliability compared to shorter sprint distances (Paul and Nassis, 2015). Recent reviews indicate that sprint testing in youth cohorts over distances up to 40 m typically display ICCs of 0.84–0.99, and CVs of 0.83–2.07%, indicating high levels of reliability for these test modalities (Paul and Nassis, 2015; Rumpf *et al.*, 2011). Interestingly, recent studies display similar reliability statistics (i.e., ICC's and CV's) in youth soccer players for sprint time over 10 and 20 m regardless of the respective age group (e.g., U11–U17) analysed (Dugdale *et al.*, 2019; Krolo *et al.*, 2020). In addition, acceptable intra- and inter-day reliability statistics (ICC = 0.88–0.98; CV = 0.83–2.07%) have been reported for youth cohorts allowing practitioners to utilise sprint measurements multiple times within a testing session and also throughout the training year (Rumpf *et al.*, 2011).

Youth players have been observed to attain high percentages (84.4–90.5%) of their maximal sprinting speeds within competitive match play, which are unlikely to be attained during sprints over distances less than 20 m; thereby confirming the necessity of longer distance sprint tests within performance monitoring batteries (Mendez-Villanueva *et al.*, 2011b). Similarly, older youth soccer players have been observed to obtain significantly faster sprint times when compared to those within younger and less mature age groups, thereby confirming maximal sprint speed can discriminate between players of varying age, maturity and experience levels (Mendez-Villanueva *et al.*, 2011a; Mendez-Villanueva *et al.*, 2013; Meyers *et al.*, 2015). Recently, 20 m sprint performance was shown to discriminate between academy and recreational youth soccer players, whereas 10 m sprint performance did not (Dugdale *et al.*, 2019). Therefore, the importance of acceleration (i.e., running speed from 5 – 20 m) within youth soccer match play is unequivocal (see section 2.3.0), highlighting the importance of continually assessing this ability in youth soccer players.

It has therefore been shown here that maximal sprint tests from 5 – 40 m hold acceptable reliability for both inter- and intra-day measurements. Measurements of sprint running speeds should however, be carried out through the use of timing gate technology to ensure reproducible results. Similarly, it has been shown that sprint tests between 5 and 30 m are valid, can discriminate between individuals of differing playing standard and are therefore important qualities to monitor within an academy setting.

2.8.0 Autonomy

It is well documented that the perception of control over one's own environment is of fundamental importance to satisfy inherent biological requirements (Leotti and Delgado, 2011), or, at least, basic psychological needs (Deci and Ryan, 2000). Therefore, it is reasonable to assume that individuals' motivation is largely impacted by their perceived control over the current task and/or the surrounding environment (Eitam, Kennedy and Tory, 2013). Indeed, providing choice, as a means to increase perceived feelings of autonomy, has been observed to result in greater levels of enjoyment following training, leading to an increased potential of subsequent training adherence (Silva *et al.*, 2011). This ability to exert control over ones environment is a main factor of well renowned theories such as the self-determination theory (Deci and Ryan, 2000), and, more recently, the optimising performance through intrinsic motivation and attention for learning theory (OPTIMAL) (Wulf and Lewthwaite, 2016). The OPTIMAL theory details how an individual's perception of autonomy enhances expectancies of performance and, when both of these motivational components are coupled with an external focus of attention, positively impacts motor skill acquisition and development through augmenting goal-action coupling (Wulf and Lewthwaite, 2016). Therefore, the OPTIMAL theory of motor learning accounts for the social-cognitive-affective-motor nature of motor behaviours (Lewthwaite and Wulf, 2010).

Given that motor skill learning is defined as the permanent change in one's ability to perform a skill (Schmidt *et al.*, 2018), it is clear why enhancing this aspect of development would be of particular interest to the applied practitioner working with youth athletes. Autonomy supportive conditions while performing physical exercise, tasks or movements has consistently been shown to improve motor learning and performance (Wulf and Lewthwaite, 2016). The positive effects of providing an autonomy supportive environment have been shown within literature

which detail motor learning and performance benefits as a result of choice provision (Colquhoun *et al.*, 2017; Grand *et al.*, 2015; Iwatsuki *et al.*, 2017; Lewthwaite *et al.*, 2015; Rauch *et al.*, 2020; Halperin *et al.*, 2017). This has been found even if the choice itself is seemingly unrelated to the task being performed (Lewthwaite *et al.*, 2015). Indeed, improvements in accuracy have been observed within athletes from a team-sport who were provided autonomy over the number of shots performed, compared to those that were not (Post *et al.*, 2014). Similarly, balance, an important attribute for development within junior athletes, has been shown to benefit through providing learners autonomy over when to utilise assistance within practice (Chiviacowsky *et al.*, 2012) and what order to carry out the selected exercises within the set (Wulf and Adams, 2014).

Although motor learning benefits have also been observed as a result of autonomous feedback (Patterson and Carter, 2010), autonomy-supportive strategies (Hooyman, Wulf and Lewthwaite, 2014), or self-determined practice order (Halperin *et al.*, 2017), less research is available on the effects of autonomy supportive strategies on performance (Halperin *et al.*, 2018). While maximising motor learning is undoubtedly important within the context of a long term athletic development programme (Wulf and Lewthwaite, 2016), it is also important for the applied practitioner to be aware of the methods which maximise performance related attributes such as movement velocity or force output. Within the limited research available, positive effects of choice provision have been observed on upper limb movement velocity and force output (Halperin *et al.*, 2017), jumping performance (Dello Iacono, Beato and Halperin, 2020), resistance training exercise power outputs (Watson *et al.*, 2020), grip strength (Iwatsuki *et al.*, 2017), lower limb leg press strength (McNamara and Stearne, 2010), and volume of work undertaken within a resistance training programme (Wulf, Freitas and Tandy, 2014; Rauch *et al.*, 2020). In addition, recent research (Emanuel *et al.*, 2020) evaluated the difference between self-selected and pre-determined resistance exercise repetition ranges on performance and psychological measures within trained individuals. In their study, Emanuel and colleagues (2020) demonstrate non-significantly different movement velocities, and absolute isometric multi-joint force production values between conditions (i.e., fixed/ controlled vs self-selected).

In agreement with the former, Comfort *et al.* (2015) displayed no differences in maximal force output, IMP or RFD during a maximal effort isometric test between a self-selected body configuration, or controlled joint trials. In addition, it was shown that the self-selected trial displayed high intra- and inter-session reliability for all kinetic variables measured, comparable

to that of the controlled trials (Comfort *et al.*, 2015). Similarly, extensive research has found reliable measures describing jump performance in both adults (Kennedy and Drake, 2021) and youth individuals (Dugdale *et al.*, 2019; Meylan *et al.*, 2012) following the execution of jumps which were entirely self-determined i.e., self-determined concentric velocity, descent depth and velocity etc.

This is of particular relevance to applied practitioners working within team sport, as allowing players to self-select their body configuration during testing protocols would considerably reduce testing times. However, the main limitation of the study of Comfort *et al.* (2015), was the bar height was standardised to the mid-point of the thigh, and as such not completely autonomous. This would impact the previously mentioned timing and methodological issue's within team sports, and particularly within youth athletes, due to the impact of growth and maturation on lower limb lengths throughout adolescence resulting in the need to continually measure lower limb length (Mirwald *et al.*, 2002). Despite the abundance of evidence highlighting the positive effects of self-determination upon motor learning (Wulf and Lewthwaite, 2016), less research is available evaluating its effect on specific performance measures, particularly within youth cohorts. In particular, no research included in this review had examined the impact of autonomy-supportive strategies during the testing procedures on the reliability of measures.

In sport and exercise settings, means of assessing autonomy has typically been carried out through the use of subjective questionnaires (Emanuel *et al.*, 2020). Scales have been specifically developed for use within sport and exercise settings, including the Basic Psychological Needs in Exercise Scale (Vlachopoulos and Michailidou, 2006), the Psychological Need Satisfaction in Exercise Scale (Wilson *et al.*, 2006), and the Perceived Autonomy Support Scale for Exercise Settings (Hagger *et al.*, 2007). Concerning the aforementioned, the Basic Psychological Needs in Exercise Scale (Vlachopoulos and Michailidou, 2006) and the Psychological Need Satisfaction in Exercise Scale (Wilson *et al.*, 2006) appear to be the most utilised within the literature. However, although the content of this questionnaire may be appropriate for use within adolescent population's due to the comparable exercise experience to that of recreationally trained adults, there are reservations surrounding the appropriateness of the wording of questions within these scales for use with this population.

Indeed, as children tend to interpret words literally (De Leeuw, Borgers and Smits, 2004), it is clear that age appropriate wording is necessary within questionnaires conducted with this

group. In addition, although validated, both scales contain complex wording relative to an immature adolescents comprehension (Table 2.8); with the Psychological Need Satisfaction in Exercise Scale (Wilson *et al.*, 2006) having previously been questioned regarding its generalisability due to the reflection of choice within its items (McDonough and Crocker, 2007). The Basic Psychological Needs in Exercise Scale (Vlachopoulos and Michailidou, 2006) is a 12-item self-report questionnaire utilised to examine the perceptions of an individual's autonomy, competence and relatedness with 4 questions assigned to each item. Vlachopoulos and Michailidou (2006) identified each of the previously mentioned subscales as distinct constructs, with evidence of cross-cultural validity being displayed within later works (Vlachopoulos, Ntoumanis and Smith, 2010). Similarly, Schneider and Kwan (2013) demonstrated high validity for autonomy related questions (Table 2.8) developed specifically within an adolescent population. However, although the wording was more appropriate within the latter research (Schneider and Kwan, 2013), questions were markedly similar to that of the Basic Psychological Needs in Exercise Scale (e.g., "*When I exercise, I do the types of activities that I want to*" vs "*I feel very strongly that the way I exercise fits perfectly with the way I prefer to exercise*" respectively) (Vlachopoulos, Ntoumanis and Smith, 2010). Therefore, future research aiming to evaluate the autonomy of adolescent athletes should opt to utilise the questions from the Basic Psychological Needs in Exercise Scale as the basis to develop new questionnaires for use within specific population. This method of adapting questions from the Basic Psychological Needs in Exercise Scale has been displayed recently within youth (age: 13.5 ± 0.5) soccer team cohorts with acceptable ($\alpha = 0.78-0.88$) Cronbach's alpha values illustrated within this population (Erikstad *et al.*, 2018).

In summary, given the psychological (Deci and Ryan, 2000) and biological (Leotti and Delgado, 2011) advantages of choice provision, benefits may ensue from its implementation on numerous aspects of athletic development, such as motor learning, performance and adherence. Although the positive effects of self-determination upon motor learning (Wulf and Lewthwaite, 2016) are well documented, there is currently a sparsity of research available evaluating its effect on specific performance measures. Specifically, there is a current lack of research examining the effects of self-determination on the reliability of assessment measures, particularly among youth cohorts. Different methods of autonomy assessment have also been presented here. Although many different methods for assessing autonomy have been developed and validated for exercise settings, practitioners should aim to utilise these as a basis for specifically examining this need within their respective populations of interest. For example,

the use of a previously validated questionnaire for the evaluation of players' perceptions of autonomy in a youth soccer setting could help explain the variance to programming often displayed by groups of athletes. Additionally, questionnaires may be used to measure the efficacy of strategies aimed at improving players' perception of autonomy within an elite sporting environment for the purposes of learning, development and engagement (Eitam, Kennedy and Tory, 2013).

Table 2.8: Autonomy scale items within research specific to exercise.

Study	Questions	Cronbach's (1951) α
Schneider and Kwan (2013)	When I exercise, I have control over the types of activities that I do	0.81
	I don't really have a choice about the types of activities I do when I exercise	
	When I exercise, I do the types of activities that I want to	
Vlachopoulos <i>et al.</i> (2006)	The exercise programme I follow is highly compatible with my choices and interests	0.84
	I feel very strongly that the way I exercise fits perfectly the way I prefer to exercise	
	I feel that the way I exercise is definitely an expression of myself	
	I feel very strongly that I have the opportunity to make choices with respect to the way I exercise	
Wilson <i>et al.</i> (2006)	Feel free to choose exercise I participate in	0.91
	Have a say in choosing exercises I do	
	I am in charge of my exercise programme decisions	
	I decide what exercises I do	
	Free to make my own decisions	
	Free to exercise in my own way	

Chapter 3.0

General Methodology

The procedures outlined in the following sections detail those adopted throughout Chapters 4, 5, 6, and 7.

3.1 Participant information

An outline of participant involvement is detailed in Figure 3.1. Briefly, a total of 4 cohorts (academy age groups) were studied in the present thesis. These included PSA Groups 1 and 2 from the professional soccer academy, aged U14 and U15 at Chapter 4 and 5 data collection start respectively, and U15 and U16 at Chapters 6 and 7 data collection start respectively (Figure 3.1). ASA groups 1 and 2 were from an amateur soccer academy aged U15 and U16 at Chapter 6 data collection start. In Chapters 4, 5, and 6, the professional soccer academy age groups were pooled into the analysis. In addition, the amateur soccer academy age groups were also pooled into the analysis for comparison with the professional soccer academy in Chapter 6. The influence of maturity differences was controlled for in the analysis (see specific Chapters for example statistical models).

3.2 Anthropometric measurements and adult height estimation

Standing stature (cm) and sitting stature (cm) were measured using a portable stadiometer (SECA, UK) to the nearest 0.10 cm. Stretch height was measured as the distance from the standing surface to the vertex of the head. Participants stood with an erect posture and the head was positioned in the Frankfort horizontal plane. Participants were instructed to maintain this position while gently inhaling. Percentage of estimated adult height was estimated using equations specific to European males' chronological age based off mid-parent height

Figure 3.1: Outline of participants involved in data collection for each chapter. **Key:** PSA: Professional soccer academy; ASA: Amateur soccer academy.

Table 3.1: Participant characteristics prior to grouping as described in Section 3.1.

		PSA Group 1	PSA Group 2	ASA Group 1	ASA Group 2
Chapter 4	Age (mean \pm SD)	12.5 \pm 0.3	13.5 \pm 0.3		
	%EAH (mean \pm SD)	0.90 \pm 0.03	0.95 \pm 0.03		
Chapter 5	Age (mean \pm SD)	13.5 \pm 0.2	14.6 \pm 0.3		
	%EAH (mean \pm SD)	0.90 \pm 0.03	0.95 \pm 0.02		
Chapter 6	Age (mean \pm SD)	13.5 \pm 0.2	14.6 \pm 0.3	14.2 \pm 0.8	14.7 \pm 0.3
	%EAH (mean \pm SD)	0.90 \pm 0.03	0.95 \pm 0.02	0.93 \pm 0.03	0.96 \pm 0.02
Chapter 7	Age (mean \pm SD)		14.8 \pm 0.3		
	%EAH (mean \pm SD)		0.96 \pm 0.02		

(Khamis and Roche, 1994). Biological parental heights were adjusted for overestimation (Epstein *et al.*, 1995). Body mass was measured prior to each jump or isometric squat testing using a force plate system (Forcedecks, Vald Performance, Newstead, Australia).

3.3 Physical performance testing

Prior to each pilot and experimental (in the case of the isometric squat test, see section 3.2.2) session, a standardised warm-up consisting of dynamic squatting, dynamic mobility, glute bridging, and lunging activities was carried out. Participants completed testing in the following order: CMJ, ISqT, and sprints.

3.3.1 Counter-movement jump

Participants completed three CMJ trials interspersed with approximately 30 seconds recovery with the best result utilized for further analysis. After an initial stationary phase of at least 2 seconds in the upright position, jumps were performed with hands akimbo so to eliminate the contribution of arm swing to jump performance (Gerodimos *et al.*, 2008). Participants squatted to a self-selected depth and then pushed onto the ground to accelerate upward attempting to gain maximum height. Subjects landed back, with their arms kept akimbo throughout the movement. If participants' hands moved from their hips the jump was repeated. CMJ height (cm) was assessed with a force plate system with a sampling rate of 1000 Hz (Forcedecks, Vald

Performance, Newstead, Australia). Acceptable reliability has previously been reported for the CMJ protocol using youth athletes (Meylan *et al.*, 2012).

3.3.2 *Isometric squat test*

Force-time characteristics were measured during an ISqT performed either with a pre-determined (PDet) or a self-determined (SDet) body (see Appendix 1 for an example effort) configuration. The PDet protocol was carried out at a fixed relative knee joint angle of 120–130°. Alternatively, participants had autonomy over the body configuration during the SDet protocol as they were instructed to assume the position at which they were able to comfortably push the floor as hard and fast as they could.

Following a single familiarisation session, three additional testing sessions were carried out separated by a period of 1–11 days following the procedures outlined below. Each familiarisation and testing session consisted of three 3–5 second maximal ISqT efforts separated by 2–3 minutes of passive rest between efforts. Augmented feedback was provided in “real-time” through the use of a TV screen stationed directly in front of the customised isometric rack (IndigoFitness, Nuneaton, England) allowing participants to view their live force-time trace (Appendix 1) so to promote increased effort (Keller *et al.*, 2014; Heinert *et al.*, 2021; Weakley *et al.*, 2019). Results of PF outputs were provided to the participants immediately after each ISqT effort to promote engagement and motivation to perform (Keller *et al.*, 2014; van Dijk, Mulder and Hermens, 2007; Weakley *et al.*, 2019). Kinetic performance was subjectively assessed by a researcher to ensure proper technique, and feedback was provided to each participant before and after each subsequent ISqT effort to maintain or improve performance (Heinert *et al.*, 2021; Keller *et al.*, 2014; Lauber *et al.*, 2013; Onate, Guskiewicz and Sullivan, 2001). Participants were informed of the test goals and outcome measures i.e., production of as much force as quickly as possible (Holtermann *et al.*, 2007; Rodríguez-Rosell *et al.*, 2018).

Then, participants carried out three warm-up isometric squats at 60%, 70%, and 80% of their perceived maximum effort, following similar protocols in previous isometric strength testing (Drake, Kennedy and Wallace, 2018). Thereafter, the researcher explained the protocol and provided the main coaching cues for a correct execution of the ISqT to help ensure consistency of technique between trials. The warm-up isometric squats and measured ISqT efforts were

performed using a custom isometric rack with an adjustable bar height to the nearest 7 cm. Portable dual-force plates (VALD Performance, ForceDecks, Queensland, Australia) were positioned directly below the isometric bar within the isometric rack and recorded GRF data at a sampling frequency of 1000Hz. A sampling frequency of 1000Hz was chosen to ensure reliable collection of time-dependent measures (Hori *et al.*, 2009). Participants' body mass was recorded whilst standing still with hands akimbo prior to the first isometric effort of each testing session for the calculation of relative force-time metrics to body mass. Force plates were zeroed before each isometric effort to accurately record participants force outputs.

Following the collection of body mass, participants were instructed to step off the force plates and then grip the barbell with equal spacing of hands from the centre of the bar without stepping onto the force plates as to ensure appropriate positioning relative to the force plates and the immovable bar. Thereafter, participants were instructed to step onto the force plates and assume a squat position. For each ISqT effort, the immovable bar was placed above the posterior deltoids and proper squat technique was ensured by the researcher. Briefly, participants were ensured to maintain a neutral pelvis and spinal alignment during each isometric effort in order to mitigate injury risk and allow for an effective transfer of force. They were also instructed to lightly press their shoulders against the bar, and be ready to push in order to remove slack from the bar, remove space between the bar and the support, and minimise early compliance as a result of skeletal muscle compression during the maximal effort (Tillin, Pain and Folland, 2013).

Participants were then instructed to hold this position and pressure against the bar to obtain a steady weighing period. A 1–3 second weighing period (Brady, Harrison and Comyns, 2020) was ensured prior to each isometric effort and confirmed by the researcher through visual inspection of the live force-time trace. As such, baseline force was obtained when participants were exerting minimal pressure against the bar. This method was chosen to obtain an accurate representation of force applied while participants were ready to initiate the isometric contraction. Baseline force values were analysed between testing sessions for consistency to ensure no impact upon time-dependent force-time metrics. Participants were then instructed to push the ground as hard and as fast as they could and an external attentional focus coaching cue was provided as it have been previously shown to maximise ground reaction force outputs during maximal isometric trials (Halperin *et al.*, 2016). The researcher provided the auditory cue “GO” to initiate the start of contraction (Drake, Kennedy and Wallace, 2018), as pilot data

indicated this method to obtain better initial rates of force development following contraction onset when compared to self-selected contraction onsets (unpublished data). Trials were stopped and discarded if the force-time trace displayed a large ($> 50\text{N}$) countermovement during the weighing period prior to the effort, reported any pain due to the test, or in the event of movement occurring during the trial. Strong verbal encouragement was provided during each effort by the assessor. Following each isometric effort, participants were instructed to carry out the child's pose stretch so to alleviate any acute posterior lumbo-pelvic muscle tension. Sheets describing the protocol (Appendix 1) and its procedures were displayed in the vicinity of the testing equipment for both participants and researchers.

3.3.3 *Self-determined isometric squat procedures*

The body configuration in the SDet protocol was fully and autonomously selected by each participant. Prior to the body mass measurement, participants stood on the force plates with a dowel rod placed on their shoulders, replicating the bar position of the ISqT as outlined above. Then, they were instructed to squat down slowly to a position they felt comfortable to push as hard and fast as they could against the floor while looking directly forward. This ensured participants utilised a position ensuring maximum GRF exertion and not the position they felt was the most difficult to produce force, as pilot testing indicated this was often the case (unpublished data).

Pilot experience in carrying out the SDet protocol also indicated that participants' bar height was often externally influenced by the squat racks bar pin height, as participants often aimed for a specific pin. Therefore, this cue ensured complete autonomy based off the individual's subjective perception. Upon assuming the preferred body position, the researcher noted the nearest corresponding pin height on the isometric rig which was used for each ISqT trial during that SDet testing session. Participants were allowed to change the bar height during the SDet protocol if they wished, in which event an average value for the session was utilised for further analysis (did not occur with the current sample). SDet ISqT body position setup procedures were the same as outlined above. Stance width, knee angle, and bar height were recorded during the weighing period prior to the first isometric effort of each session. An example SDet ISqT trial can be viewed using the QR code in Appendix 1.

3.3.3 *Isometric squat force-time data assessment*

Force time data recorded during each ISqT effort was generated automatically using commercially available software (VALD Performance, ForceDecks, Queensland, Australia). Contraction onset was defined as the first instantaneous force output rise ≥ 20 N above the value of the weighing period and was confirmed as the true onset by the researcher prior to final analysis. Previous research has found absolute contraction onset values to demonstrate high reliability when utilised with multi-joint isometric tests of strength (Dos'Santos *et al.*, 2017). The maximum force generated during the 3–5 second isometric contraction was defined as the peak force (PF) with the maximum PF during each testing session retained for further analysis. Relative PF (rPF) was calculated using ratio scaling (PF/body mass). Additional time dependent metrics included impulse (IMP) and rate of force development (RFD). RFD illustrates the initial rise of muscle force, with shorter (e.g., < 100 ms) time epochs describing an individual's starting strength (Young, McLean and Ardagna, 1995). IMP represents an individual's ability to produce force from the area under the force-time curve, with changes directly resulting in changes in momentum. Time epochs from contraction onset until 50 ms, 100 ms, 150 ms, and 200 ms (Comfort *et al.*, 2015; Thomas *et al.*, 2017) have been selected to describe early and late stages of muscular force output given the transferability of different stages to different athletic tasks (Musham and Fitzpatrick, 2020; Tillin, Pain and Folland, 2013).

3.3.4 *Sprint assessment*

Time to complete 10 m, 20 m and 30 m sprints were measured using single-beam timing gates with error detection (SmartSpeed, Vald, Queensland, Australia) previously shown to hold acceptable error rates of ≤ 0.03 s (D'Auria *et al.*, 2006) and test-retest CVs (1.9–3.5%) and ICCs (Lockie *et al.*, 2013). Sprint times were recorded for each 10m intermediate split distance along the 30 m sprint. Players self-determined the sprint start, and timing commenced when the player passed through the first timing gate positioned 1 meter after the starting line. Players were required to be completely still prior to starting and were not permitted to rock or step forward prior to the start of the sprint. Each athlete was instructed to maximally sprint past a set of cones positioned 2.5 meters after the last (30 m) timing gate to ensure full effort was maintained for the full 30 m distance. Test-retest reliability of sprint assessment in youth has reported CV and ICC values of 1.3% and 0.90–0.96 respectively (Drinkwater *et al.*, 2007).

Chapter 4.0

Reliability, Familiarisation Effect, and Comparisons Between a Predetermined and a Self-Determined Isometric-Squat Testing Protocol

The following original research study has been accepted for publication in the International Journal of Sports Physiology and Performance (<https://doi.org/10.1123/ijsp.2022-0480>).

4.1 Abstract

This study examined the inter-day reliability of a PDet or a SDet isometric squat test (ISqT) among youth soccer players. Familiarisation effects were evaluated to determine the minimum number of trials necessary to obtain consistent outputs. Lastly, protocol differences were evaluated. Thirty-one youth soccer players (mean \pm SD: age: 13.2 ± 1.0 years; body mass: 54.1 ± 3.4 kg; stature: 166.3 ± 11.2 cm; percentage of estimated adult height: $92.6 \pm 3.6\%$) from a top tier professional academy completed four experimental sessions for each protocol: familiarisation 1, familiarisation 2, test, and retest sessions. Peak force (PF), relative peak force (rPF), impulse from 0-50 ms (IMP50), 0-100 ms (IMP100), 0-150 ms (IMP150), and 0-200 ms (IMP200), and rate of force development from 0-50 ms (RFD50), 0-100 ms (RFD100), 0-150 ms (RFD150), and 0-200 ms (RFD200) were measured. Both protocols displayed acceptable (intraclass correlation coefficient ≥ 0.75 and coefficient of variation $\leq 10\%$) reliability statistics for all metrics apart from RFD of any time epoch. Differences were found between familiarisation 2 and both test and retest sessions for PF ($p = 0.034$ and 0.021 respectively) and rPF ($p = 0.035$ and 0.005 respectively) across both protocols. The ISqT is a reliable test among youth soccer players. Two familiarisation sessions seem to be sufficient to ensure data stabilisation. Outputs between the SDet and PDet are comparable, however, the latter seems preferable due to improved testing time efficiency.

4.2 Introduction

Accurate measurement of force production capabilities is paramount for practitioners, particularly those working with developing athletes, to prescribe, monitor, and evaluate training

programming given the importance of muscular strength and power as athletes transition towards the elite level (Sherwood *et al.*, 2020).

Isometric assessments, such as the isometric squat (ISqT) or mid-thigh pull (IMTP) tests, are time-effective, reliable, and are associated to a low injury risk (Brady, Harrison and Comyns, 2020; Drake, Kennedy and Wallace, 2017). Reliability is a crucial element to effectively delineate training adaptations from measurement variability and accurately determine true performance changes over time. However, no reliability evidence is available among youth cohorts for the ISqT (Brady, Harrison and Comyns, 2020). Familiarisation, rather than physiological adaptation, can affect force production capacity when athletes are repeatedly tested in quick succession, thereby also impacting reliability (Dias *et al.*, 2005; Drake, Kennedy and Wallace, 2018).

Time management is a challenge for applied practitioners or those working with large groups, as they may be unable to carry out isometric assessments due to the time-consuming procedures associated with the recommendations of specific body configurations (Comfort *et al.*, 2019). An alternative to PDet protocols is the use of SDet protocols, where athletes can choose their body configuration (Comfort *et al.*, 2015; Thomas *et al.*, 2017). Previous research found no differences between a PDet and a SDet protocol for the IMTP (Comfort *et al.*, 2015). However, empirical evidence is lacking with regard to reliability of a SDet ISqT protocol among youth, the minimum number of sessions required for data to stabilise, and differences between PDet and SDet protocols. Therefore, the aims of the current investigation were to: 1) Determine the inter-day reliability of the ISqT in well trained (i.e., ~6 training sessions per training week) youth soccer players; 2) Investigate the familiarisation effects on ISqT outputs; and, 3) Compare PDet and a SDet ISqT outputs.

4.3 Methodology

4.3.1 Experimental approach to the problem

A repeated-measures design was used to determine the inter-day reliability and compare force-time characteristics between two ISqT protocols in youth soccer players. Reliability was assessed over a 6-week period in a stepwise, randomised, and counter-balanced manner (Figure 4.1) during which each participant completed four sessions per protocol. Participants completed one unmeasured familiarisation session, a second measured familiarisation session,

followed by test, and re-test sessions. Each testing session consisted of three trials of 3 second maximal isometric efforts separated by at least 2 minutes of rest. 3 second efforts were chosen following pilot data (unpublished data) which indicated this to be sufficient in order for youth to generate maximal force.

4.3.2 Participants

A priori power analysis using G*Power (Universität Düsseldorf, Düsseldorf, Germany) determined that a minimum of 17 participants would be required to detect a large correlation of $r = 0.7$ among repeated measures with 80% power and an alpha of 5% for a correlational design study. However, this sample size was superseded by the requirement of 28 participants for the repeated measures design used to investigate familiarization effects and compare the mechanical outputs between the PDet and a SDet protocol. A conservative correlation of 0.7 was chosen following pilot testing, where a minimum correlation coefficient equal to $r = 0.9$ was observed for peak force (PF) values.

Therefore, 31 well-trained male youth soccer players (mean \pm SD: age: 13.2 ± 1.0 years; body mass: 54.1 ± 3.4 kg; stature: 166.3 ± 11.2 cm; percentage of estimated adult height (%EAH): $92.6 \pm 3.6\%$) participated in this study. %EAH was determined using equations specific to European males' chronological age based off mid-parent height (Khamis and Roche, 1994), which was adjusted for overestimation (Epstein *et al.*, 1995). Participants self-reported an average of 2.0 ± 0.9 years of strength, weight or gym training, including 6 months of supervised training which did not include back squat technique training. This investigation was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki and approved by an institutional Ethics Board (Appendix 3) prior to data collection with gatekeeper approval obtained from the corresponding institution (Appendix 4) following the provision of study details (Appendix 5).

4.4 Procedures

4.4.1 Isometric squat test

4.4.1.1 Pre-determined isometric squat procedures

The PDet ISqT protocol was performed at a knee joint angle of 120–130° as previous research

Figure 4.1: Study overview for each protocol. Participants then repeated the same process for the other protocol in a randomised fashion.

has consistently displayed excellent reliability statistics for this knee joint angle range (Bazyler *et al.*, 2014b; Bazyler, Beckham and Sato, 2015; Markovic *et al.*, 2007; Tillin, Pain and Folland, 2013). A knee joint angle range was utilised as opposed to a specific angle to reduce testing time during the PDet protocol (Darrall-Jones, Jones and Till, 2015). A 120–130° knee joint angle was confirmed prior to each testing session using manual goniometry (66fit, Merseyside, England) and corresponding to a specific bar height for each individual. The fulcrum of the goniometer was placed on the lateral epicondyle of the femur, with the goniometer arm and stationary arm directed parallel to the line of the fibula and femur respectively. Participant's stance widths were monitored and standardised for each PDet testing session. This was achieved with reference marks for each individual written on disposable tape and placed on the force plates for the participant to position the middle of their heels upon during the ISqT effort.

4.4.1.2 *Self-determined isometric squat procedures*

See section 3.2.3.

4.4.2 **Self-report measures**

The resulting impact on the participants perceptions of autonomy following each protocol was also evaluated to help explain any potential differences in outputs or reliability between the two protocols. Participants' perceptions of autonomy were measured using a modified version

of the Basic Psychological Needs in Exercise Scale (Appendix 2; Vlachopoulos and Michailidou, 2006). A modified version was utilised due to the potentially confusing wording of questions in this questionnaire for immature adolescent populations. Cross-cultural validity (Vlachopoulos, Ntoumanis and Smith, 2010) has previously been displayed for this questionnaire, with later research (Erikstad *et al.*, 2018) demonstrating acceptable consistency of an adapted version of the Basic Psychological Needs in Exercise Scale within a adolescent soccer population. Experienced and accredited applied strength and conditioning coaches, sport scientists, psychologists, and university academics were consulted and directly contributed to the formation of the questionnaire through adaptation of questions from the aforementioned Basic Psychological Needs in Exercise Scale (Vlachopoulos and Michailidou, 2006).

Immediately following the final 3–5 second effort of the final testing session of both the PDet and SDet conditions, participants completed the perception of autonomy questionnaire. Specifically, participants rated four perceptions of autonomy related questions on an A4 sheet using a Likert scale which ranged from 1 (“Strongly Disagree”) to 5 (“Strongly Agree”). The autonomy related questions were as follows: “1. The testing programme I just participated in is the same as how I would like to train/ be tested in the future”, “2. The way I was just tested is the way I want to be tested in the future”, “3. I feel I am able to decide how I am tested in the future”, and “4. Making choices about the exercise/activities I do is important to me”. This final question was added by the researcher in order to ascertain whether the participants’ feelings on the importance of having autonomy over testing procedures was influenced by the protocol they just completed. An example questionnaire is provided in Appendix 2.

4.4.3 Statistical analysis

Body configuration measures were compared between protocols using a paired t-test using the mean values of the PDet condition as critical value of the null-hypothesis testing given the consistency of the body configuration data in the PDet protocol. If assumption of normality was violated, a non-parametric Wilcoxon signed ranks test was used.

Hedges *g* effect sizes (Hedges and Olkin, 2014) were calculated to determine the magnitude of the differences in values between trials for both protocols and interpreted as described

previously (Hopkins, 2002). In addition, percentage changes between testing sessions was also calculated for all force-time and body configuration metrics.

Intraclass correlation coefficients (ICC), and coefficient of variation (CV), and associated 95% confidence intervals (CI) were calculated to test inter-day reliability. An ICC lower than 0.5, between 0.5 and 0.75, between 0.75 and 0.9, and greater than 0.90 was interpreted as poor, moderate, good, and excellent relative reliability, respectively (Koo and Li, 2016). A $CV \leq 10\%$ was deemed as acceptable absolute reliability (Hopkins, 2000). Reliability analysis was performed using customised spreadsheets (Hopkins, 2017).

The following linear mixed effects model was used to analyse effects of testing protocol on data across the three measured testing sessions:

$$Y_i = \beta_0 + \beta_{1-3} \text{session number} + \beta_4 \text{protocol} + \varepsilon_i$$

The measured dependant variable (Y) for each observation (i ; participant) represents repeated measures for each subject, β_0 is the overall grand intercept and ε_i is the residual error (i.e., unexplained variance) of the model. Predictor variables included: measurement session (β_{1-3} ; categorical variable with 3 levels [familiarisation session 2; test session, re-test session]) and protocol (β_4 ; categorical variable with 2 levels [PDet; Sdet]). Moreover, random effects were assumed for participants, training structures, and exercise, with random slopes introduced in the model if their addition did not result in a convergence error. Estimated marginal means and 95% confidence intervals were calculated alongside comparisons made using post-hoc Holm-Bonferroni adjustments. Visual inspection of residual plots was used to confirm the assumptions of homoscedasticity or normality, which was also assessed through the Shapiro-Wilk test. Analysis was performed in R language and environment for statistical computing using the lme4, lmerTest, emmeans, and ggeffects packages while model assumptions were checked using the performance package (4.0.5; R Core Team, Vienna, Austria).

4.5 Results

4.5.1 Protocol comparisons

Table 4.1 displays descriptive data of the participants average stance width, bar height, knee joint angle, and force at contraction onset for each protocol during testing sessions. Table 4.2

displays body configuration and force-time metric percentage differences and effect sizes (Hedges' g) between protocols. There were no statistically significant differences for knee joint angle between the two protocols ($p = 0.324$). There were statistically significant differences between protocols for stance width, bar height, and force at contraction onset (Tables 4.1 and 4.2). Table 4.3 displays the descriptive statistics of the force-time variables across the familiarisation and experimental trials. The SDet protocol resulted in significantly ($p = 0.048$) greater PF values compared to the PDet protocol.

4.5.2 Reliability

Reliability statistics are displayed in Table 4.4. All metrics' average values displayed moderate relative and acceptable reliability ($ICC \geq 0.75$ and $CV \leq 10\%$) except for IMP150 and IMP200 in the SDet protocol, and RFD measures in both protocols (Table 4.4).

4.5.3 Effects of familiarization

PF was significantly different between the familiarisation 2, test session ($p = 0.034$) and retest session ($p = 0.021$) for both protocols, with no difference in familiarisation trends between protocols ($p = 0.292$ and 0.431 respectively). With regards to rPF values, familiarisation 2 session outputs were significantly lower than both test ($p = 0.035$) and retest ($p = 0.005$) session outputs with no significant interaction between session and protocol observed for any testing session ($p = 0.612$ and 0.309 respectively). No other significant differences were observed between testing sessions for any other metric ($p > 0.05$).

Table 4.1: Descriptive data and familiarisation effect on participants' body configuration and force at contraction onset. Data presented are mean \pm standard deviation.

Metric	Pre-determined protocol			Self-determined protocol		
	Familiarisation 2	Test	Retest	Familiarisation 2	Test	Retest
Stance width (cm)	43.1 \pm 5.4	43.6 \pm 5.3	42.3 \pm 4.8	38.5 \pm 5.4	39 \pm 5.3	39.2 \pm 4^s
Bar height (cm)	126.6 \pm 10.3	127.3 \pm 10	127 \pm 10.4	134.4 \pm 8.9	132.7 \pm 10	134 \pm 9.2^s
Knee joint angle (°)	124.7 \pm 3.3	125 \pm 3.6	125 \pm 3.1	136.5 \pm 6.7	135 \pm 8.1	135.3 \pm 7.6
Force at contraction onset (N)	656 \pm 103	679 \pm 124	669 \pm 109	677 \pm 124	656 \pm 109	674 \pm 123^s

Key: N: newton; cm: centimetres; °: degrees; ^s: protocol average of 3 trials statistically significant different to that of pre-determined protocol.

Table 4.2: Percentage change and effect sizes of ISqT data between testing sessions for both protocols.

Metric	Pre-determined protocol				Self-determined protocol			
	Familiarisation 2-Test		Test-Retest		Familiarisation 2-Test		Test-Retest	
	Δ (%)	Hedges g	Δ (%)	Hedges g	Δ (%)	Hedges g	Δ (%)	Hedges g
Stance width (cm)	1.2	-0.10	-3.0	0.25	1.3	-0.10	0.5	-0.04
Bar height (cm)	0.5	-0.06	-0.2	0.03	-1.2	0.17	1.2	-0.17
Knee joint angle (°)	0.3	-0.11	-0.1	0.02	-1.1	0.20	0.3	-0.04
Force at contraction onset (N)	3.4	-0.20	-1.4	0.08	-3.1	0.17	2.6	-0.15
Peak force (N)	6.1	-0.25	0.2	-0.01	1.4	-0.06	1.5	-0.07
rPF (N/kg)	5.1	-0.39	1.5	-0.12	2.8	-0.18	0.0	0.00
IMP50 (Ns)	3.8	-0.21	-3.4	0.18	-3.9	0.20	2.5	-0.13
IMP100 (Ns)	3.0	-0.16	-2.7	0.15	-4.1	0.22	3.4	-0.19
IMP150 (Ns)	1.9	-0.10	-1.2	0.06	-3.3	0.16	2.7	-0.14
IMP200 (Ns)	2.4	-0.12	-1.4	0.07	-2.6	0.12	2.1	-0.11
RFD50 (N/s)	-2.5	0.04	4.8	-0.07	2.7	-0.05	-7.4	0.13
RFD100 (N/s)	-1.8	0.03	4.4	-0.08	-4.2	0.08	-0.5	0.01
RFD150 (N/s)	2.6	-0.06	-1.6	0.03	-0.3	0.01	-4.2	0.10
RFD200 (N/s)	5.2	-0.14	-1.9	0.05	1.1	-0.03	-2.2	0.06

Key: Δ : percentage change between testing sessions; rPF: relative peak force; IMP50: impulse from 0-50ms; IMP100: impulse from 0-100ms; IMP150: impulse from 0-150ms; IMP200: impulse from 0-200ms; RFD50: rate of force development from 0-50ms; RFD100: rate of force development from 0-100ms; RFD150: rate of force development from 0-150ms; RFD200: rate of force development from 0-200ms; N: newton; N/kg: newton per kilogram of body mass; Ns: newton-seconds; N/s: newtons per second.

Table 4.3: Descriptive data and familiarisation effect on force-time metrics. Data presented are mean \pm standard deviation (95% CI lower bound–95% CI upper bound).

Metric	Pre-determined protocol			Self-determined protocol		
	Familiarisation 2	Test	Retest	Familiarisation 2	Test	Retest
Peak force (N)	2009 \pm 501 (-1314–2703)	2138 \pm 505 (-1439–2837)*	2143 \pm 519 (-1424–2862)*	2145 \pm 497 (-1456–2834)\$	2176 \pm 460 (-1538.70–2813.082)\$*	2209 \pm 528 (-1478–2940)\$*
rPF (N/kg)	37.50 \pm 5.20 (-30.33–44.66)	39.50 \pm 5.00 (-32.59–46.39)*	40.10 \pm 5.20 (-32.97–47.26)*	39.73 \pm 6.10 (-31.28–48.19)	40.89 \pm 6.53 (-31.84–49.94)*	40.87 \pm 6.07 (-32.46–49.28)*
IMP50 (Ns)	35.78 \pm 5.99 (-27.47–44.08)	37.19 \pm 6.99 (-27.50–46.87)	34.6 \pm 9.08 (-22.01–47.18)	36.91 \pm 6.96 (-27.26–46.55)	35.52 \pm 6.49 (-26.53–44.52)	36.44 \pm 7.14 (-26.55–46.33)
IMP100 (Ns)	78.37 \pm 14.55 (-58.21–98.54)	80.78 \pm 14.18 (-61.13–100.42)	78.65 \pm 13.93 (-59.34–97.96)	82.03 \pm 15.20 (-60.98–103.09)	78.8 \pm 14.44 (-58.78–98.82)	81.6 \pm 14.96 (-60.87–102.34)
IMP150 (Ns)	131.01 \pm 27.76 (-92.54–169.48)	133.6 \pm 25.19 (-98.69–168.51)	132.02 \pm 26.74 (-94.97–169.076)	138.43 \pm 28.77 (-98.55–178.30)	133.94 \pm 25.88 (-98.07–169.82)	137.6 \pm 26.41 (-101–174.2)
IMP200 (Ns)	190.93 \pm 42.02 (-132.69–249.17)	188.9 \pm 52.3 (-116.39–261.40)	178.69 \pm 65.25 (-88.26–269.11)	202.92 \pm 45.17 (-140.31–265.52)	197.81 \pm 39.29 (-143.36–252.26)	202.10 \pm 41.23 (-144.96–259.24)
RFD50 (N/s)	1555.6 \pm 920.1 (-280.43–2830.77)	1465.38 \pm 1080.07 (31.49–2962.25)	1476.37 \pm 1147.69 (114.21–3066.95)	1739.48 \pm 969.42 (-395.96–3083.00)	1787.29 \pm 915.04 (-519.13–3055.44)	1664.77 \pm 964.95 (-327.44–3002.10)
RFD100 (N/s)	2997.17 \pm 1803.62 (-497.53–5496.81)	2842.79 \pm 1641.66 (-567.61–5117.98)	2850.85 \pm 1973.94 (-115.15–5586.55)	3589.55 \pm 2087.96 (-708.31–6470.79)	3444.14 \pm 1538.86 (-1311.43–5576.85)	3427.08 \pm 1775.51 (-966.39–5887.76)
RFD150 (N/s)	3199.93 \pm 1620.97 (-953.43–5446.44)	3173.69 \pm 1544.11 (-1033.7–5313.68)	2995.81 \pm 1741.63 (-582.08–5409.55)	3645.55 \pm 1752.97 (-1216.12–6075)	3634.29 \pm 1370.75 (-1734.56–5534.01)	3486.50 \pm 1624.82 (-1234.65–5738.35)
RFD200 (N/s)	3015.7 \pm 1213.79 (-1333.50–4697.9)	3072.17 \pm 1285.61 (-1290.44–4853.90)	2890.37 \pm 1440.2 (-894.39–4886.36)	3438.03 \pm 1434.27 (-1450.27–5425.8)	3477.89 \pm 1099.52 (-1954.06–5001.72)	3403.15 \pm 1377.49 (- 1494.08–5312.22)

Note: ICC: intraclass correlation coefficient; CI: confidence interval; CV: coefficient of variation; rPF: relative peak force; IMP50: impulse from 0-50ms; IMP100: impulse from 0-100ms; IMP150: impulse from 0-150ms; IMP200: impulse from 0-200ms; RFD50: rate of force development from 0-50ms; RFD100: rate of force development from 0-100ms; RFD150: rate of force development from 0-150ms; RFD200: rate of force development from 0-200ms; N: newton; N/kg: newton per kilogram of body mass; Ns: newton-seconds; N/s: newtons per second; \$: significantly different to pre-determined protocol; *: significantly different to familiarisation session 2; †: significantly different to test session; ‡: significantly different to retest session.

Table 4.4: Isometric squat inter-day reliability statistics calculated from data from all 3 testing days.

Metric	Pre-determined protocol		Self-determined protocol	
	ICC (95%CI)	CV (%) (95%CI)	ICC (95%CI)	CV (%) (95%CI)
Stance width (cm)			0.55 (0.30–0.75)	9.6 (7.5–13.3)
Bar height (cm)			0.87 (0.76–0.93)	2.9 (2.3–4)
Knee joint angle (°)			0.50 (0.23–0.71)	4.1 (3.2–5.6)
Force at contraction onset (N)			0.90 (0.81–0.95)	5.3 (4.2–7.3)
Peak force (N)	0.92 (0.83–0.97)	8.4 (6.7–11.6)	0.88 (0.74–0.95)	7.7 (6.0–10.5)
rPF (N/kg)	0.70 (0.45–0.86)	8.0 (6.3–11.0)	0.83 (0.65–0.93)	6.9 (5.4–9.4)
IMP50 (Ns)	0.78 (0.57–0.90)	9.1 (7.1–12.5)	0.82 (0.63–0.92)	8.6 (6.8–11.8)
IMP100 (Ns)	0.85 (0.70–0.94)	7.6 (6.0–10.4)	0.77 (0.55–0.90)	9.4 (7.4–12.9)
IMP150 (Ns)	0.89 (0.78–0.96)	7.2 (5.7–9.9)	0.75 (0.52–0.89)	10.5 (8.2–14.4)
IMP250 (Ns)	0.90 (0.79–0.96)	7.6 (6.0–10.5)	0.75 (0.53–0.89)	10.8 (8.5–14.9)
RFD50 (N/s)	0.45 (0.12–0.72)	62.2 (46.9–92.5)	0.37 (0.04–0.67)	61.3 (46.2–91.0)
RFD100 (N/s)	0.81 (0.62–0.92)	31.5 (24.3–44.8)	0.47 (0.14–0.74)	53.7 (40.7–79.0)
RFD150 (N/s)	0.81 (0.63–0.92)	28.4 (22.0–40.4)	0.60 (0.31–0.81)	35.4 (27.2–50.7)
RFD250 (N/s)	0.85 (0.68–0.93)	22.7 (17.6–31.9)	0.74 (0.51–0.88)	23.2 (18.1–32.7)

Key: ICC: intraclass correlation coefficient; CV: coefficient of variation; rPF: relative peak force; IMP50: impulse from 0-50ms; IMP100: impulse from 0-100ms; IMP150: impulse from 0-150ms; IMP200: impulse from 0-200ms; RFD50: rate of force development from 0-50ms; RFD100: rate of force development from 0-100ms; RFD150: rate of force development from 0-150ms; RFD200: rate of force development from 0-200ms; N: newton; N/kg: newton per kilogram of body mass; Ns: newton-seconds ; N/s: newtons per second.

4.5.4 Self-reported perceptions of autonomy

No differences were observed for any of the items of the autonomy questionnaire between the two protocols ($\chi^2 [7] = 11.834, p = 0.106$).

4.6 Discussion

The primary aim of this study was to establish the between-day reliability of force-time metrics measured in the ISqT among adolescent soccer players. The secondary aim was to determine the number of sessions required for data to stabilise. Finally, this investigation aimed to compare PDet and SDet outputs. Average values obtained from ISqT displayed acceptable reliability statistics among youth soccer players, however, the 95% CI often exceeded the aforementioned reliability threshold ($ICC \geq 0.75$ and $CV \leq 10\%$). PF, rPF and IMP for any time epoch demonstrated acceptable average reliability values for both protocols, whereas RFD was deemed unacceptable regardless of the timeframe analysed (Table 4.4). PF outputs produced during the SDet protocol were statistically significantly larger compared to the PDet protocol, with no other differences for any other mechanical measure between protocols (Table 4.3). Two familiarisation sessions consisting of three trials are sufficient when utilising an ISqT with youth athletes, regardless of the protocol employed (Table 4.3).

In agreement with previous literature, PF displayed excellent (Bazyler, Beckham and Sato, 2015; Tsoukos *et al.*, 2016; Tillin, Pain and Folland, 2013) and good (Drake, Kennedy and Wallace, 2018) average relative reliability for the PDet and SDet protocols, respectively (Table 4.4). In addition, average rPF also displayed good reliability for the SDet protocol, but moderate reliability for the PDet protocol (Table 4.4). Drake *et al.* (2019b) reported excellent between-day test reliability for rPF ($ICC: 0.92$ and $CV: 5\%$) when utilising a PDet body position in the ISqT. This maybe as a result of a change in the participants rank order as highlighted by the large 95% CIs of the ICC compared to that of the CV (Table 4.4). Indeed, differing rates of isometric data stabilisation in youth compared to adults may contribute to such a result (Ortqvist *et al.*, 2007). Therefore, the rPF metric may be slightly less reliable when measured in youth compared to adult participants.

In agreement with previous research (Bazyler, Beckham and Sato, 2015; Brady *et al.*, 2019) acceptable reliability ($ICC \geq 0.75$ and $CV \leq 10\%$) was observed for IMP across all time epochs

regardless of protocol (Table 4.4). However, RFD metrics were mostly unreliable regardless of time epoch or protocol (Table 4.4). Drake, Kennedy and Wallace (2019b) found unreliable RFD reliability statistics irrespective of the time epoch (up to 0–250 ms) analysed. Similarly, research reporting CVs across multiple time epochs highlighted variability of 19.9–89.1% in adult participants (Drake, Kennedy and Wallace, 2019b) and unacceptable (CV: 16.8%) statistics for the IMTP in adolescent athletes (Thomas *et al.*, 2017). Therefore, RFD obtained from multi-joint isometric tests is likely an unreliable metric to use with youth.

ISqT force-time outputs stabilized after two sessions consisting of three trials each (Table 4.3). This is in contrast to Drake, Kennedy and Wallace (2018), who reported stable PDet ISqT force-time characteristics after three familiarisation sessions. A potential reason explaining this finding were the different participants' characteristics. While the current study involved youth soccer players with a strength training experience of 2.0 ± 0.9 years, Drake Kennedy and Wallace (2018) investigated strength trained (training experience: 4.1 ± 1.8 years) adult males (age: 21.4 ± 4.5 years). Additionally, where the current investigation utilised the maximum PF value, Drake Kennedy and Wallace (2018) used the average between trials, confounding comparisons between studies. PF was found as stable over four weeks when testing IMTP in youth soccer players (Musham and Fitzpatrick, 2020). Therefore, six familiarisation trials are likely required for ISqT data to stabilise regardless of the protocol.

Albeit trivial, statistically significant differences in PF were found between the PDet and SDet protocols (Table 4.3). Moreover, a unimodal trend was found in favour of the SDet protocol, with all mechanical outcomes being consistently greater in comparison with the PDet protocol. Therefore, it appears that granting youth soccer players with choice over the body configuration adopted during an ISqT result in greater values compared to a controlled approach. However, given the differences in knee joint angle between protocols ($\sim 125 \pm 3^\circ$ vs $\sim 135 \pm 7^\circ$), it is unclear whether this is due to mechanical mechanisms, psychological contributions, or interactions between the two. Research should determine whether these differences persist between protocols when both are performed at the same relative knee joint angle, thus providing empirical insights regarding the underpinning mechanisms of force productions in self-determined test protocols.

Interestingly, stance width displayed trivial changes between sessions while knee joint angle displayed trivial-to-small changes between SDet sessions (Table 4.2). Similarly, participants consistently chose comparable bar heights between the two sessions, with trivial differences

between sessions (Table 4.2), indicating youth soccer players can self-determine an ISqT set up between testing sessions without any meaningful kinematic variability. This is a key finding, as a SDet protocol may accommodate for changes in individual anthropometric characteristics over prolonged periods of time. A SDet body position may be preferred by practitioners due to the reduced time needed to carry out this protocol, similar familiarisation effect and greater performance data when compare to that of a PDet protocol.

The current study is not without limitations. Participants in the current study are youth male soccer players, which limits generalization to other cohorts. However, the PF outputs of the current study were similar to those displayed by youth athletes from various sports (Young, McLean and Ardagna, 1995). In addition, generalisation to other isometric tests is not possible due to differences in body configuration between tests. In addition, previous research has found reliable time-dependent force-time metrics (e.g., RFD) through the use of ‘explosive’ 1 second protocols (Drake, Kennedy and Wallace, 2019b; Tillin, Pain and Folland, 2013), therefore it maybe that the protocol duration of the current study was not conducive to eliciting reliable RFD outputs. However, the aforementioned protocol (Drake, Kennedy and Wallace, 2019b; Tillin, Pain and Folland, 2013) remains to be evaluated in youth. In addition, due to the time commitment needed to carry out additional 1-second explosive protocols with the requisite recovery period, this was not feasible in the current investigation. Lastly, due to ecological logistic constraints within sporting environments, successive trials were performed with more than a week apart for some participants. However, it is unlikely that physiological changes contributing to strength and power improvements would have occurred throughout this time period.

In conclusion, the current research highlights the ISqT demonstrates high levels of reliability when conducted with youth soccer players depending on the metric analysed. Practitioners may be confident that reliable ISqT outputs can be obtained only after two familiarisation sessions in applied youth environments. A novel and easy-to-administer SDet protocol led to similar force-time outputs compared to a more traditional PDet protocol. Therefore, it may be considered as an elective and more advantageous alternative for use when working with youth soccer players.

4.7 Practical implications

This study promotes the use of the ISqT as a reliable test among youth soccer players. Interestingly, while both PDet and SDet protocols may be confidently used by practitioners in applied environment, the SDet protocol may be preferred compared to the PDet protocol due to a more advantageous time and logistics efficiency.

4.8 Thesis implications

This chapter demonstrates the reliability of the ISqT. The results of this chapter will therefore be used in subsequent studies where the quantification of lower body force-production capabilities is required. The current study therefore illustrates which metrics are acceptably reliable for use. In addition, the minimum required familiarisation sessions for reliable data will be utilised to ensure stability of data in subsequent chapters 5, 6, and 7. The current study also impacts the following chapters through demonstrating the utility of a time-efficient SDet ISqT protocol. The next step in determining the usefulness of the ISqT is to determine whether relationships exist between reliable ISqT metrics and dynamic proxies of soccer performance. Indeed, the ISqT has value as a stand-alone test of muscular strength and power in youth soccer, but in order for it to have broader utility by soccer practitioners, its relationship to surrogate measures of physical determinants of soccer performance needed to be evaluated

Chapter 5.0

Relationship between isometric squat test performance and measures of physical performance in youth soccer

5.1 Abstract

The ability to execute high intensity neuromuscular actions throughout youth soccer match play is critical for team success, and individual progression towards higher playing standards. Research has demonstrated the reliable measurement of lower limb force production capabilities via the ISqT in youth, however, no research has yet determined the relationship between ISqT outputs and jump or sprint performance measures in youth, an important step in determining the usefulness of a performance test in the applied environment. This study aimed to evaluate the relationship between ISqT outputs (PF, rPF, IMP50, IMP100, IMP150, IMP200) and sprint (0–10 m, 20 m and 30 m) and jump (CMJ) performance in highly trained youth soccer players (age: 13.9 ± 0.6 years). Isometric PF predicted CMJ height ($R^2 = 0.327$; $p = 0.010$); 0–10 m ($R^2 = 0.490$; $p = 0.001$), 0–20 m ($R^2 = 0.489$; $p = 0.001$) and 0–30 m ($R^2 = 0.538$; $p = 0.001$) sprint performance, while rPF and IMP200 predicted CMJ ($R^2 = 0.441$; $p = 0.004$) and 0–10 m speed ($R^2 = 0.203$; $p = 0.040$) respectively. The results from this study show ISqT outputs may predict 44.1–53.8% of the variance of speed and jumping related tasks.

5.2 Introduction

Youth soccer match play is characterised by repeated high intensity actions such as jumping activities (Aslan *et al.*, 2012), accelerations and decelerations (Pettersen and Brenn, 2019), high-speed and sprint running (Hunter *et al.*, 2015). Indeed, these actions have been suggested as critical to match success, due to their involvement in game defining periods of match play (Faude, Koch and Meyer, 2012). In addition, numerous studies have demonstrated the importance of these actions for youth players aiming to progress through an academy setting to older age groups (Al Haddad *et al.*, 2015; Bellistri *et al.*, 2017; Goto, Morris and Nevill, 2015b; Vigh-Larsen, Dalgas and Andersen, 2018a), or to higher playing standards (Sherwood

et al., 2020).

Acceleration, deceleration, sprinting, and jumping activities require the production of high GRFs in short time periods (Hunter, Marshall and McNair, 2005). Measuring GRF outputs during specific locomotive activities (such as sprinting) is difficult without specialised facilities. However, strength tests such as multi-joint isometric tests can accurately quantify the force production capabilities of the lower limbs (Drake, Kennedy and Wallace, 2017) in a safe and time efficient manner (see section 4) (Bazyler, Beckham and Sato, 2015). Indeed, maximal isometric tests have previously been implemented among youth athletes (Dos'Santos *et al.*, 2018; Morris *et al.*, 2018b; Thomas *et al.*, 2015) with performance outputs displaying strong relationships with sprint speed (Thomas *et al.*, 2015) and jumping ability (Comfort *et al.*, 2014).

The ISqT test has previously demonstrated acceptable between-session repeatability (see section 4) indicating its ability to measure force production capabilities between testing days (Atkinson and Nevill, 1998). However, the relationships between ISqT metrics and measures of physical performance has yet to be explored in youth, with such data contributing to the useability of the ISqT (see Section 2.6.1). Indeed, this data may explain the proportion of performance variation shared by two performance tests, adding to the use of the ISqT as a proxy measure of dynamic performance. Therefore, the aim of this study was to determine the relationship between ISqT force-time metrics and measures of physical performance.

5.3 Methods

5.3.1 Experimental approach to the problem

A correlation study design was employed to assess relationships between isometric outputs and sprint and jump performance.

5.3.2 Participants

A priori power analysis using G*Power (Universität Düsseldorf, Düsseldorf, Germany) determined a minimum 20 participants required to detect a large correlation of $\rho_{HI} = 0.7$ and $\rho_{H0} = 0.9$ among repeated measures with 80% power and an alpha of 5%. Pilot testing indicated a minimum correlation coefficient equal to $r = 0.9$ for PF values. Therefore, 17 well-

trained male youth soccer players (mean \pm SD: age: 13.9 ± 0.6 years; body mass: 51.9 ± 7.8 kg; stature: 163.1 ± 9.8 cm; %EAH: $91.7 \pm 3.1\%$) participated in this study. All procedures were conducted in accordance with the declaration of Helsinki and were approved by an institutional Ethics Board prior to study initiation (see Appendix 3 and Section 4.3.2). Chapter 3.1 outlines the procedures for all anthropometric and maturity related measurements and calculations.

5.4 Procedures

5.4.1 Isometric squat test

All participants were familiarised with the ISqT prior to study commencement (see section 4.0). For full protocol see section 3.2.3 and Appendix 1.

5.4.2 Counter-movement jump

See section 3.2.1.

5.4.3 Sprint assessment

See section 3.2.4.

5.4.4 Statistical analysis

Relationships between variables were assessed using Pearson product-moment correlations and were evaluated as small (0.10–0.29), moderate (0.30–0.49), large (0.50–0.69), very large (0.70–0.89), nearly perfect (0.9–0.99) and perfect (1.0) (Hopkins, 2002). The best score for each metric collected during the ISqT was used for the final analysis (Beattie *et al.*, 2017). ISqT scores were assessed for homoscedasticity using P-P Plots (Durbin, 1951). Simple linear regression analyses were performed to determine the relationships between the ISqT metrics and sprint and jump performance. All analyses were conducted in SPSS (Version 25, IBM statistics, Armonk, New York, USA). Significance level was set at $p < 0.05$.

5.5 Results

Table 5.1 illustrates the inter-correlation matrix between ISqT variables and performance testing results. Table 5.2 displays the outputs of simple linear regression analysis for all relationships between ISqT variables and physical performance characteristics. Peak force predicted CMJ ($R^2 = 0.327$; $p = 0.010$), 0–10 m ($R^2 = 0.490$; $p = 0.001$), 0–20 m ($R^2 = 0.489$; $p = 0.001$) and 0–30 m ($R^2 = 0.538$; $p = 0.001$) sprint performance. Relative PF predicted CMJ ($R^2 = 0.441$; $p = 0.004$) only. Impulse from 0–200 ms predicted 0–10 m speed ($R^2 = 0.203$; $p = 0.040$) only. Correlations between participant characteristics and testing outputs are displayed in table 5.3.

5.6 Discussion

The current investigation sought to determine the relationships between ISqT outputs and sprint and jumping performances. The results indicate that ISqT PF was statistically related to CMJ, 0–10 m, 0–20 m and 0–30 m sprint performances, whereas rPF and IMP200 were only related to CMJ and 0–10 m speed respectively (Tables 5.1 and 5.2). Previous studies examining the relationship between ISqT PF and sprint performance found similar results. For example, 5 m (Brady *et al.*, 2019; Tillin, Pain and Folland, 2013) and 10 m (Young, McLean and Ardagna, 1995) sprint times were negatively related ($r = -0.5$ to -0.71 and -0.79 respectively) with PF measured during the ISqT. However, longer sprint distances displays contrasting results. For example, in agreement with the aforementioned research, PF has been shown as statistically related to 0–20 m sprinting speed ($r = -0.72$) in the current investigation (Brady *et al.*, 2019). In addition, in contrast to the results of this study, 0–30 m sprint performance has shown as not related to ISqT outputs (Brady *et al.*, 2019). However, to the authors knowledge this is the first investigation of its kind in youth soccer players.

It is likely that ISqT performance is more strongly related to accelerative-type running in adult male populations, compared to sprint running. In addition, Sherwood *et al.* (2020)

Table 5.1: Pearsons’s correlation values between ISqT variables and performance measures.

ISqT predictor variable	CMJ (cm)	0–10 m (s)	0–20 m (s)	0–30 m (s)
Peak force (N)	0.608*	-0.722*	-0.722*	-0.734*
Relative peak force (N/kg)	0.664*	-0.420	-0.453	-0.461
Impulse 0–50ms (N.s)	0.101	-0.424	-0.393	-0.387
Impulse 0–100ms (N.s)	0.111	-0.416	-0.388	-0.379
Impulse 0–150ms (N.s)	0.205	-0.469	-0.443	-0.432
Impulse 0–200ms (N.s)	0.281	-0.503*	-0.476	-0.465

Key: CMJ: Countermovement jump; s: seconds; N: Newtons; N/kg: Newtons per kilogram; N.s: Newton-seconds; *: significant $p < 0.05$.

Table 5.2: Linear regression equations for the prediction of performance measures using ISqT variables

ISqT metric	CMJ (cm)		0–10 m (s)		0–20 m (s)		0–30 m (s)	
	Regression equation	Adjusted R ²	Regression equation	Adjusted R ²	Regression equation	Adjusted R ²	Regression equation	Adjusted R ²
PF (N)	12.605 + 7.1(N)	0.327*	2.115 - 0.0001396(N)	0.490*	3.826 - 0.0002784(N)	0.489*	5.528 - 0.0004255(N)	0.538*
rPF (N/kg)	3.236 + 0.582(N/kg)	0.441*	2.061 - 0.006102(N/kg)	0.177	3.761 - 0.0131117(N/kg)	0.152	5.431 - 0.0200815(N/kg)	0.213
IMP50 (N.s)	26.636 + 0.629(N.s)	-0.056	1.959 - 0.0043746(N.s)	0.125	3.491 - 0.0080803(N.s)	0.154	5.001 - 0.0119647(N.s)	0.15
IMP100 (N.s)	25.908 + 0.036(N.s)	-0.530	1.986 - 0.0022458(N.s)	0.118	3.542 - 0.0041741(N.s)	0.094	5.073 - 0.0061361(N.s)	0.087
IMP150 (N.s)	22.914 + 0.041(N.s)	-0.022	2.024 - 0.0015707(N.s)	0.168	3.618 - 0.0029562(N.s)	0.142	5.184 - 0.0043371(N.s)	0.132
IMP200 (N.s)	20.727 + 0.038(N.s)	0.018	2.038 - 0.0011311(N.s)	0.203*	3.646 - 0.0021347(N.s)	0.175	5.226 - 0.0031360(N.s)	0.164

Key: CMJ: Countermovement jump; s: seconds; N: Newtons; N/kg: Newtons per kilogram; N.s: Newton-seconds; *: significant $p < 0.05$.

demonstrated stronger inverse relationships between absolute squat strength scores and 10 and 20 m sprint times in younger compared to that of older academy players (e.g., U16 > U18 > U23). Indeed, the relationship between speed and absolute strength in the aforementioned research diminishes as player age increases, however the opposite seemed to occur between relative strength and sprint performance (e.g., stronger correlations for U23 compared to U18 compared to U16) (Sherwood *et al.*, 2020). Therefore, it is likely participant age and training experience is the primary reason for the observed difference in isometric relationships with sprint performance in the current study compared to that evaluating adult populations. The present study suggests the ability for youth athletes to express and tolerate large GRFs is of primary importance (Berger and Henderson, 1966), highlighting the need for strength training in youth athletic development frameworks (Lloyd *et al.*, 2015; Ryan *et al.*, 2018).

Maximal sprinting requires substantial GRFs produced in minimal ground contact times (Weyand *et al.*, 2000). Therefore, it could be assumed that time-dependent metrics such as impulse would relate strongly to performance tasks which require maximal force production in short time frames. In contrast to this notion, impulse measured over any time epoch up to 200 ms was not statistically significantly related to any performance tests with the exception of 10 m speed and IMP200ms (Table 5.1). Despite the time epochs of the impulse measures being similar to the GCTs of sprint actions, the magnitudes of forces were not comparable. This may partly explain this relationship between 10 m speed and IMP200ms, as GCTs are relatively longer during the acceleration phase, and the amount of force produced increases (see Table 4.2) from contraction onset until PF (~250–300 ms). Indeed, impulse has previously been shown as a contributor to 5 and 20 m sprint performance (Brady *et al.*, 2019; Thomas *et al.*, 2015).

In agreement with the present investigation, previous research demonstrated correlations between ISqT PF (Nuzzo *et al.*, 2008; Wagner *et al.*, 2022) and rPF (Kennedy and Drake, 2018) and CMJ height in male athletes. However, other studies have found no statistically significant associations between PF or rPF obtained via ISqT and CMJ height (Wilson *et al.*, 1995; Young, McLean and Ardagna, 1995). However, a novel aspect of the current study is the evaluation of the association between CMJ and ISqT impulse, (see section 2.7.1), whereby no statistically significant relationships for any time epoch was found (Table 5.2). While differences in knee joint angle of the ISqT only partially explains the variance described (Lum,

Haff and Barbosa, 2020), a more likely contributor could be between-individual differences in jumping technique (Pérez-Castilla *et al.*, 2021).

While the present study demonstrates 44.1–53.8% of the variance of speed and jumping performance tests can be explained by ISqT metrics, it is important to acknowledge the proportion of the variance not explained by ISqT metrics. While a statistically significant amount of the variance is indeed explained, it is likely that growth and maturation processes contribute to a large proportion of the variance also. While outside the scope of the current investigation and without a sufficient sample size for reliable analysis, sub-analysis revealed %EAH as inversely correlated with all sprint times. However, the age range of the participants was small (SD: 0.5 years) resulting in the inability to perform analysis which accurately determines the relationship between age and maturity and physical performance changes. In addition, this type of analysis assumes a linear relationship between maturation change and performance test change in the absence of a within-subject longitudinal design, meaning the results may not be transferrable to other populations. The results of the current study confirm physical performance is multi-faceted and can only be partly explained by force-derived metrics (Table 5.1), therefore, future research on the area is required.

5.7 Practical implications

ISqT PF accounts for 48.9%, 49.0% and 53.8% of the variance of 10 m, 20 m and 30 m sprint times respectively (Table 5.2). However, rPF was largely correlated with CMJ performance and accounted for 44.1% of the variance (Table 5.2). The significant proportion of variance in the physical performance tests explained by ISqT justifies its usage as an outcome measure in any serial measure of physical performance capacity in highly-trained youth soccer players given it appears to relate strongly to surrogates of dynamic physical performance (see Chapter 4).

5.8 Thesis implications

The current chapter illustrates the metrics obtainable from the ISqT which related to measures of physical performance. As a result, the metrics which were demonstrated as reliable in Chapter 4 and in addition as having described a statistically significant proportion of the

variance of physical performance tests will be utilised in further research requiring the need for the measurement of force-production capabilities. These metrics can now be better rationalised for use in longitudinal evaluations of physical development as evaluated in Chapter 6.

Chapter 6.0

A longitudinal analysis of strength and power performance between elite and amateur youth soccer players

6.1 Abstract

Strength, power, and speed are important attributes for youth soccer players to possess for both match performance, and long-term development. However, the development of these attributes may occur through involvement in soccer-specific pitch-based training and/or growth and maturation processes in the absence of strength, speed or power specific training. This study evaluated changes in physical performance over a 7–8-month period in youth professional (PSA) and amateur (ASA) soccer academy players. Two age groups from each club completed an ISqT (PF, rPF), CMJ, 10 m, 20 m, and 30 m sprint tests with both ages from individual clubs pooled into the analysis for between-club comparison. The PSA players improved ISqT PF and rPF by 208 N and 7.01 N/kg more than the ASA players over the study period. CMJ height also improved by 2.8 cm more in the PSA group compared to that of the ASA group. The PSA performed better than the ASA in the 10 m sprint test (0.11 s). Maturation was shown as impactful ($p < 0.05$) to the performance of all physical tests and metrics. The results demonstrated in the current study suggests change in physical performance in adolescent soccer players differs depending on the physical characteristic analysed. Physical development in youth soccer players may depend on maturity status, exposure to strength- and power-based training, or a combination of both.

6.2 Introduction

Soccer players are required to possess muscular strength and power in order to cope with match play demands (Chelly *et al.*, 2009; Wing, Turner and Bishop, 2018). Individuals with higher levels of muscular strength can produce larger GRFs, an important contributor to jump, change of direction, and linear sprint performance (Cronin and Hansen, 2005; Weyand *et al.*, 2000). This is likely the primary reason research demonstrates relationships between strength-based

test performance and that of dynamic surrogates of soccer performance such as sprint speed (see Chapter 5; Thomas *et al.*, 2015), change of direction performance (Appleby, Cormack and Newton, 2020) and jumping ability (see Chapter 5; Comfort *et al.*, 2014).

The development of strength, speed, and power capabilities is important as youth soccer players progress through a professional football academy (Ryan *et al.*, 2018) and reliance on these capabilities increases with player age (Spiteri, Hart and Nimphius, 2014). Therefore, monitoring physical development in youth football players is fundamental to evaluate the efficacy of implemented training programmes (Bartlett and Drust, 2021). To this end, although cross-sectional studies have corroborated the need for strength and conditioning programmes to develop these characteristics in academy settings (Brownlee *et al.*, 2018; Murtagh *et al.*, 2018a; Sherwood *et al.*, 2020), less evidence exists on how players develop strength, speed, and power performance over prolonged (e.g., > 12 weeks) periods. Physical performance evaluation over periods of time reflecting the duration of a typical sporting season (7–10 months), or training mesocycle, would be beneficial to the applied practitioner to better describe the response to the physical stimuli experienced throughout the period.

Accurate evaluation of the development of muscular strength, speed and power in adolescent soccer players is complex in an applied environment. Differences in maturity status may affect the changes observed to physical performance across players within the same age group (Asadi *et al.*, 2018; Dobbs *et al.*, 2020), thereby masking the extent physical performance changes are due to training alone. Whilst the magnitude of change may depend on an individual's maturation stage, physical performance changes may be observed in youth in as little as 6 weeks following physical development specific training (Moran *et al.*, 2017b; Radnor, Lloyd and Oliver, 2017). In addition, over ~2–5 years in the absence of specific training targeting physical development, changes in maturation alone may exert an influence on performance test outputs (Meyers *et al.*, 2016; Vääntinen *et al.*, 2011), or while combined with sport specific training (Duarte *et al.*, 2018; Sander *et al.*, 2013; Vääntinen *et al.*, 2011). Therefore, it is reasonable to state that maturation and participation in soccer specific training led to changes in physical capabilities over time in combination and separately. Therefore, the aims of this study were to determine changes in physical performance over a 7–8-month period in youth soccer players at a professional club. In addition, an age-matched control group from an amateur club not participating in a structured strength and conditioning programme was

evaluated in an attempt to quantify the change to physical capabilities attributed to maturation and sport participation only.

6.3 Methods

6.3.1 Experimental approach to the problem

This study employed a longitudinal and cross-sectional experimental design. Two age groups (U14s and U15s at study start) from a professional (PSA) and an amateur (ASA) soccer academy (four cohorts in total) completed speed, jump and power tests at two time points approximately 7–8 months apart and were pooled into the analysis for each group. Due to restricted contact time, it was not possible to conduct all performance tests on the same day, therefore different days/training weeks were utilised. However, the duration between performance tests did not differ than any more than one month.

6.3.2 Participants

Seventy youth soccer players (Table 6.1 displays participant descriptive statistics) participated in this study. The ASA group did not participate in regular supervised strength- or power-based training. The PSA group was routinely involved in 3 separate athletic development-based sessions for a total of 2 hours per week. These consisted of 2 sessions conducted prior to regular pitch-based training which included strength, power, and movement mechanics training. An additional gym-based strength session was also conducted once per week (Figure 6.1). Loading during these sessions was self-determined by the participant and followed stepwise increments in volume (e.g., ranging from 2 sets of 6 to 3 sets of 10 repetitions). The PSA group participated in 5 pitch-based sessions per week for a total of ~6 hours compared to 2 sessions for a total of 3 hours per week for the ASA group. Both groups competed in one match per week on average. All procedures were conducted in accordance with the declaration of Helsinki and were approved by an institutional Ethics Board prior to study initiation (Appendices 3, 4 and 6). Chapter 3.1 outlines the procedures for all anthropometric and maturity related measurements and calculations.

Example pre-training session

Exercise category	Exercise grouping	Example exercise
Mobility	Thoracic/lumbar spine	Quadruped rotations
	Hip	Spiderman rotations
	Hamstring	Supine knee bend-to-straight
	Ankle	Ankle rocks
Activation	Hip	Lateral lunge
	Knee	Clock squats
	Hamstring	Isometric hamstring bridges
	Calf complex	Calf raises
Movement mechanics	Closed drill	Wall drive switches
	Open drill	Partner 10m chases
Plyometrics	Frontal	Lateral hurdle hops
	Sagittal	Box jump
	Transverse	Squat jump and turn

Example strength session

Exercise category	Example exercise	Example volume load (sets x reps)
Football Strength	Rear-foot elevated split squat	3 x 6
Robustness	Dumbbell box step-ups	3 x 6
Acceleration	Barbell glute bridge	3 x 8
Max speed	Assisted nordics	4 x 4
Change of direction	Copenhagen holds	3 x 20sec
Ankle	Single leg calf raise	3 x 10
Core	6 exercises	2–3 minute circuit

Figure 6.1: Example training schedule and athletic development sessions for the PSA group. **Key:** symbols in order of appearance (left to right): rest day; pre-training session; pitch-based session; strength session.

Table 6.1: Participant characteristics at both timepoints. Values are presented as mean \pm SD.

	Professional soccer academy		Amateur soccer academy	
	T1	T2	T1	T2
Age (years)	13.9 \pm 0.6	14.5 \pm 0.6	14.2 \pm 0.8	14.7 \pm 0.8
% estimated adult height	91.7 \pm 3.1	94.0 \pm 2.8	94.8 \pm 3.2	95.9 \pm 3.0
Stature (cm)	163.2 \pm 9.8	168.0 \pm 9.1	168.9 \pm 10.8	169.9 \pm 10.5
Mass (kg)	51.9 \pm 7.8	55.8 \pm 7.5	59.9 \pm 13.2	60.4 \pm 14.1

6.4 Procedures

6.4.1 Isometric squat test

See section 3.2.3.

6.4.2 Counter-movement jump

See section 3.2.1.

6.4.3 Sprint assessment

See section 3.2.4.

6.4.4 Monitoring of external load during pitch-based training sessions

External load was monitored during pitch-based training sessions for both PSA and ASA to provide a general overview of physical outputs throughout the training week. Training load metrics included total distance (m), absolute high speed (> 5.5 m/s) running distance, sprint distance (> 7 m/s), maximum velocity (m/s), high intensity (> 2 m/s) acceleration efforts and high intensity deceleration (< -2 m/s) efforts. External loads from a typical in-season training week were monitored using Catapult Vector S7 unit GPS technology (Catapult, Melbourne, Australia; reliability statistics can be viewed in works by Crang *et al.* (2022)). Each participant was assigned a GPS unit, which was embedded in a vest worn the during the training sessions. Outdoor GPS measurements were measured at 18 Hz with a local positioning factor of 10 Hz

and integrated 100 Hz accelerometer. GPS data was downloaded using the Catapult Openfield (version 3.7.3) software and stored on the online cloud storage platform for further analysis.

6.4.5 Statistical analysis

A linear mixed-effects model was used to evaluate the changes in physical performances between the two testing time points as detailed below:

$$Y_i = \beta_0 + \beta_{1team} + \beta_{2-3testing\ session} + \beta_{4\%EAH} + \varepsilon_i$$

β_0 represents the overall grand intercept and ε_i the residual error of the model. Team (β_1 ; categorical variable with 2 levels: PSA and ASA), testing session (β_{2-3} ; categorical variable with 2 levels: testing session 1 [T1] and 2 [T2]), and EAH (β_4 ; discrete variable ≤ 1.0) were treated as predictors in the model where significance for each test indicated an effect on physical test performance (Y ; i : individual participant). A team*session interaction was analysed to determine if changes differed between teams. Lastly random effects were assumed for individual participants. Analysis was performed in R language and environment for statistical computing using the *lme4*, *lmerTest*, *emmeans*, and *ggeffects* packages while model assumptions were checked using the *performance* package (version 4.0.5, R Core Team, Vienna, Austria). Interpretation of results will favour utilising testing change estimates as opposed to dichotomously evaluating performance change through p values which may mask meaningful performance changes.

6.5 Results

Mean and standard deviation of performance test outputs for both teams are presented in Table 6.2. PSA on average improved (208.24 N; 95%CI: 17.47–399.01 N) PF values to a greater extent compared to the ASA between timepoints (Table 6.3). Maturation had a main effect on PF values (Table 6.3), on average displaying a 72.25 N (95%CI: 35.46–109.04 N) increase in PF for every 1% increment in %EAH. An example of this relationship (Table 6.3) for PF is below:

$$\text{Predicted PF value for PSA based off \%EAH} = -4327.08 + (\%EAH * 72.25)$$

Table 6.2: Physical testing results at both timepoints. Values are presented as mean ± SD.

	PSA		ASA	
	T1	T2	T1	T2
PF (N)	2321 ± 440	2259 ± 461	1863 ± 444	2037 ± 559
rPF (N/kg)	44.37 ± 5.86	38.09 ± 6.12	31.38 ± 5.30	33.55 ± 6.35
CMJ (cm)	29.06 ± 5.13	32.31 ± 5.69	29.21 ± 6.71	30.53 ± 5.35
10m sprint (s)	1.79 ± 0.09	1.75 ± 0.11	1.84 ± 0.10	1.82 ± 0.08
20m sprint (s)	3.18 ± 0.17	3.11 ± 0.19	3.17 ± 0.19	3.14 ± 0.13
30m sprint (s)	4.54 ± 0.26	4.40 ± 0.28	4.47 ± 0.29	4.43 ± 0.17

Key: PF: peak force; rPF: relative peak force; N/kg: newton per kilogram of body mass.

Table 6.3: Main effects and interaction for changes in performance measures where values are representative of the ASA group compared to that of the PSG.

Performance measure/metric	Predictor	Estimate (95% CI)	<i>p</i>
Isometric squat peak force (N)	(Intercept)	-4327 (-7715--939)	0.013
	Team	-649.52 (-914.23--384.82)	< 0.001
	Time	-201.05 (-357.14--44.96)	0.012
	Maturation (%EAH)	72.25 (35.46--109.04)	< 0.001
	Team*Time	208.24 (17.47--399.01)	0.033
Isometric squat relative peak force (N/kg)	(Intercept)	43.07 (-4.98--91.13)	0.078
	Team	-12.92 (-16.68--9.17)	< 0.001
	Time	-5.88 (-8.07--3.69)	< 0.001
	Maturation (%EAH)	0.01 (-0.51--0.53)	< 0.001
	Team*Time	7.01 (4.35--9.68)	< 0.001
CMJ Height (cm)	(Intercept)	-53.90 (-96.38--11.42)	0.014
	Team	-2.09 (-5.43--1.25)	0.216
	Time	1.31 (-3.49--0.87)	0.235
	Maturation (%EAH)	0.91 (0.44--1.37)	< 0.001
	Team*Time	-2.79 (-5.54--0.04)	0.047
10m Speed (s)	(Intercept)	3.64 (3.05--4.23)	< 0.001
	Team	0.11 (0.06--0.16)	< 0.001
	Time	0.01 (-0.02--0.04)	0.574
	Maturation (%EAH)	-0.02 (-0.03--0.01)	< 0.001
	Team*Time	-0.00 (-0.04--0.04)	0.996
20m Speed (s)	(Intercept)	5.84 (4.68--7.00)	< 0.001
	Team	0.07 (-0.02--0.16)	0.108
	Time	0.02 (-0.03--0.06)	0.487
	Maturation (%EAH)	-0.03 (-0.04--0.07)	< 0.001
	Team*Time	0.01 (-0.04--0.07)	0.640
30m Speed (s)	(Intercept)	9.36 (7.77--10.94)	< 0.001
	Team	0.08 (-0.04--0.21)	0.191
	Time	-0.00 (-0.07--0.14)	0.882
	Maturation (%EAH)	-0.05 (-0.07--0.04)	< 0.001
	Team*Time	0.07 (-0.01--0.14)	0.076

$$\text{Predicted PF value for ASA based off \%EAH} = -4327.08 + (\%EAH * 72.25) - 649.52$$

For example, using the average %EAH from T2 (94%, table 6.1), an estimated CMJ height for a PSA player would be as follows:

$$-53.90 + (94 * 0.91) = 31.6\text{cm}$$

All other relationships between predictor variables and performance test changes are displayed in Table 6.3.

The average weekly pitch-based training GPS outputs for both sets of players is displayed in Table 6.4.

6.6 Discussion

The main aim of this study was to evaluate physical performance changes in elite youth soccer players following a 7–8-month period, a duration similar to that of a typical season length. In addition, this study aimed to compare physical performance changes between youth soccer players from a professional and amateur club in ISqT, CMJ, 10 m, 20 m, and 30 m speed over a period of approximately 7–8 months. The primary finding was that inclusion in a professional academy promotes greater development (see Table 6.3) of force production capabilities (PF), relative maximal force production capabilities (rPF) in the ISqT, and CMJ height over a 7–8-month period after controlling for maturation, compared to that of amateur soccer club players. In addition, it appears that maturation was the key determinant of overall physical performance change (see Table 6.3). Lastly, after controlling for maturation, the ISqT outputs in all measured metrics and 10 m sprint performance were superior in the PSA compared to the ASA regardless of the testing timepoint (Table 6.3).

The data from the current study demonstrates greater improvements in ISqT PF, and rPF of 208 N, 7.01 N/kg respectively for the PSA compared to the ASA. In addition, CMJ improved 2.79 cm, 20 m speed 0.01 s, and 30 m speed 0.07 s more for the PSA compared to the ASA, whereas 10 m speed showed no difference (Table 6.3). To the authors knowledge, this study is unique, due to the comparison of physical development in a group of highly-trained youth soccer players affiliated to a professional football club that participate in both gym and pitch-based sessions to that of an amateur soccer club who partake in regular, structured pitch-based

Table 6.4: Average GPS training outputs of a typical training week from both clubs.

Average Weekly Training GPS	PSA	ASA
Total Pitch Sessions	5	2
Total Distance (m)	22149	9533
High Speed Distance (m)	600	222
Sprint Distance (m)	110	30
Maximum Velocity (m/s)	7.9	6.8
High Intensity Accelerations	220	15
High Intensity Decelerations	185	15

soccer specific training only, whilst controlling for the influence of maturation.

In addition, lower body maximal isometric force has been shown to improve in highly trained players compared to an age-matched control group, both over the course of a playing season (Morris *et al.*, 2018a), and a 2-year period (Vänttinen *et al.*, 2011). In contrast to the present results, Morris *et al.* (2018a) demonstrated a larger change in CMJ height in post-PHV PSA compared to an age-matched control group while controlling for maturation and initial test values. However, while controlling for the same variables, Wrigley *et al.* (2018a) demonstrated a greater change in a professional compared to a control group, both of which estimated as circa-PHV at the beginning of their 3-year study. In addition, Morris *et al.* (2018a) also evaluated differences in circa-PHV professional and control groups and found greater change in the professional group. Therefore, it is possible changes in CMJ height are greater as a result of training in circa-PHV individuals compared to those who are post-PHV (Malina *et al.*, 2004). Nonetheless, the current study demonstrates an average improvement of 2.79 cm more in the PSA compared to the ASA (Table 6.3), which has been suggested as meaningful (Morris *et al.*, 2018a).

Sprint performance changes in the present study displayed smaller differences between groups compared to that of some previous research (Sander *et al.*, 2013; Wrigley *et al.*, 2014). However, the study period of previous research was 2/3 years in duration, and any chronic effects therefore had up to 2 years longer than the current study to elicit an effect on sprint performance. In addition, previous studies (Morris *et al.*, 2018a; Wrigley *et al.*, 2014) often included school children not participating in soccer via structured training within an academy setting as controls. This may explain the contrasting findings between this study and the previous evidence.

Physical performance indicators of soccer tend to consistently include sprint performance (Unnithan *et al.*, 2012) and it is possible sprinting capabilities improve through soccer participation, due to the necessity to produce high intensity running activities during soccer play (Table 6.2; Goto, Morris and Nevill, 2015b). This may be a primary reason for some subtle differences in results of the current study, and that of previous research (Duarte *et al.*, 2018; Morris *et al.*, 2018a; Sander *et al.*, 2013; Vääntinen *et al.*, 2011; Wrigley *et al.*, 2014). For example, the accelerated development of maximal strength over a 2-year period in highly trained youth soccer players undertaking strength and power training compared to those participating in soccer training only has been demonstrated previously (Sander *et al.*, 2013). However, this research did not control for the impact of maturation on physical performance change.

In the current study, it is unclear whether the additional strength, power, and pitch-based training has a positive effect on PSA sprint performance in the stipulated timeframe. Indeed, higher on-pitch training volumes often experienced by youth PSA (Table 6.4) has been suggested as detrimental to sprint capabilities development, but not strength-based performance (Morris *et al.*, 2018a). Sprint performance has been shown to decrease due to high training loads (Noon *et al.*, 2015), potentially as a result of insufficient recovery (Banister *et al.*, 1975), rationalising the suggestion to avoid high workloads in the developing adolescent athlete, regardless of maturation status (Gabbett *et al.*, 2014). In agreement with this notion, Sander *et al.* (2013) demonstrate differences in sprint performance independent of on-pitch locomotive differences as a result of strength training. This study was, however, conducted over a longer period of time than the current study as mentioned previously. Conversely, it could also be argued that the training volumes the PSA players were exposed to throughout the current study period may have hindered sprint development, and reducing these may actually improve sprint performance. Further research controlling for the aforementioned methodological contributors to change in sprint performance may therefore be required.

Due to the potential influence of maturation on physical performance (Dobbs *et al.*, 2020; Lloyd *et al.*, 2016; Meylan *et al.*, 2014; Moran *et al.*, 2018), the current and previous research (Morris *et al.*, 2018a; Wrigley *et al.*, 2014) opted to control for the impact of this variable on physical performance in longitudinal research. Due to the vast physiological changes which occur due to growth and maturation processes (Malina, Bouchard and Bar-Or, 2004), performance improvements may be augmented in adolescent populations (Duarte *et al.*, 2018;

Morris *et al.*, 2018a). Indeed, it appears from the results presented here (Table 6.3) that maturation at this chronological age exerts a positive effect on all evaluated measures of strength and power development. As a result, it is recommended that %EAH form the basis of performance prediction equations at this biological age (an example is provided in section 6.5). Indeed, differences in maturation status (e.g., pre-, circa-, post-PHV) have been shown to result in different magnitudes of change over the course of a playing season (Morris *et al.*, 2018a). While the influx of circulating levels of hormones, primarily testosterone (Malina, Bouchard and Bar-Or, 2004; Murray and Clayton, 2013), due to the onset of puberty do not directly have an effect on physical performance, changes which occur as a result of this change (e.g., increased fat-free muscle mass) have been shown as strong predictors of strength and power related development in adolescent soccer players (see section 2.4; Vääntinen *et al.*, 2011). It is therefore surprising that the PSA did not display greater improvements in speed and power related performance, due to this interaction of training and maturation. Therefore, research should quantify the change in physiological characteristics (e.g., muscle thickness) which underpin strength and power development and compare this change to that in performance measures.

6.7 Practical implications

The current study provides further evidence of the longitudinal improvement in physical performance characteristics in youth soccer players. Comparative changes between PSA and ASA indicate the efficacy of professional soccer academy training practices augmented by growth and maturation. However, it should be noted that the primary aim of strength and conditioning programmes for individuals of similar chronological age as the PSA at the study commencement is to develop movement proficiency and technical exercise competency as opposed to performance improvements (Lloyd *et al.*, 2015; Ryan *et al.*, 2018). This may have contributed to the lack of performance change observed in some tests (Table 6.4). In conclusion, the current study hints that physical performance related change in adolescent soccer players varies depending on the physical metric evaluated, and may be dependent upon change in maturity status, or a combination of change in maturity and exposure to strength and power-based training.

6.8 Thesis implications

The study described here in Chapter 6 illustrates the development of physical performance over a 7–8-month period using repeated testing of relevant physical performance capabilities. The final study in this thesis was originally planned to evaluate the underpinning physiological mechanisms which could partly explain the performance changes, or lack thereof, displayed in the current study. This was intended to be evaluated through imaging muscle morphological characteristics via sonography. However, logistical constraints imposed by real-world applied environments negated the potential to synchronise physical performance testing and muscle imaging, thereby eliminating any possibility of statistically analysing the impact of any interactions between the two. However, it remained possible to carry out the ultrasound assessments and to describe muscle morphological changes over an 8-month period only in the U16 age group analysed in Chapters 4, 5, and 6. Based on the average %EAH in Chapter 7, the participants are post-PHV, meaning this study design allowed for the influence of the training stimulus to be explored in the absence of a statistically significant maturation effect.

Chapter 7.0

Morphological changes in the Vastus Lateralis of highly-trained youth soccer players: a longitudinal evaluation

7.1 Abstract

Changes in physical performance is likely influenced by changes of the musculo-skeletal system. Strength, speed, and power are important physical contributors to physical performance in youth soccer. The aim of this study was to determine the change in vastus lateralis (VL) muscle thickness (MT), fibre pennation angle (FPA) and fascicle length (FL) over an 8-month period in adolescent soccer players when exposed to both a training- and match-load stimulus. MT, FPA, and FL displayed no differences over time ($p > 0.05$), while relative FL (rFL) was statistically significantly longer following the study duration. In addition, no interactions with maturity were observed for any of the morphological measures. In conclusion, the training stimulus detailed in the current study was likely insufficient to elicit change to the measured musculature.

7.2 Introduction

Strength, speed, and power development is underpinned by neuromuscular and morphological adaptations (Folland and Williams, 2007; Kraemer and Ratamess, 2005). The underpinning muscle morphological adaptations to strength, speed, and power training can be explained in-part by changes in size and architecture in trained individuals (Mitchell *et al.*, 2011; Wisdom, Delp and Kuhl, 2015). In addition, as suggested in Section 2.1, these underpinning contributors to muscular strength, speed, and power likely primarily enhance the force generation capabilities at different contraction velocities of the working musculature.

Muscle morphology changes in youth are impacted by modifiable factors such as measurement site (Kanehisa *et al.*, 2006) and method (see Section 2.5.1; Legerlotz, Smith and Hing, 2010), intervention duration (see Section 2.5.1), and periodisation type (Gavanda *et al.*, 2019). Additionally non-modifiable factors such as an individual's maturation stage (Kanehisa *et al.*,

2003; Radnor *et al.*, 2020), current (Vanrenterghem *et al.*, 2017) and previous (McKinlay *et al.*, 2018; Secomb *et al.*, 2017) training exposure, and also sex (Kanehisa *et al.*, 2006), impact the magnitude of change to musculature in youth (see Section 2.5 for a full review). For example, it has been consistently demonstrated that youth can achieve improvements in morphological adaptations to training (Mersmann *et al.*, 2017), which are likely further enhanced by the interaction with maturity status especially among mid- and post-PHV groups (Radnor *et al.*, 2020). Indeed, maturation has been suggested to lead to increases in muscle volume, length, and CSA throughout adolescence (O'Brien *et al.*, 2010a; Radnor *et al.*, 2020) which drive the improvement of force production capabilities in this cohort (see Section 2.5.1; Tonson *et al.*, 2008). Furthermore, FPA and FL have been suggested to increase from childhood to early adolescence, reaching near-adult sizes at adolescence (Binzoni *et al.*, 2001).

Morphological adaptations include changes in muscle size, fibre length, and pennation angle (O'Brien *et al.*, 2010b), with each of these adaptations suggested to impact contraction force and/or velocity (Murtagh *et al.*, 2018b). Increasing muscle thickness (MT), size or volume is proposed to positively impact strength-based activities (O'Brien *et al.*, 2009), due to the addition of a greater number of sarcomeres in parallel (Goldspink, 1985; Johnson and Klueber, 1991) which contributes towards greater force and power production capabilities (Narici *et al.*, 1996) (see Section 2.1). In addition, quadriceps CSA is related to power output during a CMJ in active youth (12.1 ± 1.1 years), with increments in muscle mass suggested as necessary for progressions in movement performance in this cohort (Gillen *et al.*, 2019).

In view of the rapid and forceful contractions associated with the physical demands of soccer match-play, adaptations of the muscle architecture, specifically changes in muscle fibre pennation angle (FPA) and length (FL), are contributing mechanisms. Increases in muscle FPA is associated with an increase in force outputs due to an increase in CSA (Aagaard *et al.*, 2001), and amount of contractile material attached to the aponeurosis (Alexander and Vernon, 1975). However, as mentioned previously (see Section 2.5.2.1), increases in FPA may also result in a decrease in contraction velocity (Alexander and Vernon, 1975), assuming MT and FL remain unchanged. Furthermore, larger muscle FPA has been shown as inversely correlated with RFD (Degens, Erskine and Morse, 2009), and may adversely impact horizontal-based jumps, but positively influence vertical-based jumps (Murtagh *et al.*, 2018b). Indeed, larger decrements in FPA has been shown to occur as a consequence of training involving ballistic-type movements

(-11.6%) compared to resistance training (-6.2%) in competitive youth (14 ± 1.8 years) athletes (Secomb *et al.*, 2017).

Longer muscle FL is related to greater contraction velocities (Stafilidis and Arampatzis, 2007) due to the potential for a greater number of sarcomeres in series within the fibre (Goldspink, 1985). Research has shown increases in muscle FL following general resistance training (Secomb *et al.*, 2017), specific resistance training protocols (Lacome *et al.*, 2019), and gymnastics and plyometric training (Secomb *et al.*, 2017) in youth athletes. Indeed, FL is suggested as positively associated with sprint capabilities (Abe, Kumagai and Brechue, 2000; Kumagai *et al.*, 2000), an important performance indicator for soccer performance (Bangsbo, Nørregaard and Thorsø, 1991; Bloomfield, Polman and O'Donoghue, 2007; Mendez-Villanueva *et al.*, 2013; Reilly *et al.*, 2000; Unnithan *et al.*, 2012). Similarly, Murtagh *et al.* (2018b) demonstrate a significant ($p = 0.031$) relationship ($r = 0.482$) between FL and peak vertical power obtained during a unilateral horizontal CMJ, a metric impacted by both force output and velocity (see Section 2.1).

In addition, in soccer cohorts, training exposure may also contribute to a change in muscle morphological characteristics such as increments in MT, FPA, and FL (Mendiguchia *et al.*, 2020; Ripley *et al.*, 2023). Despite this, few studies thus far have evaluated the combined effect of specific strength and conditioning, and sport-specific locomotor training on morphological adaptations across a regular soccer season (see Section 2.5). Therefore, the aim of this investigation was to investigate the changes in muscle MT, FPA and FL of the vastus lateralis (VL) in highly-trained youth soccer players participating in a structured strength and conditioning programme over an 8-month period (for example see Figure 6.1).

7.3 Methods

7.3.1 Experimental approach to the problem

This study used a longitudinal observational study design. One age group (mean \pm SD: T1: 14.9 ± 0.2 years, $96.4 \pm 1.7\%$ EAH; T2: 15.5 ± 0.3 years, $97.7 \pm 1.4\%$ EAH) from a professional soccer academy underwent lower limbs' muscle ultrasound imaging in-season before and after an 8-month training period.

7.3.2 Participants

Sixteen youth soccer players participated in this study. Due to injury ($n = 2$), absence from training ($n = 1$) or incomplete data ($n = 1$) four participants were removed from the final sample (participants' characteristics at each timepoint are provided in Table 7.1). The participants' training routine has been described earlier in the text (see Section 6.3.2 and Figure 6.1). All procedures were conducted in accordance with the declaration of Helsinki and were approved by an institutional Ethics Board prior to study initiation. Chapter 3.1 outlines the procedures for all anthropometric and maturity related measurements and calculations.

7.4 Procedures

7.4.1 Vastus lateralis muscle imaging

Due to time constraints induced by the global COVID-19 pandemic, training to conduct ultrasonography assessments was not possible for the author of this thesis. Instead, muscle imaging was conducted by a trained researcher (Dr Hannah Lithgow). Imaging scanning was performed with participants in the supine position. They were asked to relax their lower limbs' muscles and care was taken to position the limb and apply pressure with the transducer on the scanned muscle in a consistent manner, thereby limiting compression of the muscle. A water-soluble transmission gel was applied to the transducer prior to contact with the skin.

Morphological variables of interest in the current study were MT, FPA, and FL. An exemplar image is provided in Figure 7.1 Transverse images of the right VL muscle were scanned from each player with a portable brightness mode (Bmode) ultrasound-imaging device (Echoblaster 128 Ext; Telemed Ltd, Vilnius, Lithuania) using a 7.5 Hz linear array transducer. Prior to attaining images, anatomical locations were identified and marked with a skin marker. Measurements were acquired at mid distance between the upper pole of the patella and the

Table 7.1: Participant characteristics.

	T1	T2
Age	14.9 ± 0.2	15.5 ± 0.3
%Estimated Adult height	96 ± 1.7%	98 ± 2.9%
Height (cm)	172.2 ± 10.1	176.4 ± 10.4
Mass (kg)	57.1 ± 8.7	62.2 ± 9.1

Data is provided as mean ± standard deviation.

Figure 7.1: Exemplar muscle image obtained via muscle ultrasound assessment in the current study. Method of calculating each variable is described in the text.

anterior iliac crest, and 10% (of thigh circumference) lateral to the mid-thigh anatomical line (Gavanda *et al.*, 2019). Intra-researcher within-session reliability displayed acceptable reliability for MT (CV: T1: 1.1%; T2: 1.2%), FPA (CV: T1: 2.4%; T2: 2.5%) and FL (CV: T1: 1.6%; T2: 5.6%) within both testing sessions. In addition, it was not possible to determine the between-session reliability of ultrasound measurements due to time restrictions. However, previous research displays acceptable between-day reliability statistics for the measurement of MT (ICC: 0.94–0.98; CV: 2.1–3.1%), FL (ICC: 0.87–0.96; CV: 4.5–6.3%), and FPA (ICC: 0.85–0.96; CV: 4.1–6.0%) in youth populations (Legerlotz, Smith and Hing, 2010).

Vastus lateralis muscle thickness was defined as the distance between the superficial aponeurosis and the deep aponeurosis of the vastus lateralis muscle and used to calculate relative muscle thickness (rMT ; VL MT [cm] \div thigh circumference [cm]). Fascicle length (FL) was defined as the fascicular distance between the superficial and deep aponeurosis (Erskine *et al.*, 2009), with FL used further to calculate relative FL (rFL ; VL FL [cm] \div thigh length [cm]). Pennation angle (FPA) was defined as the angle formed between the muscle fascicle and the deep aponeurosis (Erskine *et al.*, 2009). Three measures of FL and FPA were taken from each image, with the mean reported. All measurements and subsequent image analyses were performed by the same researcher (HL) 8 months apart.

7.4.2 Monitoring of external load during pitch-based training sessions

See section 6.4.3 for measurement methodology. Table 7.2 shows a typical structure for each ‘main’ pitch-based session; note: session design as displayed in Table 7.2 stayed constant throughout the study i.e., no differing periodisation was introduced. Figure 7.2 displays session targeted physical components and average locomotor data from a typical training week over the study period.

7.4.3 Statistical analysis

A linear mixed effects model was used to evaluate the impact of time and maturity status on muscle morphology:

$$Y_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{-testing session number} + \beta_3 \%EAH + \epsilon_i$$

Time (categorical variable with two levels: T1 and T2) and maturation (%EAH; discrete variable) were included as fixed effects. Participant was included as a random effects ensuring individual differences in the dependent variable at T1 were accounted for. Analysis was performed in R using the *lmerTest* package. Model assumptions were checked using the *performance* package (version 4.0.5, R Core Team, Vienna, Austria).

7.5 Results

Table 7.2 illustrates VL imagining values, and percentage change between T1 and T2. %EAH was significantly ($p < 0.001$) higher (+ 1.3%, 95%CI: 1–1.7%) at T2 compared to T1. Table 7.3 shows the output of the mixed model analysis.

Table 7.2: Average drill information from pitch-based training from a typical training microcycle.

Drill Category	Duration (mins)
Warm-Up Including Athletic Development	15-20
Passing Practice	15-20
Game-Related Practice	20-25
Small-Sided Games	20-25

Figure 7.2: Example physical targets of each pitch-based training session as described in Section 6 with average outputs across the study duration. **Key:** symbols in order of appearance (left to right): mechanical loading; active recovery; distance at high-intensities (> 5.5m/s); reactions.

Table 7.3: Mean VL muscle characteristics and change from testing point 1 and 2 (T1 and T2).

Measure	T1	T2	% Change
Thigh Length (cm)	45.3 ± 3.6	45.8 ± 3.5	1.0%
Thigh Circumference (cm)	48.4 ± 3.0	50.4 ± 3.1	4.2%
Muscle Thickness (mm)	20.1 ± 4.7	22.1 ± 4.1	9.9%
Fascicle Length (mm)	8.5 ± 1.5	9.5 ± 0.9	11.6%
Pennation angle (°)	13.9 ± 1.6	14.2 ± 1.8	2.2%
Relative Muscle Thickness	0.41 ± 0.08	0.44 ± 0.06	5.7%
Relative Fascicle Length	0.19 ± 0.03	0.21 ± 0.03	11.1%

Table 7.4: Main effects and interaction for changes in sonography measures where values are representative of T1 compared to that of T2.

Performance measure/metric	Predictor	Estimate	<i>p</i>
Muscle thickness (mm)	(Intercept)	-108.06 (-243.84–27.73)	0.112
	Time	0.32 (-2.19–2.83)	0.793
	Maturation (%EAH)	1.33 (-0.08–2.74)	0.063
Fibre pennation angle (°)	(Intercept)	0.50 (-48.67–49.67)	0.983
	Time	0.12 (-0.62–0.86)	0.733
	Maturation (%EAH)	0.14 (-0.37–0.65)	0.575
Fascicle length (cm)	(Intercept)	-15.90 (-56.32–24.51)	0.420
	Time	0.68 (-0.19–1.54)	0.118
	Maturation (%EAH)	0.25 (-0.17–0.67)	0.221
Relative muscle thickness	(Intercept)	-0.12 (-0.34–0.11)	0.280
	Time	0.00 (0.00–0.00)	0.912
	Maturation (%EAH)	0.00 (0.00–0.00)	0.151
Relative fascicle length	(Intercept)	0.35 (-0.53–1.24)	0.412
	Time	0.02 (0.00–0.04)	0.034
	Maturation (%EAH)	-0.00 (-0.01–0.01)	0.698
Thigh circumference (cm)	(Intercept)	-33.77 (-107.24–39.69)	0.348
	Time	0.93 (-0.20–2.06)	0.102
	Maturation (%EAH)	0.85 (0.09–1.62)	0.030
Thigh length (cm)	(Intercept)	-0.25 (-44.18–44.32)	0.991
	Time	-0.13 (-0.76–0.50)	0.674
	Maturation (%EAH)	0.47 (0.01–0.94)	0.045

7.6 Discussion

The aim of this study was to investigate changes in VL thickness and architecture following an 8-month period in youth soccer players. VL MT did not increase over the study period, and no interaction was found between time and maturation. However, MT changes due to maturation may be meaningful despite the lack of significance (Table 7.2), and may have been impacted by the relatively small ($n = 12$) sample size. The effects of maturation on force production capabilities are deemed greater compared to that of contraction velocities (Radnor *et al.*, 2022). Increased circulating testosterone and growth hormone during PHV result in the development of muscle volume during PWV (see Section 2.5.1 for further discussion; McCarthy *et al.*, 2014), which likely lead to greater force production capabilities (Stock *et al.*, 2017). For example, following an 8-month period, the average change in participant %EAH was approximately 2% (from 96% at T1 to 98% at T2; Table 7.1). The participants were therefore post-PHV (Parr *et al.*, 2020) at both timepoints and presumably around the initiation of their PWV (McCarthy *et al.*, 2014). Considering the estimates provided in Table 7.2, this change in maturation would result, on average, in a change of MT from 19.62–22.28mm:

Predicted VL MT value based off %EAH = $-108.06 + (\%EAH * 1.33)$:

$$T1: \quad -108.06 + (96 * 1.33) = 19.62\text{mm}$$

$$T2: \quad -108.06 + (98 * 1.33) = 22.28\text{mm}$$

Therefore, for every 1% increase in %EAH, an estimated 1.33mm increase in MT is expected to occur (Table 7.3). Whether this change can be considered as meaningful requires further evaluation. Percentage changes (Table 7.3) observed for VL MT values in the current study were similar to that of previous research (Gavanda *et al.*, 2019; Sekine, Hoshikawa and Hirose, 2019). However, in contrast with previous research (Gavanda *et al.*, 2019; McKinlay *et al.*, 2018; Secomb *et al.*, 2015b; Sekine, Hoshikawa and Hirose, 2019) the change in MT values displayed here did not reach significance (Table 7.4). There are many reasons for this difference such as differences in statistical approaches adopted between studies, the small sample size of the current study, and the large between-individual variation in VL MT change (percentage change range: -15.7–50.5%). Regardless, given the between-individual variability of the impact of maturation on muscle characteristics (Radnor *et al.*, 2020), youth training programmes should incorporate appropriate training stimulus to ensure skeletal muscle development across the cohort as a whole, as maturation processes may not result in similar

muscle development for each individual (see Section 5.2.1). The results presented here (Table 7.2) also display a statistically significant increase in thigh circumference between testing points possibly attributable to changes in maturation (Table 7.3), tentatively indicating an increase in total thigh musculature as displayed previously (Table 2.1; Kanehisa *et al.*, 2003; Kanehisa *et al.*, 2006; Mersmann *et al.*, 2017). Indeed, this study used a single muscle and measurement site (e.g., 50% of femur length) to indicate muscle development which may mask total quadriceps development (Kanehisa *et al.*, 2003; Kanehisa *et al.*, 2006; O'Brien *et al.*, 2010b).

In agreement with some previous literature (Secomb *et al.*, 2015b; Secomb *et al.*, 2017), there were non-significant changes in FPA from T1 to T2 (Table 7.1) in the current study. Secomb *et al.* (2015b) evaluated changes to VL muscle structure longitudinally in youth of similar chronological age (15.1 ± 1.4 years) as the participants of the current study and found non-significant change in FPA (Table 2.4). However, this study was conducted across a shorter intervention period of 7 weeks, which precludes direct comparisons. Finally, in a similar study Secomb *et al.* (2017) observed a statistically significant decrease (-11.6%) in VL FPA following 7 weeks of gymnastic and plyometric training in a group of competitive surfers aged 14 ± 1.8 years, but to a lesser extent following resistance training (-6.2%). Therefore, it appears that training modality, contraction time and movement velocities (e.g., through sprints, high threshold plyometrics [e.g., bounds] etc.) would induce morphological specific adaptations. The training stimuli in the current study (Tables 6.4, 7.1, and 7.2; Figures 6.1 and 7.2) likely had insufficient amounts of high velocity training to result in changes in muscle architecture to reflect this (Alexander and Vernon, 1975).

While the current results display no change in FL, rFL displayed a main effect for time over the study period (Table 7.3). Therefore, it is recommended future research incorporates relative measures of MT and FL to normalise muscle morphology measures to indicators of growth and maturation given the observed disproportionate rate of growth of the skeletal system compared to skeletal muscle (Kubo *et al.*, 2001). In addition, an increase of FL have been previously observed among adolescent soccer players following specific training protocols (Lacome *et al.*, 2019). FL is an important consideration for applied practitioners due to its positive relationship with muscle fibre shortening velocity (Thom *et al.*, 2007). Furthermore, relationships between rFL and performance in youth has previously been observed as discriminant between faster and slower swimmers (Nasirzade *et al.*, 2014), potentially highlighting a transference to global

physical performance. FL changes are suggested as independent of changes in maturity status in post-PHV adolescents (Kubo *et al.*, 2014; Radnor *et al.*, 2020), potentially due to the concurrent growth of the femur, fascicle, muscle, and tendon (O'Brien *et al.*, 2010b). It is therefore likely that changes in VL FL are more closely related to training as opposed to changes in maturation in adolescents (Kubo *et al.*, 2014; Radnor *et al.*, 2020). From the results presented here (Tables 7.1 and 7.2), it can be argued that the VL MT, FPA, or FL was not significantly altered over the study period (Table 7.3). Although MT and FL changes were not statistically significant, whether the absolute average change of 2.1 cm and 1.6 cm (respectively) is meaningful requires further evaluation. Nevertheless, this is in agreement with previous research in youth which demonstrates greater increases in MT compared to FPA (Radnor *et al.*, 2020).

The impact of pitch-based training is an additional likely contributing factor to changes in muscle characteristics in youth soccer players (Vanrenterghem *et al.*, 2017). Alongside the previously mentioned (see Section 6.6) potential interference effect of pitch-based training on physical and physiological change, pitch-based training could also result in changes to an individual's muscle structure. In agreement, Ripley *et al.* (2023) demonstrated larger changes (9.1%) in bicep femoris fascicle length following a 7-week period in collegiate team sport athletes. However, soccer specific training has previously been observed to trivially (effect size < 0.20) increase biceps femoris MT ($1.43 \pm 1.98\%$) and FPA ($1.12 \pm 3.00\%$) following a 6-week period in adult male participants (Mendiguchia *et al.*, 2020). Furthermore, the changes to biceps femoris FL displayed a trivial negative change ($0.31 \pm 1.69\%$) (Mendiguchia *et al.*, 2020). Nonetheless, changes to the musculature across both studies was more stable following specific resistance or sprint training (Mendiguchia *et al.*, 2020; Ripley *et al.*, 2023). Speculatively, this indicates the participants' exposure to specific resistance training (Figure 6.1) and/or sprint running (Tables 6.4 and 7.1; Figures 6.1 and 7.2) in the current study may have been insufficient for all participants to induce favourable adaptation (e.g., increased MT and FL), or, adaptation was blunted due to high training loads (Noon *et al.*, 2015). This may have led to the observed lack of significance despite large percentage changes in MT, FPA and FL in the current study (Table 7.1).

In conclusion, common VL sonography measures described here displayed no statistically significant changes throughout the study duration. However, relative FL change was

statistically significant highlighting a potential training-related adaptation. Nonetheless, further research is required to elucidate this question in highly-trained youth soccer players.

7.7 Practical implications

This study describes the physiological development of muscle characteristics which underpin strength and power development. Estimated values for each of the evaluated VL morphological characteristics based off %EAH can be calculated from the current results provided in Table 7.3.

Chapter 8.0

Findings, implications, limitations and identified areas for future research

The current thesis had many aims and objectives as outlined below:

- **Aim 1:** To determine the reliability of two isometric squat protocols in youth soccer players.
 - Objective 1: To determine the inter-day reliability of a pre-determined and a self-determined ISqT protocol.
 - Objective 2: Investigate the effects of familiarisation on force-time outputs of the ISqT.
 - Objective 3: To compare ISqT outputs obtained via a traditional pre-determined and a self-determined ISqT protocol.
- **Aim 2:** To explore the relationships between reliable ISqT metrics determined in study 1 and physical determinants of soccer performance.
 - Objective 1: Determine the relationship between different ISqT metrics and dynamic measures of speed and power capabilities.
 - Objective 2: Calculate how changes in ISqT performance related to changes in dynamic speed and jump performance measures.
- **Aim 3:** Examine how youth soccer players develop strength and power adaptations throughout adolescence.
 - Objective 1: Compare the changes in strength, speed, and power-based performance between professional and recreational youth soccer players.
 - Objective 3: Examine the influence of maturation as a mediating factor on the development of strength and power capabilities in well-trained and recreational youth soccer players.
- **Aim 4:** Examine the changes in underpinning physiological adaptations over time in elite youth soccer players.
 - Objective 1: Determine the changes in muscle morphology over a 9-month period in elite adolescent soccer players.

The following chapter will firstly communicate the findings from each chapter in this thesis with respect to the realisation of the aims and objectives. Secondly, this chapter aims to outline the broader implications of the results, and lastly discuss the respective limitations identifying areas for future research.

8.1 Thesis findings

Despite the extensive evidence on the reliability and validity of speed (Dugdale *et al.*, 2019; Krolo *et al.*, 2020) and power (Meylan *et al.*, 2012) measurements, less research is available detailing the repeatability of maximum strength assessments in youth (Brady, Harrison and Comyns, 2020). In fact, assessing the variability of performance testing outputs allows an individual the ability to determine the level of error associated with a performance test (Atkinson and Nevill, 1998). This may provide coaches with confidence in the reporting of actual performance change, and not change potentially attributable to measurement error (Hopkins, 2000).

In addition, youth males, particularly those participating in sport (Sander *et al.*, 2013), undergo substantial changes throughout adolescence due to the impact of growth and maturation processes which may exacerbate the variability observed in performance change (Malina, Bouchard and Bar-Or, 2004). Increased circulating anabolic hormones (Vänttinen *et al.*, 2011) and training stimuli (Sander *et al.*, 2013) may interact to induce changes in the musculoskeletal system which may positively impact global strength, speed, and power performance (Radnor *et al.*, 2020; Radnor *et al.*, 2022). Therefore, it is important the applied practitioner understands how these changes impact physical performance to better determine the resulting impact on a training programme/intervention. To this end, multiple methods of assessing an individual's biological maturity (e.g., maturity offset, percentage of estimated adult height) have been developed and evaluated (Kozieł and Malina, 2018; Malina *et al.*, 2004; Malina and Kozieł, 2014a; Malina and Kozieł, 2014b; Parr *et al.*, 2020). Data from maturity assessments may provide the applied practitioner with the ability to delineate the impact of maturity on physical performance change.

The aforementioned applied and theoretical considerations for physical performance testing informed the first methodological study of this thesis. The study outlined in Chapter 4 aimed to determine the reliability of a traditional pre-determined isometric squat protocol, whose

theoretical rationale, conceptualisation, and methodological procedures were informed by previous research as outlined in Section 2.6.0. Multiple time-epochs were evaluated in this study to allow the use of the test for monitoring of force-production capabilities across multiple different ground contact times, similar to those observed in sprinting in youth soccer. However, due to the time commitment required by practitioners to standardise the body configuration for a pre-determined isometric squat protocol, a self-determined alternative protocol was developed, which entailed the participants assuming a fully autonomous body position. Motor learning related improvements can contribute to performance changes (Drake, Kennedy and Wallace, 2017) through improvements in neurological learning and coordination. Therefore, this study also aimed to determine the number of familiarisation sessions required for data to stabilise, and finally compare outputs between the two protocols. The results of the study '*Reliability, Familiarisation Effect, and Comparisons Between a Predetermined and a Self-Determined Isometric-Squat Testing Protocol*' in chapter 4 demonstrate similar reliability between protocols, with level of reliability being metric dependent. In addition, it was shown that two testing sessions (consisting of three, 3-second efforts) was required for data to stabilise; with similar outputs between the two protocols. Therefore, aim 1 and its associated objectives were met, resulting in specific metrics which displayed acceptable reliability being preferentially selected for the next study. In addition, given the similar testing outputs and rate of familiarisation, the self-determined testing protocol was chosen for the subsequent research due to its superior timing efficiency for practitioners working within soccer and the associated time constraints of that environment.

With the findings presented in Chapter 4 demonstrating the repeatability of ISqT measures, this thesis then aimed to explore the relationships between the measures which demonstrated acceptable reliability in Chapter 4 and physical performance measures of soccer. Such knowledge may allow the calculation of the expected physical performance at a given time, such as speed, based off ISqT performance, resulting in the potential use of the ISqT for time-efficient monitoring of the physical state. Therefore, the relationships and expected change between ISqT variables and speed and power performance were evaluated in Chapter 5. This study demonstrates the relationships between ISqT variables and physical performance are metric dependent, with strongest associations with physical performance measures displayed with peak force or relative peak force (Tables 5.1 and 5.2). The results of this study presented in Chapter 5 indicate a stronger relationship between the ISqT and accelerative-type sprint running (e.g., 0-20 m) when compared to sprint running of longer distances. In addition,

statistically significant correlations between ISqT PF and CMJ height were observed (Table 5.2). Therefore, this study hints that it may be advantageous for youth soccer players to develop lower body strength. However, while a statistically significant proportion (44.1–53.8%) of the variance of sprint and jumping performance is described by ISqT performance, it was highlighted that a large amount of the variance was not attributed to ISqT performance, thus likely related to maturation status (see Section 5.6). Therefore, it is important research considers maturation when evaluating youth of this age (13.9 ± 0.6 years), as analysis was not possible in this study (see Section 5.6).

The primary purpose of the two research studies presented up until this point in the thesis was to determine which metrics of an ISqT test are reliable and are related to physical performance measures of youth soccer match play. These aims were chosen to assist the third aim of evaluating changes in strength and power characteristics of youth soccer players throughout adolescence. Additionally, it has been shown that sport participation may directly enhance physical performance characteristics, particularly when combined with growth and maturation processes (Sander *et al.*, 2013). Therefore, the second main objective of Chapter 6 was to compare physical performance changes between youth soccer players at a professional and an amateur academy, when both groups were normalised for the same maturity status. This allowed the training exposure at elite full-time youth level soccer to be compared with individuals who were systematically training, but at a recreational level. It has also been displayed thus far in the thesis the important considerations for interpreting youth physical performance change, which was illustrated as primarily being maturation (see Section 2.4). Therefore, the final objective of this chapter was to determine the influence of these factors on global strength-, speed-, and power-based performance measures.

This study, described in Chapter 6, found that the youth soccer players from the professional club developed ISqT peak and relative peak force, and counter-movement jump height to a greater extent than a control group of players of an amateur soccer academy over the 7–8-month period after controlling for maturation. When values were pooled from both testing sessions and maturation was controlled for, the youth players from the professional academy displayed greater average ISqT peak and relative peak force, and faster 10 m sprinting times (Table 6.3). However, using significance values to determine change may mask change. For example, although non-significant, on average 30 m sprint time improved by 0.07 s more over the study period for the players from the professional academy, a likely practically meaningful

change. In addition, the results from this study suggest maturation exerted an influence on all measured physical performance metrics (Table 6.3).

Originally, as displayed in Figure 1.1, the final study of this thesis aimed to determine the underpinning morphological adaptations and contextualise any observed changes to that of physical performance testing described in Chapter 6. However, due to logistical constraints which are commonplace in applied settings such as soccer, this was not possible due to a change in the testing schedule within the professional soccer academy. This then resulted in the testing of the physical performance tests described in Chapter 6 no longer aligning with that of the muscle scanning described in Chapter 7 to the extent conclusions/inferences on casual relationships between the two could not be made. Nonetheless, research into the underpinning morphological adaptations which occur in applied sport settings over durations such as evaluated in Chapter 7 are scarce and tentatively could provide the practitioner with meaningful data. Therefore, the remaining study instead aimed to describe the morphological changes to the vastus lateralis muscle in adolescent (14.9 ± 0.2 years; 96 ± 1.7 %EAH) soccer players and evaluate the impact of maturation on the change observed between timepoints.

This study described in Chapter 7 found that vastus lateralis muscle thickness, fascicle length, pennation angle, and muscle thickness expressed relative to thigh circumference (see Section 7.4.3) displayed no changes over the intervention and did not change as a result of changes in maturation (see Table 7.3 for specific results). Additionally, fascicle length expressed relative to limb length increased significantly over the intervention period however showed no change attributable to maturation.

In conclusion, this thesis aimed to validate a reliable methodology to measure force production capabilities in youth, evaluate how adolescent youth soccer players' strength and power performance change following a typical period of common season durations, and describe physiological changes to the musculature which mediate the aforementioned training effects. A novel aspect of this thesis is the evaluation of the between-day reliability of a novel isometric strength-testing protocol. This thesis indicates isometric testing can be determined reliably in youth soccer cohorts while allowing players choice over the body configuration adopted during the testing. The reliability of specific force-time metrics and how they relate to global measures of physical performance has also been described. Additionally, this thesis uniquely attempted to delineate the impact of growth, maturation, and soccer-specific training from the influence of strength and conditioning specific training by evaluating the performance change of a

recreational soccer group. The resulting data demonstrates that maturation likely explains the majority of the variance in physical performance, and physical performance change evaluated longitudinally. Indeed, the current research suggests the youth soccer players evaluated on average did not develop statistically significant strength and power capabilities due to specific strength and conditioning training, pitch-based locomotive demands, or a combination of both. This may be partly related to the lack of development of specific musculature which could positively impact global lower-body strength and power performance. This is of importance to the applied practitioner, as it suggests training within a youth soccer academy setting such as that evaluated in the current thesis may benefit from more targeted strength and conditioning specific training. This is also suggested by the lack of change observed in muscle morphological characteristics over an ~8-month period in the final original research chapter of this thesis; another study which is novel in its design and approach.

This thesis therefore adds to the current literature by supporting the use of autonomy for performance testing and describes the physical and physiological change youth soccer players may undergo over an 8-month period. Indeed, the concept of autonomy in performance settings is a new and emerging area of research, and it appears that youth soccer players can accurately self-select body positioning for specific strength testing. This thesis adds to the literature in suggesting the variance to youth soccer players' physical performance is multi-faceted and only partly explained by maturation. The change, or lack-there-of, to physical and physiological performance described here could serve as an indication of additional training required for the development of strength and power characteristics in a professional soccer academy.

8.2 Practical implications

The current thesis provides data from four separate studies which could be used to inform practice among applied practitioners. Chapter 4 demonstrates that the isometric squat test can be used in applied settings reliably, and can provide the applied practitioner/researcher with a list of force-time metrics to choose from. Indeed, a primary motivation for conducting this study was to provide an isometric squat test metric 'menu' for the applied practitioner so they could make an informed decision as to the metric which best suits their specific needs i.e., maximal or time-related. This has merit for a few reasons. Firstly, this protocol does not require the use of goniometers or any other equipment (e.g., measuring tapes etc.) for the purpose of

standardisation. Second, given the lack of change in body configuration between trials, the self-determined protocol may accommodate for anthropometric changes over prolonged periods of time; such as commonly reported in adolescents. Third, the participants perceived the self-determined protocol more comfortable than the pre-determined protocol, likely due to psychological or mechanical mechanisms, or a combination of the two. Fourth, the isometric squat test protocols described in this thesis can be implemented flexibly within a wider training programme. To explain, when a single session consisting of three maximal pushes lasting 3 seconds were incorporated (details in Chapter 4), the resulting fatigue was minimal, allowing the players to perform a pitch-based training session immediately after the testing in a non-fatigued state. In addition, there was a trend for larger outputs with the self-determined protocol. This has been observed in previous research which demonstrates the efficacy of autonomy promoting strategies on force-production capabilities. Lastly, another implication of these findings is the psychological benefit associated with choice-provision on performance, learning, control, accuracy, and mental health. Indeed, anecdotal evidence obtained from 5 years of experience in full-time professional soccer academies indicates this to be an important consideration; with practitioners, particularly from a sport science/psychology discipline regularly attempting to maximise any ‘window of opportunity’ where feelings of autonomy can be felt by players. Lastly, the results from Chapter 4 indicate that two familiarisation sessions consisting of three 3-second maximal efforts to be sufficient for data to stabilise, suggesting practitioners can use this result as a guide as to when performance improvements via neuromuscular-related learning is likely to plateau.

Further to evaluating the reliability of an isometric squat test for a measurement of full-body strength and power, an additional step was to explore how this test relates to proxies of physical performance in soccer. This was an attempt to further explore the reliable metrics’ relationship with global performance. A potential application of finding the isometric squat test strongly relates to global speed and power performance may have allowed the applied practitioner to utilise the test more frequently as a surrogate of these performance measures for the purpose of fatigue monitoring or in the event logistical, time- or player-to-staff ratios prevent from conducting a larger testing battery. The correlations provided in Chapter 5 were accompanied by regression equations for this reason, although it is recommended not to use a single performance test for athlete profiling. This chapter displays statistically significant correlations between the isometric squat test and physical performance measures. Furthermore, it appears relationships were predominantly associated with maximal force production, strengthening the

use of peak and/or relative peak force metrics. These metrics are also the simplest among the possible metrics to calculate (see Chapter 4), with automated devices providing values instantaneously. Finally, additional analysis of the data in Chapter 5 displayed standing stature and body mass as strongly associated with strength and speed-based measures, but not CMJ. Given these relationships, it can be speculatively assumed that PWV is more strongly related to strength and speed than PHV, due to the stronger relationships with ISqT metric and sprint speed (see section 2.4). Indeed, prepubertal and postpubertal males display similar isometric strength values when outputs are normalised to body mass (DiStefano *et al.*, 2015). Therefore, it could be suggested that PWV is more closely aligned with strength and power performance than PHV.

It appears from the results of Chapter 6 that strength, accelerative-type (10 m) sprint, and vertical jump performances improved in the professional soccer group. It could therefore be speculated that the changes to strength and power performance helped mediate improvement to acceleration sprint running, given the similarities in these performance measures indicating the ability for a system to rapidly overcome inertia. The results presented in Chapter 6 may also provide an indication that the training described (Figure 6.1) throughout the study period was insufficient to induce changes in maximum speed performance. For example, an applied practitioner working with the cohort described in this study may recommend exposure to greater amounts of sprint distance throughout the training week; if applicable within the weekly periodised model. Additionally, athletic development sessions may instead be designed to prioritise more maximal speed-related work. It is unlikely a ceiling effect on maximum sprint performance resulted in the lack of change in both groups, however, a lack of specificity of training and/or a significant interference effect may help explain these results. Lastly, it can also be considered that cultural factors within Scottish sport impacted the results presented here. While soccer participation rates are relatively high in Scotland, it is reasonable to suggest that sport development is not at a comparable level to multiple other European nations, and so provisions in soccer may be developmentally and financially constrained (Adams, Morrow and Thomson, 2017). Indeed, Scotland has previously been suggested as more comparable to emerging and developing nations due to these limitations (Dugdale, McRobert and Unnithan, 2021), highlighting a potential for hindered developmental opportunities for participants across sports.

Nevertheless, the results presented in Chapter 6 provide practitioners with objective physical performance data specific to adolescent soccer players from clubs of two competitive levels which could be used as a comparative indicator or baseline measure of performance or improvement. For example, practitioners working within a professional academy with players of similar age and maturity to the cohort evaluated in Chapter 6, could use the results presented (using equations constructed from the data similar to the example presented in section 6.5) as an estimate of performance change of the evaluated performance tests due to:

- a combination of changes in maturity and pitch-based training only (amateur soccer group data), or,
- a combination of pitch- and structured strength- and power-based training (professional soccer group data).

Furthermore, these results objectively characterise the development of relevant physical performance tests during arguably the most turbulent development period during adolescence; providing data seldom described within the literature.

As described previously, due to logistical restraints, the purpose of the final study described in Chapter 7 was revisited to describe the changes to vastus lateralis thickness and architecture following an 8-month period in youth soccer players. During the process of the current thesis, it emerged that it was not possible to include the physical performance results as described in Chapter 6 for the analysis of Chapter 7. However, given the similarities in duration of both studies, and the point at which the data was collected, conceptual associations can be drawn between the two studies and are discussed below. Indeed, those players who participated in the study outlined in Chapter 7 were also involved in the study described in Chapter 6.

Chapter 7 illustrates no statistically significant changes in any vastus lateralis muscle thickness or architecture value throughout the study period, with the exception of relative fascicle length. The length of the vastus lateralis fascicles relative to the length of the femur showed significant change between timepoints, but was not however, impacted due to maturation. Nonetheless, it can be seen from the results displayed in Table 7.3 maturation seems to have exerted a larger absolute change on muscle thickness values compared to the main effect of time. However, it appears increases to vastus lateralis fascicle length occurred primarily due to additional developmental mechanisms, such as specific strength and conditioning training or pitch-based training exposure.

FPA was effectively unchanged between testing points (i.e., 14 vs 14.4°) in the study described in Chapter 7, it therefore appears the training the participants of the current study undertook throughout the 8-month period resulted in changes which may increase both muscle thickness and fascicle length proportionally. Nonetheless, while non-significant, it appears here that the youth soccer players of the current investigation developed vastus lateralis muscle thickness and fascicle length in equal proportions.

In addition, the changes to relative fascicle length described previously also seem contradictory relative to the lack of performance change observed in Chapter 6. While relative fascicle length increased throughout the study period, neither absolute fascicle length or 30 m sprint performance were altered. Interestingly, while relative fascicle length showed no significant changes attributable to maturation, the opposite was true for physical performance measures which conceptually benefit from increased muscle contraction velocities, such as the 30 m sprint. However, specific underpinning physiological adaptations which contribute to global physical performance measures likely do not explain a significant proportion of the variance of these tests and therefore may not directly lead to concurrent changes in global physical performance. However, vastus lateralis contraction velocities likely do not contribute significantly to maximum sprinting performance. While it could speculatively be suggested that changes to muscle characteristics were similar between muscle groups (such as the biceps femoris which likely impacts sprint performance to a greater extent) due to identical training stimuli, this was not measured in this study.

The influence of maturation and its impact on vastus lateralis morphological characteristics was also evaluated in the study outlined in Chapter 7 and showed a contrasting impact depending on the variable analysed. Therefore, the results indicate adolescent soccer players participating in a professional soccer academy do not significantly develop vastus lateralis muscle thickness values over durations similar to that of standard season lengths. It could be loosely recommended that a greater proportion of the training programme should aim to bridge this lack of development e.g., aim to improve those elements which were unchanged in the current thesis. However, in contrast to this notion was the statistically significant increases in strength-based measures observed in Chapter 6; with global physical performance change arguably more important compared to that of muscle size changes. The lack of muscle morphological change may therefore relate to a potential interference effect, which would diminish muscle mass gain more so than that of neural improvements such as motor unit

recruitment. Finally, the results presented here may indicate a potential ceiling of effect for the players analysed. Therefore, practitioners aiming to increase muscle mass in youth athletes should consider potential mechanisms for this result, such as specific training exposure, volume and intensity alongside nutritional mechanisms.

8.3 Reflections: research, and applied practice

Although the research questions and broader aims of the current thesis were decided upon during the PhD process, it is probable my own personal experiences which influence my philosophy as an applied practitioner that also inspired the research question prior to my even undertaking this process. Indeed, when this concept was first presented to me it was immediately obvious how my experiences as an athlete likely directed my research interest. During adolescence and while competing as a sports person I was fascinated with understanding the most efficient ways of developing strength and power to enhance my sporting performance. Although a direct cause-effect relationship cannot be drawn, a clear link exists which indicates my experiences likely steered the current research areas towards my own interests in strength and power development.

As stated in the introduction, at the start of the current research process I believed the aim of research should be “to assist practitioners in operating within, and/or impacting the applied field in a meaningful way”. My journey throughout this process has highlighted the numerous nuances which exist in conducting research, particularly within an applied setting. Specifically, this has better educated me on some benefits of research, and some limitations of research in general. A main benefit of research is the provision of evidence which can highlight, suggest, describe, or inform best practice. However, there are many methodological factors which can impact the use of results presented in research. Reflecting on the research presented here, some of the studies highlight this. For example, the research in the current thesis was conducted in an applied setting, and therefore presents findings ‘realistic’ to similar environments. Figure 8.1 illustrates the final flow of the thesis chapters in relation to one another. While not significantly different, differences exist from what was presented at the start of the process in Chapter 1 (Figure 1.1). While the research presented here was being collected, time constraints impacted the testing schedule to the extent where it was not possible to align the testing for the data presented in Chapters 6 and 7. This process as a result also highlighted the difficulty in

collecting data in a dynamic and ecologically valid environment and the need for both proactivity and reactivity during the research process.

It was also stated in the introduction that the research questions presented here arose initially as applied problems which came up during conversation and which current research could not elucidate. The experience of working specifically as a research practitioner also helped better illustrate what is required as a 'research practitioner'. Prior to the process, my thoughts would simply have been an individual who can apply the best theoretical practice in a practical environment relative to the constraints specific to that environment. This, however, was slightly ignorant of the reality that the ability to practice is strongly related to one's ability to disseminate knowledge and expertise. Indeed, application in a practical setting requires the transfer and application of knowledge often in restricted settings. Restrictions are environment specific, and can include time-, equipment-, staff-, facility-, or financial-related restrictions. However, effective practice also likely requires the ability to communicate, and the mutual engagement in the process of knowledge translation between the practitioner and the player. Figure 8.2 illustrates a simple representation of the elements personally believed to be required for the applied practitioner to successfully impact an applied environment. Briefly, the ability of an individual's technical knowledge to be impactful in an applied environment is likely limited by their ability to communicate this knowledge and any related information indeed. Additionally, whether or not the service recipient will be receptive to the applied practitioner in turn is dependent upon the relationship between the two among other factors. Interpersonal relationships are dynamic and, as such, are constantly changing in response to a multitude of factors. Factors such as the practitioners' personality, knowledge, communication and evaluation skills, ability to collaborate, and progressiveness all likely directly impact this practitioner/player relationship. In addition, the relationship is in turn likely impacted by the recipients' personality and collaboration. Therefore, it appears the applied practitioner must possess the ability to apply theoretically sound principals in an applied environment, but also understand the dynamic interaction between associated constraints, how to positively communicate and impact their relationship with the athlete.

Figure 8.1: Final flow of thesis chapters.

Figure 8.2: Schematic of the proposed contributors for effective influence in an applied sporting environment.

8.4 Limitations and areas for future research

The studies presented in the current thesis are not without limitations. First, participants evaluated in the thesis are youth male soccer players, thus limiting generalisation of the results to other cohorts. Second, the research was conducted in an applied, real-world setting. Despite this granting high levels of ecological validity, conditions were naturally less controlled for when compared to laboratory settings. Consequently, results may have been impacted by unmeasured variables which may have influenced the tests conducted in this thesis e.g., growth and maturation processes in the case of Chapters 4 and 5. Therefore, future research should address whether any potential additional mediating factors described in each chapter contribute to the results displayed here.

Specifically, while demonstrated as reliable, it is not possible to generalise the results of the ISqT test to other strength/force tests, thereby eliminating any potential comparisons to results of different tests in the same cohort. In addition, different protocols, may elicit different levels of reliability for different metrics, therefore it may be that the reliability and associations described in Chapters 4 and 5 are specific to the ISqT protocols evaluated. Due to the differences in knee joint angle between protocols in Chapter 4, future research should aim to determine whether differences in outputs between the pre- and self-determined protocols is attributable to mechanical mechanisms, psychological contributions, or interactions between the two.

In addition, it is unclear whether the additional strength, power, and pitch-based training affect the performance tests in the 7–8-month study duration described in Chapter 6. Future research should therefore explore the impact of additional specific training on performance outcomes further. In addition, the possibility that players in each group described in Chapter 6 reached a plateau in performance relative to the training they were undertaking should be explored further by evaluating players from different professional clubs and age groups. Further research

controlling for contributors to change in performance such as age group and on-pitch locomotion may therefore be required.

Finally, inferring meaningful change due to significance level alone may mask changes which may well be worthwhile. However, utilising absolute change values as described in Chapter 7 is not without its limitations. For example, as is clear with the vastus lateralis metrics detailed in Chapter 7, determining whether absolute changes in muscle thickness, fascicle pennation angle, or fascicle length is impactful to global physical performance is difficult. Therefore, while it is worth mentioning that vastus lateralis muscle thickness measurement is utilised as a less invasive, more time efficient proxy of total quadriceps musculature cross-sectional area, it does not directly indicate whether changes observed were meaningful. As mentioned previously in Chapter 7, future research should aim to clarify whether any change to ultrasonography-measured muscle thickness or architecture data is actually meaningful with regards to overall development of the musculature system, and whether this change translates to physical performance improvements. In addition, the measurement of multiple muscle groups may provide useful information as to whether musculature develops similarly between muscle groups. Practitioners aiming to increase muscle mass in youth athletes should also consider additional contributing mechanisms for the results displayed in Chapter 7, such as specific training exposure, volume, intensity, alongside nutritional mechanisms. Furthermore, the addition of a control group would have allowed for the control of certain variables, such as age, growth, and maturation. Future research should aim to conduct controlled trials to delineate confounding variables such as these. Future research should also aim to better align GPS data and muscle morphological changes in soccer-based research. Indeed, the need to quantify volume and intensity of pitch-based training has been illustrated here. Finally, the sample size of the study described in Chapter 7 was insufficient to draw clear conclusions, therefore future research should aim to conduct similar research with a larger sample size.

Chapter 9.0

References

Aagaard, P., Andersen, J. L., Dyhre-Poulsen, P., Leffers, A. M., Wagner, A., Magnusson, S. P., Halkjaer-Kristensen, J. and Simonsen, E. B. (2001) 'A mechanism for increased contractile strength of human pennate muscle in response to strength training: changes in muscle architecture', *The Journal of physiology*, 534(Pt. 2), pp. 613- 623.

Abe, T., Kumagai, K. and Brechue, W. F. (2000) 'Fascicle length of leg muscles is greater in sprinters than distance runners', *Medicine and science in sports and exercise*, 32(6), pp. 1125-1129.

Adams, A., Morrow, S. and Thomson, I. (2017) 'Changing boundaries and evolving organizational forms in football: Novelty and variety among Scottish clubs', *Journal of Sport Management*, 31(2), pp. 161-175.

Al Haddad, H., Simpson, B. M., Buchheit, M., Di Salvo, V. and Mendez-Villanueva, A. (2015) 'Peak match speed and maximal sprinting speed in young soccer players: effect of age and playing position', *International journal of sports physiology and performance*, 10(7), pp. 888-896.

Alexander, R. M. and Vernon, A. (1975) 'The dimensions of knee and ankle muscles and the forces they exert.', *Journal of Human Movement Studies*, 1, pp. 115- 123.

Ali, M. A., Ashizawa, K., Kato, S., Kouchi, M., Koyama, C. and Hoshi, H. (2007) 'Biological variables in height growth of Japanese twins: a comparison with those of singletons', *Annals of human biology*, 34(3), pp. 283-95.

Amarante do Nascimento, M., Januário, R. S., Gerage, A. M., Mayhew, J. L., Cheche Pina, F. L. and Cyrino, E. S. (2013) 'Familiarization and reliability of one repetition maximum strength testing in older women', *Journal of strength and conditioning research*, 27(6), pp. 1636- 1642.

Ansdell, P., Brownstein, C. G., Škarabot, J., Angius, L., Kidgell, D., Frazer, A., Hicks, K. M., Durbaba, R., Howatson, G., Goodall, S. and Thomas, K. (2020) 'Task-specific strength increases after lower-limb compound resistance training occurred in the absence of corticospinal changes in vastus lateralis', *Experimental physiology*, 105(7), pp. 1132-1150.

Appleby, B. B., Cormack, S. J. and Newton, R. U. (2020) 'Unilateral and bilateral lower-body resistance training does not transfer equally to sprint and change of direction performance.', *Journal of Strength and Conditioning Research.*, 34(1), pp. 54- 64.

Arruda, A. F., Carling, C., Zanetti, V., Aoki, M. S., Coutts, A. J. and Moreira, A. (2015) 'Effects of a very congested match schedule on body-load impacts, accelerations, and running measures in youth soccer players', *International journal of sports physiology and performance*, 10(2), pp. 248- 252.

- Asadi, A., Ramirez-Campillo, R., Arazi, H. and Sáez de Villarreal, E. (2018) 'The Effects of Maturation on Jumping Ability and Sprint Adaptations to Plyometric Training in Youth Soccer Players', *Journal of sports sciences*, 36(21), pp. 3039-3050.
- Aslan, A., Acikada, C., Güvenç, A., Gören, H., Hazir, T. and Ozkara, A. (2012) 'Metabolic demands of match performance in young soccer players', *Journal of sports science & medicine*, 11(1), pp. 170- 179.
- Atkinson, G. and Nevill, A. M. (1998) 'Statistical methods for assessing measurement error (reliability) in variables relevant to sports medicine', *Sports medicine (Auckland, N.Z.)*, 26(4), pp. 217- 238.
- Bangsbo, J., Mohr, M. and Krstrup, P. (2006) 'Physical and metabolic demands of training and match- play in the elite football player.', *Journal of Sports Science*, 24(7), pp. 665- 674.
- Bangsbo, J., Nørregaard, L. and Thorsø, F. (1991) 'Activity profile of competition soccer', *Canadian journal of sport sciences = Journal canadien des sciences du sport*, 16(2), pp. 110-116.
- Banister, E. W., Calvert, T. W., Savage, M. V. and Bach, T. (1975) 'A systems model of training for athletic performance', *Aust J Sports Med*, 7(3), pp. 57-61.
- Baratta, R., Solomonow, M., Zhou, B. H., Letson, D., Chuinard, R. and D'Ambrosia, R. (1988) 'Muscular coactivation. The role of the antagonist musculature in maintaining knee stability', *The American journal of sports medicine*, 16(2), pp. 113- 122.
- Barker, M., Wyatt, T. J., Johnson, R. L., Stone, M. H., O'Bryant, H. S., Poe, C. and Kent, M. (1993) 'Performance factors, physiological assessment, physical characteristics, and football playing ability', *Journal of Strength and Conditioning Research.*, 7(4), pp. 224- 233.
- Bartlett, J. D. and Drust, B. (2021) 'A framework for effective knowledge translation and performance delivery of Sport Scientists in professional sport', *European journal of sport science*, 21(11), pp. 1579-1587.
- Bartolomei, S., Nigro, F., D'Amico, A., Cortesi, M. and Di Michele, R. (2022) 'Mud Pack With Menthol and Arnica Montana Accelerates Recovery Following a High-Volume Resistance Training Session for Lower Body in Trained Men', *Journal of strength and conditioning research*, 36(7), pp. 1909-1915.
- Bartolomei, S., Nigro, F., Malagoli, L., I., Masina, F., Di Michele, R. and Hoffman, J. R. (2021) 'A Comparison Between Total Body and Split Routine Resistance Training Programs in Trained Men', *Journal of strength and conditioning research*, 35(6), pp. 1520-1526.
- Bartolomei, S., Sadres, E., Church, D. D., Arroyo, E., Gordon, J. A., Varanoske, A. N., Wang, R., Beyer, K. S., Oliveira, L. P., Stout, J. R. and Hoffman, J. R. (2017) 'Comparison of the recovery response from high-intensity and high-volume resistance exercise in trained men', *European journal of applied physiology*, 117(7), pp. 1287- 1298.
- Bazyler, C. D., Bailey, C. A., Chiang, C. Y., Sato, K. and Stone, M. H. (2014a) 'The effects of strength training on isometric force production symmetry in recreationally trained males', *Journal of Trainology*, 3(1), pp. 6- 10.

- Bazyler, C. D., Beckham, G. K. and Sato, K. (2015) 'The use of the isometric squat as a measure of strength and explosiveness', *Journal of strength and conditioning research*, 29(5), pp. 1386-1392.
- Bazyler, C. D., Sato, K., Wassinger, C. A., Lamont, H. S. and Stone, M. H. (2014b) 'The efficacy of incorporating partial squats in maximal strength training', *Journal of strength and conditioning research*, 28(11), pp. 3024- 3032.
- Beattie, K., Carson, B. P., Lyons, M. and Kenny, I. C. (2017) 'The Relationship Between Maximal Strength and Reactive Strength', *International journal of sports physiology and performance*, 12(4), pp. 548-553.
- Behm, D. G., Young, J. D., Whitten, J. H. D., Reid, J. C., Quigley, P. J., Low, J., Li, Y., Lima, C. D., Hodgson, D. D., Chaouachi, A., Prieske, O. and Granacher, U. (2017) 'Effectiveness of Traditional Strength vs. Power Training on Muscle Strength, Power and Speed with Youth: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis', *Frontiers in physiology*, 8, pp. 8: 423.
- Behringer, M., Vom Heede, A., Matthews, M. and Mester, J. (2011) 'Effects of strength training on motor performance skills in children and adolescents: a meta-analysis', *Pediatric exercise science*, 23(2), pp. 186- 206.
- Bellistri, G., Marzorati, M., Sodero, L., Sforza, C., Bradley, P. S. and Porcelli, S. (2017) 'Match running performance and physical capacity profiles of U8 and U10 soccer players', *Sport Sciences for Health*, 13(2), pp. 273- 280.
- Berger, R. A. and Henderson, J. M. (1966) 'Relationship of power to static and dynamic strength', *Research quarterly*, 37(1), pp. 9-13.
- Binzoni, T., Bianchi, S., Hanquinet, S., Kaelin, A., Sayegh, Y., Dumont, M. and Jéquier, S. (2001) 'Human gastrocnemius medialis pennation angle as a function of age: from newborn to the elderly', *Journal of physiological anthropology and applied human science*, 20(5), pp. 293-298.
- Blagrove, R. C., Bishop, C., Howatson, G. and Hayes, P. R. (2021) 'Inter-limb strength asymmetry in adolescent distance runners: Test-retest reliability and relationships with performance and running economy', *Journal of sports sciences*, 39(3), pp. 312-321.
- Blazevich, A. J., Gill, N. and Newton, R. U. (2002) 'Reliability and validity of two isometric squat tests', *Journal of strength and conditioning research*, 16(2), pp. 298- 304.
- Blazevich, A. J., Gill, N. D., Bronks, R. and Newton, R. U. (2003) 'Training-specific muscle architecture adaptation after 5-wk training in athletes', *Medicine and science in sports and exercise*, 35(12), pp. 2013-2022.
- Bloomfield, J., Polman, R. and O'Donoghue, P. (2007) 'Physical Demands of Different Positions in FA Premier League Soccer', *Journal of sports science & medicine*, 6(1), pp. 63-70.
- Bogdanis, G. C. and Kalapotharakos, V. I. (2016) 'Knee Extension Strength and Hamstrings-to-Quadriceps Imbalances in Elite Soccer Players', *International journal of sports medicine*, 37(2), pp. 119- 124.

Brady, C. J., Harrison, A. J. and Comyns, T. M. (2020) 'A review of the reliability of biomechanical variables produced during the isometric mid-thigh pull and isometric squat and the reporting of normative data', *Sports biomechanics*, 19(1), pp. 1- 25.

Brady, C. J., Harrison, A. J., Flanagan, E. P., Haff, G. G. and Comyns, T. M. (2018) 'A Comparison of the Isometric Midthigh Pull and Isometric Squat: Intraday Reliability, Usefulness, and the Magnitude of Difference Between Tests', *International journal of sports physiology and performance*, 13(7), pp. 844- 852.

Brady, C. J., Harrison, A. J., Flanagan, E. P., Haff, G. G. and Comyns, T. M. (2019) 'The Relationship Between Isometric Strength and Sprint Acceleration in Sprinters', *International journal of sports physiology and performance*, pp. 1- 8.

Brownlee, T. E., Murtagh, C. F., Naughton, R. J., Whitworth-Turner, C. M., O'Boyle, A., Morgans, R., Morton, J. P., Erskine, R. M. and Drust, B. (2018) 'Isometric maximal voluntary force evaluated using an isometric mid-thigh pull differentiates English Premier League youth soccer players from a maturity-matched control group', *Science and Medicine in Football*, 2(3), pp. 209-215.

Buchheit, M. and Laursen, P. B. (2013) 'High-intensity interval training, solutions to the programming puzzle. Part II: anaerobic energy, neuromuscular load and practical applications', *Sports medicine (Auckland, N.Z.)*, 43(10), pp. 927-954.

Buchheit, M. and Mendez-Villanueva, A. (2014) 'Effects of age, maturity and body dimensions on match running performance in highly trained under-15 soccer players', *Journal of sports sciences*, 32(13), pp. 1271- 1278.

Buchheit, M., Mendez-Villanueva, A., Simpson, B. M. and Bourdon, P. C. (2010a) 'Match running performance and fitness in youth soccer', *International journal of sports medicine*, 31(11), pp. 818- 825.

Buchheit, M., Mendez-villanueva, A., Simpson, B. M. and Bourdon, P. C. (2010b) 'Repeated-sprint sequences during youth soccer matches', *International journal of sports medicine*, 31(10), pp. 709- 716.

Bujalance-Moreno, P., Latorre-Román, P. Á. and García-Pinillos, F. (2019) 'A systematic review on small-sided games in football players: Acute and chronic adaptations', *Journal of sports sciences*, 37(8), pp. 921-949.

Calder, K. M. and Gabriel, D. A. (2007) 'Adaptations during familiarization to resistive exercise', *Journal of electromyography and kinesiology : official journal of the International Society of Electrophysiological Kinesiology*, 17(3), pp. 328- 335.

Catley, M. J. and Tomkinson, G. R. (2013) 'Normative health-related fitness values for children: analysis of 85347 test results on 9-17-year-old Australians since 1985', *British journal of sports medicine*, 47(2), pp. 98- 108.

Chaabene, H., Prieske, O., Moran, J., Negra, Y., Attia, A. and Granacher, U. (2020) 'Effects of Resistance Training on Change-of-Direction Speed in Youth and Young Physically Active and Athletic Adults: A Systematic Review with Meta-Analysis', *Sports medicine (Auckland, N.Z.)*, 50(8), pp. 1483-1499.

Chan, V. W. S. and Abbas, S. (2008) *Ultrasound Imaging for Regional Anesthesia: A Practical Guide*. Toronto: ON: Toronto Publishing.

Chelly, M. S., Chérif, N., Amar, M. B., Hermassi, S., Fathloun, M., Bouhlel, E., Tabka, Z. and Shephard, R. J. (2010) 'Relationships of peak leg power, 1 maximal repetition half back squat, and leg muscle volume to 5-m sprint performance of junior soccer players', *Journal of strength and conditioning research*, 24(1), pp. 266- 271.

Chelly, M. S., Fathloun, M., Cherif, N., Ben, A. M., Tabka, Z. and Van Praagh, E. (2009) 'Effects of a back squat training program on leg power, jump, and sprint performances in junior soccer players', *Journal of strength and conditioning research*, 23(8), pp. 2241- 2249.

Chiviacowsky, S., Wulf, G., Lewthwaite, R. and Campos, T. (2012) 'Motor learning benefits of self-controlled practice in persons with Parkinson's disease', *Gait & posture*, 35(4), pp. 601- 605.

Close, R. I. (1972) 'Dynamic properties of mammalian skeletal muscles', *Physiological reviews*, 52(1), pp. 129- 197.

Cobley, S., Baker, J., Wattie, N. and McKenna, J. (2009) 'Annual age-grouping and athlete development: a meta-analytical review of relative age effects in sport', *Sports medicine (Auckland, N.Z.)*, 39(3), pp. 235- 256.

Colquhoun, R. J., Gai, C. M., Walters, J., Brannon, A. R., Kilpatrick, M. W., D'Agostino, D. P. and Campbell, B. I. (2017) 'Comparison of Powerlifting Performance in Trained Men Using Traditional and Flexible Daily Undulating Periodization', *Journal of strength and conditioning research*, 31(2), pp. 283- 291.

Comfort, P., Dos'Santos, T., Beckham, G. K., Stone, M. H., Guppy, S. N. and Haff, G. G. (2019) 'Standardization and Methodological Considerations for the Isometric Midthigh Pull', *Strength & Conditioning Journal*, 41(2), pp. 57-79.

Comfort, P., Graham, -. S., P., Matthews, M. J. and Bamber, C. (2011) 'Strength and power characteristics in English elite rugby league players', *Journal of strength and conditioning research*, 25(5), pp. 1374- 1384.

Comfort, P., Jones, P. A., McMahan, J. J. and Newton, R. (2015) 'Effect of knee and trunk angle on kinetic variables during the isometric midthigh pull: test-retest reliability', *International journal of sports physiology and performance*, 10(1), pp. 58- 63.

Comfort, P., Stewart, A., Bloom, L. and Clarkson, B. (2014) 'Relationships between strength, sprint, and jump performance in well-trained youth soccer players.', *Journal of Strength and Conditioning Research.*, 28(1), pp. 173- 177.

Cormie, P., McCaulley, G. O. and McBride, J. M. (2007) 'Power versus strength-power jump squat training: influence on the load-power relationship', *Medicine and science in sports and exercise*, 39(6), pp. 996- 1003.

Cormie, P., McGuigan, M. R. and Newton, R. U. (2010) 'Influence of strength on magnitude and mechanisms of adaptation to power training.', *Medicine and Science in Sports and Exercise.*, 42(8), pp. 1566- 1581.

- Crang, Z. L., Duthie, G., Cole, M. H., Weakley, J., Hewitt, A. and Johnston, R. D. (2022) 'The inter-device reliability of global navigation satellite systems during team sport movement across multiple days', *Journal of science and medicine in sport*, 25(4), pp. 340-344.
- Cronin, J. B. and Hansen, K. T. (2005) 'Strength and power predictors of sports speed', *Journal of strength and conditioning research*, 19(2), pp. 349-357.
- Daly, R. M., Saxon, L., Turner, C. H., Robling, A. G. and Bass, S. L. (2004) 'The relationship between muscle size and bone geometry during growth and in response to exercise', *Bone*, 34(2), pp. 281- 287.
- Darrall-Jones, J. D., Jones, B. and Till, K. (2015) 'Anthropometric and Physical Profiles of English Academy Rugby Union Players', *Journal of strength and conditioning research*, 29(8), pp. 2086- 2096.
- Davies, R. W., Bass, J. J., Carson, B. P., Norton, C., Koziar, M., Wilkinson, D. J., Brook, M. S., Atherton, P. J., Smith, K. and Jakeman, P. M. (2020) 'The Effect of Whey Protein Supplementation on Myofibrillar Protein Synthesis and Performance Recovery in Resistance-Trained Men', *Nutrients*, 12(3).
- Davies, R. W., Carson, B. P., Bass, J. J., Holohan, S. and Jakeman, P. M. (2018) 'Acute reduction of lower-body contractile function following a micro biopsy of m. vastus lateralis', *Scandinavian journal of medicine & science in sports*, 28(12), pp. 2638- 2642.
- De Leeuw, E., Borgers, N. and Smits, A. (2004) 'Pretesting questionnaires for children and adolescents', *Methods for testing and evaluating survey questionnaires*, pp. 409- 429.
- Deci, E. L. and Ryan, R. M. (2000) 'The " what" and " why" of goal pursuits: Human needs and the self-determination of behavior', *Psychological inquiry*, 11(4), pp. 227- 268.
- Degens, H., Erskine, R. M. and Morse, C. I. (2009) 'Disproportionate changes in skeletal muscle strength and size with resistance training and ageing', *Journal of musculoskeletal & neuronal interactions*, 9(3), pp. 123- 129.
- Delaney, J. A., Cummins, C. J., Thornton, H. R. and Duthie, G. M. (2018) 'Importance, Reliability, and Usefulness of Acceleration Measures in Team Sports', *Journal of strength and conditioning research*, 32(12), pp. 3485- 3493.
- Dello Iacono, A., Beato, M. and Halperin, I. (2020) 'Self-Selecting the Number of Repetitions in Potentiation Protocols: Enhancement Effects on Jumping Performance', *International journal of sports physiology and performance*, 16(3), pp. 353-359.
- Demling, R. H. and Orgill, D. P. (2000) 'The anticatabolic and wound healing effects of the testosterone analog oxandrolone after severe burn injury', *Journal of critical care*, 15(1), pp. 12- 17.
- Dempsey, A. R., Lloyd, D. G., Elliott, B. C., Steele, J. R., Munro, B. J. and Russo, K. A. (2007) 'The effect of technique change on knee loads during sidestep cutting', *Medicine and science in sports and exercise*, 39(10), pp. 1765- 173.

Deprez, D., Coutts, A. J., Franssen, J., Deconinck, F., Lenoir, M., Vaeyens, R. and Philippaerts, R. (2013) 'Relative age, biological maturation and anaerobic characteristics in elite youth soccer players', *International Journal of Sports Medicine*, 34(10), pp. 897- 903.

Dias, R. M. R., Cyrino, E. S., Salvador, E. P., Caldeira, L. F. S., Nakamura, F. Y., Papst, R. R., Bruna, N. and Gurjão, A. L. D. (2005) 'Influence of familiarization process on muscular strength assessment in 1-RM tests', *Revista Brasileira de Medicina do Esporte*, 11, pp. 34-38.

DiStefano, L. J., Martinez, J. C., Crowley, E., Matteau, E., Kerner, M. S., Boling, M. C., Nguyen, A. D. and Trojian, T. H. (2015) 'Maturation and Sex Differences in Neuromuscular Characteristics of Youth Athletes', *Journal of strength and conditioning research*, 29(9), pp. 2465-2473.

Dobbs, I. J., Oliver, J. L., Wong, M. A., Moore, I. S. and Lloyd, R. S. (2020) 'Effects of a 12-Week Training Program on Isometric and Dynamic Force-Time Characteristics in Pre- and Post-Peak Height Velocity Male Athletes', *Journal of strength and conditioning research*, 34(3), pp. 653- 662.

Doncaster, G., Iga, J. and Unnithan, V. (2018) 'Assessing Differences in Cardiorespiratory Fitness With Respect to Maturity Status in Highly Trained Youth Soccer Players', *Pediatric exercise science*, 30(2), pp. 216- 228.

Dons, B., Bollerup, K., Bonde-Petersen, F. and Hancke, S. (1979) 'The effect of weight-lifting exercise related to muscle fiber composition and muscle cross-sectional area in humans', *European journal of applied physiology and occupational physiology*, 40(2), pp. 95- 106.

Dos'Santos, T., Thomas, C., Jones, P. A. and Comfort, P. (2017) 'Assessing Muscle-Strength Asymmetry via a Unilateral-Stance Isometric Midthigh Pull', *International journal of sports physiology and performance*, 12(4), pp. 505-511.

Dos'Santos, T., Jones, P. A., Comfort, P. and Thomas, C. (2017) 'Effect of Different Onset Thresholds on Isometric Midthigh Pull Force-Time Variables', *Journal of strength and conditioning research*, 31(12), pp. 3463- 3473.

Dos'Santos, T., Thomas, C., Comfort, P., McMahon, J. J., Jones, P. A., Oakley, N. P. and Young, A. L. (2018) 'Between-Session Reliability of Isometric Midthigh Pull Kinetics and Maximal Power Clean Performance in Male Youth Soccer Players', *Journal of strength and conditioning research*, 32(12), pp. 283-299.

Drake, D., Kennedy, R. and Wallace, E. (2017) 'The Validity and Responsiveness of Isometric Lower Body Multi-Joint Tests of Muscular Strength: a Systematic Review', *Sports medicine - open*, 3(1).

Drake, D., Kennedy, R. and Wallace, E. (2018) 'Familiarization, validity and smallest detectable difference of the isometric squat test in evaluating maximal strength', *Journal of sports sciences*, 36(18), pp. 2087- 2095.

Drake, D., Kennedy, R. A. and Wallace, E. S. (2019a) 'Measuring what matters in isometric multi-joint rate of force development', *Journal of sports sciences*, 37(23), pp. 2667- 2675.

- Drake, D., Kennedy, R. A. and Wallace, E. S. (2019b) 'Multi-joint rate of force development testing protocol affects reliability and the smallest detectable difference', *Journal of sports sciences*, 37(14), pp. 1570- 1581.
- Drinkwater, E. J., Hopkins, W., G., McKenna, M. J., Hunt, P. H. and Pyne, D., B (2007) 'Modelling age and secular differences in fitness between basketball players', *Journal of sports sciences*, 25(8), pp. 869-878.
- Duarte, J. P., Valente-Dos-Santos, J., Coelho-E-Silva, M. J., Malina, R. M., Deprez, D., Philippaerts, R., Lenoir, M. and Vaeyens, R. (2018) 'Developmental Changes in Isometric Strength: Longitudinal Study in Adolescent Soccer Players', *International journal of sports medicine*, 39(9), pp. 688-695.
- Dugdale, J. H., Arthur, C. A., Sanders, D. and Hunter, A. M. (2019) 'Reliability and validity of field-based fitness tests in youth soccer players', *European journal of sport science*, 19(6), pp. 745- 756.
- Dugdale, J. H., McRobert, A. P. and Unnithan, V. B. (2021) "'He's Just a Wee Laddie": The Relative Age Effect in Male Scottish Soccer', *Frontiers in psychology*, 12.
- Durbin, J., Watson, G.S. (1951) 'Testing for serial correlation in least squares regression. II', *Biometrika*, 38(1-2), pp. 159-178.
- D'Auria, S., Tanner, R., Sheppard, J. and Manning, J. 'Evaluation of various methodologies used to assess sprint performance'. *Australian Institute of Sport Applied Physiology Conference*.
- Eitam, B., Kennedy, P. M. and Tory, H., E. (2013) 'Motivation from control', *Experimental brain research*, 229(3), pp. 475- 484.
- Eliakim, A., Barstow, T. J., Brasel, J. A., Ajie, H., Lee, W. N., Renslo, R., Berman, N. and Cooper, D. M. (1996) 'Effect of exercise training on energy expenditure, muscle volume, and maximal oxygen uptake in female adolescents', *The Journal of pediatrics*, 129(4), pp. 537- 543.
- Eliakim, A., Scheett, T., Allmendinger, N., Brasel, J. A. and Cooper, D. M. (2001) 'Training, muscle volume, and energy expenditure in nonobese American girls', *Journal of applied physiology (Bethesda, Md. : 1985)*, 90(1), pp. 35- 44.
- Emanuel, A., Har-Nir, I., Rozen Smukas, I. I. and Halperin, I. (2020) 'The effect of self-selecting the number of repetitions on motor performance and psychological outcomes', *Psychological research*, pp. 1-10.
- English, C., Fisher, L. and Thoirs, K. (2012) 'Reliability of real-time ultrasound for measuring skeletal muscle size in human limbs in vivo: a systematic review', *Clinical rehabilitation*, 26(10), pp. 934- 944.
- Epstein, L. H., Valoski, A. M., Kalarchian, M. A. and McCurley, J. (1995) 'Do children lose and maintain weight easier than adults: a comparison of child and parent weight changes from six months to ten years', *Obesity research*, 3(5), pp. 411-417.

- Erikstad, M. K., Martin, L. J., Haugen, T. and Høigaard, R. (2018) 'Group cohesion, needs satisfaction, and self-regulated learning: A one-year prospective study of elite youth soccer players' perceptions of their club team', *Psychology of Sport and Exercise*, 39, pp. 171-178.
- Erskine, R. M., Jones, D. A., Maganaris, C. N. and Degens, H. (2009) 'In vivo specific tension of the human quadriceps femoris muscle', *European journal of applied physiology*, 106(6), pp. 827-838.
- Falk, B., Usselman, C., Dotan, R., Brunton, L., Klentrou, P., Shaw, J. and Gabriel, D. (2009) 'Child-adult differences in muscle strength and activation pattern during isometric elbow flexion and extension', *Applied physiology, nutrition, and metabolism = Physiologie appliquee, nutrition et metabolisme*, 34(4), pp. 609- 615.
- Faude, O., Koch, T. and Meyer, T. (2012) 'Straight sprinting is the most frequent action in goal situations in professional football.', *Journal of Sports Science*, 30(7), pp. 625- 631.
- Fitze, D. P., Franchi, M. V., Fröhlich, S., Frey, W. O. and Spörri, J. (2022) 'Biceps femoris long head morphology in youth competitive alpine skiers is associated with age, biological maturation and traumatic lower extremity injuries', *Frontiers in physiology*, 13.
- Flück, M. and Hoppeler, H. (2003) 'Molecular basis of skeletal muscle plasticity--from gene to form and function', *Reviews of physiology, biochemistry and pharmacology*, 146, pp. 159- 216.
- Folland, J. P. and Williams, A. G. (2007) 'The adaptations to strength training : morphological and neurological contributions to increased strength', *Sports medicine (Auckland, N.Z.)*, 37(2), pp. 145- 168.
- Franchi, M. V., Raiteri, B. J., Longo, S., Sinha, S., Narici, M. V. and Csapo, R. (2018) 'Muscle Architecture Assessment: Strengths, Shortcomings and New Frontiers of in Vivo Imaging Techniques', *Ultrasound in medicine & biology*, 44(12), pp. 2492- 2504.
- Fry, C. S., Noehren, B., Mula, J., Ubele, M. F., Westgate, P. M., Kern, P. A. and Peterson, C. A. (2014) 'Fibre type-specific satellite cell response to aerobic training in sedentary adults', *The Journal of physiology*, 592(12), pp. 2625- 2635.
- Gabbett, T. J., Whyte, D. G., Hartwig, T. B., Wescombe, H. and Naughton, G. A. (2014) 'The relationship between workloads, physical performance, injury and illness in adolescent male football players', *Sports medicine (Auckland, N.Z.)*, 44(7), pp. 989-1003.
- Gannon, E. A., Stokes, K. A. and Trewartha, G. (2016) 'Strength and Power Development in Professional Rugby Union Players Over a Training and Playing Season', *International journal of sports physiology and performance*, 11(3), pp. 381- 387.
- Gaudino, P., Alberti, G. and Iaia, F. M. (2014) 'Estimated metabolic and mechanical demands during different small-sided games in elite soccer players', *Human movement science*, 36, pp. 123-133.
- Gavanda, S., Geisler, S., Quittmann, O. J. and Schiffer, T. (2019) 'The Effect of Block Versus Daily Undulating Periodization on Strength and Performance in Adolescent Football Players', *International journal of sports physiology and performance*, 14(6), pp. 814– 821.

- Gerodimos, V., Zafeiridis, A., Perkos, S., Dipla, K., Manou, V. and Kellis, S. (2008) 'The contribution of stretch-shortening cycle and arm-swing to vertical jumping performance in children, adolescents, and adult basketball players', *Pediatric exercise science*, 20(4), pp. 379-389.
- Gillen, Z. M., Jahn, L. E., Shoemaker, M. E., McKay, B. D., Mendez, A. I., Bohannon, N. A. and Cramer, J. T. (2019) 'Effects of Eccentric Preloading on Concentric Vertical Jump Performance in Youth Athletes', *Journal of applied biomechanics*, 35(5), pp. 327- 335.
- Gillen, Z. M., Miramonti, A. A., McKay, B. D., Leutzinger, T. J. and Cramer, J. T. (2018) 'Test-Retest Reliability and Concurrent Validity of Athletic Performance Combine Tests in 6-15-Year-Old Male Athletes', *Journal of strength and conditioning research*, 32(10), pp. 2783-2794.
- Goldspink, G. (1985) 'Malleability of the motor system: a comparative approach', *The Journal of experimental biology*, 115, pp. 375- 391.
- Goto, H., Morris, J. G. and Nevill, M. E. (2015a) 'Match analysis of U9 and U10 english premier league academy soccer players using a global positioning system: relevance for talent identification and development', *Journal of strength and conditioning research*, 29(4), pp. 954-963.
- Goto, H., Morris, J. G. and Nevill, M. E. (2015b) 'Motion analysis of U11 to U16 elite English Premier League Academy players', *Journal of sports sciences*, 33(12), pp. 1248- 1258.
- Grand, K. F., Bruzi, A. T., Dyke, F. B., Godwin, M. M., Leiker, A. M., Thompson, A. G., Buchanan, T. L. and Miller, M. W. (2015) 'Why self-controlled feedback enhances motor learning: Answers from electroencephalography and indices of motivation', *Human movement science*, 43, pp. 23- 32.
- Griggs, R. C., Kingston, W., Jozefowicz, R. F., Herr, B. E., Forbes, G. and Halliday, D. (1989) 'Effect of testosterone on muscle mass and muscle protein synthesis', *Journal of applied physiology (Bethesda, Md. : 1985)*, 66(1), pp. 498- 503.
- Hagger, M. S., Chatzisarantis, N. L. D., Hein, V., Pihu, M., Soos, I. and Karsai, I. (2007) 'The perceived autonomy support scale for exercise settings (PASSES): Development, validity, and cross-cultural invariance in young people', *Psychology of Sport and Exercise*, 8(5), pp. 632-653.
- Halperin, I., Chapman, D. W., Martin, D. T., Lewthwaite, R. and Wulf, G. (2017) 'Choices enhance punching performance of competitive kickboxers', *Psychological research*, 81(5), pp. 1051- 1058.
- Halperin, I., Williams, K. J., Martin, D. T. and Chapman, D. W. (2016) 'The Effects of Attentional Focusing Instructions on Force Production During the Isometric Midthigh Pull', *Journal of strength and conditioning research*, 30(4), pp. 919- 923.
- Halperin, I., Wulf, G., Vigotsky, A. D., Schoenfeld, B. J. and Behm, D. G. (2018) 'Autonomy: a missing ingredient of a successful program?', *Strength & Conditioning Journal*, 40(4), pp. 18-25.

- Hannon, M. P., Carney, D. J., Floyd, S., Parker, L. J. F., McKeown, J., Drust, B., Unnithan, V. B., Close, G. L. and Morton, J. P. (2020) 'Cross-sectional comparison of body composition and resting metabolic rate in Premier League academy soccer players: Implications for growth and maturation', *Journal of sports sciences*, 38(11-12), pp. 1326- 1334.
- Hansen, L., Bangsbo, J., Twisk, J. and Klausen, K. (1999) 'Development of Muscle Strength in Relation to Training Level and Testosterone in Young Male Soccer Players', *Journal of applied physiology (Bethesda, Md. : 1985)*, 87(3), pp. 1141-1147.
- Hart, N. H., Nimphius, S., Cochrane, J. L. and Newton, R. U. (2012a) 'Reliability and validity of unilateral and bilateral isometric strength measures using a customised, portable apparatus.', *Journal of Australian Strength and Conditioning*, (1), pp. 61- 67.
- Hart, N. H., Nimphius, S., Cochrane, J. L. and Newton, R. U. (2012b) 'Reliability and validity of unilateral and bilateral isometric strength measures using a customised, portable apparatus.', *Journal of Australian Strength and Conditioning*, 20(1), pp. 61- 67.
- Hedges, L. V. and Olkin, I. (2014) *Statistical methods for meta-analysis*. Academic press.
- Heinert, B., Rutherford, D., Cleereman, J., Lee, M. and Kernozek, T. W. (2021) 'Changes in landing mechanics using augmented feedback: 4-Week training and retention study', *Physical therapy in sport : official journal of the Association of Chartered Physiotherapists in Sports Medicine*, 52, pp. 97-102.
- Helsen, W. F., van Winckel, J. and Williams, A. M. (2005) 'The relative age effect in youth soccer across Europe', *Journal of sports sciences*, 23(6), pp. 629- 636.
- Hill-Haas, S. V., Dawson, B., Impellizzeri, F. M. and Coutts, A. J. (2011) 'Physiology of small-sided games training in football: a systematic review', *Sports medicine (Auckland, N.Z.)*, 41(3), pp. 199-220.
- Hodgson, C., Akenhead, R. and Thomas, K. (2014) 'Time-motion analysis of acceleration demands of 4v4 small-sided soccer games played on different pitch sizes', *Human movement science*, 33, pp. 25-32.
- Holtermann, A., Roeleveld, K., Vereijken, B. and Ettema, G. (2007) 'The effect of rate of force development on maximal force production: acute and training-related aspects', *European journal of applied physiology*, 99(6), pp. 605-613.
- Hooyman, A., Wulf, G. and Lewthwaite, R. (2014) 'Impacts of autonomy-supportive versus controlling instructional language on motor learning', *Human movement science*, 36, pp. 190-198.
- Hopkins, W. 2017. Spreadsheets for analysis of validity and reliability.: Sportscience.
- Hopkins, W. G. (2000) 'Measures of reliability in sports medicine and science', *Sports medicine (Auckland, N.Z.)*, 30(1), pp. 1- 15.
- Hopkins, W. G. (2002) *A scale of magnitudes for effect statistics. A new view of statistics*. <http://www.sportsci.org/resource/stats/index.html>: Academic Press. Available at: <http://www.sportsci.org/resource/stats/index.html> (Accessed: 20/02/2023. 2023.).

- Hopkins, W. G., Hawley, J. A. and Burke, L. M. (1999) 'Design and analysis of research on sport performance enhancement', *Medicine and science in sports and exercise*, 31(3), pp. 472-485.
- Hori, N., Newton, R. U., Kawamori, N., McGuigan, M. R., Kraemer, W. J. and Nosaka, K. (2009) 'Reliability of performance measurements derived from ground reaction force data during countermovement jump and the influence of sampling frequency', *Journal of strength and conditioning research*, 23(3), pp. 874-882.
- Hunter, F., Bray, J., Towlson, C., Smith, M., Barrett, S., Madden, J., Abt, G. and Lovell, R. (2015) 'Individualisation of time-motion analysis: a method comparison and case report series', *International journal of sports medicine*, 36(1), pp. 41- 48.
- Hunter, J. P., Marshall, R. N. and McNair, P. J. (2005) 'Relationships between ground reaction force impulse and kinematics of sprint-running acceleration', *Journal of applied biomechanics*, 21(1), pp. 31- 43.
- Ihnatsenka, B. and Boezaart, A. P. (2010) 'Ultrasound: Basic understanding and learning the language', *International journal of shoulder surgery*, 4(3), pp. 55- 62.
- Ingebrigtsen, J., Dalen, T., Hjelde, G. H., Drust, B. and Wisløff, U. (2015) 'Acceleration and sprint profiles of a professional elite football team in match play', *European journal of sport science*, 15(2), pp. 101- 110.
- Ishida, A., Bazylar, C. D., Suarez, D. G., Slaton, J. A., White, J. B. and Stone, M. H. (2023a) 'The difference between several neuromuscular tests for monitoring resistance-training induced fatigue', *Journal of sports sciences*, 41(3), pp. 209-216.
- Ishida, A., Suarez, D. G., Travis, S. K., Slaton, J. A., White, J. B., Bazylar, C. D. and Stone, M. H. (2023b) 'Intrasession and Intersession Reliability of Isometric Squat, Midthigh Pull, and Squat Jump in Resistance-Trained Individuals', *Journal of strength and conditioning research*, 37(1), pp. 18-26.
- Iwatsuki, T., Abdollahipour, R., Psotta, R., Lewthwaite, R. and Wulf, G. (2017) 'Autonomy facilitates repeated maximum force productions', *Human movement science*, 55, pp. 264- 268.
- James, L. P., Roberts, L. A., Haff, G. G., Kelly, V. G. and Beckman, E. M. (2017) 'Validity and Reliability of a Portable Isometric Mid-Thigh Clean Pull', *Journal of strength and conditioning research*, 31(5), pp. 1378-1386.
- Johnson, T. L. and Klueber, K. M. (1991) 'Skeletal muscle following tonic overload: functional and structural analysis', *Medicine and science in sports and exercise*, 23(1), pp. 49- 55.
- Kadlec, D., Jordan, M. J., Snyder, L., Alderson, J. and Nimphius, S. (2021) 'Test Re-test Reliability of Single and Multijoint Strength Properties in Female Australian Footballers', *Sports medicine - open*, 7(1).
- Kanehisa, H., Funato, K., Kuno, S., Fukunaga, T. and Katsuta, S. (2003) 'Growth trend of the quadriceps femoris muscle in junior Olympic weight lifters: an 18-month follow-up survey', *European journal of applied physiology*, 89(3-4), pp. 238- 242.

- Kanehisa, H., Kuno, S., Katsuta, S. and Fukunaga, T. (2006) 'A 2-year follow-up study on muscle size and dynamic strength in teenage tennis players', *Scandinavian journal of medicine & science in sports*, 16(2), pp. 93- 101.
- Kawakami, Y., Abe, T., Kuno, S. Y. and Fukunaga, T. (1995) 'Training-induced changes in muscle architecture and specific tension', *European journal of applied physiology and occupational physiology*, 72(1-2), pp. 37- 43.
- Kawamori, N., Nosaka, K. and Newton, R. U. (2013) 'Relationships between ground reaction impulse and sprint acceleration performance in team sport athletes', *Journal of strength and conditioning research*, 27(3), pp. 568- 573.
- Keller, M., Lauber, B., Gehring, D., Leukel, C. and Taube, W. (2014) 'Jump performance and augmented feedback: immediate benefits and long-term training effects', *Human movement science*, 36, pp. 177-189.
- Kelly, A. L., Wilson, M. R., Gough, L. A., Knapman, H., Morgan, P., Cole, M., Jackson, D. T. and Williams, C. A. (2020) 'A longitudinal investigation into the relative age effect in an English professional football club: Exploring the ‘underdog hypothesis’', *Science and Medicine in Football*, 4(2), pp. 111- 118.
- Kennedy, R. A. and Drake, D. (2018) 'Dissociated Time Course of Recovery Between Strength and Power After Isoinertial Resistance Loading in Rugby Union Players', *Journal of strength and conditioning research*, 32(3), pp. 748- 755.
- Kennedy, R. A. and Drake, D. (2021) 'Improving the Signal-To-Noise Ratio When Monitoring Countermovement Jump Performance', *Journal of strength and conditioning research*, 35(1), pp. 85- 90.
- Khamis, H. J. and Roche, A. F. (1994) 'Predicting adult stature without using skeletal age: the Khamis-Roche method', *Pediatrics*, 94(4 Pt 1), pp. 504- 507.
- Kobal, R., Loturco, I., Barroso, R., Gil, S., Cuniyochi, R., Ugrinowitsch, C., Roschel, H. and Tricoli, V. (2017) 'Effects of Different Combinations of Strength, Power, and Plyometric Training on the Physical Performance of Elite Young Soccer Players', *Journal of strength and conditioning research*, 31(6), pp. 1468-1476.
- Koo, T. K. and Li, M. Y. (2016) 'A Guideline of Selecting and Reporting Intraclass Correlation Coefficients for Reliability Research', *Journal of chiropractic medicine*, 15(2), pp. 155-163.
- Kozieł, S. M. and Malina, R. M. (2018) 'Modified Maturity Offset Prediction Equations: Validation in Independent Longitudinal Samples of Boys and Girls', *Sports medicine (Auckland, N.Z.)*, 48(1), pp. 221- 236.
- Kraemer, W. J. and Ratamess, N. A. (2005) 'Hormonal responses and adaptations to resistance exercise and training', *Sports medicine (Auckland, N.Z.)*, 35(4), pp. 339- 361.
- Kraska, J. M., Ramsey, M. W., Haff, G. G., Fethke, N., Sands, W. A., Stone, M. E. and Stone, M. H. (2009) 'Relationship between strength characteristics and unweighted and weighted vertical jump height', *International journal of sports physiology and performance*, 4(4), pp. 461- 473.

- Krolo, A., Gilic, B., Foretic, N., Pojskic, H., Hammami, R., Spasic, M., Uljevic, O., Versic, S. and Sekulic, D. (2020) 'Agility Testing in Youth Football (Soccer)Players; Evaluating Reliability, Validity, and Correlates of Newly Developed Testing Protocols', *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 17(1), pp. 294- 309.
- Kubo, K., Kanehisa, H., Kawakami, Y. and Fukunaga, T. (2001) 'Growth changes in the elastic properties of human tendon structures', *International journal of sports medicine*, 22(2), pp. 138-143.
- Kubo, K., Teshima, T., Ikebukuro, T., Hirose, N. and Tsunoda, N. (2014) 'Tendon properties and muscle architecture for knee extensors and plantar flexors in boys and men', *Clinical biomechanics (Bristol, Avon)*, 29(5), pp. 506-511.
- Kumagai, K., Abe, T., Brechue, W. F., Ryushi, T., Takano, S. and Mizuno, M. (2000) 'Sprint performance is related to muscle fascicle length in male 100-m sprinters', *Journal of applied physiology (Bethesda, Md. : 1985)*, 88(3), pp. 811-816.
- Kwah, L. K., Pinto, R. Z., Diong, J. and Herbert, R. D. (2013) 'Reliability and validity of ultrasound measurements of muscle fascicle length and pennation in humans: a systematic review', *Journal of applied physiology (Bethesda, Md. : 1985)*, 114(6), pp. 761- 769.
- Köklü, Y., Aşçi, A., Koçak, F. U., Alemdaroğlu, U. and Dündar, U. (2011) 'Comparison of the physiological responses to different small-sided games in elite young soccer players', *Journal of strength and conditioning research*, 25(6), pp. 1522-1528.
- Lacome, M., Avrillon, S., Cholley, Y., Simpson, B. M., Guilhem, G. and Buchheit, M. (2019) 'Hamstring Eccentric Strengthening Program: Does Training Volume Matter?', *International journal of sports physiology and performance*, pp. 1- 27.
- Lauber, B., Keller, M., Leukel, C., Gollhofer, A. and Taube, W. (2013) 'Specific interpretation of augmented feedback changes motor performance and cortical processing', *Experimental brain research*, 227(1), pp. 31-41.
- Legerlotz, K., Marzilger, R., Bohm, S. and Arampatzis, A. (2016) 'Physiological Adaptations following Resistance Training in Youth Athletes-A Narrative Review', *Pediatric exercise science*, 28(4), pp. 501- 520.
- Legerlotz, K., Smith, H. K. and Hing, W. A. (2010) 'Variation and reliability of ultrasonographic quantification of the architecture of the medial gastrocnemius muscle in young children', *Clinical physiology and functional imaging*, 30(3), pp. 198- 205.
- Leotti, L. A. and Delgado, M. R. (2011) 'The inherent reward of choice', *Psychological science*, 22(10), pp. 1310- 1318.
- Lewthwaite, R., Chiviawsky, S., Drews, R. and Wulf, G. (2015) 'Choose to move: The motivational impact of autonomy support on motor learning', *Psychonomic bulletin & review*, 22(5), pp. 1383- 2388.
- Lewthwaite, R. and Wulf, G. (2010) 'Grand challenge for movement science and sport psychology: embracing the social-cognitive-affective-motor nature of motor behavior', *Frontiers in psychology*, 1, pp. 1-3.

- Lichtwark, G. (2018) *Ultrasound technology for examining the mechanics of the muscle, tendon, and ligament. Handbook of human motion* Cham: Springer, p. 1- 20.
- Lieber, R. L. and Fridén, J. (2000) 'Functional and clinical significance of skeletal muscle architecture', *Muscle & nerve*, 23(11), pp. 1647- 1666.
- Lieber, R. L. and Ward, S. R. (2011) 'Skeletal muscle design to meet functional demands', *Philosophical transactions of the Royal Society of London. Series B, Biological sciences*, 366(1570), pp. 1466- 1476.
- Lloyd, R. S., Oliver, J. L., Faigenbaum, A. D., Howard, R., De Ste Croix, M. B., Williams, C. A., Best, T. M., Alvar, B. A., Micheli, L. J., Thomas, D. P., Hatfield, D. L., Cronin, J. B. and Myer, G. D. (2015) 'Long-term athletic development- part 1: a pathway for all youth', *Journal of strength and conditioning research*, 29(5), pp. 1439-1450.
- Lloyd, R. S., Oliver, J. L., Hughes, M. G. and Williams, C. A. (2009) 'Reliability and validity of field-based measures of leg stiffness and reactive strength index in youths', *Journal of sports sciences*, 27(14), pp. 1565- 1573.
- Lloyd, R. S., Radnor, J. M., De Ste Croix, M. B., Cronin, J. B. and Oliver, J. L. (2016) 'Changes in Sprint and Jump Performances After Traditional, Plyometric, and Combined Resistance Training in Male Youth Pre- and Post-Peak Height Velocity', *Journal of strength and conditioning research*, 30(5), pp. 1239- 1247.
- Lockie, R. G., Schultz, A. B., Callaghan, S. J., Jeffriess, M. D. and Berry, S. P. (2013) 'Reliability and validity of a new test of change-of-direction speed for field-based sports: the change-of-direction and acceleration test (CODAT)', *Journal of sports science & medicine*, 12(1), pp. 88.
- Lum, D., Barbosa, T. M. and Balasekaran, G. (2021) 'Sprint Kayaking Performance Enhancement by Isometric Strength Training Inclusion: A Randomized Controlled Trial', *Sports (Basel, Switzerland)*, 9(2).
- Lum, D., Haff, G. G. and Barbosa, T. M. (2020) 'The Relationship between Isometric Force-Time Characteristics and Dynamic Performance: A Systematic Review', *Sports (Basel)*, 8(5).
- Lynch, A. E., Davies, R. W., Jakeman, P. M., Locke, T., Allardyce, J. M. and Carson, B. P. (2021) 'The Influence of Maximal Strength and Knee Angle on the Reliability of Peak Force in the Isometric Squat', *Sports (Basel, Switzerland)*, 9(10).
- Maffiuletti, N. A., Aagaard, P., Blazevich, A. J., Folland, J., Tillin, N. and Duchateau, J. (2016) 'Rate of force development: physiological and methodological considerations', *European journal of applied physiology*, 116(6), pp. 1091 1116.
- Malina, R. M. and Bouchard, C. (2004) *Growth, Maturation, and Physical Activity*. Human Kinetics.
- Malina, R. M., Bouchard, C. and Bar-Or, O. (2004) *Growth, Maturation, and Physical Activity*. Champaign, IL: Human Kinetics.

- Malina, R. M., Eisenmann, J. C., Cumming, S. P., Ribeiro, B. and Aroso, J. (2004) 'Maturity-associated variation in the growth and functional capacities of youth football (soccer) players 13-15 years', *European journal of applied physiology*, 91(5-6), pp. 555- 562.
- Malina, R. M. and Kozieł, S. M. (2014a) 'Validation of maturity offset in a longitudinal sample of Polish boys', *Journal of sports sciences*, 32(5), pp. 424- 437.
- Malina, R. M. and Kozieł, S. M. (2014b) 'Validation of maturity offset in a longitudinal sample of Polish girls', *Journal of sports sciences*, 32(14), pp. 1374- 1382.
- Malina, R. M., Ribeiro, B., Aroso, J. and Cumming, S. P. (2007) 'Characteristics of youth soccer players aged 13-15 years classified by skill level', *British journal of sports medicine*, 41(5), pp. 290- 295.
- Marcora, S. and Miller, M. K. (2000) 'The effect of knee angle on the external validity of isometric measures of lower body neuromuscular function', *Journal of sports sciences*, 18(5), pp. 313- 319.
- Marián, V., Katarína, L., Dávid, O., Matúš, K. and Simon, W. (2016) 'Improved Maximum Strength, Vertical Jump and Sprint Performance after 8 Weeks of Jump Squat Training with Individualized Loads', *Journal of sports science & medicine*, 15(3), pp. 492-500.
- Markovic, G., Jukic, I., Milanovic, D. and Metikos, D. (2007) 'Effects of sprint and plyometric training on muscle function and athletic performance', *Journal of strength and conditioning research*, 21(2), pp. 543- 549.
- Marshall, J., Turner, A. N., Jarvis, P. T., Maloney, S. J., Cree, J. A. and Bishop, C. J. (2019) 'Postactivation Potentiation and Change of Direction Speed in Elite Academy Rugby Players', *Journal of strength and conditioning research*, 33(6), pp. 1551- 1556.
- Marshall, P. W., Robbins, D. A., Wrightson, A. W. and Siegler, J. C. (2012) 'Acute neuromuscular and fatigue responses to the rest-pause method', *Journal of science and medicine in sport*, 15(2), pp. 153- 158.
- Mauras, N., Hayes, V., Welch, S., Rini, A., Helgeson, K., Dokler, M., Veldhuis, J. D. and Urban, R. J. (1998) 'Testosterone deficiency in young men: marked alterations in whole body protein kinetics, strength, and adiposity', *The Journal of clinical endocrinology and metabolism*, 83(6), pp. 1886- 1892.
- McCarthy, H. D., Samani-Radia, D., Jebb, S. A. and Prentice, A. M. (2014) 'Skeletal muscle mass reference curves for children and adolescents', *Pediatric obesity*, 9(4), pp. 249- 259.
- McDonough, M. H. and Crocker, P. R. (2007) 'Testing self-determined motivation as a mediator of the relationship between psychological needs and affective and behavioral outcomes', *Journal of sport & exercise psychology*, 29(5), pp. 645- 663.
- McGinnis, P. M. (2013) *Technology in biomechanics. Biomechanics of sport and exercise* Champaign: Human Kinetics, p. 361- 370.
- McKinlay, B. J., Wallace, P., Dotan, R., Long, D., Tokuno, C., Gabriel, D. A. and Falk, B. (2018) 'Effects of Plyometric and Resistance Training on Muscle Strength, Explosiveness, and

Neuromuscular Function in Young Adolescent Soccer Players', *Journal of strength and conditioning research*, 32(11), pp. 3039- 3050.

McMahon, J. J., Suchomel, T. J., Lake, J. P. and Comfort, P. (2018) 'Understanding the key phases of the countermovement jump force-time curve', *Strength & Conditioning Journal*, 40(4), pp. 96-106.

McMaster, D. T., Gill, N., Cronin, J. and McGuigan, M. (2014) 'A Brief Review of Strength and Ballistic Assessment Methodologies in Sport', *Sports Medicine*, 44(5), pp. 603-623.

McNamara, J. M. and Stearne, D. J. (2010) 'Flexible nonlinear periodization in a beginner college weight training class', *Journal of strength and conditioning research*, 24(1), pp. 17 -22.

Mendez-Villanueva, A., Buchheit, M., Kuitunen, S., Douglas, A., Peltola, E. and Bourdon, P. (2011a) 'Age-related differences in acceleration, maximum running speed, and repeated-sprint performance in young soccer players', *Journal of sports sciences*, 29(5), pp. 477- 484.

Mendez-Villanueva, A., Buchheit, M., Simpson, B. and Bourdon, P. C. (2013) 'Match play intensity distribution in youth soccer', *International journal of sports medicine*, 34(2), pp. 101-110.

Mendez-Villanueva, A., Buchheit, M., Simpson, B., Peltola, E. and Bourdon, P. (2011b) 'Does on-field sprinting performance in young soccer players depend on how fast they can run or how fast they do run?', *Journal of strength and conditioning research*, 25(9), pp. 2634- 2638.

Mendiguchia, J., Conceição, F., Edouard, P., Fonseca, M., Pereira, R., Lopes, H., Morin, J. B. and Jiménez-Reyes, P. (2020) 'Sprint versus isolated eccentric training: Comparative effects on hamstring architecture and performance in soccer players', *PloS one*, 15(2).

Mersmann, F., Bohm, S., Schroll, A., Boeth, H., Duda, G. and Arampatzis, A. (2014) 'Evidence of imbalanced adaptation between muscle and tendon in adolescent athletes', *Scandinavian journal of medicine & science in sports*, 24(4).

Mersmann, F., Bohm, S., Schroll, A., Boeth, H., Duda, G. N. and Arampatzis, A. (2017) 'Muscle and tendon adaptation in adolescent athletes: A longitudinal study', *Scandinavian journal of medicine & science in sports*, 27(1), pp. 75- 82.

Metaxas, T. I., Mandroukas, A., Vamvakoudis, E., Kotoglou, K., Ekblom, B. and Mandroukas, K. (2014) 'Muscle fiber characteristics, satellite cells and soccer performance in young athletes', *Journal of sports science & medicine*, 13(3), pp. 493- 501.

Meyers, R. W., Oliver, J. L., Hughes, M. G., Cronin, J. B. and Lloyd, R. S. (2015) 'Maximal sprint speed in boys of increasing maturity', *Pediatric exercise science*, 27(1), pp. 85- 94.

Meyers, R. W., Oliver, J. L., Hughes, M. G., Lloyd, R. S. and Cronin, J. B. (2016) 'The Influence of Maturation on Sprint Performance in Boys over a 21-Month Period', *Medicine & Science in Sports & Exercise*, 48(12), pp. 2555-2562.

Meylan, C. M., Cronin, J. B., Oliver, J. L., Hopkins, W. G. and Contreras, B. (2014) 'The effect of maturation on adaptations to strength training and detraining in 11-15-year-olds', *Scandinavian journal of medicine & science in sports*, 24(3), pp. e156- 164.

- Meylan, C. M., Cronin, J. B., Oliver, J. L., Hughes, M. G. and McMaster, D. T. (2012) 'The reliability of jump kinematics and kinetics in children of different maturity status', *Journal of strength and conditioning research*, 26(4), pp. 1015- 1026.
- Mirwald, R. L., Baxter-Jones, A. D., Bailey, D. A. and Beunen, G. P. (2002) 'An assessment of maturity from anthropometric measurements', *Medicine and science in sports and exercise*, 34(4), pp. 689- 694.
- Mitchell, C., Cohen, R., Dotan, R., Gabriel, D., Klentrou, P. and Falk, B. (2011) 'Rate of muscle activation in power- and endurance-trained boys', *International journal of sports physiology and performance*, 6(1), pp. 94- 105.
- Mogi, Y. and Wakahara, T. (2022) 'Effects of growth on muscle architecture of knee extensors', *Journal of anatomy*, 241(3), pp. 683-691.
- Moran, J., Sandercock, G. R., Ramírez-Campillo, R., Meylan, C., Collison, J. and Parry, D. A. (2017a) 'A meta-analysis of maturation-related variation in adolescent boy athletes' adaptations to short-term resistance training', *Journal of sports sciences*, 35(11), pp. 1041- 1051.
- Moran, J., Sandercock, G. R. H., Ramírez-Campillo, R., Wooller, J. J., Logothetis, S., Schoenmakers, P. P. J. M. and Parry, D. A. (2018) 'Maturation-Related Differences in Adaptations to Resistance Training in Young Male Swimmers', *Journal of strength and conditioning research*, 32(1), pp. 139- 149.
- Moran, J. J., Sandercock, G. R., Ramírez-Campillo, R., Meylan, C. M., Collison, J. A. and Parry, D. A. (2017b) 'Age-Related Variation in Male Youth Athletes' Countermovement Jump After Plyometric Training: A Meta-Analysis of Controlled Trials', *Journal of strength and conditioning research*, 31(2), pp. 552- 565.
- Morgan, O. J., Drust, B., Ade, J. D. and Robinson, M. A. (2022) 'Change of direction frequency off the ball: new perspectives in elite youth soccer', *Science & medicine in football*, 6(4), pp. 473-482.
- Moritani, T. and deVries, H. A. (1979) 'Neural factors versus hypertrophy in the time course of muscle strength gain', *American journal of physical medicine*, 58(3), pp. 115- 130.
- Morris, R., Emmonds, S., Jones, B., Myers, T. D., Clarke, N. D., Lake, J., Ellis, M., Singleton, D., Roe, G. and Till, K. (2018a) 'Seasonal changes in physical qualities of elite youth soccer players according to maturity status: comparisons with aged matched controls', *Science and Medicine in Football*, 2(4), pp. 272-280.
- Morris, R. O., Jones, B., Myers, T., Lake, J., Emmonds, S., Clarke, N. D., Singleton, D., Ellis, M. and Till, K. (2018b) 'Isometric Midhigh Pull Characteristics in Elite Youth Male Soccer Players: Comparisons by Age and Maturity Offset', *Journal of strength and conditioning research*, 0(0), pp. 1- 9.
- Mota, J. A., Stock, M. S. and Thompson, B. J. (2017) 'Vastus lateralis and rectus femoris echo intensity fail to reflect knee extensor specific tension in middle-school boys', *Physiological measurement*, 38(8), pp. 1529- 1541.
- Murray, P. G. and Clayton, P. E. (2013) 'Endocrine control of growth', *American journal of medical genetics. Part C, Seminars in medical genetics*, 163C(2), pp. 76-85.

- Murtagh, C. F., Brownlee, T. E., O'Boyle, A., Morgans, R., Drust, B. and Erskine, R. M. (2018a) 'Importance of Speed and Power in Elite Youth Soccer Depends on Maturation Status', *Journal of strength and conditioning research*, 32(2), pp. 297- 303.
- Murtagh, C. F., Nulty, C., Vanrenterghem, J., O'Boyle, A., Morgans, R., Drust, B. and Erskine, R. M. (2018b) 'The Neuromuscular Determinants of Unilateral Jump Performance in Soccer Players Are Direction-Specific', *International journal of sports physiology and performance*, 13(5), pp. 604-611.
- Musham, C. and Fitzpatrick, J. F. (2020) 'Familiarisation and reliability of the isometric mid-thigh pull in elite youth soccer players', *Sports Perf Sci Reports*, 85, pp. 1-4.
- Narici, M. (1999) 'Human skeletal muscle architecture studied in vivo by non-invasive imaging techniques: functional significance and applications', *Journal of electromyography and kinesiology : official journal of the International Society of Electrophysiological Kinesiology*, 9(2), pp. 97- 103.
- Narici, M. V., Hoppeler, H., Kayser, B., Landoni, L., Claassen, H., Gavardi, C., Conti, M. and Cerretelli, P. (1996) 'Human quadriceps cross-sectional area, torque and neural activation during 6 months strength training', *Acta physiologica Scandinavica*, 157(2), pp. 175- 186.
- Nasirzade, A., Ehsanbakhsh, A., Ilbeygi, S., Sobhkhiz, A., Argavani, H. and Aliakbari, M. (2014) 'Relationship between sprint performance of front crawl swimming and muscle fascicle length in young swimmers', *Journal of sports science & medicine*, 13(3), pp. 550-556.
- Ngan, D. C., Kharbanda, O. P., Geenty, J. P. and Darendeliler, M. A. (2003) 'Comparison of radiation levels from computed tomography and conventional dental radiographs', *Australian orthodontic journal*, 19(2), pp. 67- 75.
- Nimphius, S., McBride, J. M., Rice, P. E., Goodman-Capps, C. L. and Capps, C. R. (2019) 'Comparison of Quadriceps and Hamstring Muscle Activity during an Isometric Squat between Strength-Matched Men and Women', *Journal of sports science & medicine*, 18(1), pp. 101-108.
- Noon, M. R., James, R. S., Clarke, N. D., Akubat, I. and Thake, C. D. (2015) 'Perceptions of well-being and physical performance in English elite youth footballers across a season', *Journal of sports sciences*, 33(20), pp. 2106-2115.
- Noorkoiv, M., Nosaka, K. and Blazevich, A. J. (2010) 'Assessment of quadriceps muscle cross-sectional area by ultrasound extended-field-of-view imaging', *European journal of applied physiology*, 109(4), pp. 631- 639.
- Norman, G. R., Wyrwich, K. W. and Patrick, D. L. (2007) 'The mathematical relationship among different forms of responsiveness coefficients', *Quality of life research : an international journal of quality of life aspects of treatment, care and rehabilitation*, 16(5), pp. 815- 822.
- Nuzzo, J. L., McBride, J. M., Cormie, P. and McCaulley, G. O. (2008) 'Relationship between countermovement jump performance and multijoint isometric and dynamic tests of strength', *Journal of strength and conditioning research*, 22(3), pp. 699- 707.

- O'Brien, T. D., Reeves, N. D., Baltzopoulos, V., Jones, D. A. and Maganaris, C. N. (2009) 'Strong relationships exist between muscle volume, joint power and whole-body external mechanical power in adults and children', *Experimental physiology*, 94(6), pp. 731-738.
- O'Brien, T. D., Reeves, N. D., Baltzopoulos, V., Jones, D. A. and Maganaris, C. N. (2010a) 'In vivo measurements of muscle specific tension in adults and children', *Experimental physiology*, 95(1), pp. 202- 210.
- O'Brien, T. D., Reeves, N. D., Baltzopoulos, V., Jones, D. A. and Maganaris, C. N. (2010b) 'Muscle-tendon structure and dimensions in adults and children', *Journal of anatomy*, 216(5), pp. 631- 642.
- Onate, J. A., Guskiewicz, K. M. and Sullivan, R. J. (2001) 'Augmented feedback reduces jump landing forces', *The Journal of orthopaedic and sports physical therapy*, 31(9), pp. 511-517.
- Ortqvist, M., Gutierrez-Farewik, E. M., Farewik, M., Jansson, A., Bartonek, A. and Broström, E. (2007) 'Reliability of a new instrument for measuring plantarflexor muscle strength', *Archives of physical medicine and rehabilitation*, 88(9), pp. 1164-1170.
- Osgnach, C., Poser, S., Bernardini, R., Rinaldo, R. and di Prampero, P. E. (2010) 'Energy cost and metabolic power in elite soccer: a new match analysis approach', *Medicine and science in sports and exercise*, 42(1), pp. 170- 178.
- Ozmun, J. C., Mikesky, A. E. and Surburg, P. R. (1994) 'Neuromuscular adaptations following prepubescent strength training', *Medicine and science in sports and exercise*, 26(4), pp. 510-514.
- Palmer, T. B., Pineda, J. G. and Durham, R. M. (2018) 'Effects of Knee Position on the Reliability and Production of Maximal and Rapid Strength Characteristics During an Isometric Squat Test', *Journal of applied biomechanics*, 34(2), pp. 111-117.
- Panidi, I., Bogdanis, G. C., Gaspari, V., Spiliopoulou, P., Donti, A., Terzis, G. and Donti, O. (2020) 'Gastrocnemius Medialis Architectural Properties in Flexibility Trained and Not Trained Child Female Athletes: A Pilot Study', *Sports (Basel, Switzerland)*, 8(3).
- Panidi, I., Bogdanis, G. C., Terzis, G., Donti, A., Konrad, A., Gaspari, V. and Donti, O. (2021) 'Muscle Architectural and Functional Adaptations Following 12-Weeks of Stretching in Adolescent Female Athletes', *Frontiers in physiology*, 12.
- Parr, J., Winwood, K., Hodson-Tole, E., Deconinck, F. J. A., Parry, L., Hill, J. P., Malina, R. M. and Cumming, S. P. (2020) 'Predicting the timing of the peak of the pubertal growth spurt in elite youth soccer players: evaluation of methods', *Annals of human biology*, pp. 1- 23.
- Patterson, J. T. and Carter, M. (2010) 'Learner regulated knowledge of results during the acquisition of multiple timing goals', *Human movement science*, 29(2), pp. 214- 227.
- Paul, D. J. and Nassis, G. P. (2015) 'Physical Fitness Testing in Youth Soccer: Issues and Considerations Regarding Reliability, Validity and Sensitivity', *Pediatric exercise science*, 27(3), pp. 301- 313.

Pekünlü, E. and Ozsu, I. (2014) 'Avoiding Systematic Errors in Isometric Squat-Related Studies without Pre-Familiarization by Using Sufficient Numbers of Trials', *Journal of human kinetics*, 42, pp. 201- 213.

Pettersen, S. A. and Brenn, T. (2019) 'Activity Profiles by Position in Youth Elite Soccer Players in Official Matches', *Sports medicine international open*, 3(1), pp. E19- E24.

Peña-González, I., Fernández-Fernández, J., Cervelló, E. and Moya-Ramón, M. (2019) 'Effect of biological maturation on strength-related adaptations in young soccer players', *PloS one*, 14(7).

Philippaerts, R. M., Vaeyens, R., Janssens, M., Van Renterghem, B., Matthys, D., Craen, R., Bourgois, J., Vrijens, J., Beunen, G. and Malina, R. M. (2006) 'The relationship between peak height velocity and physical performance in youth soccer players', *Journal of sports sciences*, 24(3), pp. 221- 230.

Portney, L. G. and Watkins, M. P. (2000) *Foundations of clinical research: applications to practice*. Oxford: Blackwell Science Ltd.

Post, P. G., Fairbrother, J. T., Barros, J. A. C. and Kulpa, J. D. (2014) 'Self-controlled practice within a fixed time period facilitates the learning of a basketball set shot', *Journal of Motor Learning and Development*, 2(1), pp. 9-15.

Pérez-Castilla, A., Rojas, F. J., Gómez-Martínez, F. and García-Ramos, A. (2021) 'Vertical jump performance is affected by the velocity and depth of the countermovement', *Sports biomechanics*, 20(8), pp. 1015-1030.

Radnor, J. M., Lloyd, R. S. and Oliver, J. L. (2017) 'Individual Response to Different Forms of Resistance Training in School-Aged Boys', *Journal of strength and conditioning research*, 31(3), pp. 787- 797.

Radnor, J. M., Oliver, J., Waugh, C., Myer, G. and Lloyd, R. (2020) 'The Influence of Maturity Status on Muscle Architecture in School-Aged Boys.', *Pediatric exercise science.*, pp. 1- 8.

Radnor, J. M., Oliver, J. L., Waugh, C. M., Myer, G. D. and Lloyd, R. S. (2022) 'Muscle Architecture and Maturation Influence Sprint and Jump Ability in Young Boys: A Multistudy Approach', *Journal of strength and conditioning research*, 36(10), pp. 2741-2751.

Ramsay, J. A., Blimkie, C. J., Smith, K., Garner, S., MacDougall, J. D. and Sale, D. G. (1990) 'Strength training effects in prepubescent boys', *Medicine and science in sports and exercise*, 22(5), pp. 605- 514.

Ramírez-Campillo, R., Vergara-Pedrerros, M., Henríquez-Olguín, C., Martínez-Salazar, C., Alvarez, C., Nakamura, F. Y., De La Fuente, C. I., Caniuqueo, A., Alonso-Martinez, A. M. and Izquierdo, M. (2016) 'Effects of plyometric training on maximal-intensity exercise and endurance in male and female soccer players', *Journal of sports sciences*, 34(8), pp. 687- 693.

Rauch, J. T., Ugrinowitsch, C., Barakat, C. I., Alvarez, M. R., Brummert, D. L., Aube, D. W., Barsuhn, A. S., Hayes, D., Tricoli, V. and De Souza, E. O. (2020) 'Auto-Regulated Exercise Selection Training Regimen Produces Small Increases in Lean Body Mass and Maximal Strength Adaptations in Strength-trained Individuals', *Journal of strength and conditioning research*, 34(4), pp. 1133-1140.

- Reilly, T., Williams, A. M., Nevill, A. and Franks, A. (2000) 'A multidisciplinary approach to talent identification in soccer', *Journal of sports sciences*, 18(9), pp. 695- 702.
- Ripley, N. J., Cuthbert, M., Comfort, P. and McMahon, J. J. (2023) 'Effect of additional Nordic hamstring exercise or sprint training on the modifiable risk factors of hamstring strain injuries and performance', *PloS one*, 18(3).
- Ritsche, P., Bernhard, T., Roth, R., Lichtenstein, E., Keller, M., Zingg, S., Franchi, M. V. and Faude, O. (2021) 'M. Biceps Femoris Long Head Architecture and Sprint Ability in Youth Soccer Players', *International journal of sports physiology and performance*, 16(11), pp. 1616-1624.
- Robbins, D. W. (2012) 'Relationships between National Football League combine performance measures', *Journal of strength and conditioning research*, 26(1), pp. 226- 231.
- Robertson, D. G. E., Caldwell, G. E., Hamill, J., Kamen, G. and Whittlesey, S. (2013) *Signal processing. Research methods in biomechanics* Champaign: Human kinetics, p. 227- 238.
- Rock, K., Nelson, C., Addison, O. and Marchese, V. (2021) 'Assessing the Reliability of Handheld Dynamometry and Ultrasonography to Measure Quadriceps Strength and Muscle Thickness in Children, Adolescents, and Young Adults', *Physical & occupational therapy in pediatrics*, 41(5), pp. 540-554.
- Rodríguez-Rosell, D., Pareja-Blanco, F., Aagaard, P. and González-Badillo, J. J. (2018) 'Physiological and methodological aspects of rate of force development assessment in human skeletal muscle', *Clinical physiology and functional imaging*, 38(5), pp. 743-762.
- Rumpf, M. C., Cronin, J. B., Oliver, J. L. and Hughes, M. (2011) 'Assessing youth sprint ability-methodological issues, reliability and performance data', *Pediatric exercise science*, 23(4), pp. 442- 467.
- Ryan, D., Lewin, C., Forsythe, S. and McCall, A. (2018) 'Developing world-class soccer players: An example of the academy physical development program from an English premier league team', *Strength & Conditioning Journal*, 40(3), pp. 2-11.
- Sander, A., Keiner, M., Wirth, K. and Schmidtbleicher, D. (2013) 'Influence of a 2-year strength training programme on power performance in elite youth soccer players', *European journal of sport science*, 13(5), pp. 445- 451.
- Schmidt, R. A., Lee, T. D., Winstein, C., Wulf, G. and Zelaznik, H. N. (2018) *Motor control and learning: A behavioral emphasis*. Human kinetics.
- Schneider, M. L. and Kwan, B. M. (2013) 'Psychological need satisfaction, intrinsic motivation and affective response to exercise in adolescents', *Psychology of sport and exercise*, 14(5), pp. 776- 785.
- Secomb, J. L., Farley, O. R., Nimphius, S., Lundgren, L., Tran, T. T. and Sheppard, J. M. (2017) 'The training-specific adaptations resulting from resistance training, gymnastics and plyometric training, and non-training in adolescent athletes', *International Journal of Sports Science & Coaching*, 12(6), pp. 762- 773.

Secomb, J. L., Nimphius, S., Farley, O. R., Lundgren, L. E., Tran, T. T. and Sheppard, J. M. (2015a) 'Relationships Between Lower-Body Muscle Structure And, Lower-Body Strength, Explosiveness and Eccentric Leg Stiffness in Adolescent Athletes', *Journal of sports science & medicine*, 14(4), pp. 691-697.

Secomb, J. L., Nimphius, S., Farley, O. R. L., Lundgren, L., Tran, T. T., Parsonage, J. and Sheppard, J. M. (2015b) 'Three weeks cessation from strength training in adolescent athletes increases lower-body isometric strength', 23(6), pp. 26- 29.

Sekine, Y., Hoshikawa, S. and Hirose, N. (2019) 'Longitudinal Age-Related Morphological and Physiological Changes in Adolescent Male Basketball Players', *Journal of Sports Science and Medicine*, 18(4), pp. 751-757.

Seo, D. I., Kim, E., Fahs, C. A., Rossow, L., Young, K., Ferguson, S. L., Thiebaud, R., Sherk, V. D., Loenneke, J. P., Kim, D., Lee, M. K., Choi, K. H., Bemben, D. A., Bemben, M. G. and So, W. Y. (2012) 'Reliability of the one-repetition maximum test based on muscle group and gender', *Journal of sports science & medicine*, 11(2), pp. 221- 225.

Seynnes, O. R., de Boer, M. and Narici, M. V. (2007) 'Early skeletal muscle hypertrophy and architectural changes in response to high-intensity resistance training', *Journal of applied physiology (Bethesda, Md. : 1985)*, 102(1), pp. 368- 373.

Sherwood, C., Read, P., Till, K., Paxton, K., Keenan, J. and Turner, A. (2020) 'Strength, power and speed characteristics in Elite Academy Soccer', *Journal of Australian Strength and Conditioning*.

Siddle, J., Weaver, K., Greig, M., Harper, D. and Brogden, C. M. (2022) 'A low-volume Nordic hamstring curl programme improves change of direction ability, despite no architectural, strength or speed adaptations in elite youth soccer players', *Research in sports medicine (Print)*, pp. 1-12.

Silva, M. N., Markland, D., Carraça, E. V., Vieira, P. N., Coutinho, S. R., Minderico, C. S., Matos, M. G., Sardinha, L. B. and Teixeira, P. J. (2011) 'Exercise autonomous motivation predicts 3-yr weight loss in women', *Medicine and science in sports and exercise*, 43(4), pp. 728- 737.

Smidt, G. L. (1973) 'Biomechanical analysis of knee flexion and extension', *Journal of biomechanics*, 6(1), pp. 79- 92.

Spiteri, T., Hart, N. H. and Nimphius, S. (2014) 'Offensive and defensive agility: a sex comparison of lower body kinematics and ground reaction forces', *Journal of applied biomechanics*, 30(4), pp. 514- 520.

Stafilidis, S. and Arampatzis, A. (2007) 'Muscle - tendon unit mechanical and morphological properties and sprint performance', *Journal of sports sciences*, 25(9), pp. 1035-1046.

Stock, M. S., Mota, J. A., Hernandez, J. M. and Thompson, B. J. (2017) 'Echo intensity and muscle thickness as predictors Of athleticism and isometric strength in middle-school boys', *Muscle & nerve*, 55(5), pp. 685- 692.

Stone, M. H., Sanborn, K., O'Bryant, H. S., Hartman, M., Stone, M. E., Proulx, C., Ward, B. and Hruby, J. (2003) 'Maximum strength-power-performance relationships in collegiate throwers', *Journal of strength and conditioning research*, 17(4), pp. 739- 745.

Stone, M. H., Sands, W. A. and Stone, M. E. (2007) *Principles and practice of strength-power training*. Champaign, IL: Human Kinetics.

Street, G., McMillan, S., Board, W., Rasmussen, M. and Heneghan, J. M. (2001) 'Sources of error in determining countermovement jump height with the impulse method', *Journal of Applied Biomechanics*, 17(1), pp. 43-54.

Stølen, T., Chamari, K., Castagna, C. and Wisløff, U. (2005a) 'Physiology of soccer: an update', *Sports medicine (Auckland, N.Z.)*, 35(6), pp. 501-536.

Stølen, T., Karim Chamari, K., Castagna, C. and Wisløff, U. (2005b) 'Physiology of soccer: an update.', *Sports Medicine.*, 35(6), pp. 501- 536.

Tang, R., Murtagh, C., Warrington, G., Cable, T., Morgan, O., O'Boyle, A., Burgess, D., Morgans, R. and Drust, B. (2018) 'Directional Change Mediates the Physiological Response to High-Intensity Shuttle Running in Professional Soccer Players', *Sports (Basel, Switzerland)*, 6(2).

Tanner, J. M., Whitehouse, R., Cameron, N., Marshall, W., Healy, M. and Goldstein, H. (2001) *Assessment of skeletal maturity and prediction of adult height (TW2 method)*. Saunders London.

Taylor, K. L., Cronin, J., Gill, N. D., Chapman, D. W. and Sheppard, J. (2010) 'Sources of variability in iso-inertial jump assessments', *International journal of sports physiology and performance*, 5(4), pp. 546- 558.

Thom, J. M., Morse, C. I., Birch, K. M. and Narici, M. V. (2007) 'Influence of muscle architecture on the torque and power-velocity characteristics of young and elderly men', *European journal of applied physiology*, 100(5), pp. 613-619.

Thomas, C., Comfort, P., Chiang, C. and Jones, P. (2015) 'Relationship between isometric mid-thigh pull variables and sprint and change of direction performance in collegiate athletes.', *Journal of Trainology.*, 4(1), pp. 6- 10.

Thomas, C., Dos'Santos, T., Comfort, P. and Jones, P. A. (2017) 'Between-Session Reliability of Common Strength- and Power-Related Measures in Adolescent Athletes', *Sports (Basel, Switzerland)*, 5(1).

Tillin, N. A., Pain, M. T. and Folland, J. (2013) 'Explosive force production during isometric squats correlates with athletic performance in rugby union players', *Journal of sports sciences*, 31(1), pp. 66- 76.

Timmins, R. G., Shield, A. J., Williams, M. D., Lorenzen, C. and Opar, D. A. (2016) 'Architectural adaptations of muscle to training and injury: a narrative review outlining the contributions by fascicle length, pennation angle and muscle thickness', *British journal of sports medicine*, 50(23), pp. 1467- 1472.

- Tonson, A., Ratel, S., Le Fur, Y., Cozzone, P. and Bendahan, D. (2008) 'Effect of maturation on the relationship between muscle size and force production', *Medicine and science in sports and exercise*, 40(5), pp. 918-925.
- Travis, S. K., Mujika, I., Zwetsloot, K. A., Gentles, J. A., Stone, M. H. and Bazyler, C. D. (2022) 'The Effects of 3 vs. 5 Days of Training Cessation on Maximal Strength', *Journal of strength and conditioning research*, 36(3), pp. 633-640.
- Travis, S. K., Zwetsloot, K. A., Mujika, I., Stone, M. H. and Bazyler, C. D. (2021) 'Skeletal Muscle Adaptations and Performance Outcomes Following a Step and Exponential Taper in Strength Athletes', *Frontiers in physiology*, 12.
- Tsoukos, A., Bogdanis, G. C., Terzis, G. and Veligeas, P. (2016) 'Acute Improvement of Vertical Jump Performance After Isometric Squats Depends on Knee Angle and Vertical Jumping Ability', *Journal of strength and conditioning research*, 30(8), pp. 2250- 2257.
- Unnithan, V., White, J., Georgiou, A., Iga, J. and Drust, B. (2012) 'Talent identification in youth soccer', *Journal of sports sciences*, 30(15), pp. 1719-1726.
- Vaeyens, R., Philippaerts, R. M. and Malina, R. M. (2005) 'The relative age effect in soccer: a match-related perspective', *Journal of sports sciences*, 23(7), pp. 747- 756.
- van Dijk, H., Mulder, T. and Hermens, H. J. (2007) 'Effects of age and content of augmented feedback on learning an isometric force-production task', *Experimental aging research*, 33(3), pp. 341-353.
- Van Hooren, B., Teratsias, P. and Hodson-Tole, E. F. (2020) 'Ultrasound imaging to assess skeletal muscle architecture during movements: a systematic review of methods, reliability, and challenges', *Journal of applied physiology (Bethesda, Md. : 1985)*, 128(4), pp. 978- 999.
- Vanrenterghem, J., Nedergaard, N. J., Robinson, M. A. and Drust, B. (2017) 'Training Load Monitoring in Team Sports: A Novel Framework Separating Physiological and Biomechanical Load-Adaptation Pathways', *Sports medicine (Auckland, N.Z.)*, 47(11), pp. 2135-2142.
- Verdijk, L. B., Snijders, T., Drost, M., Delhaas, T., Kadi, F. and van Loon, L. J. (2014) 'Satellite cells in human skeletal muscle; from birth to old age', *Age (Dordrecht, Netherlands)*, 36(2), pp. 545- 547.
- Vigh-Larsen, J. F., Dalgas, U. and Andersen, T. B. (2018a) 'Position-Specific Acceleration and Deceleration Profiles in Elite Youth and Senior Soccer Players', *Journal of strength and conditioning research*, 32(4), pp. 1114- 1122.
- Vigh-Larsen, J. F., Dalgas, U. and Andersen, T. B. (2018b) 'Position-Specific Acceleration and Deceleration Profiles in Elite Youth and Senior Soccer Players', *Journal of strength and conditioning research*, 32(4), pp. 1114-1122.
- Vlachopoulos, S. P. and Michailidou, S. (2006) 'Development and initial validation of a measure of autonomy, competence, and relatedness in exercise: The Basic Psychological Needs in Exercise Scale', *Measurement in physical education and exercise science*, 10(3), pp. 179-201.

Vlachopoulos, S. P., Ntoumanis, N. and Smith, A. L. (2010) 'The basic psychological needs in exercise scale: Translation and evidence for cross-cultural validity', *international Journal of sport and exercise psychology*, 8(4), pp. 394-412.

Vänttinen, T., Blomqvist, M., Nyman, K. and Häkkinen, K. (2011) 'Changes in Body Composition, Hormonal Status, and Physical Fitness in 11-, 13-, and 15-year-old Finnish Regional Youth Soccer Players During a Two-Year Follow-Up', *Journal of strength and conditioning research*, 25(12), pp. 3342-3351.

Wagner, C. M., Warneke, K., Bächer, C., Liefke, C., Paintner, P., Kuhn, L., Brauner, T., Wirth, K. and Keiner, M. (2022) 'Despite Good Correlations, There Is No Exact Coincidence between Isometric and Dynamic Strength Measurements in Elite Youth Soccer Players', *Sports (Basel, Switzerland)*, 10(11).

Wang, T., Lin, Z., Day, R. E., Gardiner, B., Landao-Bassonga, E., Rubenson, J., Kirk, T. B., Smith, D. W., Lloyd, D. G., Hardisty, G., Wang, A., Zheng, Q. and Zheng, M. H. (2013) 'Programmable mechanical stimulation influences tendon homeostasis in a bioreactor system', *Biotechnology and bioengineering*, 110(5), pp. 1495-1507.

Watson, K., Halperin, I., Aguilera-Castells, J. and Dello Iacono, A. (2020) 'A comparison between predetermined and self-selected approaches in resistance training: effects on power performance and psychological outcomes among elite youth athletes', *PeerJ*, 8.

Weakley, J., Till, K., Sampson, J., Banyard, H., Leduc, C., Wilson, K., Roe, G. and Jones, B. (2019) 'The Effects of Augmented Feedback on Sprint, Jump, and Strength Adaptations in Rugby Union Players After a 4-Week Training Program', *International journal of sports physiology and performance*, pp. 1205-1211.

Weakley, J. J. S., Till, K., Darrall-Jones, J., Roe, G. A. B., Phibbs, P. J., Read, D. B. and Jones, B. L. (2017) 'The Influence of Resistance Training Experience on the Between-Day Reliability of Commonly Used Strength Measures in Male Youth Athletes', *Journal of strength and conditioning research*, 31(7), pp. 2005- 2010.

Wells, J. E. T., Mitchell, A. C. S., Charalambous, L. H. and Fletcher, I. M. (2018) 'Relationships between highly skilled golfers' clubhead velocity and force producing capabilities during vertical jumps and an isometric mid-thigh pull', *Journal of sports sciences*, 36(16), pp. 1847-1851.

West, D. J., Owen, N. J., Jones, M. R., Bracken, R. M., Cook, C. J., Cunningham, D. J., Shearer, D. A., Finn, C. V., Newton, R. U., Crewther, B. T. and Kilduff, L. P. (2011) 'Relationships between force-time characteristics of the isometric midthigh pull and dynamic performance in professional rugby league players', *Journal of strength and conditioning research*, 25(11), pp. 3070- 3075.

Weyand, P. G., Sternlight, D. B., Bellizzi, M. J. and Wright, S. (2000) 'Faster top running speeds are achieved with greater ground forces not more rapid leg movements', *Journal of applied physiology (Bethesda, Md. : 1985)*, 89(5), pp. 1991- 1999.

Wilhelm, E. N., Radaelli, R., da Silva, B. G. C., Cintia, E. B., Barboas, R., Bottaro, M., Brown, L. E. and Pinto, R. S. (2013) 'Single joint isometric rate of torque development is not related to

counter movement jump performance in soccer players', *Isokinetics and Exercise Science*, 21(3), pp. 181- 186.

Wilson, G. J., Lyttle, A. D., Ostrowski, K. J. and Murphy, A. (1995) 'Assessing dynamic performance: A comparison of rate of force development tests ', *Journal of Strength and Conditioning Research*, 9(3), pp. 176- 181.

Wilson, G. J. and Murphy, A. J. (1996) 'The use of isometric tests of muscular function in athletic assessment', *Sports medicine (Auckland, N.Z.)*, 22(1), pp. 19- 37.

Wilson, P. M., Rogers, W. T., Rodgers, W. M. and Wild, T. C. (2006) 'The psychological need satisfaction in exercise scale', *Journal of Sport and Exercise Psychology*, 28(3), pp. 231- 251.

Wing, C. E., Turner, A. N. and Bishop, C. J. (2018) 'The importance of strength and power on key performance indicators in elite youth soccer.', *Journal of Strength and Conditioning Research*.

Wisdom, K. M., Delp, S. L. and Kuhl, E. (2015) 'Use it or lose it: multiscale skeletal muscle adaptation to mechanical stimuli', *Biomechanics and modeling in mechanobiology*, 14(2), pp. 195-215.

Wisloff, U., Castagna, C., Helgerud, J., Jones, R. and Hoff, J. (2004) 'Strong correlation of maximal squat strength with sprint performance and vertical jump height in elite soccer players.', *British Journal of Sports Medicine.*, 38(3), pp. 285- 288.

Wisloff, U., Helgerud, J. and Hoff, J. (1998) 'Strength and endurance of elite soccer players.', *Medicine and Science in Sports and Exercise.*, 30(3), pp. 462- 467.

Wrigley, R. D., Drust, B., Stratton, G., Atkinson, G. and Gregson, W. (2014) 'Long-term soccer-specific training enhances the rate of physical development of academy soccer players independent of maturation status', *International journal of sports medicine*, 35(13), pp. 1090-1104.

Wulf, G. and Adams, N. (2014) 'Small choices can enhance balance learning', *Human movement science*, 38, pp. 235- 240.

Wulf, G., Freitas, H. E. and Tandy, R. D. (2014) 'Choosing to exercise more: Small choices increase exercise engagement', *Psychology of Sport and Exercise*, 15(3), pp. 268- 271.

Wulf, G. and Lewthwaite, R. (2016) 'Optimizing performance through intrinsic motivation and attention for learning: The OPTIMAL theory of motor learning', *Psychonomic bulletin & review*, 23(5), pp. 1382- 1414.

Young, W., McLean, B. and Ardagna, J. (1995) 'Relationship between strength qualities and sprinting performance', *The Journal of sports medicine and physical fitness*, 35(1), pp. 13- 19.

Zhao, W., Pan, J., Zhao, Z., Wu, Y., Bauman, W. A. and Cardozo, C. P. (2008) 'Testosterone protects against dexamethasone-induced muscle atrophy, protein degradation and MAFbx upregulation', *The Journal of steroid biochemistry and molecular biology*, 110(1-2), pp. 125-1249.

Appendices

Publication from the current thesis

McGoldrick, C.D., Dello Iacono, A., Morgan, O.J., Nayler, J., Buchanan, J., McCart, C., & Unnithan, V.B. (2023). Reliability, familiarisation effect and comparisons between a pre-determined and a self-determined isometric squat testing protocol. *International Journal of Sports Physiology and Performance*, In press. <https://doi.org/10.1123/ijsp.2022-0480>.

Appendix 1: Isometric testing protocol participant reference sheet

Isometric squat test protocol sheet

- **Grip the barbell** with equal spacing of hands from the centre of the bar **without stepping** onto the force plates (image 1)
- Then stand on the force plates at the **foot width** chosen by your coach (image 2)
- **Lightly press your shoulders** against the bar so you are ready to push (image 2)
- Make sure **not to arch or round your lower back** (image 2)
- **Hold** this position and bar pressure (image 2)

- When instructed to do so by your coach, **push the ground as hard and as fast as you can** until told to stop by your coach
- Always push as hard as you can from the start of the effort
- Make sure to do some **light stretching between efforts**; the exercise is below:

Example of the self-determined isometric squat protocol

Use the QR code below to watch a video of a player completing the isometric squat test:

Appendix 2: Participant perception of autonomy questionnaire

Name: _____

Feelings on testing (using the scale provided please answer the following statements as accurately as possible; place a tick in the appropriate circle)

1) The testing/ training programme I just participated in is the same as how I would like to train/ be tested in the future

1. Strongly Disagree

2. Disagree

**3. Neutral
Agree**

4. Agree

5. Strongly

2) The way I was just tested/ trained is the way I want to be tested/ trained in the future

1. Strongly Disagree
Agree

2. Disagree

3. Neutral

4. Agree

5. Strongly

3) I feel I am able to decide how I am tested/ trained in the future

1. Strongly Disagree
Agree

2. Disagree

3. Neutral

4. Agree

5. Strongly

4) Making choices about the exercise/activities I do is important to me

1. Strongly Disagree
Agree

2. Disagree

3. Neutral

4. Agree

5. Strongly

Participant history question (please answer the following as accurately as possible in the box provided to the right)

1. How many years have you done strength training, weight training or gym training?

Appendix 3: Ethical approval

06/07/2020

Dear Cillian McGoldrick,

Your application 13175: Test-retest reliability of two isometric squat test protocols among young football players, submission 10444, has been approved by the Health and Life Sciences SEC . You may now proceed with your study. If you wish to make any significant changes to the study you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them.

Good luck with your research.

Dr Gary Boyd

11/08/2020

Dear Cillian McGoldrick,

Your application 12046: How do elite youth soccer players develop strength and power characteristics during adolescence: Influence of training adaptations, submission 10522, has been approved by the Health and Life Sciences SEC . You may now proceed with your study. If you wish to make any significant changes to the study you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them.

Good luck with your research.

Dr Gary Boyd

Appendix 4: Organisational approval

Dear Cillian,

Please use this letter as confirmation of approval to carry out research within Celtic FC Academy as part of your PhD investigations, in accordance to the association between University of West Scotland and Celtic FC.

We're delighted to be working alongside UWS to produce research that will impact on our processes of long-term athlete development within the talent development pathway at Celtic FC.

We look forward to collaborating with yourself Cillian over the next three years.

Kindest Regards,

Oliver Morgan

Head of Academy Sports Science

Appendix 5: Informed consent

Informed Consent

Title of Project: How do elite youth soccer players develop strength and power characteristics during adolescence: Influence of training adaptations?

Name of Researcher: Cillian McGoldrick

Please initial box

- 1 I confirm that I have read and understand the information sheet for the above study and have had the opportunity to ask questions.

- 2 I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time, without giving any reason.

- 3 I agree to take part in the above study.

Name of Participant:

Participant Signature:

Participant Parent Signature (only needed if player is less than 16 years old):

Date:

Name of researcher:

Signature:

Date:

1 copy for participant and 1 for researcher

PARTICIPANT INFORMATION SHEET

Project title: Test-retest reliability of two isometric squat test protocols among young football players

Investigator

Cillian McGoldrick (Lead Investigator) – PhD student; School of Health and Life Sciences, University of the West of Scotland.

Prof Vish Unnithan (Director of studies) – School of Health and Life Sciences, University of the West of Scotland.

Dr. Antonio Dello Iacono – School of Health and Life Sciences, University of the West of Scotland.

Introduction

You have volunteered interest to take part in the above study. Before you participate in the study, please read the following information which will help you fully understand the research process and what it will involve for you. Please read this information sheet carefully, and if anything is unclear or you would like for more details to be provided please ask.

Purpose of the study

The purpose of this study is to investigate the reliability of 2 isometric squat test protocols, and the required number of familiarisation sessions for ensuring reliable results among young football players.

What is involved in the study?

You should avoid intense training 24 hours prior to each day of testing, prohibited from consuming any known stimulant or depressant substances for 24 hours before testing, and instructed not to eat a main meal for 1-2 hours before each assessment session. Before the initiation of the study, you will be asked to fill out a PAR-Q training questionnaire. The PAR-Q is a simple self-screening tool to determine your health and safety status based on health history and current symptoms or possible risk associated to the physical efforts demanded when performing the testing procedures of this study.

During the study, you will report to the Celtic FC training ground gymnasium at Lennoxton for four non-consecutive testing sessions administered with at least one week between each testing session.

The testing sessions will begin with a warm-up procedure including general movement exercises and dynamic stretches. Then, you will perform:

- The Isometric squat: An isometric force test performed in the position shown in Figure 1. Prior to the four main testing sessions, between 1 and 3 familiarisation sessions will be conducted to determine the optimum number of familiarisation sessions to produce accurate results. Each familiarisation session will comprise of three maximal intensity repetitions. During the isometric squat, an immovable barbell is positioned directly above force plates at a bar height equating to 120- 130 degrees of knee flexion or at a height determined by you, depending on the testing session. During each test you will be instructed to assume the testing position, and keep this position during a rest phase lasting 3 seconds prior to the test start. For the test execution, you will be asked to push the feet against the ground “as hard and as fast as possible” for 5 seconds. Three maximal trials will be performed during each testing session with at least 3 minutes of passive recovery between each test.

Figure 1. Setup of Isometric squat test

Confidentiality

All data gathered within the study will be dealt with in confidence by the lead investigator, stored in an electronic form and secured by an encrypted password. Your personal data will be assigned with a numeric code so to avoid that the personal information provided (Name, surname, date of birth, weight and height) can be used to identify your person. Hard copies of the consent form and PAR-Q training questionnaire will be securely stored. The data will remain anonymous throughout the study. Once the study is complete all of the data that has been stored will be used for publication but kept anonymous. One year from the study completion, any data previously collected and stored electronically or in written form will be destroyed.

Risks

A risk assessment will be completed prior to the study being carried out on both testing days. The study will not present any additional risks to you. A trained physiotherapist will be present during the testing at all times in the unlikely event of any muscle discomfort being experienced. Following every testing day, a post-test protocol will be undertaken to reduce the likelihood of any muscular discomfort. This will include cool-down recovery activities and stretching exercises.

Right to withdraw

If you choose to participate in this study, you also have the right to withdraw at any time and do not have to give any reason for doing so. In this case, any data previously collected and stored electronically or in written form will be immediately destroyed.

Further information

If you have any queries or require further information, do not hesitate to contact:

Appendix 6: PAR-Q training questionnaire

PAR-Q & YOU

Questionnaire - PAR-Q

Physical Activity Readiness

(revised 2002)

(A Questionnaire for People Aged 15 to 69)

Regular physical activity is fun and healthy, and increasingly more people are starting to become more active every day. Being more active is very safe for most people. However, some people should check with their doctor before they start becoming much more physically active.

If you are planning to become much more physically active than you are now, start by answering the seven questions in the box below. If you are between the ages of 15 and 69, the PAR-Q will tell you if you should check with your doctor before you start. If you are over 69 years of age, and you are not used to being very active, check with your doctor.

Common sense is your best guide when you answer these questions. Please read the questions carefully and answer each one honestly: check YES or NO.

YES	NO
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> 1. Has your doctor ever said that you have a heart condition <u>and</u> that you should only do physical activity recommended by a doctor?
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> 2. Do you feel pain in your chest when you do physical activity?
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. In the past month, have you had chest pain when you were not doing physical activity?
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> 4. Do you lose your balance because of dizziness or do you ever lose consciousness?
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Do you have a bone or joint problem (for example, back, knee or hip) that could be made worse by a change in your physical activity?
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> 6. Is your doctor currently prescribing drugs (for example, water pills) for your blood pressure or heart condition?
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Do you know of <u>any other reason</u> why you should not do physical activity?

If you answered

YES to one or more questions

Talk with your doctor by phone or in person BEFORE you start becoming much more physically active or BEFORE you have a fitness appraisal. Tell your doctor about the PAR-Q and which questions you answered YES.

- You may be able to do any activity you want — as long as you start slowly and build up gradually. Or, you may need to restrict your activities to those which are safe for you. Talk with your doctor about the kinds of activities you wish to participate in and follow his/her advice.
- Find out which community programs are safe and helpful for you.

NO to all questions

If you answered NO honestly to all PAR-Q questions, you can be reasonably sure that you can:

- start becoming much more physically active — begin slowly and build up gradually. This is the safest and easiest way to go.
- take part in a fitness appraisal — this is an excellent way to determine your basic fitness so that you can plan the best way for you to live actively. It is also highly recommended that you have your blood pressure evaluated. If your reading is over 144/94, talk with your doctor before you start becoming much more physically active.

PLEASE NOTE: If your health changes so that you then answer YES to any of the above questions, tell your fitness or health professional.

Ask whether you should change your physical activity plan.

DELAY BECOMING MUCH MORE ACTIVE:

- if you are not feeling well because of a temporary illness such as a cold or a fever — wait until you feel better; or
- if you are or may be pregnant — talk to your doctor before you start becoming more active.

Informed Use of the PAR-Q: The Canadian Society for Exercise Physiology, Health Canada, and their agents assume no liability for persons who undertake physical activity, and if in doubt after completing this questionnaire, consult your doctor prior to physical activity.

No changes permitted. You are encouraged to photocopy the PAR-Q but only if you use the entire form.

NOTE: If the PAR-Q is being given to a person before he or she participates in a physical activity program or a fitness appraisal, this section may be used for legal or administrative purposes.

"I have read, understood and completed this questionnaire. Any questions I had were answered to my full satisfaction."

NAME _____

SIGNATURE _____

DATE _____

SIGNATURE OF PARENT _____

WITNESS

or GUARDIAN (for participants under the age of majority)

Note: This physical activity clearance is valid for a maximum of 12 months from the date it is completed and becomes invalid if your condition changes so that you would answer YES to any of the seven questions.